

Euscorpius

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

**A standardized list of scorpion names in
Chinese, with an etymological approach**

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May 2022 — No. 350

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Derivatio Nominis

The name *Euscorpius* Thorell, 1876 refers to the most common genus of scorpions in the Mediterranean region and southern Europe (family Euscorpiidae).

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Publication date: 21 May 2022

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:8647194C-5CF2-49FF-8867-58BAD6A203B5>

A standardized list of scorpion names in Chinese, with an etymological approach

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Summary

The scientific (Latin) names of scorpion species are widely used across the world by both experts and amateurs. However, in China, there is a great need for designating standardized Chinese names for various scorpions since it is difficult for those not familiar with Latin alphabet to memorize the scientific names. Currently used Chinese names often cause confusion and misunderstanding due to a lack of standardized, unified naming. The present work critically revises the existing formal Chinese scorpion names, vernacular names (used by local population and amateurs), and the names used in Chinese scientific publications, along with the confusion they have caused. A general review of the etymology and types of scientific names in scorpions is also provided. A standardized rule for translating scientific names into Chinese names (exclusively for the Order Scorpiones) is established for the first time. A list of all the scientific names of the valid extant scorpion species is given, translated into Chinese along with the Latin names.

Introduction

The Swedish botanist, zoologist, taxonomist and physician, Carl von Linné (1707 – 1778; also known as Carl Linnaeus) was the one who formalized the binomial nomenclature, the foundation of the system of scientific classification. Linnaeus's major contribution to taxonomy was the establishment of universally accepted conventions for the naming of organisms which marked the starting point of consistent use of binomial nomenclature (Reveal & Pringle, 1993).

The binomial nomenclature (literally meaning “two-name system”) is a formal system of naming living organisms. The name comprises two parts, both of which are in Latin grammatical forms, although they can originate from other languages (see below). Such a name is the only true scientific name, or more informally it is also called as a Latin name. Latin is used for scientific names for one main reason, as it is a dead language, used by no people or nation as an official language, thus it does not change over time.

In modern biology, the application of Latin in scientific names is ruled by internationally agreed codes of rules, of which the two most important are the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN) for animals and the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (ICNafp). Although the general principles of binomial nomenclature are similar between these two codes, there are some differences, and the present study only focuses on animal naming.

The first part of a binomial Latin name is the genus name, or generic epithet. It stands for the genus to which the species belongs. It must be in the form of a noun or a substantivised adjective treated as a noun (James, 2010).

The second part is the specific name, or specific epithet, which distinguishes the species within the genus (congeneric species). Only in combination with a generic name does it have any validity or make any sense, but it can be used in more than one genus. Neither generic nor specific names need to be descriptive, accurate or relevant, and they cannot be rejected merely for being erroneous in these respects, although some earlier authors sought to do so (James, 2010). For example, in scorpions, *Somalicharmus* Kovařík, 1998 is a geographically erroneous name since the only species of this genus is actually found in Ethiopia rather than Somalia. The name *Srilankametrus indus* (DeGeer, 1778) is also misleading as the species only occurs in Sri Lanka but not India. These Latin names cannot be changed due to the ICZN principles of priority and stability. Nevertheless, it still could be useful to provide an explanation to a non-specialist when using such names.

The first letter of the generic epithet must be capitalized, while that of the specific epithet is not, even if it is a name of a person or a place. Additionally, both parts of a binomen are italicized. If a complete scientific name has been mentioned earlier in the text, the generic epithet can then be abbreviated into the first letter with a period. For example, *Androctonus bicolor* can be abbreviated as *A. bicolor* if the whole name was referred to previously. If a lower rank (subspecies) is accepted for one species, there will be a third part denoting the subspecific epithet. Similar to the binomen, the name of a subspecies is called as “trinomen” or “triple name”. The subspecific epithet is also italicized without capitalized letter. If there is a subsequently named subspecies, then the original species becomes an “aggregation” of two subspecies, the type subspecies (or nominate subspecies) and the subsequently

Figures 1–2. **Figure 1.** A group of *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879), the most common scorpion in China, *in vivo* habitus. **Figure 2.** Three representative specimens of *O. martensii*. Adult male (2a), adult female (2b), pallid immature (2c).

named subspecies. The type subspecies is synonymous with the original species (before the other subspecies is found), and the subspecific epithet is the same as the specific epithet.

The main body (binomen) of a scientific name is followed by the name of the author and the year of publication, separated by a comma and not italicized (e.g., *Androctonus afghanus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006). If the species was originally described in another genus, the author's name and the year will be enclosed in parentheses (e.g., *Androctonus australis* (Linnaeus, 1758) was originally described as *Scorpio australis* Linnaeus, 1758, a name addressed as the *protonym*).

There are cases for amending the status of scientific names. An animal name is regarded as a *homonym* if there are two identical names within the Kingdom Animalia. According to the ICZN, such name is not accepted and has to be changed according to priority of the name described earlier. For instance, the scorpion genus *Orthochirus* Karsch, 1892 was originally described as *Orthodactylus* Karsch, 1881, a name, which already existed in Sauropsida as *Orthodactylus* Hitchcock, 1858. In a case of *synonymy*, the same taxon might have several available names but the senior synonym must be used as valid: thus, *Orthodactylus*, a fossil crocodile, is now a junior synonym of *Batrachopus* Hitchcock, 1845. One should consult ICZN for much more details on homonymy, synonymy, availability, validity, etc.

All the scientific names, regardless of their etymology, are grammatically treated as Latin. Most are derived from Latin and its successors or from ancient Greek (James, 2010). Latin nouns are declined, and verbs are conjugated, that is, their endings change according to their case, tense, person and number, or, more simply, the manner in which they are used (James, 2010). Adjectival specific epithet must agree with their genus in gender. If a species is transferred from a genus that has a masculine name to a feminine one (or vice versa), the ending of the specific epithet must be altered accordingly. If a specific epithet, which appears to be an adjective, is in fact a noun in apposition, their endings do not change to agree with the gender of the generic epithet. There are three common Latin endings: (i) *-us* (masculine), *-a* (feminine), *-um* (neuter); (ii) *-is* (masculine), *-is* (feminine), *-e* (neuter); (iii) *-er* (masculine), *-era* (feminine), *-erum* (neuter).

Types of animal names used in China

Just like names of people, animal names in local languages can be rather diverse if those animals are well-known among different cultures or groups of people. There are usually five types of names for animals in China:

(a) a native/folk name (indigenous to a certain country or even a region, it may have a long history but is not based on scientific studies);

(b) a vernacular/common name (used only by the amateurs, coined by someone who has a better knowledge of the animal group than those using a native/folk name; such names are usually created and used among animal breeders, keepers and traders);

(c) a Chinese translation of a scientific Latin name (the translation can be literal, free or transliterated);

(d) a Chinese translation of a foreign native/common name (usually from English);

(e) the “formal Chinese name (中文正名)” (established by the Chinese researchers in certain fields and used in their science publications).

Moreover, there is a concept of “Chinese scientific name (中文学名)” in China. However, as stated before, the only scientific name for an animal is its Linnean name (Latin or at least Latinized), so if one replaces the term “scientific name (学名)” with “Latin name”, the outcome will be as weird as “Chinese Latin name”. How can a name be both Chinese and Latin at the same time? Such concept is clearly contradictory and misleading. The “Chinese scientific name” is a name that seems somewhat academic, but one species may still have multiple “Chinese scientific names” and not all of them are applied in the Chinese science publications. Nevertheless, so-called “Chinese scientific names” are used more or less equally with formal Chinese names, and the term “Chinese academic names (中文学术名)” can best replace it. A formal Chinese name, however, is the most chaotic category. It can come from any of abovelisted categories (a, b, c, or d). As a result, formal Chinese names are not “academic” at all since they also include native/common names. Besides, the “self-created name” is the most ubiquitous among formal Chinese names coined by researchers which have no origin at all, and are certainly irrelevant to the etymology of scientific Latin names. Such self-created name is highly restricted by the knowledge of a certain group if coined according to the morphology. There is a high possibility that a self-created name can have the etymological meaning of another existing taxon (which leads to conflict), or fails to summarize unique characters of its taxon (which makes it meaningless). A Latin name, if it is a morphonym, does not have to be fully descriptive since naming is limited by knowledge of this taxon. However, in the case of Chinese names, there is no such an excuse as there exist all the available contributions, much more adequate than what the original author had. If one really craves for renaming a taxon in Chinese, the new name should be superior to the existing one (at least in its meaning). Most of the self-created names in the formal Chinese names among the taxa that I had studied fail to achieve this, making the action of renaming rather meaningless. Those who coin them are reluctant to translate scientific Latin names — either because of finding it rather difficult or due to ill-conceived “cultural confidence”.

As a result, an apparently academic (to a non-scientist) formal Chinese name is not academic at all. Origins of these names are extremely diverse and chaotic due to the fact that no formally recognized Chinese nomenclature exists (unlike the scientific Latin names), thus causing lots of confusion and conflicts. The formal Chinese names of scorpions are poorly constructed.

The present contribution critically revises the current formal Chinese names of scorpions used in the Chinese scientific publications (as well as the folk and vernacular

Figure 3. The only academic scorpion book in China, *Scorpion Biology and Toxins*.

names). An improved principle of translation of Latin names and a list of all valid names of extant scorpion taxa are offered. Also, the most comprehensive study of the etymology of scorpion names is presented.

Folk names applied to scorpions in China: a history

About 2000 years ago, the first dictionary in China, *Er Ya* (尔雅, in Chinese) or *Literary Expositor*, had already made a rough record of scorpions (Li, 2016). During the Spring and Autumn period (770–476 BC), *The Book of Songs* (诗经, in Chinese) recorded the occurrence of scorpions as well, leading people to realize that this creature can be used as a medicine. The book *Shu Bencao* (蜀本草, in Chinese), during the Later Shu Dynasty, formally treated scorpions as medicine. In the Song Dynasty, the book *Kaibao Bencao* (开宝本草, in Chinese) initiated to use the word “蝎子” (simplified as “蝎”, a Chinese equivalence of “a scorpion”). The *Compendium of Materia Medica* written by Shizhen Li (李时珍, in Chinese) during the Ming Dynasty provided a very detailed description of scorpion, such as morphology, usability, processing method and prophylaxis and treatment for scorpion sting, for the first time. Additionally, *Shennong’s Classic of Materia Medica*

(*Shennong Bencaojing*, in Chinese) during the Eastern Han Dynasty, *Bencao Tujing* (本草图经, in Chinese) or *Illustrated Classics of Materia Medica* during the Song Dynasty, *Bencao Beiyao* (本草备要, in Chinese) or *Essentials of Materia Medica* in 1694 and *Bencao Zhengyi* (本草正义, in Chinese) during the Qing Dynasty also described the medical usage of scorpions. The most widely distributed scorpion species in China is *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879) (Figs 1–2; originally described in the genus *Buthus* Leach, 1815 by the German arachnologist Ferdinand Karsch and then assigned to *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950 for a long time). This species has been used as traditional Chinese medicine for more than a thousand years (and even today) to treat several diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, apoplexy, epilepsy and chronic pain. As a result, it is given a large variety of names.

The most commonly used and famous name is “钳蝎 (*qián xiē*)” (“pincer scorpion”) reflecting its obvious pedipalps. The same name “钳蝎” is currently the formal Chinese name for the family Buthidae C. L. Koch, 1837 (see below). *O. martensii* alone, however, may also be called “东亚钳蝎 (*dōng yà qián xiē*)” (“East Asian pincer scorpion”). In Chinese scientific publications, this species is also referred to as “马氏钳蝎 (*mǎ shì qián xiē*)” (“Martens’s pincer scorpion”) when it is considered as *Buthus martensii* and as “

马氏正钳蝎 (*mǎ shì zhèng qián xiē*) (“Martens’s true pincer scorpion”) when it is considered as *Mesobuthus martensii*. “东亚钳蝎” may also be related with another folk name, “远东蝎 (*yuǎn dōng xiē*)” (the “Far East scorpion”).

Besides the name “钳蝎”, another most used name is “全蝎 (*quán xiē*)” (“complete scorpion”) or “全虫 (*quán chóng*)” (“integral bug”) in Chinese medicine. It is also called “蒙山全蝎 (*méng shān quán xiē*)”, “沂蒙全蝎 (*yí méng quán xiē*)” or “沂蒙山全蝎 (*yí méng shān quán xiē*)” since it is said (incorrectly, of course) that the scorpions in Mengshan (“蒙山 (*méng shān*)”), Linyi City (临沂市), Shandong Province differ from those in other regions by having two pedipalps and eight legs whereas others only possess six legs, which is the reason for the name “integral scorpion” (having a total of ten appendages). Additionally, names like “会蝎 (*huì xiē*)” or “会全蝎 (*huì quán xiē*)” may be miswritings of “全蝎”. Alternative names include “东全蝎 (*dōng quán xiē*)” (“Eastern complete scorpion”), “咸全蝎 (*xián quán xiē*)” (the “salty complete scorpion”), “盐水蝎 (*yán shuǐ xiē*)” (“saltwater scorpion”), “淡全蝎 (*dàn quán xiē*)” (“tasteless complete scorpion”) and “淡全虫 (*dàn quán chóng*)” (“tasteless complete bug”) for unknown reasons.

Three names may be associated with the morphology, i.e., “链蝎 (*liàn xiē*)” (“chain scorpion”), “荆蝎 (*jīng xiē*)” (“thorny scorpion”) and “剑蝎 (*jiàn xiē*)” (“sword scorpion”). Other names do not end with the word “蝎”. “琵琶虫 (*pípa chóng*)” is also a morphonym and it may result from the description of scorpion’s body by the Chinese as they consider it is similar to the shape of pipa (“琵琶”, a traditional Chinese musical instrument). The name “茯背虫 (*fú bèi chóng*)” comes from the Chinese medicine “茯苓 (*fú líng*)” (refers to the mushroom *Wolfiporia extensa* (Peck) Ginns (1984) which, according to the Chinese dictionary, exhibits a light-black or puce-colored surface. As a result, it can be freely translated as “brownish back bug”.

The word “蚤 (*chài*)” is a general word for the venomous creatures like scorpions, wasps and snakes and there might be no English equivalent. “蚤尾虫 (*chài wěi chóng*)” is a name used exclusively for the scorpions (as well as the word “蚘祁 (*yī qí*)”). It cannot be directly translated into English as well, but “a bug with a poisonous tail” will be the closest interpretation.

The final two names are connected with specific historical characters. “杜伯 (*dù bó*)” is given after a homonymous minister of the emperor Xuan Wang in the Zhou Dynasty. This person had curly hair that resembled “蚤” (probably referring to a scorpion metasoma) according to *Festal Songs·Durenshi* (小雅·都人士) within *The Book of Songs*. “主簿虫 (*zhǔ bù chóng*)” is named after an ancient official title “主簿 (*zhǔ bù*)” (similar to the registrar, in modern sense). Several ancient books (e.g., the *YawYang Essays·Chapter Insecta* (酉阳杂俎·虫篇), the *Supplement of National History of the Tang Dynasty* (唐国史补) and the *Biography of the Tang Dynasty* (大唐传载)) provide an analogous explanation: once upon a time, there was a registrar who accidentally introduced scorpions to Jiangnan (“江南”, in some literature as Jiannan “

剑南”; these are two different places), in which the scorpions were never recorded before.

The other two species that may sometimes be found in Chinese medicine are *Lychas mucronatus* (Fabricius, 1798) (common in the Southwest) and *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839) (common in the Northwest), but they have no folk names.

Scorpions are fortunate to have a single, exclusive Chinese name “蝎” representing all the members of the Order Scorpiones. Similar cases are, for example, “蜘蛛” or “蛛” for spiders and “蜈蚣” or “蚣” for centipedes. However, many other taxa are not lucky to have exclusive names. For instance, the members of Solifugae are usually termed as “避日蛛” (“sun-avoiding spider”, and many other names such as “风蝎 (wind scorpion)” or “骆驼蜘蛛 (camel spider)” directly translated from English common names; at least this name is partially from the etymology of Latin name) yet they are not true spiders. Members of Thelyphonida (Uropygi sensu stricto) and Amblypygi are termed “鞭蝎” and “鞭蛛” according to their English common names, “whip scorpion” and “whip spider”, respectively. These names can easily mislead the public to believe that they are either scorpions or spiders. Similar cases are seen in vertebrates, namely, geckos, which are usually termed as “壁虎” (“wall tiger”), and their Chinese names often end with “虎”, which is the name used exclusively for tigers. Many other taxa of Arachnida also do not have a single-word Chinese name, such as Palpigradi and Schizomida. Some names do not conflict with a large group (on the order level), but they still do make conflicts if a smaller group (on the generic level) is translated. For example, Opiliones in China are usually termed as “盲蛛” (“blind spider”) (which should better be translated as “牧羊蛛” or “牧蛛” (“shepherd spider”, a translated name that has occurred in Chinese literature but was not accepted as a formal name) if no exclusive name is given). However, it is not a spider; at the same time, one generic name in the Araneae, *Nops* MacLeay, 1839, can be literally translated and deserves the name “盲蛛” (“blind spider”). On the other hand, although some taxa do have a single exclusive word that represents them (for example, “蟹” for termites and “蚊” for millipedes), their current Chinese names still are either confusing (e.g. “白蚁” (“white ant”) for termites, which are not ants) or obscure (e.g. “马陆”, two words that are directly translated as “horse” and “land”) for millipedes, which cannot be transliterated). Despite that this is not so relevant with the current study (as scorpion names do not have such problems, though the names of other taxa may be mistaken for scorpions), I believe it is essential to establish and designate exclusive names for those taxa, which do not have one, in order to reduce confusion and increase simplicity (one word for a taxon is always better than two).

Current confusion in Chinese scorpion names

There are generally three categories of Chinese names for scorpions: the folk names, the vernacular names used by amateurs (including keepers, breeders and

traders), and the formal Chinese names. Aside from the folk names, which has been discussed in detail above, the other two types of names are most commonly used, and, at the same time, exhibit the highest degree of confusion. Vernacular names used by players and traders are rather confusing and arbitrary. Most of these names are a combination of a name of a locality (where the species may be either found or not), a characteristic of the scorpion and sometimes a folk/vernacular “generic name”. The most often seen names are borrowed from English common names (as well as in other taxa; the formal Chinese name will take those as the so-called “formal names” as well). The name of the locality applied in the vernacular name can be erroneous; it usually reflects the species’ range (but rarely the type locality). Below, I list several examples currently found among the vernacular names.

Vernacular Chinese names for the species of the genus *Uroplectes* Peters, 1861 all begin with “Namibian”; however, not all its species occur in this country (e.g., “纳米比亚蓝宝石蝎” (the “Namibian sapphire scorpion”, in English; the following Chinese vernacular names will all be directly translated into English) is the Chinese vernacular name of the species *U. flavoviridis* Peters, 1861 which only occurs in Mozambique, Republic of Malawi, Zambia, Tanzania, Zimbabwe and Republic of South Africa). The vernacular name of *Hottentotta tamulus indicus* (Pocock, 1900) and *H. t. gangeticus* (Pocock, 1900) (both now synonymized with *H. tamulus* (Fabricius, 1798)) are “Indian crocodile-backed scorpion” and “Pakistan crocodile-backed scorpion”, respectively. However, the subspecific epithet of the former is derived from a province in Pakistan (Sind) while that of the latter, from the Gange, a river which does not flow through Pakistan. Similarly, the naming by the locality can be rather arbitrary. For instance, the species *Androctonus crassicauda* (Olivier, 1807) is named “Turkish black fat-tailed scorpion” and it has no subspecies (the previous subspecies was returned back to the species rank as *A. gonneti* Vachon, 1948). However, some Chinese traders fabricated a subspecies name, “*Androctonus crassicauda israe*” (since it is not a valid name I will not italicize it), without even correctly turning the locality name (Israel) into Latinized “*israelis*”. They gave it another name “Israeli black fat-tailed scorpion”. Turkey is not the type locality of this species (type locality: Persia (now Iran), Esfahan Province, Kashan) and both Turkey and Israel were just two countries of the previously recognized distribution (a recent study showed that the Turkish populations may refer to another species in the south, *A. turkiyensis* Yağmur, 2021, at least for the Şanlıurfa Province; the true *A. crassicauda* is restricted to the Iranian Plateau (E.A. Yağmur, pers. comm.)). It will be relatively reasonable if a vernacular name of this species was limited to “black fat-tailed scorpion” adding Turkey or Israel as geographic modifiers when sources of scorpions that are sold in China are known (nevertheless, no specimens sold in China and labeled as “Turkish black fat-tailed scorpion” originate from Turkey, and at the same time, specimens from the Mardin Province of Turkey are called a

“Syrian brown fat-tailed scorpion”). Likewise, *Androctonus cf. crassicauda* (labeled so by the foreign sellers) is named an “Oman brown fat-tailed scorpion” by the Chinese traders. It is obvious from the abbreviation *cf.* (from Latin word *conferre*, meaning “compare” or “confer”) that the foreign sellers are not sure of the identity of the species yet they thought it was most close to the species *A. crassicauda*. However, the Chinese vernacular name does not indicate such meaning.

The “Israeli golden scorpion” name assigned for *Leiurus quinquestriatus* (Ehrenberg, 1828) in China (for *Scorpio palmatus* (Ehrenberg, 1828) in other countries) is one of the most misleading common names. Those Chinese users distinguish three different “species” as *L. quinquestriatus*, *L. quinquestriatus quinquestriatus* and *L. quinquestriatus hebraeus* (wrongly identified, with the true identity being *Leiurus haenggii* Lowe, Yagmur & Kovařík, 2014; this subspecies was elevated to species in 2014 as *L. hebraeus* (Birula, 1908)). This clearly shows the lack of knowledge of trinomial nomenclature. They define the type subspecies as “the golden-back subspecies” and *L. q. hebraeus* as “the black-back subspecies”. The premodifier “Israeli” is only one of the known countries (Israel) of distribution for *L. q. hebraeus*, but never for the type subspecies. As a result, logically, this premodifier can only apply to the second subspecies, but not the type subspecies or the species (since those Chinese users consider them separately).

Furthermore, *Leiurus nasheri* Kovařík, 2007 is named a “Yemen golden scorpion”. However, it has already found to be a junior synonym of *L. brachycentrus* (Ehrenberg, 1829) and the true identity of the scorpions they sell is *Leiurus arabicus* Lowe, Yagmur & Kovařík, 2014, which differs greatly from the former and does *not* occur in Yemen.

The names based on the characteristics can also be unrepresentative. For example, the vernacular name of the genus *Opisthophthalmus* C. L. Koch, 1837 is “yellow claw scorpion” which only stands for several yellow-colored species while dark species of *Opisthophthalmus* without yellow claws do exist. *O. glabrifrons* Peters, 1861 and *O. wahlbergi* Thorell, 1876 were both given the name “African yellow claw scorpion”, although the latter never appeared in the market. Additionally, the name “yellow claw scorpion” is also referred to a completely unrelated but yellow species, *Bothriurus coriaceus* Pocock, 1893, combined with the geographic modifier “Chilean”. This is a typical group of examples that indicates the ignorance of the generic sense (i.e., people do not limit a certain name to a certain taxon). *Opisthophthalmus boehmi* (Kraepelin, 1896) was given the name “South African tricolor scorpion”, while *Cheloctonus jonesii* Pocock, 1892 was named as “tricolor earth-digging scorpion”. *Parabuthus granulatus* (Ehrenberg, 1831) is a polymorphic species with color forms of brownish black, bicolor (dark body with light legs), light brown, brownish red and yellow. However, its vernacular name is a “red thick-tailed scorpion” while red is the rarest color form and has never appeared on the Chinese market. Likewise, *P. capensis* (Ehrenberg, 1831) and *P. mossambicensis* (Peters, 1861) are named a “golden back

thick-tailed scorpion” and “yellow thick-tailed scorpion”, respectively. Yet both of the species are usually orange yellow (exceptions are when the former may be greenish yellow or pitch black and the latter may be light yellow).

Similarly, the name “flat rock scorpion” is referred both to the genus *Hadogenes* Kraepelin, 1894 and a species, *Scorpiops validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010) (combined with the geographic modifier “Yunnan” or “Vietnam”, the latter is not in the range of the species). Both the genus *Cheloctonus* Pocock, 1892 and *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861 are called “earth-digging scorpion”. Both the species *Buthus occitanus* (Amoreux, 1789) and *Aegaeobuthus gibbosus* (Brullé, 1832) are called “Mediterranean yellow scorpion” or “Greek golden scorpion”. Both the species *Lychas mucronatus* and *Isometrus maculatus* (DeGeer, 1778) are called a “Hainan double-stinger scorpion”. Both the species *Tityus serrulatus* Lutz & Mello, 1922 (or *T. carrilloi* Ojanguren Affilastro, 2021, a new species which used to represent the Argentinian population of the former) and *Odontobuthus odonturus* (Pocock, 1897) are called a “man killer scorpion”, with the geographic modifier “Brazilian” and “Iranian”, respectively. All the Tibetan black species within the genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 are termed as a “Tibetan scorpion” without modifiers for distinguishment. Similarly, the name “golden scorpion” is used in some species across several genera: *Androctonus* Ehrenberg, 1828, *Buthus*, *Chihuahuanus* González-Santillan & Prendini, 2013, *Hadrurus* Thorell, 1876, *Heteroctenus* Pocock, 1893, *Javanimetrus* Couzijn, 1981, *Leiurus* Ehrenberg, 1828, *Mesobuthus*, *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987, *Parabuthus* Pocock, 1890, *Scorpio* Linnaeus, 1758, *Smeringurus* Haradon, 1983 and *Uroplectes*. For example, *Hadrurus arizonensis* Ewing, 1928 was given the name “Arizona desert golden scorpion” and its *pallidus* color morph (as a subspecies) was named as “Florida desert golden scorpion” (an erroneous locality!). However, the name “California desert golden scorpion” assigned for *Smeringurus mesaensis* (Stahnke, 1957) led many people to believe that those species are closely related.

In a more complicated case, the name “fat-tailed scorpion” is used for both the genus *Androctonus* (except for *A. amoreuxi* (Audouin, 1826)) and the species *Mesobuthus thersites* (as *M. mongolicus*, see Kovařík et al. (2022)) with a geographic modifier “Pakistan”, an erroneous distribution of the species), leading many newcomers to believe the latter was a species of the former. Additionally, the *Androctonus baluchicus* (Pocock, 1900) is named a “Pakistan black fat-tailed scorpion” which further confuses its relationship with the species *M. thersites*. *A. amoreuxi* is named a “Libyan golden scorpion” while the source of the specimens is actually Morocco. Moreover, the name “fat-tailed scorpion” is often confused with the name “thick-tailed scorpion” which usually refers to the genus *Parabuthus*. As a result, names like “fat thick tail scorpion” appeared. Furthermore, in the genus *Parabuthus*, the vernacular names of two species (*P. pallidus* Pocock, 1895 and *P. maximus* Werner, 1913 (wrongly identified as *P. liosoma* (Ehrenberg, 1828))) were ended with “thick tail golden scorpion”, arousing the confusion of their

assignments to the “vernacular genera” “golden scorpion” or “thick-tailed scorpion”. The name “fat-tailed scorpion”, combined with an adjective modifier “black”, referred to either a certain species in the genus *Androctonus* (e.g., *A. bicolor* and *A. mauritanicus* (Pocock, 1902)) or all the black species within it. The name “black thick-tailed scorpion” refers to a single species, *Parabuthus transvaalicus* Purcell, 1899. The distinctions between *A. mauritanicus* and *P. transvaalicus* are actually rather obvious, yet such similar vernacular names have “pre-inculcated” a sense of similarity which obstructed the beginners’ judgement. Finally, the species *P. pallidus* is also called an “albino black thick-tailed scorpion”. However, it is not a color form of *P. transvaalicus* and these two species are not phylogenetically close.

By the same token, the name “rainforest scorpion” refers to both the species *Heterometrus silenus* (Simon, 1884) and its genus. The name “emperor scorpion” refers to both the species *Pandinus imperator* and its genus. These names are not specifically confined and lead to the confusion when a “diagnostic key” is proposed by some Chinese amateurs. They define a “rainforest scorpion” as a scorpion with black telson and smooth chela and an “emperor scorpion” a scorpion with red telson and rough chela. These characteristics are actually only valid for the specific species, *H. silenus* and *P. imperator*. However, since these two vernacular names can also refer to the two genera, some beginners may consider it as a “generic key”, which further aroused confusions when they saw *Heterometrus* species with a red telson and rough chela (e.g., *Chersonesometrus fulvipes* (C.L. Koch, 1837), previously in the genus *Heterometrus*), wondering why it is not assigned to *Pandinus*. The vernacular name of *H. longimanus* (Herbst, 1800) is a “long-clawed rainforest scorpion”. This vernacular name is partially reasonable as the specific epithet is a combination of *longus* (long) and *manus* (hand). However, another species that appeared later in the Chinese pet trade, *H. thorellii* (Pocock, 1892) is also called a “long-clawed rainforest scorpion”, and sometimes as “Thorell’s long-clawed rainforest scorpion”. As a result, many beginners refer to the latter as the “long-clawed rainforest scorpion”, which overrides the legitimacy and priority of the vernacular name for *H. longimanus*.

Finally, just like for the so-called “*Androctonus crassicauda israe*” case mentioned above, many traders fabricated a subspecific name for *A. australis* from Tunisia, “*Androctonus australis tunisia*” (or sometimes “tunisien”). There has never been such a subspecies, yet many amateurs firmly believe it to be a valid name. The confirmed distribution of *A. australis* in Africa includes Algeria, Chad, Egypt, Libya, Mali, Morocco, Niger, Sudan and Tunisia. Tunisia is actually the region with the most abundant occurrence of this species in Africa. Many *A. australis* sold on pet market are from this country, so this fabricated “subspecific name” is not meaningful if no precise locality is provided. Additionally, several Chinese vernacular names were used for the species *A. australis* and its former subspecies. *A. australis* was named an “Egyptian yellow fat-tailed scorpion” (or simply “yellow fat-tailed scorpion”), *A.*

australis hector a “Hector yellow fat-tailed scorpion”, *A. australis libycus* “Libyan yellow fat-tailed scorpion” and the fabricated name “*Androctonus australis tunisia*” as “Tunisian yellow fat-tailed scorpion”. Later, when the existence of the nominotypic subspecies, *A. australis australis*, was realized by the traders, they treated it as a taxon independent from *A. australis*. This created further confusion. Nominotypic subspecies indeed has a separate range and identity but often it appears in literature by default, “automatically”, when any other subspecies is described. Its type specimen and locality are the same as in the species. At any rate, all the subspecies of *A. australis* were synonymized in 2009 by A. Ben Othmen et al., currently leaving no subspecies valid.

Breene et al. (2003) updated a list of English common names of arachnids and the code for designating common names, mostly for the common species distributed in United States and Canada, as well as several globally well-known taxa. They stated in the introduction that common names had been demonstrated as more stable than scientific names since the latter may change due to priority, improper use of Latin, misidentification (including taxonomic changes), and many other reasons. However, the most prominent problem of many common names is that one name can be used for multiple taxa and one taxon could have multiple names that are used contemporaneously (they will not be replaced in case of junior synonyms in scientific names). For scorpions only, their list failed to list many other common names for one species (which will falsify the superiority of the common names) and some names are not exclusively for one species. For instance, the English common name for the species *Androctonus australis* was given as “fattail scorpion”. However, this species also has names like “yellow fat-tailed scorpion”, “Egyptian fat-tailed scorpion” and “Sahara scorpion”. On the other hand, the name “fattail scorpion” alone (without any premodifier) is also used for the genus *Androctonus* (the entire genus or some species), genus *Parabuthus* (the entire genus or some species), genus *Hottentotta* (some species), genus *Lychas* (some species), *Orthochirus scrobiculosus negebensis*, and even family Buthidae. Similarly, the name “Asian forest scorpion” was used only for *Heterometrus longimanus* by Breene et al. (2003), but this name (sometimes with a middle modifier such as “giant” or “blue”) actually refers to many other congeneric species (e.g. *H. spinifer*, *H. silenus* (formerly misidentified as *H. petersii*), *H. laoticus* and *H. cyaneus* (now *Javanimetrus cyaneus*)) and even the genus itself. Although a regulation for designating common names is provided in their paper, there seems to be no specific reason for each name and those names may just had been selected from several well-known common names. Their intention of setting a regulation for the common names is exemplary, although it will be rather difficult (and even minimally effective since the common names are subjective and arbitrary) to formally establish a list with each species having its exclusive name. Their regulation is not so informative for the present study since their nomenclature is not simply based on the etymology of the taxon, not to mention that an English translation of the

Latin name can simply be much longer than the original one (and would often sound weird).

In China, a non-English speaking country, the formal Chinese names are given to the animal species that are involved in research for the convenience of the daily communication and public cognition. This formal Chinese name somewhat resembles the English common names *sensu* Breene et al. (2003) in the sense of purpose. Nevertheless, the nomenclature is as well far from standardization. These formal Chinese names can be subdivided into several types: (a) the translated names of Latin names (usually including: literal translation, free translation and transliteration, often wrongly or incompletely translated), (b) the translated names of English common names, (c) the Chinese folk names, (d) the vernacular names used in pet trades and among amateurs, and (e) the self-created names for certain taxa that have nothing to do with the original meanings of the Latin names. These different approaches lead to a chaotic condition which often causes misunderstandings or conflicts. This current situation may result from the neglect of the global-scale taxonomy and the lack of the sense of overall view. These names usually occur in the Chinese scientific publications and college students’ thesis which influence the self-learning of amateurs. The following examples will keep the original Chinese names.

The folk names for certain species are relatively scarce in China, since almost only one species is the best known, i.e., *O. martensii*; yet one is applied in the formal Chinese name for the genus *Buthus*, which is the “钳蝎”, as mentioned above. But this genus currently is only known from Middle East, Africa, and Southern Europe (Sousa et al., 2017). This genus has never been recorded from China; nevertheless, it is given a Chinese name. The reason could be the old classification, as *O. martensii* was originally described in the genus *Buthus*. Thus, the name may simply come from the appellation by the civilians who would easily spot this species in rural areas. However, there are people wondering why it is named as the “pincer scorpion”, as all the scorpions have a pair of pedipalps and there is nothing special in either the morphology or the function of the pincers of the genus *Buthus*. Since the reason to call this genus as “钳蝎” is irrational and it is not endemic to China (a fact that would eliminate the excuse of “for a cultural and historical sense”; i.e., some people hold on to the opinion that if a species holds a traditional name for hundreds or thousands of years, this name can be reckoned as its formal Chinese name), the name should be altered (see below).

In the Chinese publication “中国宠物商店出售的2种越南异蝎” by Mingsheng Zhu (朱明生) and Xiaofeng Yang (杨啸风) (2007) (the paper, which published the species *Heterometrus liangi*), two species names were wrongly translated. *Heterometrus laoticus* Couzijn, 1981 was called as “石异蝎” (the “rock different-scorpion”, if directly translated). “异蝎” is the formal Chinese name of the genus *Heterometrus* which will be further discussed. However, the word “石” means “stone” while the specific epithet is a Latinized toponym denoting the species’ distribution in Laos. *Centruroides limpidus* Karsch, 1879 was called “弯曲帝王蝎”.

However, “帝王蝎” is the Chinese equivalence of “emperor scorpion” which generally refers to the species *P. imperator* as mentioned before (“非洲波蝎” is also used in a Chinese scorpology book; the “African wave scorpion”, if directly translated). The specific epithet *limpidus* means “light”, from ancient Greek λάμπω (*lámō*, “to shine”). It does not mean “bent (as in Chinese “弯曲”)). In the college student thesis “沙漠蝎子体表感受器的仿生研究” by Huaxing Zhang (2018), two species in the article were wrongly identified. He used the vernacular name “巴基斯坦黄鳄背蝎”, which originally refers to the subspecies *H. tamulus gangeticus*, for *A. australis*, and used the formal Chinese name of *Mesobuthus* (now *Olivierus*) *caucasicus* (Nordmann, 1840), “高加索正钳蝎”, for *P. maximus*.

Several names can be contradictory within one Chinese paper, or the name of a certain taxon can differ among different papers. In the thesis “中国藏滇琼三省区蝎目分类区系研究（螯肢亚门：蛛形纲）” by Zhiyong Di (2009), there are several inconsistent Chinese names for certain taxa, or wrongly or incompletely translated names of Latin names. The first time when family Bothriuridae Simon, 1880 appeared, the author called it “穴居蝎科” (the “borrow-dwelling scorpion”; “科” stands for the Chinese equivalence of family rank) while it was subsequently termed as “穴尤蝎科” (cannot be literally translated; the Pinyin will be “xué yóu xī kē”). The superfamily Chactoidea Pocock, 1893 was called “刚毛蝎总科” (the “seta scorpion”; “总科” or “超科” stands for the Chinese equivalence of superfamily rank; “超” is equal to “super” while “总” is equal to “overall”). However, the superfamily Pseudochactoidea Gromov, 1998, which only differs from the former in the prefix *pseudo-* (meaning “fake” or “false”), was called as “拟湿地蝎总科” (the “false wetland scorpion”). Since the word “拟” is equal to the meaning of the prefix, the author apparently referred to Chactoidea as “湿地蝎总科” which is inconsistent with the former parlance. The subfamily Superstitioniinae Stahnke, 1940 (now elevated to the family rank as Superstitioniidae) was wrongly translated as “幻蝎亚科” (“亚科” stands for the Chinese equivalence of subfamily rank). “幻” means “illusory”, “unreal”, “magical”, or “changeable”, but not “superstition”. However, this taxon was named after a place, Superstition Mountains in Arizona, USA. The family Vaejovidae Thorell, 1876 was wrongly translated as “狱神蝎科” which literally means “hell god scorpion”. Although the etymology of its type genus *Vaejovis* C. L. Koch, 1836 was indeed named after a god’s name, it has nothing to do with the Underworld (which will be further discussed below). The subfamily Urodacinae Pocock, 1893 (now elevated to the family rank as Urodacidae) seems to be transliterated. It was called as “拟尤里蝎亚科” in the paper as “尤里” (Pinyin “yóu lǐ”) may be the transliteration of the first three letters. However, the prefix “拟” was added for unknown reason as there is no prefix of equivalence in the Latin name. Superfamily Iuroidea Thorell, 1876 was transliterated as “尤蝎总科” (transliteration of the first two letters) but in other papers, there is an alternative name “巨蝎总科”. The name “巨蝎” (“giant scorpion”) is again used as the formal

Chinese name of genus *Pandinus* as seen in IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Chinese edition). Similarly, family Microcharmidae Lourenço, 1996 was called in this paper “悦蝎科” (“pleasing scorpion”; wrongly translated), but as “小迷蝎科” (“little charming scorpion”; probably correctly translated, see below) in other papers. Family Caraboctonidae Kraepelin, 1905 was called in this paper “棘蝎科” (“spiny scorpion”; wrongly translated), but as “毛蝎科” (“hairy scorpion”; wrongly translated) in other papers. Family Troglotayosicidae Lourenço, 1998 was wrongly translated as “掘洞蝎科 (cave-digging scorpion)”. The name is a combination of prefix *troglo-* (meaning “troglobitic”) and a toponym, Caves of Los Tayos, Ecuador. The species under this family do not dig deep burrows by themselves; instead, they live in already existed natural caves. Superfamily Chaeriloidea Pocock, 1893 was wrongly translated as “豚蝎总科” or “豕蝎总科” (both of which mean “pig scorpion”), based on an erroneous etymology (ancient Greek χοίρος (*choiros*), meaning “pig”; the etymology will be further discussed below). Finally, family Liochelidae Fet & Bechly, 2001 (a junior synonym of Hormuridae Laurie, 1896) was translated as “链尾蝎科”. However, this is a correct translation of the family Hormuridae Laurie, 1896 as it derives from ancient Greek ὄρμος (*hórmos*) which means “a necklace (“项链”, in Chinese)” or “a chain (“锁链”, in Chinese)” and οὐρά (*ourá*) which means “tail (“尾”, in Chinese)”. Yet the formal Chinese name of Hormuridae was transliterated by the first three letters as “霍尔蝎科”.

In the thesis “中国蝎目分类与资源状况（螯肢亚门：蛛形纲）” by Dong Sun (2010), the Chinese name of Pseudochactidae was changed into “伪毛蝎科” (“伪” is another Chinese equivalence for the prefix), maybe to ensure the consistence of the translation of Chactidae; however, this conflicts with one of the formal names of Caraboctonidae (“毛蝎科”). Superstitioniidae was changed into “顶蝎科”, which might be a misunderstanding of the word “super” since “顶” means “top” in English. Urodacidae was changed into “尾煞蝎科”, which is half right (*uro-* means “tail” while *dakos* means “bite” or “sting”, meanings that are not considered for the Chinese word “煞”). Vaejovidae was wrongly transliterated as “瓦乔蝎科” as the original name of the god is Vejovis (Latin: Vēiovis or Vēdiovis; rare Vēive or Vēdius) which sounds more like “维 (wéi)” in Chinese rather than “瓦 (wǎ)”. Subfamily Diplocentrinae Karsch, 1880 was translated as “双轴蝎亚科” (the “double-axis scorpion”) whereas other papers correctly translated it as “双棘蝎” (*diplos* means “two” and *kentron* means “spike”, referring to the subaculear tubercle on the telson). Several other names were also wrongly translated. Subfamily Megacorminae Karsch, 1881 was literally translated as “巨木蝎亚科” (the “giant wood scorpion”). Although κόρμος (*kormos*) itself does mean “tree trunk” or “log”, it also stands for “trunk” or “body” which hereby refers to the massive body of the scorpion. A closely related taxon, tribe Troglacormini Francke, 1981 was wrongly translated as “朽木蝎族” (“族” stands for the Chinese equivalence of tribe rank). This genus was based on the prefix *troglo-* and its sister genus *Megacormus*, alluding to its habitat and relationship. The

Chinese word “朽” literally means “rotten” which, in turn, “朽木蝎” is translated as “rotten wood scorpion”. Inconsistencies also exist in this paper. When the family Euscorpidae Laurie, 1896 first appeared in this paper, it was correctly translated as “真蝎科” (prefix *eu-* stands for “true, real, good, beautiful” and “真” means “real”). But when it is referred as a subfamily (i.e., Euscorpinae), its name changed into “欧蝎亚科”. Obviously, the author mistook the prefix as “Europe” (“欧” is the transliteration of Europe). Etymologically, the word “Europe” derives from ancient Greek combination of εὐρύς (eurys, “wide”) and ὄψ (ops, “face” or “eye”). If the scorpion’s name meant “European scorpion”, it should have been named an “Euroscorpium” instead. “异蝎科” (“different scorpion”) is a correct translation of family Heteroscorpionidae Kraepelin, 1905 (prefix *heteros-* means “different”) used in Chinese publications but arouses conflicts with the formal Chinese name designated for the genus *Heterometrus*. A fossil taxon, family Palaeoeuscorpidae Lourenço, 2003 was translated as “古欧蝎科”. The prefix *palaeo-* was correctly translated (“古” means “old” or “ancient”), yet it seems that the author again changed the name of Euscorpidae into “欧蝎科”. Another two fossil taxa were also wrongly translated. Family Protoischnuridae Carvalho & Lourenço, 2001 was translated as “原异蝎科”. The prefix *proto-* was correctly translated (“原” means “original” or “initial” in English), yet the second half was wrongly translated for unknown reason. The second half, derived from the family name Ischnuridae Simon, 1879 (a senior synonym of Hormuridae Laurie, 1896, although Hormuridae is considered as a valid name today) was correctly translated as “瘦尾蝎科” (“thin tailed scorpion”) in other papers (prefix *ischnos-* means “spindly, slender or thin”). Finally, family Palaeopisthacanthidae Kjellesvig-Waering 1986 was translated as “古豆蝎科” for unknown reason. The prefix *palaeo-* was correctly translated, but the second half comes from a genus under Hormuridae, genus *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861, which is a combination of *opisthe-* (behind) and *-akantha* (spine), yet the word “豆” means “a bean” in English. The problem of *Heterometrus*, *Heteroscorpion*, *Euscorpions* and *Euscorpium* has already attracted attention in the Chinese academic circle (pers. comm. of Chinese scorpologist Di Zhiyong).

Besides these suprageneric ranks, the formal Chinese names for several genera and species are also either wrongly translated or unrelated to the original meaning. Genus *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908 was named after the Hottentots (Khoikhoi), nomad pastoral people of Namibia and South Africa. Its formal Chinese name is “壕蝎属” (“属” stands for the Chinese equivalence of genus rank), apparently a transliteration of the first two letters. However, “壕” (háo) means “moat” or “ditch”, which may lead to the misunderstanding that all the species of this genus lives in soil pits. Genus *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845 is wrongly translated as “狼蝎属” (the “wolf scorpion”), based on a mistaken etymology, λύκος (lúkos or lykanos, “wolf”). The etymology of this name will be further discussed below. As mentioned before, *Buthus* was named as “钳蝎”, hence, *Mesobuthus* is

named as “正钳蝎”. However, the prefix *mesos* (μέσος) means “middle, intermediate”. This could be due to the relatively medium size of the type species, *M. eupeus* (C. L. Koch, 1839) (35–60 mm) when comparing with that of genus *Buthus* (*B. occitanus* (Amoreux, 1789), 60–80 mm). The prefix is often seen in many words, such as Mesopotamia (“between rivers”). In other fields, this prefix is never translated as “正” (e.g., “中生代” for “Mesozoic”). As in English, “正” usually means “upright” or “orthodox”, or “straight”, “positive”, “normal” and “correct”. There is one scorpion genus that can be more reasonably translated as “正钳蝎”, *Orthochirus*, as the prefix *orthos-* means “straight” or “upright”, and *chirus* means “hand” (for scorpions referring to the pedipalp chela). But its current formal Chinese name “直钳蝎” is flawless (“直” equals to “straight”), as the reason for naming it as *Orthochirus* results from the straight shape of its chela. The formal Chinese name for genus *Sassanidotus* Farzanpay, 1987 is redundantly translated as “萨钳蝎” since there is either no “*buthus*” or word that stands for “chela” presented in its name. “萨 (sà)” is apparently the transliteration of the first two letters, and the etymology will be discussed below. Genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay 1987 was initially wrongly translated as “橄蝎” (the “olive scorpion”). However, the genus name does not come from “olive”, but from the French entomologist, Guillaume-Antoine Olivier and it was correctly re-translated in a subsequent paper (Shi & Zhang, 2005) as “奥氏蝎” (“Olivier’s scorpion”). Incomplete translations are used for the genus *Tibetiomachus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 and *Heterometrus*. The former is a combination of geographic modifier *tibet-* (Tibet) and genus *Iomachus* Pocock, 1893 (literally meaning “poisonous warrior”, from *ios-* and *makhētēs*). Yet its Chinese name is only designated as “藏蝎” (the “Tibetan scorpion”). The latter is a combination of *heteros-* and *metrios* (measurement). The reason for naming as such is that the type species (the species that presents the characters of the genus, designated originally or subsequently) *Heterometrus spinifer* (Ehrenberg, 1828) was originally described in the genus *Buthus*. However, the morphological traits are inconsistent with the type species of the latter, thus a new genus was then established. Its formal Chinese name is “异蝎” (the “different scorpion”) which conflicts with another, correctly translated taxon, Heteroscorpionidae (see above). Similarly, genus *Isometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 is simply translated as “等蝎” (“equal scorpion”), but there has been no conflict for now. The naming of two taxa, *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 and *Euscorpions* Vachon, 1980, are inconsistent and erroneous. The former is translated as “琵琶蝎” (“pipa scorpion”) while the latter, which merely added a prefix, is translated as “真蝎” (“real scorpion”). As mentioned before, Euscorpidae was correctly translated as “真蝎科”, hence its type genus, *Euscorpium* Thorell, 1876 ought to be “真蝎属”. However, such naming of the genus *Euscorpions* will lead to the confusion between it and the genus *Euscorpium*. The reason of naming *Scorpiops* as “琵琶蝎” is hereby conjectured. *Scorpiops* is a combination of genus *Scorpio* Linnaeus, 1758 and suffix *-ops*, while the suffix means “appearance”. As a result, those people may have

mistaken the meaning as “scorpionish scorpion” (they did not realize that the “scorpio” part actually stands for another genus rather than “a scorpion”). As mentioned above, the Chinese consider the scorpion body similar to the shape of the Chinese musical instrument, pipa “琵琶”. Consequently, “琵琶蝎” (the “pipa-shaped scorpion”) was named as an alternative for “蝎形蝎” (the “scorpion-shaped scorpion”). However, the etymology of this genus alludes to the similar morphology of these two genera. Nevertheless, even if the *Scorpiops* is called as “琵琶蝎”, “真琵琶蝎” should be the name of *Euscorpiops*, accordingly (in fact, *Euscorpiops* is now synonymized with *Scorpiops*.)

Finally, the formal Chinese names of several species are also either wrongly or disorderly translated. For example, *Lychas scutillus* C. L. Koch, 1845 is given a name as “盾狼蝎”. Though the suffix *scuti-* does mean “shield” (“盾” as in Chinese), *scutillus* is an independent word which actually means “slender”. If the specific epithet is an eponym, the formal Chinese names will either be a complete transliteration of a name or a transliteration of the first syllable followed by “氏” (denoting that the species was named after a person). Obviously, the simultaneous use of these two methods is disorderly as toponyms are also fully transliterated in China, which creates a confusion in whether the name is derived from a person or a place. In scorpions, one species’ name was wrongly transliterated. *Euscorpiops novaki* Kovařík, 2005 (now *Scorpiops novaki*) was completely transliterated as “诺瓦基真蝎” (the Pinyin of the first three words are “nuò wǎ jī”), which is similar to the pronunciation of “novaki”. However, “i” is not included in the original name (Jindřich Novák, a Czech ichthyologist) but is a termination (masculine), which implies the specific epithet is named after a male person.

The examples given above demonstrate the confusion in the current Chinese names for scorpions. The problems presented by the amateur names result from a lack of sense of science and if the issue is not resolved, there will be more beginners confused with the puzzling names. Yet, even in the professional papers, names are chaotic likewise. This is a consequence of lacking a standardized (nationally recognized) translation regulation and an ignorance of the Chinese naming of scorpions since Latin names are academically the only important ones. The strong existence of this phenomenon can be proved by the only Chinese academic book for scorpions, *Scorpion Biology and Toxins* (Fig. 3). The consistent and ubiquitous problem in this book is the disordered employment of Latin names and Chinese names. Many species were called by their old Latin names (even considering the time of publication of this book, 2016) and some of them were wrongly spelled (even within a same species). The Chinese name for the same species (or genus, family) may not be consistent as well. For many species, names initially appeared in Latin only, while given Chinese names later (and some of them later again appearing only in Latin). In this case, both the inconsistent Chinese name and Latin name can appear solely, or together. Besides, using terms like “buthid” or “vaejovid” without explanation cannot make the beginners to understand

what they mean. This shows that even Chinese experts do not pay much attention to the names of scorpions, which will obviously cause confusion for those who do not know much about scorpions. There will be amateurs who search for domestic papers for intensive study and those confusing names are the obstacles in their way. In my opinion, the public should have a sense of scientific names, and scientific names are the only true names of the animals. Nevertheless, the Chinese public is mostly either unfamiliar with or good at memorizing Latin names. Therefore, Chinese equivalents are rather important for the knowledge of the animals. And in order to respect those who created Latin names, to reduce the confusion and to grasp a fundamental idea of the taxonomy (indicated by the Latin names), the formal Chinese names should better be correctly translated, based on the etymology of the Latin names as far as possible under a standardized regulation. The correctly translated Latin names (when possible) are merely equivalents in another language which do not alter the original meaning. All the Chinese names that are not related to the Latin names should be noted. The public should know that, in the context of biological science, there is no such thing as “original names”; the only valid, objective names given to animals are the Latin ones.

The present study formally proposes a regulation of translation of Latin names, and provides translations of all the valid extant scorpion species. This regulation is intended only for China (or may also be applicative to the countries sharing similar grammatical rules). However, there are some problems that need to be mentioned. As a matter of fact, I have been perfecting my translating method for years since I realized the chaos in the Chinese names of scorpions. All my translated names were published as articles online. Some people consider that common names are more likely to spread. However, this only results from the fact that the first impressions are firmly entrenched. In those amateur circles where formal names (most of which are correctly translated) are more abundant than common names, people use and memorize these formal names anyway. The only thing that matters is which name is pre-inculcated. Those who consider common names to be easily spread are merely comparing the translated names that appeared later with the common names they encountered first. No one has ever proved him- or herself to be capable of naming all the species regardless of the etymologies of their scientific names. Moreover, some radical people in China are fond of renaming the species after their morphology; but one cannot ensure the feature they use to be unique and unchangeable (it has to be, or there is no justified superiority over Latin names with the same problem). The species that were originally named after modern persons are usually the most common “victims”. There is a misguided sentiment among some Chinese public that memorizing the names of foreigners denigrates one’s own culture. Such behavior demonstrates disrespect of the original authors who created important eponyms naming species after their friends, colleagues, mentors, etc. Many of the eponyms were given after famous names (in scorpology, such as Pocock, Simon,

Birula, or Vachon). Changing those names erases precious memory about personalities, and destroys the historical record of scientific discovery, as would do any arbitrary renaming of cities or streets or “canceling” historical figures and events.

Although numerous people either do not want to change the scorpion names they use (due to personal sentiment or habit), or consider it unimportant, more and more people are now accepting and using my translated names, either because of the popularization of these names by other keepers or traders, or the common view we share on this matter. This is solid evidence that the names for scorpions can be changed with effort and by time, and turning chaotic vernacular names into standardized translations is not as difficult or negative as some people may deem.

Actually, I later found that I was not the first one who proposed a standardization in Chinese animal names. Qiyu Hu (1991) discussed vernacular names applied in the nematodes that are parasitic on plants and criticized its limited usability in coining formal Chinese names. Cangsang Pan (1998) was the first to systematically translate all the mermithid names according to the etymology. Zhang (Zhisheng) et al. (2015) proposed the first advice on formulating Chinese names for spiders. Similar proposals appeared in botany. Already Changan Wang (1958) categorized several common situations in the etymology of plant scientific names, listed with examples. Yanwen Zhang (1992) argued that the Chinese names for plants should be standardized. Wang (Yuan) et al. (2013) proposed the Chinese naming regulation for plants. Wang (Xinguo) et al. (2012) also emphasized the danger that confusing Chinese names may bring in the professional areas (e.g., biological quarantine). Although I am not familiar with the plants (but I do know many plant names are rather hard to translate into Chinese even when the etymology is known, unlike in animals), these previous authors demonstrate that the standardization of Chinese name for living organisms is not an opinion of a single individual. The aim of this contribution is not to gain acceptance; instead, it provides all the true scorpion aficionados in China with a systematized reference, as well as a train of thought for the researchers in other fields in translating the Latin names (if they want to use translation instead of renaming).

Etymological diversity of scientific scorpion names

Scorpions are named in a variety of ways, reflecting the morphology, type locality, behavior, habitat, modern people name, ancient character or mythology, vernacular or native name, and taxonomic relationship. The present study will demonstrate the etymological diversity of scorpion scientific names in detail. All the names can be allocated into several categories which will be explained below. In addition, examples of generic and specific epithets of scorpions will be given in order to propose a new standardized translating regulation. The terminology (morphonyms, taxonyms, etc) follows James (2010) and Dupré (2016).

Abbreviations: Gr. = Greek; L. =Latin.

1. Morphonym

Morphonym (Gr. *morphē* form; *onuma* name) is the name that based on coloration and physical characters. It is one of the most common etymologies used in the nomenclature for both genus and species. The name can be a single word or a combination of several words. Sometimes the type of the specific epithet can be told from certain suffixes. For example, in *Opisthophthalmus flavescens* Purcell, 1898 and *Centruroides nigrescens* Pocock, 1898, both of the specific epithets are a combination of a certain color (*nigros* for “black” and *flavus* for “yellow”) with the suffix *-escens* (becoming) that usually follows after the word indicating color. Similarly, in *Uroplectes olivaceus* Pocock, 1896 and *Javanimetrus cyaneus* (C.L. Koch, 1836), both of the specific epithets are combinations of a certain color (*oliva* for “olive-colored” and *cyan* for “greenish blue”) with the suffix *-āceus* (suffix *-āx* “inclined to” and *-eus*) or *-eus* (suffix indicating origin) that also usually follow after the word indicating color. These names can be classified as chromonyms (which will be considered separately from morphonyms in the Appendix). The morphonym can also be an adjective (e.g., *parvulus* = “dwarf”; *elongatus* = “prolonged”), a combination of an adjective and a body part (e.g., *cavimanus* = “sunken hand”), a structure or a pattern with a prefix or a suffix (e.g., *Bioculus* = “two eyed”; *trilineatus* = “three lined”; *spinifer* = “with spine”), a pattern without a prefix or a suffix (e.g., *vittatus* = “lined”), and a color with a type of a pattern (e.g., *flavostictus* = “yellow spot”) or a combination of several colors (e.g., *flavoviridis* = “yellow green”).

Although the morphonym can sometimes (rarely) be called a “charactonym”, the definition of the latter is hereby restricted to the features of a species that exclude the direct descriptions for phenotypic characters. For example, the specific epithet of *Pandinurus exitialis* (Pocock, 1888) means “lethal”; *Centruroides infamatus* C. L. Koch, 1844 was named for its infamous toxicity. Words that mean “fearsome” are also included here as I do not know whether an author’s impression was triggered by the appearance or toxicity. The morphonym in the Appendix is considered as “using specific body structures for naming” or “using explicit adjectives/prefixes/suffixes to describe a species or a genus (e.g., small, median, big, shiny, translucent, beautiful, colorful, simple, complicated and distinguished; adjectives that only suggest resemblance, uncertainty or difference will be excluded)”. Even if other types of names may indicate the morphology of the species, they are not hereby classified as morphonyms. Additionally, a chromonym is only defined as explicit description of color or color pattern (spots and stripes).

2. Taxonym

Taxonym (Gr. *taxis* arrangement; *onuma* name) is the name that suggests interspecific or intergeneric relationships (either morphologically or phylogenetically) or resemblances. It is usually in either the combination of two taxa or one taxon that is modified by a prefix or a suffix. For example, *Chaerilus pseudoconchiformus* Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015 was named after *Chaerilus conchiformus* Zhu, Han & Lourenço,

2008 with a prefix *pseudo-* (fake) indicating the similar morphology while not being the same species. *Heteroscorpion opisthacanthoides* (Kraepelin, 1896) was named after the genus *Opisthacanthus* with suffix *-oides* (resembling). *Parascorpiops* Banks, 1928 was named after *Scorpiops* with prefix *para-* (close to, nearby). *Pandinopsis* Vachon, 1974 was named after *Pandinus* with suffix *-opsis* (appearance, same with *-ops*). *Tityobuthus* Pocock, 1893 is a combination of the genera *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836 and *Buthus*. A similar case is *Cicileiurus* Teruel, 2007, which is a combination of the genera *Cicileus* Vachon, 1948 and *Leiurus*. However, not all the generic names named after another with a prefix indicate the close relationship or resemblance. For example, *Microbuthus* Kraepelin, 1898 only means “a small buthid (buthid stands for the taxa that are under Family Buthidae C. L. Koch, 1837)”. Nevertheless, it still serves as a taxonym as it indicates its subordinate relationship with the family Buthidae. Additionally, some taxonyms will be misleading if the relationship indicated by the original author is erroneous. For instance, the genus *Pseudochactas* Gromov, 1998 was named after *Chactas* Gervais, 1844. Yet, the former genus is not related to the latter, but to *Buthus* and *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 instead. In the specific epithet, however, some adjectives also indicate relationships and these names do not state which species do they resemble.

The taxonym in the appendix is considered as “contains another genus/species name or other genera names”, “uses prefix or suffix that suggest resemblance, uncertainty or difference” and “indirectly suggests resemblance, uncertainty or difference by using adjectives (e.g., similar, close, uncertain, fake, problematic, intermediate, half, dubious, confusing and deceiving)”.

3. Toponym

Toponym (Gr. *topos* place; *onuma* name) is the name of the type locality (or at least labeled so) of the species or the genus, which is usually ended with suffix like *-ensis* (e.g., *Neochactas sarisarinamensis* (González-Sponga, 1985)), *-us* (e.g., *Compsobuthus pakistanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2007) or *-ia* (e.g., *Microtityus eustatia* Armas, 2018). The toponym can also be in the generic epithet which is usually modified by a prefix (e.g., *Aegaeobuthus* = buthid of the Aegean Region). Additionally, the name of the place of itself can also be Latinized as the genus name (e.g., *Karasbergia* Hewitt, 1913, named after the Karasberg Hill in Northern Cape, South Africa). This name can be classified as a oronym which is named after a mountain. More precise terms within the toponym like insulonym (or nesonym, e.g., *Hottentotta socotrensis* (Pocock, 1889)), limnonym (e.g., *Uroplectes malawicus* Prendini, 2015), oceanym (e.g., *Serradigitus pacificus* (Williams, 1980)), potamonym (e.g., *Hottentotta niloticus* (Birula, 1928)) and speleonym (e.g., *Tityus grottoedensis* Botero-Trujillo & Flórez, 2014) are used for islands, lakes, oceans, rivers and caves, respectively.

Toponym is a general word while choronym is used for places like a region, a country or any other territories. This

concept hereby (in the appendix) only refers to a rough geographic range like “from southern region (*australis*)”. Sometimes, the toponym is not a geographical place. Eponym (or oeconym, oikonym) is a general word used for any inhabited settlement or place. The astionym is coined exclusively for names that used in apposition to cities and towns (e.g., *Neobuthus erigavoensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018) and comonym for villages (e.g., *Isometrus amboli* Shauri, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020). The term ecodomonym is used to refer specifically to a building as an inhabited place. For example, *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987 was named after Institute Razi in Iran; *Kovarikia oxy* Bryson, Graham & Soleglad, 2018 was named after the nickname of Occidental College; *Tityus imei* Borges, de Sousa & Manzanilla, 2006 was named after the abbreviation of Instituto de Medicina Experimental, and it is also an acronym (a term named by the initials); likewise, *Tityus ivicnancor* González-Sponga, 1997 was named after the abbreviation of Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas and Latin *nancor* (found). Slightly different, *Akrav israchanani* Levy, 2007 was named after the type locality (Israel) and its finder Chanan Dimentman, thus making it a combination of a toponym and an eponym (see below).

Sometimes a name may be a metonym. For example, *Uroctonites sequoia* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) was named after the Sequoia National Park; *Pseudouroctonus peccatum* Tate, Riddle, Soleglad & Graham, 2013 was named for its type locality being near Las Vegas (the “Sin City”) and the specific epithet means “sin” in Latin; the specific epithet of *Auyantepuia aurum* Ythier, 2018 means “gold” in Latin as there had been a gold rush in its type locality, Saül, during the early 19th century; the specific epithet of *Konetontli ignes* González-Santillan & Prendini, 2015 itself is the Latin word for “fire” and the name of its type locality Fogos is the Portuguese word for “fires”. A special case is for the genus *Sassanidotus*, which was named after Sassanide dynasty, an empire that was in Persia (now Iran), alluding its locality. This case can be classified as the paleonym (the ancient name for a place) and will be considered separately from the toponym in the Appendix.

The toponym in the Appendix is only considered as “using the modern name of a place (no restriction on its range or type)” or “using metonym to allude to a place”.

4. Eponym

Eponym (Gr. *epōnumos* ‘named after’) is a name that commemorates a person. There are various suffixes indicating it is a person’s name, such as *-i*, *-ii*, *-ius*, *-ae*, *-um*, *-ia* and *-us*. The former four are usually seen in specific epithets while the last two in generic ones (*-oides* is rarely seen but *Simonoides* Vachon & Farzanpay, 1987 (a junior synonym of *Orthochirus*) is an example). For instance, *Birulatus* Vachon, 1974 was named after the Russian scorpologist, Alexei A. Byalynitskii-Birula. A consonant “t” was added to ensure it reads smoothly. In a specific epithet, it ends with *-i*, as in *Buthacus birulai* Lourenço, 2006. Likewise, when a genus was named after

the German arachnologist, Carl Ludwig Koch, his last name was transformed into *Kochius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008 but ended with *-i* when served as a specific epithet; e.g., *Franckeus kochi* (Sissom, 1991). For a woman's name, it usually ends with *-ae*. If the name consists of multiple names, the termination will be *-orum* (masculine) or *-arum* (feminine). The eponym can also be a combination of a person's name and a name of a related genus (e.g., *Hoffmannihadrurus* Fet & Soleglad, 2004 was named after a Mexican scorpologist, Carlos C. Hoffmann and its sister genus *Hadrurus*). To be more specific, the term "anthroponym" is used for a person's name and especially his/her last name, which is often seen in many taxa. There are also terms like "patronym" or "matronym" (or "metronym"), which indicate a name derived from that of the father (or a paternal ancestor) and the mother (or a maternal ancestor), respectively (in the Appendix, these two are considered for names after author's parents). The term "necronym" is used for someone who had died when the species was found. This name is rarely seen in the scorpions, however, the gecko *Phelsuma hielscheri* Rösler, Obst & Seipp, 2001 was named after Michael Hielscher who was shot by a Malagasy soldier shortly after the species was found. The junior synonym of *Olivierus martensii*, *Buthus confucius* can also be classified as a "hagionym" (or agionym), which commemorates the Chinese saint Confucius (Kongzi, 孔子). Besides the name of a specific individual, an eponym can also be an ethnonym or demonym that used for a native inhabitant, tribe or ethnic group, which is more often seen in scorpions. *Buthus nabataeus* Lourenço, Abu Afifeh & Al-Saraireh, 2021 was named after the Nabataeans, ancient Bedouin people who inhabited northern Arabia and the southern Levant.

Eponym does not always have to be the name of a modern person or ethnic group. For example, *Timogenes* Simon, 1880 was named after Timagène (Τιμαγένης), a Greek historian from 1st century B.C.; *Chaerilus* was named after Choerilus (Χοηρίλος), a Greek epic poet; *Belisarius* Simon, 1879 is the homonym (Βελισάριος) of a general of the Byzantine Empire; *Urophonius eugenicus* (Mello-Leitão, 1931), named after Marcus Eugenicus, the archbishop of Ephesus; *Pachakutej* Ochoa, 2004 is the homonym of the Ninth Inca sovereign from XVth century; *Hottentotta schach* (Birula, 1905), named after Shah, a king in Farsi (now Iran).

Additionally, an eponym can be a "mythonym" when taken from a mythological or folklore character. If the name is from a god or goddess, it can be called a "deonym" (or "theonym"). Such tendency is seen in the species named by Carl Ludwig Koch and Eugène Simon (a French arachnologist), as well as in many recent names. Examples in generic names are as follows: *Teuthraustes* Simon, 1878, named after Teuthras (Τεϋθρας), king of Mysia in Greek mythology; *Zabius* Thorell, 1893, named after the king of Hyperboreans in Greek mythology; *Oiclus* Simon, 1880, named after Oiclus (Οϊκλῆς), father of Amphiarus in Roman mythology; *Hadogenes* Kraepelin, 1894, named after Hades (Ἅδης), the god of the underworld in Greek mythology; *Vaejovis* C. L. Koch, 1836, named after Vejovis,

a god of healing in Roman mythology; *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845, named after Lichas (Λίχας), Hercules' herald in Greek mythology; *Calchas* Birula, 1899, named after Kalkhas (Κάλχας), a Greek seer or priest; *Brotheas* C.L. Koch, 1837, named after Broteas (Βροτέας), son of Tantalus in Greek mythology; *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836 named after Tityos (Τιτυός), a giant in Greek mythology (and additionally a subgenus, *Tityus* (*Atreus*) Gervais, 1843, named after Atreus (Ἄτρεύς), a king of Mycenae in Greek mythology); *Chanek* Francke, Teruel & Santibáñez-López, 2014, named after the Chanekes, legendary creatures in Mexican folklore; *Maaykuyak* González-Santillan & Prendini, 2013 is the Kiliwa for "god of the warrior". Examples in specific epithets are as follows: *Heterometrus silenus* (Simon, 1884), named after Seilēnós (Σειληνός), a god of the forests in Greek mythology; *Srilankametrus caesar* (C.L. Koch, 1841), named after Gaius Julius Caesar, a Roman General and politician; *Androctonus aeneas* C. L. Koch, 1839, named after Aineias (Αἰνείας), a Trojan hero; *Buthus ajax* (C. L. Koch, 1839), named after the Trojan hero Aias (Αἴας); *Buthus halius* (C. L. Koch, 1839), named after a Trojan soldier, Ἄλιόν; *Buthus paris* (C. L. Koch, 1839), named after Paris (Πάρις), prince of Troy; *Mesobuthus eupheus* (C.L. Koch, 1839), named after Epeius (Ἐπειός), a Greek soldier who helped to built the Trojan Horse; *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839), named after Thersites (Θερσίτης), a Greek soldier who was fond of fighting and insulting; *Jaguajir agamemnon* (C.L.Koch, 1839), named after Agamēmnōn (Ἀγαμέμνων), king of Mycenae and the leader of the Greek army in the Trojan war; *Hadogenes tityrus* (Simon, 1888), named after Tityre, a shepherd in Greek mythology; *Scorpiops artemisae* (Kovařík et al., 2015) and *Scorpiops orioni* (Kovařík et al., 2015), both named after two Greek characters who are related with the constellation of Scorpio; *Birulatus astartiae* Stathi & Lourenço, 2003, named after Astarte, an ancient goddess of earth and fertility who was worshiped in the area where this species was collected (the name was inspired by the scorpion digging burrows in the rocky desert); *Femtobuthus shutuae* Lowe, 2010, named after Shutu, a Babylonian goddess of the South Wind (a reference to the night winds in the type locality); *Microbuthus satyrus* Lowe et al., 2018, named after sátyros, a male natural spirit in Greek mythology; *Hadruioides inti* Ythier, 2021, named after the Incan sun god; *Hadruioides pachamama* Ythier, 2021, named after the Incan earth goddess; *Orthochirus krishnai* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983, named after Krishna, a Hindu deity whose name means "blue" in Sanskrit, also a pun denoting the color of the scorpion; *Chactopsis chullachaqui* Ochoa et al., 2013, named after a mythical spirit of the forest with unequal feet (Quechua words, *chulla* and *chaqui* meaning "unequal foot"); *Chactopsis curupira* Ochoa et al., 2013, named after a mythical creature from the folklore of Brazilian Amazonia; *Megachactops kuemoi* Ochoa et al., 2013, named after a deity from the folklore of Piara of Venezuelan Amazonia; *Tityus curupi* Ojanguren-Affilastro et al., 2017, named after Curupí, a goblin of the Guaraní mythology (the legend says

that it chases women in the forests when they venture alone to get firewood); *Teuthraustes newaribe* Lourenço et al., 2011, named after mischievous entities called “nè waribè” or “nè waripè”, who bring disease and death in the Yanomami folklore; *Diplocentrus diablo* Stockwell & Nilsson, 1987, named after a fictional entity, a noun in apposition corresponding to the Spanish word for “evil” (scorpions are the consorts of evil forces for Hispanic locals); *Alacran chamuco* Francke, 2009, named after name of an underworld devil used in parts of Mexico. The invalid names which are also mythonyms are omitted here.

Other eponyms come from the characters of fictional novels: *Chactas*, named after a Natchez Indian character in François-René de Chateaubriand’s novel *Atala, a noble savage*; *Centruroides rodolfoi* Santibanez-Lopez & Contreras-Félix, 2013, named after Rodolfo (Rudolph), the red-nose reindeer which brings hope, peace and joy on Christmas holidays; *Vaejovis baggins* Azzinnari et al., 2021, named after the fictional character Bilbo Baggins in J.R.R. Tolkien’s *The Hobbit* in reference to its small size.

Finally, there are also several eponyms which were given after a group of people, a non-human entity, or occupation: *Euscorpium studentium* Karaman, 2020, named after a group of college students of the Faculty of Sciences in Novi Sad who initiated the cave expedition, leading to the discovery of the new species; *Chactas oxfordi* González-Sponga, 1978 commemorates the collectors of the “Club de Exploradores de la Universidad de Oxford”; the specific epithet of *Mesobuthus brutus* Fet et al., 2018 is a noun in apposition which refers to a famous Czech rock band; the specific epithet of *Vaejovis vaquero* Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972 is a Spanish word for “cowboy”; *Paravaejovis puritanus* (Gertsch, 1958) was named after Puritan-American Museum Expedition; *Bothriurus jesuita* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 was named after the Spanish name for Jesuit catholic order since the species has been collected near the ruins of the missions that the Jesuit order constructed in the XVII and XVIII centuries; *Neobuthus factorio* Kovařík et al., 2018 was named after the computer game (Factorio) created by the son of the first author, Michal Kovařík. In conclusion, the eponym can be given after a commemoration, a personal interest of the author, a pun, a metonym of a locality, or an allusion to the scorpion’s morphology, behavior or habitat.

The eponyms in the Appendix is only considered as “named after a modern, fictional or historical character, or even a group of people or a symbolic figure”. Names given after gods will be separately classified as deonyms; names given after mythological or folkloric characters, as mythonyms; names after ethnic groups, as ethnonyms. Patronyms, matronyms and necronyms are excluded from the eponyms and will be considered separately.

5. Bionyms

Bionym (Gr. *bios* life; *onuma* name) is a name that directly or indirectly describes the type of habitat and environmental conditions. A toponym that describes a certain geography

can be called a geonym, which is applied in the Appendix. Most of the generic epithets in this category are just modified with a prefix, such as *troglo-* (cave, e.g., *Troglorhopalurus* Lourenço, Baptista & Giupponi, 2004) or *oro-* (mountain, e.g., *Orobothriurus* Maury, 1975). As a result, they can also be considered as taxonyms. Some bionyms can be somewhat obscure. The prefix of *Sotanochactas* Francke, 1986 (i.e., *sotano-*) is the Spanish word for “pit” (as a result, this prefix is also an autochthonym, see below), which refers to the type locality of the type species *S. elliotti* (Mitchell, 1971), Sótano de Yerbaniz. Sometimes the etymology of a bionym can be a mythonym. The prefix of *Stygochactas* Vignoli & Prendini, 2009 (i.e., *stygo-*) is the underworld river, Styx, in Greek mythology. Another special case is *Rumikiru* Ojanguren-Affilastro et al., 2012, a name constructed of two Quechua words, *rumi* (stone) and *kiru* (tooth), which signify that the species inhabits a rocky area and has an enlarged tooth on the movable finger of the pedipalp. Apparently, this name is a combination of morphonym and bionym, while also an autochthonym as a whole. Examples of specific epithets that are bionyms are more abundant and some are not the direct description of the habitat. The specific epithet of *Vietbocap quinquemilia* Lourenço et al., 2018 (= *V. canhi* Lourenço & Pham, 2010) means “5000 meters”. It is the distance between the entrance of the cave and the place where the species was found. The specific epithet of *Brachistosternus kamanhaca* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2007 is a noun in apposition, which is the local name (autochthonym) for sea fog occurring along the arid Pacific coastline of central and northern South America. The specific epithet of *Paruroctonus ventosus* Williams, 1972 means “like the wind, speedy” in Latin, a metonym for the original habitat, which is characterized by prevalent wind and little shelter from it. Bionyms may refer to the climate and temperature: e.g., the specific epithet of *Oichus ardens* Ythier, 2019 alludes to the geothermal activity and many hot (ardent, Latin *ardens*) springs located in the area where the new species was found. The specific epithet of *Serradigitus calidus* (Soleglad, 1974) means “warm, hot” in Latin, based on the hot climate of the Cuatro Ciénegas basin of Cohahuila, Mexico. The specific epithet of *Serradigitus torridus* Williams & Berke, 1986 means “burning” in Latin, a reference to hot, dry desert habitat. Other bionyms may refer to the microhabitat and substrate type: e.g., *Kochius colluvius* Ayrey, Jones & Myers, 2019 was named after the colluvial soil where the type specimens were found. Similarly, *Microtityus vulcanicus* Teruel, 2019 was named after volcanic soil of the habitat to which this species seems to be endemic (cactus scrub that grows on very dark, volcanic sandy soil; all specimens were found under black, volcanic sandstone rocks). *Tityus rupestre* Lourenço 2019 was named after the Campo Rupestres biotype. The word *rupestre* itself comes from the Latin *rupestris* (living on cliffs or rocks). *Brachistosternus quiscapata* Ochoa & Acosta, 2002 was named after two Quechua words (an autochthonym), *quisca* for spine and *pata* for spiny place, referring to the habitat with cacti. The etymology of the specific epithet of *Brachistosternus ninapo*

Ochoa, 2004 is more interesting. It is the combination of *nina poqchiq orco*, “volcano” in Quechua language (an autochthonym). Both specific epithets of *Diplocentrus actun* Armas & Palacios-Vargas, 2002 and *Diplocentrus cueva* Francke, 1978 mean “cave”, except that the former is Maya language and the latter, Spanish.

6. Autochthonym

Autochthonym (Gr. *autokhthōn* indigenous, native; *onuma* name) is a name used by the natives. For the generic epithets in scorpions, when an autochthonym is chosen, it is usually the word for “scorpion” in an indigenous language. Most autochthonyms in scorpion scientific names are classified as zoonyms (a general word for name given after an animal). For example, *Aemngvantom* Prendini, Ehrental & Loria, 2021 is the Laotian word for “scorpion”; *Gint* Kovařík et al., 2013 is the Amharic word for “scorpion”; *Jaguajir* Esposito et al., 2017 is the Tupi word for “scorpion”; *Tehuanka* Cekalovic, 1973 is the Araucana word (*tehuanke*) for “scorpion”; *Kuarapu* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2010 is the Purhépecha word for “scorpion”; *Kolotl* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2014 is the Nahuatl word for “scorpion”. Two special cases are: *Alacran* Francke, 1982, which is the Spanish word for “scorpion”, and *Akrav* Levy, 2007 is the Biblical Hebrew word for “scorpion”, both of which implicitly indicate the locality of the species (Mexico and Israel). Similar examples can be seen in several specific epithets. *Pandinurus hangarale* Kovařík et al., 2017 was named after the Somali word for “big black scorpion”; *Pandiborellius igdu* Kovařík et al., 2017, after the Afar word for “scorpion”; *Parabuthus kajibu* Kovařík et al., 2016, after the Oromia word for “scorpion”; *Tityus kukuttee* Ythier, Chevalier & Gangadin, 2020, after the Ndyuka word for “scorpion”; *Hottentotta vinchu* Mirza, Ambekar & Kulkarni, 2019, after the Marathi word for “scorpion”; *Troglorhopalurus lacrau* (Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 1997), after the Portuguese word for “scorpion”; *Diplocentrus sinaan* Armas & Martin-Frias, 2000, after the Maya word for “scorpion”; and *Ananteris sipilili* Ythier, Chevalier & Lourenço, 2020, after the Kalina word for “scorpion”. Sometimes an autochthonym does not mean “scorpion”, such as *Konetontli* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013 is the Nahuatl word for “infant, small creature”. Additionally, an autochthonym can be a metonym given after the type locality or morphology. *Diplocentrus oxlajujbaktun* Trujillo & Armas, 2012 was named after Oxlajuj B’ak’tun, 394 years cycle in the Mayan calendar. *Thorellius yuyuawi* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2018 was named after the word for grains of black maize in the language of the Wixarika people. According to the original authors, the name refers to the smoothness and dark color of the integument, especially the chelae, of this species, which resembles kernels of black maize.

Finally, aside from the zoonyms and metonyms, an autochthonym in the specific epithet can also be a morphonym (e.g., *Buthus bonito* Lourenço & Geniez, 2005 is Spanish for “beautiful”, *Tityus dedoslargos* Francke & Stockwell, 1987 is Spanish for “long fingers”); a chromonym (e.g., *Grosphus*

mavo Lourenço & Rossi 2020 is Malagasy for “yellow”); an entonym (e.g., *Buthus manchego* Teruel & Turiel 2020 is the Spanish word used locally to name the natives of Castilla-La Mancha); a toponym (e.g., *Tityus quisqueyanus* (Armas, 1982) is the native name (Quisqueya) for the Hispaniola Island); a choronym (e.g., *Vaejovis norteno* Sissom & González-Santillán, 2004 is the Spanish word *norteño*, “northern”); a bionym (e.g., *Centruroides cuauhmapan* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 is Nahuatl for “up in a tree”); a geonym (e.g., *Troglotayosicus muranunkae* Sanchez-Vialas, Blasco-Arostegui, Garcia-Gila & Lourenço, 2020 is the Shuar word (Mura Nunka) for “the vegetation formations of the sandstone plateaus that characterize the region”); an ergonym (see below; e.g., *Thorellius tekuan* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2018 is Nahuatl for “ferocious”); and an axionym (see below; e.g., *Pachakutej iskay* (Acosta & Ochoa, 2001) is Quechua for “two” (the second species from Peru)). Autochthonyms used as eponyms (e.g., *Bothriurus jesuita*), mythonyms (e.g., *Chactopsis chullachaqui*) or deonyms (e.g., *Maaykuyak*) were already listed before.

For the convenience of categorizing, all the names that originate from languages except for English (scorpion), Greek (*skorprios / scorpio*) and Latin (*scorpius, nepa*) and taken in apposition will be classified as autochthonyms in the Appendix, no matter what they indicate, but they will be further explained in the parentheses. The name that originates from a native language is termed a glossonym (glottonym) or linguonym.

7. Ergonym

Ergonym (Gr. *ergon* work, occupation; *onuma* name) is a name that usually describes behavior of a species. For the generic epithet, the only existing case in scorpions is *Trypanothacus* Lowe et al., 2019, a combination of Greek word *τρύπανν* (*trypani*, “drill”) and genus name *Buthacus* Birula, 1908 as a reference to the habit of burrowing in more consolidated soils by these scorpions. However, generic names like *Androctonus* will also be classified in this category in this study, where a name represents the aggressiveness of the scorpion. For the specific epithet, it usually presents an implied importance or identity in scorpions. The most famous case is *Pandinus imperator* (originally as *Buthus imperator*) whose specific epithet stands for “a commander, a leader, or an absolute ruler” derived from the Latin verb *imperare* which means “to command, to order”. The English word “emperor” is derived from this word. This might be a reference to the massive body size of *P. imperator* as it is the third largest scorpion in the world (total length about 220 mm); in fact, at the time of its description it could be the largest known species (the currently largest, although not the longest, scorpion is *Gigantometrus swammerdami* (Simon, 1872), described 31 years later). A similar case is the *Pandinopsis dictator* (Pocock, 1888) which might follow the same naming trend as it means “dictator”. This is also a species of large size, up to 200 mm. Other cases are more likely to be based on the behavior. The species epithet of *Opisthophthalmus fossor* Purcell, 1898 means “burrower”,

which describes the digging behavior of the species. The species epithet of *Opisththalmus praedo* Thorell, 1876 means “robber” which might imply that the species was discovered when it was scrambling for prey, or it might had taken the burrow of others as its own. *Pandipalpus viatoris* (Pocock, 1890) may be named for its wide distribution as *viatoris* means “traveller”. Obviously, both *Tityus pugilator* Pocock, 1898 and *Pandinops pugilator* (Pocock, 1900) are named for their habits of attacking enemy with their pedipalps as *pugilator* means “boxer”. The reason why *Opisthacanthus piscatorius* Lawrence, 1955 was named after the Latin word *piscator* (fisherman) is unknown. The species is endemic to the West Cape of South Africa. To be more specific, it was found in Hangklip, Overstrand Municipality, a place which is near the sea. The scorpion might have been found scavenging for dead fish on the beach nearby (scorpions are not agile enough to catch living fish, and they cannot detect them from outside of water in the first place).

Other names used for describing the habits of a species will be classified as ergonyms in this paper.

8. Tautonym

Tautonym (Gr. *tauto* the same; *onuma* name) is a scientific name, in which the generic and the specific epithets are the same (also called an autonym). Such a name is usually the name of a type species. Strictly speaking, there is only one case in the scorpions, which is *Hottentotta hottentotta* (Fabricius, 1787). However, there are other similar cases which both the generic and the specific epithets have the same meaning. These cases can be termed as a typonym in which the genus is named after its type species. For example, the generic and the specific epithets of *Vizcaino viscainensis* (Williams, 1970) mean the Vizcaino Desert on the west coast of the central Baja California peninsula. The generic epithet of *Aemngvantom lao* (Lourenço, 2012) is “scorpion” in Laotian while its specific epithet is its country of origin. One can see from the parentheses that both of the species were not originally assigned to these genera. Their newly described genera directly took the etymologies of their specific epithets as the generic names. Actually, the case of *H. hottentotta* is the same as it was initially described as *Scorpio hottentotta* by Fabricius. Similarly, both the generic and the specific epithets of *Darchenia bernadettae* Vachon, 1977 commemorate the French entomologist, Bernadette Darchen. And there is another slightly different case. The generic epithet of *Kuarapu purhepecha* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2010 is the “scorpion” in Purhépecha language, the name of which was directly taken as the specific epithet.

9. “Ordonym”

A rare trend of naming scorpions by Greek letters is continued by some recent authors. The first such group were *Alpiscorpius alpha*, *A. beta* and *A. gamma* by Di Caporiacco (1950; originally named as three subspecies of *Euscorpius germanus*), followed by *A. delta*, *A. kappa*, *A. lambda*, *A. omega*, *A. omikron*, *A. sigma* and *A. ypsilon* by Kovařík et al. (2019). The rarely used word “ordonym (L. *ordo* order;

Gr. *onuma* name)” is hereby applied only to accommodate this special case. Besides, sometimes the species name also represents subjective judgement, such as words like “expected”, “unexpected” and “important”. These names are hereby classified within the axionyms.

New nomenclature for the Chinese names of scorpions

1. General approach

As mentioned in the beginning, the current Chinese names for scorpions are rather confusing and inconsistent. One species could be assigned multiple names and vice versa. Also, the name may not be indicative for the taxonomy, or it is not the Chinese equivalence of Latin name in meaning. It is either unfavorable for the public cognition or for the amateur study. As such, the major aim of this work is to provide standardized translation rules in Chinese for the Latin names of the scorpions. The etymology of scientific Latin names of scorpions is rather diverse. Hence, the rules can only be enforced when the etymology of every species is investigated. Since I have already translated names of all valid species, the suggested regulation is now complete. The core principles of this regulation are: (i) be precise and concise as far as possible; (ii) no arbitrary alteration without the original explanation unless the etymology is unknown; (iii) the translation of the same word is unified but also emphasizes the easiness of spoken speech if necessary. The basic and the most important rule is *not to change the meaning* as far as possible. The most conservative translation ensures the lowest possibility of future conflicts.

Since most of the etymology of the scientific names that will be mentioned below have been explained before, they will not be repeated in detail if unnecessary.

Note: the following content will only provide the Chinese translation of the genus names without the English equivalence. For the detailed list of species, refer to the Appendix.

In the Appendix 1, the genus names of unknown etymology will be noted with #; the genus names that are translated by its junior synonym will be noted with @. If the classification or the validity of the taxon is controversial, it will be noted with *. Species with ★ are the ones that are endemic to China; species with ☆ are the ones with confirmed records in China; species with ○ are the ones with dubious records in China.

Please note that no subgenus, species-group or species-complex will be included in the Appendix 1. All the currently recognized subgenera are presented in the Appendix 2. The appendix will only provide key information of the etymology of each species, subspecies, genus and subgenus described after 2016 (for the detailed explanation of taxa described in or before 2016, please refer to Dupré’s dictionary).

Additionally, all the scientific names will be classified into the following categories by the abbreviations as shown in the brackets: autochthonym (^{au}), axionym (^{ax}), bionym (^{bi}), charactonym (^{cha}), choronym (^{cho}), chromonym (^{chr}), deonym (^{de}), eponym (^{ep}), ergonym (^{er}), ethnonym (^{et}), geonym (^{ge}),

linguonym (^l), matronym (^{ma}), morphonym (^{mo}), mythonym (^{my}), necronym (^{ne}), ordonym (^{ord}), paleonym (^{pal}), patronym (^{pat}), tautonym (^{tau}), taxonym (^{ta}), toponym (^{to}, including the astionym, comonym, conym, insulonym, limnymym, oceanym, oronym, potamonym and speleonym), and typonym (^{ty}). However, the following regulation will only be discussed in general categories.

2. Generic epithet

2.1 Morphonym

2.1.1 If the etymology is clear, such as a morphonym that is combined of several independent parts, use literal translation without arbitrarily changing the original meaning or adding to translation.

E.g. *Androctonus crassicauda* is literally translated as “肥尾杀人蝎”.

2.1.2 If the literal translation is too simple and equivocal, use free translation only when there is explanation in the original paper.

E.g. The literal translation of *Rumikiru* is “石齿蝎”, however, this will lead to misunderstanding that the tooth of the scorpion is stone-like, which is inconsistent with the original meaning (see above). As a result, it is better to be paraphrased like “石栖巨齿蝎”.

2.1.3 The name is best to be catchy when reading. The name used for translating a body structure is best to be uniform unless it does not read smoothly.

E.g. The part “*manus*” can be seen in both *Compsobuthus brevimanus* and *Diplocentrus longimanus*, hence they are translated as “短掌秀杀牛蝎” and “长掌双棘蝎”, respectively by keeping “*manus*” unified as “掌”. However, *Srilankametrus gravimanus* is translated as “沉螯斯里兰卡异距蝎”, turning “掌” into “螯”.

2.2 Taxonym

2.2.1 If a genus is named basing on another genus, then the complete translation of the original genus should be kept in order to indicate the derivation.

E.g. *Srilankametrus* was named based on the *Heterometrus*, and the latter is translated as “异距蝎”. As a result, *Srilankametrus* should be translated as “斯里兰卡异距蝎”.

2.2.2 If a genus name is a combination of two generic names, then the translation will also be the combination of two translations.

E.g. *Broteochactas* Pocock, 1893 is a combination of *Brotheas* (“猎人蝎”, see below) and *Chactas* (“蛮蝎”, see below), so it will be translated as “猎人蛮蝎”.

2.2.3 If the genus name is in a form of “prefix/suffix + original genus name”, then the translation of the prefix/suffix is best to be uniform (e.g., *pseudo*-拟, *-ops*类, *-opsis*仿, *-oides/-odes*似, *-olus*小, *an-*假, *apisto-*伪, *eu-*真, *hetero-/xeno-/anomalo-/allo-*异/诡/奇/歧, *iso-*等, *neo-*新, *palaeo-*古, *opith-/opisto-*后, *meso-*中, *hemi-*半, *ortho-*直, *plesio-*邻, *pan-*泛, *micro-*微, *pico-*侏, *femto-*毫, etc.; note that these prefixes or suffixes will not only occur in taxonyms). If the differently spelled prefix or suffix is of same meaning, they should be

translated with synonyms or use free translation.

E.g. The composition of *Buthiscus* is “*Buthus* + *-iscus*”. Here, “*-iscus*” is a diminutive suffix. However, if literally translated as “小杀牛蝎”, it will cause conflict with *Butheolus*, which is also modified with a diminutive suffix. Since *Buthiscus* is reckoned to be of weak toxicity, it can then be freely translated as “弱杀牛蝎” as “弱” (weak) is a similar word to “小” in Chinese, while indicating its weak toxicity at the same time. Further, *Buthoscorpio* only means “a buthid-like scorpion” and is not the combination of *Buthus* and *Scorpio*, so it is translated as “似杀牛蝎”.

2.3 Toponym

2.3.1 If the genus is named after a single location, then the translation of the genus name will be the translation (in Chinese, usually transliteration) of this location. If there is an existing translation of the location, apply; if not, better transliterate it according to the local pronunciation. If the transliteration is too long in Chinese, translating it according to the meaning is acceptable.

E.g. *Auyantepuia* is translated as “魔屋山蝎”, while it will be too long to use the transliteration, “奥扬特普伊蝎”.

2.3.2 If the current translation of a location’s name is literal (according to its etymology) and one cannot tell whether it is a toponym, add a geographical modifier (such as “mount” and “island”) if there is none; a method which can also be applied when using transliteration. On the contrary, if the name already contains a geographic feature, then that part will be literally translated rather than transliterated.

E.g. *Superstitionia* was named after the Superstition Mountain which is literally translated as “迷信山” in Chinese, but not transliterated as “修珀斯蒂逊山”. The direct translation will merely be “迷信蝎” (“superstition scorpion”) as the genus name does not contain any geographic feature, so it should better be translated as “迷信山蝎”. Although *Karasbergia* was named after the Karasberg Hill, the word “berg” stands for “mount” already, so it will simply be translated as “卡拉斯山蝎” rather than the transliteration of “Karasberg”.

2.3.3 If the genus is a combination of a location name and a name of another genus, then the translation will be the combination of the translation of the location and the original genus. Additionally, if there is an accepted brief transliteration of the location, apply it in order to make the name concise.

E.g. *Himalayotityobuthus* will be translated as “喜山戾杀牛蝎” as “喜山” is the brief translation of “喜马拉雅山”. Further, *Vietbocap* is translated into “越南蝎”, but the genus name is a combination of *viet-* (Vietnam) and *bocap* (Vietnamese for “scorpion”), so it is not a single-location-type name, but a combination of toponym and autochthonym.

2.3.4 If the toponym is not a geographical place, literally translate it according to the Chinese equivalence (which is transliteration in most of the time).

E.g. *Sassanidotus* was named after a dynasty (see above) and represents a paleonym, although it is a metonym after the type locality. The name is translated by the transliteration of the dynasty name as “萨珊蝎”. *Razianus* is simply transliterated

as “拉兹蝎” according to its etymology, Razi, although it is not a geographical location as well as the other ecdonymyms.

2.4 Eponym

2.4.1. If the genus is simply named after a modern person's name, then the translation will be in the form of “a transliteration of the first syllable + 氏 + 蝎”. The transliteration can follow the widely accepted one, or it is re-transliterated according to the certain pronunciation of that country.

E.g. *Polisius* is translated as “珀氏蝎” (after American arachnologist Gary Allan Polis).

2.4.2. If the genus is in a combination of a modern person's name with another genus, the person's name follows the previous rule and simply add the translation of the basic genus.

E.g. *Hoffmannihadrurus* is translated as “霍氏厚尾蝎” (after Mexican scorpologist Carlos C. Hoffmann).

2.4.3. If a person's name is used many times for different genera, then the higher taxa where the genus belongs should be added for distinguishment.

E.g. *Vachonia* is of the same etymology as *Vachonus* (after French arachnologist Max Vachon). The former is translated into “瓦氏沟尾蝎” as it belongs to the family Bothriuridae (which is hereby translated as “沟尾蝎科”).

2.4.4. If the genus is named after a certain ethnic group of people, use transliteration or the already existing name for that group.

E.g. *Hottentotta* is translated as “霍屯督蝎”.

2.4.5. If the genus is named after a historical, mythological or fictional character, usually translate it according to the identity of that character.

E.g. *Belisarius* is translated as “将军蝎” as it is the name of a historical general. *Hadogenes* is translated as “冥神蝎” as it is the name of the god of the underworld in Greek mythology. *Vaejovis* is translated as “愈神蝎” as *Vejovis* was described as a god of healing. *Lychas* is translated as “信使蝎” as it was named after Hercules's herald. *Calchas* is translated as “祭司蝎” as it was named after a Greek priest. *Brotheas* is translated as “猎人蝎” as the character is described as a hunter. *Chaneke* was named after a natural spirit in folklore, so it is translated as “精灵蝎”. *Chactas* is translated as “蛮蝎” as the description for this character is “a noble savage” in the fictional novel.

2.4.6. If the identity is the same in two genera, use synonyms to distinguish.

E.g. *Pachakutej* is translated as “君主蝎” as it is the name of a sovereign. Similarly, *Teuthraustes*, *Zabius* and *Oiclus* were all named after kings, so they are respectively translated as “国王蝎”, “国君蝎” and “君王蝎” for distinguishment.

2.4.7. If the identity of a historical character is too strange to translate, transliterate the first two syllables (usually according to the Greek pronunciation of the name).

E.g. *Timogenes* is translated as “提玛蝎” as the identity of historian is too strange for a scorpion name. *Chaerilus* is translated as “寇里蝎” for the same reason.

2.4.8. If the identity of the mythological character is too strange or inappropriate to translate, translate it by the etymology of that character (this method can be also used for a historical character).

E.g. *Tityus* was named after a giant, but the general size of this genus is very small so it will be appropriate to translate it as “巨人蝎”. Also, it will be strange when this translation is applied in a closely related genus which is modified by the prefix *micro-* that means “small”. According to Tiniakos et al. (2010), name of *Tityus* is probably derived from the ancient Greek word “*tisis*”, meaning “he who suffers retribution”. A Chinese equivalence is “戾” which in some cases stands for “retribution”. As a result, the genus is translated as “戾蝎” and it does read smoothly in this way. The genus is not transliterated because that will be too long when applied in another derived names (e.g., *Himalayotityobuthus*). Additionally, one subgenus of this genus, *Atreus*, was named after the king of Mycenae (*Atreus*, Ἀτρεύς), so it is translated as “王戾蝎”. Similarly in the genus *Buthus*, according to Sousa et al. (2017), Leach did not offer an explanation for his choice of the genus name. However, they discussed the etymology of this genus in great detail and all the clues led to an unambiguous conclusion that *Buthus* is a name of a victorious athlete of the ancient Pythian Games, βουθός (*Bouthos*), who used to devour a great ox in a day. Several authors (Hofmann et al. (1698), Noël (1824), Müller (1848), Christesen (2007) and Dupré (2016)) also reached the same interpretation that this name literally means “sacrifice of an ox” (e.g., according to Dupré (2016), “Gr. *bous*, ox; - *thouéin*, killer”), an etymology formally adopted by Lowe et al. (2019) in their creation of a new genus, *Trypanothacus*. Therefore, the name *Buthus* could potentially refer to an animal which was considered so venomous that it could kill an ox at that time (the medically important type species, *Buthus occitanus* (Amoreux, 1789)). As such, the name *Buthus* should be translated as the “ox-killer scorpion”, which leads to the Chinese name, “杀牛蝎”. On the other hand, the name “钳蝎” would just be as weird as if one calls the *Homo sapiens* “手人” (hand human). Another hereby proposed translation is “竞蝎” (competitor scorpion), according to the identity of the person named βουθός (an athlete). However, since there is no proof that the person is the etymology of the genus *Buthus* (albeit the high likelihood), while Lowe et al. (2018) had already used “ox + sacrifice” as the etymology for *Trypanothacus*, a genus that contains the root “*buthus*”, I will just use “杀牛蝎” as the translation.

2.5 Bionym

This is rarely seen as the genus name and it is usually presented as “prefix + a basic genus”. The most common prefix is *troglo-*.

E.g. *Troglotityobuthus* is both a bionym (indicated by the prefix *troglo-*) and a taxonym (*Tityobuthus* is a taxonym), and it is translated as “穴戾杀牛蝎”. *Orobothriurus* is translated as “山沟尾蝎”. Autochthonyms and mythonyms that actually serve as bionyms like *Sotanochoctas* and *Stygochoctas* are translated as “深洞蛮蝎” and “冥河蛮蝎”, respectively.

2.6 Autochthonym

2.6.1 If the genus is named in apposition with the equivalence of “scorpion” in another language, translate by the name of the language. If the language has a brief translation, use the brief one.

E.g. *Aemngyantom* is translated as “老挝蝎”; *Gint* is translated as “阿姆哈拉蝎”; *Jaguajir* is translated as “图皮蝎”; *Tehuanka* is translated as “阿拉乌咖那蝎”; *Kuarapu* is translated as “布雷佩查蝎”; *Kolotl* is simply translated as “纳瓦蝎” (“Nahuatl language” has a complete Chinese translation as “纳瓦特尔语”, but it can also be shortened as “纳瓦语”). *Alacran* is the “scorpion” in Spanish; however, it cannot be translated as “西班牙蝎” as it does not occur in Spain. The reason why it is name in a Spanish name is that people of Mexico where it is found speak Spanish. Thus, it should better be translated as “西语蝎”. *Akrav* is the “scorpion” in Biblical Hebrew and it will be briefly translated as “圣经蝎”.

2.6.2 If the autochthonym does not mean “scorpion”, freely translate it according to certain cases. *E.g.* *Konetontli* is not the “scorpion” in Nahuatl, but the “small creature”. Thus, the genus is translated as “微纳瓦蝎”.

2.6.3 If the autochthonym actually serves as a morphonym and so forth, translate it according to the rule of that type of name. *E.g.* As shown in *Rumikiru*.

2.7 Ergonym

As mentioned above, strictly speaking, there is only one example in scorpion genera, which is the *Trypanothacus*, a combination of the prefix *trypano-* that indicates the behaviour and the basic genus *Buthacus*. The prefix indicates that the scorpion digs burrow in more consolidated soil, which means it is a borrow-dwelling species. As a result, it is freely translated as “穴螫杀牛蝎” (*Buthacus* = *Buthus* + *-acus*, the suffix means “needle”, a reference to the long aculeus of the genus). As for the other names that indicates the habits and are categorized into this type of name, they are all literally translated; please refer to the Appendix.

3. Specific epithet

3.1 Morphonym

The translation for a morphonym of specific epithet is generally the same with that of a generic epithet. Likewise, if a literal translation is too simple and equivocal, use free translation only when there is an explanation in the original paper. Most of the morphological terminologies will be uniform unless the name does not read smoothly (depending on the tones and consonants).

E.g. The specific epithet of *Scorpio palmatus* is a combination of *palma* and *-atus* (literally means “with hand”), a reference to its wide chelal manus (in the scientific names, if a specific epithet means “with a specific body structure”, it usually indicates the pronounced development of that structure) and it is thus translated as “阔掌蝎”. *Liocheles oranghutan* was named as a pun. Orangutan (*oranghutan* in the Malay language) was found living in the same area with the scorpion. Also, the reddish brown color of the scorpion resembles that of the orangutan. Hence, it is translated as “猩红滑螫蝎”. The specific epithet of *Hemiscorpius falcifer* means “scythe bearing”, a reference to the sickle-shaped raptorial pedipalp fingers. It is thus freely translated as “镰指半蝎”. *Hemiscorpius flagelliraptor* was named in a combination of Latin nouns, “*flagellum*”, referring to the long,

whip-like metasoma, and “*raptor*” meaning a predator or robber. However, “predator” is somewhat redundant to modify a scorpion as all the scorpions are active predators. It is thus simply translated as “鞭尾半蝎”. *Brotochactas vestigialis* was named for vestigial characteristics that have the lateral keels and ventral half of caudal segment V. It is thus freely translated as “弱脊猎人蛮蝎”. The name of *Brachistosternus anandrovestigia* refers to the lack of metasomal glands, or androvestigia, on metasomal segment V. It is thus freely translated as “缺腺短胸蝎”. *Bothriurus ypsilon*, named after the Greek letter Y for the form of denticulation on caudal segment V. It is thus freely translated as “岔脊沟尾蝎” according to the shape of the letter. *Kraepelinia palpator* was named for its stout pedipalps. This is not implied in the specific epithet, but the translation will complement that meaning. It is thus translated as “壮肢克氏蝎”. The same case is in *Fetilinia dentator* which is constructed to rhyme with the former. The specific epithet refers to the prominently enlarged dentition on the metasoma. It is thus translated as “齿尾费氏蝎”. The specific epithet of *Hottentotta conspersus* means “sprinkled, moistened”, a reference to the black spots on its exoskeleton. It is thus freely translated as “喷斑霍屯督蝎”. *Hormurus penta* was named for five trichobothria on the ventral aspect of the pedipalp tibia (*penta* only stands for “five”). It is thus freely translated as “五孔链尾蝎”. The specific epithet of *Ananteris claviformis* merely means club-shaped, which refers to the stoutness of the bristles on the fourth and fifth metasomal segments, so it is thus freely translated as “强鬃无支蝎”.

The words *manus*, *cheles* and *chelys* (all refer to the pedipalp manus in scorpions) will be translated into “螫” or “掌” depending on situation (whether it reads smoothly). In Chinese Pinyin, “螫(áo)” is a rising tone (2nd tone) while “掌(zhǎng)” is a falling-rising tone (3rd tone). Phonologically, a phrase with two same tones will read smoothly (i.e., 2nd + 2nd, or 3rd + 3rd); however, in reality, the first word will turn into a 2nd tone in the second combination) and the translation in this combination should be given the priority. Moreover, a rising tone combines well with a falling tone (4th tone) with the latter before it (i.e., 4th + 2nd). It also sounds smoothly when two words of adjacent tones are combined together in the positive sequence (i.e., 2nd + 3rd) unless their consonants are the same (e.g., “zh-” + “zh-” has an awkward-sounding, but “ch-” + “zh-” will be better). Additionally, a “consonant + vowel” combination is better than a “consonant + consonant” combination. For example, *granimanus* is translated as “疣(yóu)螫(áo)” rather than “疣(yóu)掌(zhǎng)” (a “2nd + 2nd” example; the alternative is a “2nd + 3rd”, but it is a “consonant + consonant” combination), *leptochelys* is translated as “瘦(shòu)螫(áo)” rather than “瘦(shòu)掌(zhǎng)” (a “4th + 2nd” example), *crassimanus* is translated as “粗(cū)螫(áo)” rather than “粗(cū)掌(zhǎng)” (a “1st + 2nd” example) and *rectimanus* is translated as “直(zhí)螫(áo)” rather than “直(zhí)掌(zhǎng)” (a “2nd + 2nd” example; the alternative is a “2nd + 3rd”, but does not read smoothly because they have the same consonant; however, both “长(cháng)螫(áo)” and “长(cháng)掌(zhǎng)” sounds well as the former is a “2nd + 2nd” form and the latter is a “2nd + 3rd” with different consonants).

3.2 Taxonym

In the case of a specific epithet, the taxonym is usually presented as a combination of “prefix/suffix + another taxon name / a specific epithet of another taxon”. The translation will maintain the translation for another taxon name / the specific epithet of another taxon. Adjectives that suggest resemblance, uncertainty and difference will be directly translated (explaining in detail may result in a very long name).

E.g. *Heteroscorpion opisthacanthoides* was named for its resemblance with the genus *Opisthacanthus* by adding the suffix *-oides*. The translation will only keep the translation of the genus itself, without adding “蝎” (strictly speaking, most of the scorpion genera names are not literally translated, but they are complemented by adding “蝎” in order to indicate the original name; exceptions are *Alpiscorpius*, *Euscorpium*, *Sardoscorpium*, *Hemiscorpius* and *Heteroscorpion*, who already have the word “scorpion” in their names). It is thus translated as “似后棘异蝎”. *Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis* was named for its resemblance with the species *Chaerilus conchiformis*. It is thus translated as “拟贝形寇里蝎”.

3.3 Toponym

3.3.1 The translation for a toponym in a specific epithet is generally the same with that of a genus name. If the species is named after a single location, then the translation of the specific epithet will be the transliteration of the location. If there is an existing translation of the location, apply; if not, better transliterate it according to the local pronunciation.

E.g. *Tityus sarisarinamensis* is simply translated as “萨里萨里尼亚马戾蝎” despite the length of the toponym (Tepui Sarisariñama).

3.3.2 If a current translation of a location’s name is literal (according to its etymology) and one cannot tell whether it is a toponym, add a geographical modifier (such as “mount” and “island”) if there is none; this method can also be applied when using transliteration. On the contrary, if a name already contains a geographic feature, then that part will be literally translated rather than transliterated.

E.g. *Hormurus boholiensis* is translated as “薄荷岛链尾蝎”. The toponym Bohol is transliterated as “薄荷” in China, which, however, will cause a confusion with the Chinese word for “mint”. As a result, the geographical modifier “岛” is added to eliminate confusion.

3.3.3 All the metonyms will be literally translated in order to be concise. This is according to the principle of concision and having no alteration of the meaning. Even if the name is equivocal, it does not always have to be complemented since the basic rule is to not to change the meaning. One will only have to add some further explanation as they introduce the species in the context of popularizing science.

E.g. Both *Kovarikia oxy* and *Tityus imei* were named after a college/institution, so they are simply translated as “西方学院寇氏蝎” and “医研所戾蝎”. However, *Tityus ivicnancor* was named after the abbreviation of an institution and the Latin word *nancor* (found). The translation will omit the “*nancor*” to avoid redundancy, so it will be “委内瑞拉科研所戾蝎”. Slightly differently, *Akrav israchanani* was

named after both the type locality and its finder, so it will be completely translated as “以色列沙氏圣经蝎”. *Uroctonites sequoia* is translated as “红杉近尾戮蝎”, *Pseudouroctonus peccatum* as “罪恶拟尾戮蝎” and *Auyantepuia aurum* as “金矿奥扬特普伊蝎”. As for *Konetontli ignes*, the specific epithet is clearly a replacement of the type locality Fogos as both of them mean “fire”. The species name is thus translated after this type locality as “佛戈斯微纳瓦蝎”.

3.4 Eponym

3.4.1. If a species is simply named after a modern person, then translation is generally the same as for the genus name and will be in the form of “the transliteration of the first syllable + 氏”. The transliteration can follow the widely accepted one, or it is re-transliterated according to the certain pronunciation in that country. If the pronunciation of the first syllables are the same in the names of different people of congeneric species and there are not enough Chinese words to choose from, completely transliterate the species that with fewer syllables, or only transliterate the first two to three syllables for distinguishing. Additionally, if the popularity or importance of the species names that have the same pronunciation of the first syllable is unequal, give the priority of simplicity to the better or best known one (i.e., the transliteration of the first syllable + 氏). The current translation of every single scorpion species name in this naming method (an eponym after a modern person) has considered the likelihood of future conflict. All the *nomina dubia* are completely transliterated to give the priority of simplicity to the future certain taxa.

E.g. The syllables of *Tityus annea* is fewer than that of *Tityus angelesae*. In order to be concise, the former is completely transliterated as “安妮氏戾蝎” while the latter is simply transliterated as “安氏戾蝎”. One special case is in *Scorpiops zubairahmedi* and *Scorpiops zubairi*, both of which were named after the same person (Zubair Ahmed, Pakistani arachnologist), so the latter one with fewer syllables is completely translated as “祖拜尔氏类蝎” (while the former as “祖氏类蝎”). *Androctonus amoreuxi* is translated as “阿氏杀人蝎” by the first syllable while *Androctonus aleksandrplotkini* is translated as “阿莱氏杀人蝎” by the first two syllables since the former is better known than the latter and is more frequently medically relevant, despite that the first syllable of both species has the same pronunciation.

3.4.2. If the specific name starts from the preposition or article of a person, translate it according to the first syllable of the surname of the person.

E.g. *Buthus delafuentei* was named after Félix Samuel Rodríguez de la Fuente and the species name starts from the particle “de”, so it will be translated as “弗氏杀牛蝎” by the first syllable of “Fuente”. Additionally, *Neochactas sanmartini*, which was named after the Uruguayan entomologist, Pablo R. San Martín, merely transliterating the first syllable will be unclear as “San” is a common part of the composite last name. It is thus translated as “圣马丁氏新蛮蝎”. For *Buthus jianxinae*, which was named after the Chinese arachnologist, Jian-xin Qi (戚建新), Jian-xin is not her surname so it will be inappropriate to simply add “氏”.

So it can be either translated as “建新杀牛蝎” or “威氏杀牛蝎”.

3.4.3. If a species is named after two persons' names, transliterate the first syllable of each.

E.g. *Chactas raymondhansi* was named after two collectors, Raymond A. Mendez and Hans E. A. Boos. It is thus translated as “瑞翰氏蛮蝎”. A similar case is the *Lisposoma josehermana* which was named after the parents of the author, Marie-Josée and Herman Lamoral. It is thus translated as “休赫氏滑体蝎”.

3.4.4. If a species is named after a certain race of people, use transliteration or the already existed name for that race.

E.g. *Buthus nabataeus* is translated as “纳巴泰杀牛蝎”.

3.4.5. If a species is named after a fictional character, translate it according to the resemblance with that character, or complete transliteration is also acceptable as that does not alter the meaning.

E.g. *Centruroides rodolfoi* is freely translated as “欢愉似刺尾蝎”; *Vaejovis baggins* is freely translated as “侏儒愈神蝎”.

3.4.6. If a species is named after a historical or mythological character, translate it according to the identity of that character, or complete transliteration is also acceptable as that does not alter the meaning. If the identity is the same in two genera, use synonyms to distinguish.

E.g. Examples have all been listed in the previous text; for the translation, please refer to the Appendix.

3.4.7. For the special cases mentioned before (eponyms after a group of people or a symbolic entity, etc.), they are all literally translated (except for two cases).

E.g. *Euscorpium studentium* is literally translated as “学徒真蝎”; *Chactas oxfordi* is literally translated as “牛津蛮蝎”; *Mesobuthus brutus* is literally translated as “布鲁图斯中杀牛蝎”; *Vaejovis vaquero* is literally translated as “牛仔愈神蝎”; *Paravaejovis puritanus* is literally translated as “清教徒副愈神蝎”; *Bothriurus jesuita* is literally translated as “耶稣沟尾蝎”. *Neobuthus factorio* is freely translated as “米氏新杀牛蝎” by the name of the game creator. *Urophonius eugenicus* is translated as “主教尾弑蝎” according to the identity of that person.

3.5 Bionym

3.5.1 If the species is named after the type of its habitat or environmental conditions, literally translate it if the Latin meaning is clear for indicating the habitat. Words end in *-cola* will all be ended with “栖 (dwell)” in Chinese.

E.g. A special case is for *Diplocentrus actun* and *Diplocentrus cueva*, both of which were named after the word “cave”, just in different languages. The former is translated as “玛雅洞穴双棘蝎” to distinguish from the latter as the premodifier can also allude to its locality. The latter is simply translated as “洞穴双棘蝎” since Spanish is a widely spoken language and the scorpion does not occur in Spain.

3.5.2 If a bionym is shown as a metonym or using adjectives, use literal or free translation.

E.g. *Paruroctonus ventosus* is freely translated as “风地副尾戮蝎”; *Oiclus ardens* is freely translated as “热泉君

王蝎”; *Serradigitus calidus* is literally translated as “炎热锯指蝎”; *Serradigitus torridus* is freely translated as “灼热锯指蝎”; *Kochius colluvius* is literally translated as “崩积科氏蝎”; *Microtityus vulcanicus* is literally translated as “火山土微炭蝎”; *Tityus rupestre* is literally translated as “石栖炭蝎”.

3.6 Autochthonym

3.6.1 The translation for an autochthonym of specific epithet is generally the same with that of the generic epithet. If the species is named in apposition with the equivalence of “scorpion” in another language, translate by the name of the language. If the language has a brief translation, use the brief one.

E.g. *Pandinurus hangarale* is translated as “索马里尾惧蝎”; *Pandiborellius igdu* is translated as “阿法尔博氏惧蝎”; *Parabuthus kajibu* is translated as “奥罗米亚副杀牛蝎”; *Tityus kukututee* is translated as “恩迪乌卡炭蝎”; *Hottentotta vinchu* is translated as “马拉提霍屯督蝎”.

3.6.2 If a name of the language may cause confusion, add the word “语” (similar to the case of *Alacran*).

E.g. *Trogloorhopalurus lacrau* is translated as “葡语穴棍尾蝎” as the scorpion does not occur in Portugal. *Diplocentrus sinaan* is translated as “玛语双棘蝎” instead of “玛雅双棘蝎” because of an existing species, *Diplocentrus maya* Francke, 1977. Similarly, *Ananteris sipilili* is translated as “卡里那语无支蝎” to avoid conflict with *Ananteris kalina* Ythier, 2018 whose specific epithet is the language origin of that of the former.

3.6.3 If the autochthonym does not mean “scorpion”, freely translate it according to certain cases.

E.g. *Vaejovis pequeno* is Spanish for “the little one”, thus translated as “娇小愈神蝎”.

3.6.4 If an autochthonym actually serves as a morphonym, etc., translate it according to the rule of that type of name.

E.g. *Tityus dedoslargos* is Spanish for “long fingers” and literally translated as “长指炭蝎”. *Brachistosternus kamanchaca* is freely translated as “海岸短胸蝎”. *Brachistosternus quiscapata* is literally translated as “棘丛短胸蝎”. *Brachistosternus ninapo* is literally translated as “火山短胸蝎”.

3.6.5 If an autochthonym is a metonym after the type locality or morphology, use literal translation to avoid (maybe future) conflicts.

E.g. *Diplocentrus oxlajujbaktun* was named after the Mayan calendar to allude to its type locality. However, it cannot be translated as “玛雅双棘蝎” as it causes a conflict with the translation of *Diplocentrus maya*. Consequently, it is literally translated as “历法双棘蝎”. *Thorellius yuyuawi* is literally translated as “黑黍托氏蝎” to avoid a conflict with a potential species named “Thorellius atrolaevigatus”.

3.6.6 Linguonyms will be directly translated according to the Chinese names of those languages.

E.g. *Parabuthus kuanyamarum* is translated as “宽亚玛副杀牛蝎”.

3.7 Ergonym

All the names that indicate behavior of the species are

literally translated; please refer to the Appendix. Some of the names are named after human identities with the suffix *-tor* forming agent nouns. Most of them will be literally translated with an end of “者” instead of “人” to reduce their association with humans since the former is more widely used as it can be seen in the Chinese equivalence of “predator” (捕食者), which can be used to describe the ecological niche of an animal. Some identities in Chinese do not end with “人” and they will be adopted directly.

E.g. *imperator*, *dictator*, *fossor*, *praedo*, *viatoris* and *piscatorius* are translated as “统治者”, “独裁者”, “掘洞者”, “掠夺者”, “旅行者” and “捕鱼者”, respectively (although the last species is not reckoned to be able to catch fish), while *pugilator* is translated as “拳击手”.

For other ergonyms, such as *Uroctonus mordax* (both the genus and species names are ergonyms), please refer to the Appendix.

3.8 Tautonym

All the cases are listed in the previous text and all of them are the type species of their genus. As a result, since the Chinese term for type species is “模式种”, the specific epithet will be replaced by “模式” to avoid repetition and indicate their taxonomic status.

E.g. For the translation, please refer to the Appendix.

3.9 “Ordonym”

All the species that are included in this special case are listed in the previous text and all of them will be transliterated according to the current Chinese names for the Greek letters. Moreover, axionyms will all be literally translated.

E.g. For the translation, please refer to the Appendix.

4.0 Problematic cases

Fortunately, there are not many names that are etymologically unclear in scorpions, but such cases still exist. To begin with, *Babycurus* Karsch, 1886 was not given an etymology by the author. However, it might be a combination of *babyc-* and *-urus*. The prefix is unknown but the suffix is commonly seen, and means “tail”. Luckily, this genus has a junior synonym, *Rhoptrurus* Karsch, 1886, which can be literally translated as “club-tailed scorpion”. The two synonyms have one word in common. As a result, the senior synonym is translated by its junior synonym as “棒尾蝎”. Hence, if a genus is of unknown etymology and it has a junior synonym which is translatable, use the translation of the junior synonym. If it has multiple junior synonyms, give the priority to the earliest one. If the earliest one is not translatable, use the second, and so on. If all the synonyms are not translatable, then consider transliteration or create a new name, or use the autochthonym, if it exists.

According to Dupré (2016), *Charmus* Karsch, 1879 was named after the ancient Indian people, Charmae. It seems that Charmae is a plural form of Charma, an ancient character in Hindu mythology, who is a son of Shradhdhadeva Manu, the ancestor of mankind. This name has also occurred in the book *The history of initiation, in twelve lectures: comprising detailed account of the rites and ceremonies, doctrines and discipline of all the secret and mysterious institutions of the*

ancient world by Oliver (1782-1867). However, the type species of this genus is *C. laneus* Karsch, 1879. As it can be seen from the complete scientific name that, the type species was instantly designated when the genus was established. The type locality is Ceylon (now Sri Lanka) (Kovařík et al., 2016), which has never been a part of India, so Charma is not justified. Hence, the name is currently considered to be derived from Medieval English *charme*, from Latin *carmen*, which means “magical spell”. The English word “charm” is of the same origin. This may be cognate with the Greek word χάρμα (khárma) that means joy or delight. Thus the name is temporarily translated as “迷蝎” (the “charming/mysterious scorpion”) and also as a pun to allude to its mysterious etymology.

Also according to Dupré (2016), *Grosphus* Simon, 1880 was named after a character in the *Odes* by Horace. The character Grosphus was described as a wealthy Sicilian landlord. This is very much possible as Simon had named several genera after literary characters. However, I have looked into the original paper and the etymology was not given, so it is only a speculation. The word “grosphus” comes from ancient Greek γρόςφος (grósphos) which means the “point of a javelin”. Similar with *Tityus* and *Buthus*, many ancient Greek characters’ names are derived from certain words. For example, Aeneas is the Romanization of the hero’s original Greek name Αινείας (Aineías). Aineías is first introduced in the *Homeric Hymn to Aphrodite* when Aphrodite gives him a name from the adjective αινόν (ainon, “terrible”), for the “terrible grief” (αινόν ἄχος) he has caused her by being born as a mortal who will age and die (Nagy, 2001). As a result, *Grosphus* is currently translated as “矛蝎” (the spear scorpion) after the etymology of the person’s name.

Akin to *Babycurus*, the etymology of *Thestylus* Simon, 1880 was not given. It might be a Greek character name since it was named by Simon, but no such name was found. The word *stylus* means “a stake or pale” in Latin, from ancient Greek στῦλος (stûlos, “a pillar”). The junior synonym of this genus is *Maecocentrus* Karsch, 1880 whose prefix *maeco-* is of an unknown origin and *centrus* means “sharp point”. The word *centrus* is from Latin *centrum*, from ancient Greek κέντρον (kéntron), from κεντεῖν (kenteîn, “to prick, goad”), which is also the etymology of the English word “center”. Apparently, *stylus* and *centrus* are of similar meaning. As a result, the genus named is currently partially translated as “尖刺蝎” (the spike scorpion).

Finally, in one species, although the etymology of *Teuthraustes carmelinae* Scorza, 1954 is unknown, it is temporarily considered as a female name and translated as “卡氏国王蝎”.

Conclusions

The scientific Latin name is the only exclusive name for an animal while the binominal nomenclature is the regulation for how a scientific name should be coined. The etymology of

the scientific names is rather diverse. Although one scientific name may not be “correct” (mostly due to the lack of knowledge at that time) and sometimes it may be arbitrary or inconclusive, it represents the view of the original author and what is reckoned in the current classification for most of the time. The Latin name can be misleading by its meaning, yet it acts as the “identity card” of a species so usually no academic confusion or complexity (unlike in other various names for an animal) will occur.

Animal names are more diverse in China than in other countries as there are “formal” names aside from the folk/vernacular names. So how should one consider the question “what is the name of this animal”? All the names above can be considered as the names of one species (folk names, vernacular names or formal names, etc.); however, they must be ranked with priority (in this paper: scientific Latin names > translation (equivalent) of the scientific names (when one does not use Latin) > formal names (of academic value and only in China) > folk names (of cultural value) > vernacular names (the most casual one)). Science popularization of zoology is rather ubiquitous in the Chinese society today. Yet, most of the science communicators fail to emphasize the importance of knowing the scientific names of the animals they address either because of the difficulty of memorizing Latin names (for both the communicators and their audience), or lack of knowledge of basic science (or the importance of the scientific names is not reinforced in their cognition), or reluctance to use Latin name (due to hypocritical “cultural confidence” or radical bias against all foreign cultures). As a result, many do not provide Latin names; they may use various names (including the formal Chinese names), which leads to the confusion among the target audience. They have no clear knowledge of the types of animal names, so they usually do not explain what kind of the name they use. Even if they provide the audience with a scientific name, the audience may think that the Chinese name is the equivalent to it. However, this is only justified if the Chinese name is a translation of the Latin name, yet, more often it is not. Consequently, people argue about the correctness of those various names and they never realize that those are not “linguistically Chinese versions of the Latin names”, or they do not know that Latin names are the only valid names for animals in biology.

Being a minority field with little attention in China, the Chinese name of scorpion inevitably exhibits a high level of confusion. The knowledge of scorpion species is mainly induced by the Chinese scientific publications and the amateur circles. The names used in both cases are filled with inconsistency and confusion. Leaving aside vernacular names, the names used in the scientific field should be standardized; yet just like for all the other animal taxa, they so far failed to achieve this in scorpionology.

The present contribution provided the first detailed introduction to the scorpion scientific names by thoroughly investigating their categories, along with Chinese names for all the extant, valid species proposed by using the

method of translating Latin names according to their etymology in a systematic fashion. In the beginning, this article has also discussed at length the current confusion and chaos in Chinese scorpion names. Since most people in China are neither familiar with nor good at Latin names, standards of formally naming Chinese names for animals should be established. The current formal Chinese names may come from folk names, vernacular names, translation of Latin names, and translation of common names used in foreign countries. Self-created names frequently appear as well. Such phenomenon is also found for many other taxa; it is reasonable to believe that this is a common problem. Moreover, current Chinese translations of Latin names further fall into three groups: incomplete, inappropriate, and inconsiderate translation. All these different kinds of names have complicated the identity of certain species, which, I believe, causes confusion in public cognition and amateur study. However, at least those previous authors had tried to translate the Latin names and only some refinement is needed.

I am not saying that one must only give a Chinese name to an animal by translating the Latin names; nevertheless, this proved to be the most orderly and coherent way, and it has also been performed in several other taxa (by my personal trials) with most of the translating rules being feasible as well (of course, one can easily coin a scientific name that would be hard to translate, or the translation would conflict with the existing one if they object to the principle of translating Latin names to respect the original meaning). More importantly, many of the names that I translated are being accepted and used by more and more people. Besides scorpions, one of the most widely used Chinese names among amateurs translated by me in Mantodea Latreille, 1802 is “中敛纹螳” for *Pnignomantis medioconstricta* Westwood, 1889. However, many names like “斧螳” (ax mantis; for *Hierodula* Burmeister, 1838) and “刀螳” (knife mantis; for *Tenodera* Burmeister, 1838) originated from common name “刀螂” (a folk name for all the common mantis species), while *Machairima* Beier, 1965 is the genus that deserves the name “刀螳” (etymology: *mákhaira* or *machairi*, a large knife). One of the excuses commonly used by the protesters against translating Latin names according to their etymologies is the theory of cognition. They believe that if one name has been used for a long time and both the public and scientists have already become familiar with it, the name should not be replaced. However, my personal trials and observations in people’s application of the Chinese names of scorpions have demonstrated that, although such novelty will certainly cause conflicts, it will only be temporary since the old usage will vanish while new people will continuously emerge who use the new name. If those new people are introduced to the new names in the first place, with the increase of their number, the old confusing names will go extinct eventually (nevertheless, folk names do not have to perish as they represent the culture of certain regions). However, if no action is taken, the current condition will only become worse as there will be more species recognized

by both the professionals and the public with the previous naming methods, thus leading to further difficulties and chaos in Chinese names for animals. Habit should never be an excuse of rejecting novelty. Many people who are against of designating the Chinese names in a more systemized way with etymological supports claim that creating new names will only cause chaos and it is neither necessary or beneficial for communication. However, I personally believe that a Chinese name does not have to be permanently invariant, because taxonomy constantly changes, and one should update the name in order to be consistent with the current study for a better cognition. Certainly, an experienced researcher does not have such a need, but creation of a Chinese name itself serves the purpose of helping those who are unfamiliar with Latin names, which includes new hobbyists. Those new hobbyists will be confused by the old names and the contradictory taxonomy. Without question, there will be people who may ask “why not update a Chinese name?” They will certainly be suppressed in the current ideological environment as the previous hobbyist/researchers have already got used to their comfort zones of using those old names. Apparently, this matter is totally subjective, while I believe that refining the names is essential and avoiding making changes is merely an excuse for laziness (or just due to the utter indifference, which gives one no right to interfere with others’ choice).

Translating Latin names according to the etymologies is rather routine in the field of palaeontology albeit many people object to this method in the studies of extant taxa. If one insists on naming animals in Chinese by not using translation (or partially), they ought to organize a standardized regulation in order to reduce chaos. However, absence of a nationally accepted formal Chinese nomenclature for animals is why the chaos keeps appearing. Without regulation, there will be chaos. On the contrary, this is exactly why the binominal nomenclature is still followed by all the scientists worldwide: a well-established regulation prevents almost all of the potential confusion. The protesters of translating Latin names assert that it is not necessary to name animals in Chinese according to the etymology of Latin names. But who defines the necessity? There is no rule, and such definition is completely subjective. Designation of formal Chinese names is for the convenience of Chinese to know animals. However, many cannot deliver a clear and systematic picture to those who want to know more. Designation of Chinese names should not only concern the ordinary public which is given chaotic although vulgar names, but also those who want to study them as well as those who are interested in etymology and translation. Despite the fact that some people in China oppose and taunt the ideology of designating Chinese names for animals by the etymology of their scientific names, none of them has ever endeavored to provide a systemized regulation of naming animals in Chinese or a complete list of Chinese names for a certain taxon. On the other hand, true scorpologists in China consider this matter much more rationally as they admit previous mistakes in the existing formal Chinese names for scorpions.

The present contribution is not to gain acceptance or replace all the names, because this matter is utterly conceptual and subjective; instead, this acts as an evidence for the feasibility and superiority of designating Chinese names according to the etymologies. Inevitably, more obstacles may occur when trying to translate other taxa, however, this contribution also serves as an example. There is no right or wrong in choosing which name to use. Yet, I tend to provide an alternative perspective for those beginners who may not have a clear cognition of the types of various names. No one should be dictated by the so-called “trend” (i.e., for the Chinese animal names, use Chinese formal names only), but they deserve the opportunity to think critically. All the beginners and those who start to have a inclination of translating Latin names should be offered help; if everyone else is trying to force the beginners to use the Chinese formal names only because they feel comfortable with it and intend to have the complete control over those beginners, then I shall be the one to show them another path. The Chinese names for animals are not as formal as scientific names, no one should be asked to use a certain type of name, and everyone has the right to propose a more orderly naming system, as long as they prove its feasibility. Asserting different principles and performing the corresponding measures in choosing which type of names to use (a casual and subjective context) is just like applying different phylogenetic hypotheses (a much more serious context). Conflicts and modifications will constantly exist in all aspects of human history.

Acknowledgements

I thank Professor Victor Fet for his help. I also show my greatest thankfulness to Professor Fet for being given a chance to publish this study; such a long article without academic content is hard to publish in China, although this article is precisely aimed at the Chinese readers.

In addition, I would like to express my great gratitude to the French scorpologist Gérard Dupré, who has published the first dictionary of scientific scorpion names and solved most of my translation troubles.

Then, my gratefulness also goes to the Norwegian scorpologist Jan Ove Rein, who established the website of *Scorpion Files* which became the portal into scorpion world for numerous amateurs in scorpology (including myself) and provided the most convenient channel to get to know the basic scorpion classification (and also the foundation of the Appendix in the present contribution).

Besides, I would like to thank Zhiyong Di for admitting my efforts of translation, as well as the objective admission of the problem in the contradictory formal Chinese names.

Moreover, I also appreciate the help of two anonymous reviewers in refining this paper.

Finally, I extend my respect to all scorpion researchers. It is the joint effort of everyone that makes the study of scorpology reach this far.

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Appendix 1

Chinese scorpion names checklist

Note: The list below does not include any superfamilies, subfamilies, tribes, subtribes, subgenera, or species-groups/complexes. Currently recognized subgenera (with Chinese translations) and a classification of supraspecific taxa based on current consensus are given in the end.

蝎目 Order Scorpiones C. L. Koch, 1837

新蝎亚目 Suborder Neoscorpionina Thorell & Lindström, 1885

直胸下目 Infraorder Orthosternina Pocock, 1911

杀牛蝎小目 Parvorder **Buthida** Soleglad & Fet, 2003杀牛蝎科 Family **Buthidae** C. L. Koch, 1837爱琴杀牛蝎属 Genus **Aegaeobuthus** Kovařík, 2019 [*aegaeo-* (Aegean) + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}

塞浦路斯爱琴杀牛蝎 *Aegaeobuthus cyprius* (Gantenbein & Kropf, 2000) [Cyprus]^{to}

伽氏爱琴杀牛蝎 *Aegaeobuthus galliano* (Ythier, 2018) [Raymond Galliano]^{ep}

隆背爱琴杀牛蝎 *Aegaeobuthus gibbosus* (Brullé, 1832) [hunch-backed (*gibbus* (gibbous) + *-osus* (full of, overly))]^{mo}

黑环爱琴杀牛蝎 *Aegaeobuthus nigrocinctus* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [*nigro-* (black) + *cinctus* (banded)]^{chr}

非洲等蝎属 Genus **Afroisometrus** Kovařík, 1997 [*afro-* (African) + *Isometrus*]^{to&ta}

敏氏非洲等蝎 *Afroisometrus minshullae* (Fitzpatrick, 1994) [Jacqueline Minshull]^{ep}

非洲信使蝎属 Genus **Afrolychas** Kovařík, 2019 [*afro-* (African) + *Lychas*]^{to&ta}

布氏非洲信使蝎 *Afrolychas braueri* (Kraepelin, 1986) [August Brauer]^{ep}

伯氏非洲信使蝎 *Afrolychas burdoi* (Simon, 1882) [Adolphe Burdo]^{ep}

无刺杀牛蝎属 Genus **Akentrobuthus** Lamoral, 1976 [*a-* (without) + *kentro-* (here as “spur”) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}

阿塔科拉无刺杀牛蝎 *Akentrobuthus atakora* Vignoli & Prendini, 2008 [Range of Atakora, Benin]^{to}

雷氏无刺杀牛蝎 *Akentrobuthus leleupi* Lamoral, 1976 [Narcisse Leleup]^{ep}

阿氏炭蝎属 Genus **Alayotityus** Armas, 1973 [Pastor Alayo Dalmau + *Tityus*]^{ep&ta}

克氏阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus delacruz* Armas, 1973 [Jorge de la Cruz]^{ep}

费氏阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus feti* Teruel, 2004 [Victor Fet]^{ep}

格拉玛阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus granma* Armas, 1984 [Granma Province, Cuba]^{to}

胡拉瓜阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus juraguaensis* Armas, 1973 [Playa Juraguá, Oriente Province, Cuba]^{to}

石栖阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus lapidicola* Teruel, 2002 [*lapidi-* (stone) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}

侏儒阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus nanus* Armas, 1973 [dwarf]^{mo}

淡色阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus pallidus* Teruel, 2002 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}

马埃斯特腊山阿氏炭蝎 *Alayotityus sierramaestrae* Armas, 1973 [Maestra Mts., Cuba]^{to}

无支蝎属 Genus **Ananteris** Thorell, 1891 [*an-* (without) + *anteris* (here as “fulcra”)]^{mo}

阿氏无支蝎 *Ananteris arcadioi* Botero-Trujillo, 2008 [Arcadio Botero]^{pat}

阿沙宁卡无支蝎 *Ananteris ashaninka* Kovařík, Teruel, Lowe & Friedrich, 2015 [Asháninka, people of Amazonian Peru]^{et}

艾氏无支蝎 *Ananteris ashmolei* Lourenço, 1981 [Nelson Philip Ashmole]^{ep}

亚松森无支蝎 *Ananteris asuncionensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [La Asunción, a city in Venezuela]^{to}

巴氏无支蝎 *Ananteris balzanii* Thorell, 1891 [Luigi Balzan]^{ep}

巴里纳斯无支蝎 *Ananteris barinensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Barinas State, Venezuela]^{to}

伯氏无支蝎 *Ananteris bernabei* Giupponi, Vasconcelos & Lourenço, 2009 [Tiago Nascimento Bernabé]^{ep}

彼氏无支蝎 *Ananteris bianchini* Lourenço, Aguiar-Neto & Limeira-de-Oliveira, 2009 [Mario Luciano Bianchini]^{ep}

绚丽无支蝎 *Ananteris bonito* Lourenço, 2012 [Spanish for “beautiful”]^{au(mo)}

卡欣布无支蝎 *Ananteris cachimboensis* Lourenço, Motta & da Silva, 2006 [Serra do Cachimbo, Pará State, Brazil]^{to}

卡玛坎无支蝎 *Ananteris camacan* Lourenço, Giupponi & Leguin 2013 [Camacan Municipality, Bahia State, Brazil]^{to}

巴拿马无支蝎 *Ananteris canalera* Miranda & Armas, 2020 [refers to the inhabitants of Panama]^{et}

卡雅布无支蝎 *Ananteris capayaensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Capaya, a town in Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}

加拉加斯无支蝎 *Ananteris caracensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Caracas, a city in Venezuela]^{to}

卡拉斯科无支蝎 *Ananteris carrasco* Lourenço & Motta, 2019 [a topographic name in Spanish, from Latin *cerrus* (pine tree)]^{au(to)}

科迈罗无支蝎 *Ananteris catuaroi* González-Sponga, 2006 [Catuaró, a village in Sucre State, Venezuela]^{to}

高加圭塔无支蝎 *Ananteris caucaguitensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Caucagüita suburb, Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}

恰氏无支蝎 *Ananteris chagasi* Giupponi, Vasconcelos & Lourenço, 2009 [Amazonas Chagas Júnior]^{ep}

查氏无支蝎 *Ananteris charlescor* ieldi Lourenço, 2001 [Charles Corfield]^{ep}

奇里马克无支蝎 *Ananteris chirimak* González-Sponga, 2006 [Quebrada Chirimak, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}

安第斯无支蝎 *Ananteris cisandinus* Lourenço, 2015 [*cis-* (on the same side) + *andinus* (Andes)]^{to}

- 强鬃无支蝎 *Ananteris claviformis* González-Sponga, 2006 [*clavi-* (club) + *formis* (form)]^{mo}
- 柯氏无支蝎 *Ananteris coineaui* Lourenço, 1982 [Yves Coineau]^{ep}
- 哥伦比亚无支蝎 *Ananteris columbiana* Lourenço, 1991 [Colombia]^{to}
- 隐居无支蝎 *Ananteris cryptozoicus* Lourenço, 2005 [*crypto-* (hidden) + *-zoic* (life)]^{bi}
- 康比无支蝎 *Ananteris cumbensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [“Cumbe”, refers to a region in Venezuela during the colonial period]^{pal}
- 库拉里无支蝎 *Ananteris curariensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Curari, Falcón State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 鄂氏无支蝎 *Ananteris cussinii* Borelli, 1910 [Alfredo Cussini]^{ep}
- 达氏无支蝎 *Ananteris dacostai* Ythier, Chevalier & Lourenço, 2020 [José Da Costa]^{ep}
- 德氏无支蝎 *Ananteris dekeyseri* Lourenço, 1982 [Pierre Louis Dekeyser]^{ep}
- 詹氏无支蝎 *Ananteris deniseae* Lourenço, 1997 [Denise V. Tambourgy]^{ep}
- 德西德里奥无支蝎 *Ananteris desiderio* Lourenço, Giupponi & Leguin 2013 [São Desidério Municipality, Bahia State, Brazil]^{to}
- 迪氏无支蝎 *Ananteris diegorojasi* Rojas-Runjaic, 2005 [Diego Francisco Rojas-Runjaic]^{ep}
- 多氏无支蝎 *Ananteris dorae* Botero-Trujillo, 2008 [Dora Elizabeth Mendoza]^{ep}
- 埃氏无支蝎 *Ananteris ehrlichi* Lourenço, 1994 [Paul Ralph Ehrlich]^{ep}
- 埃尔瓜波无支蝎 *Ananteris elguapoi* González-Sponga, 2006 [El Guapo, Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 伊氏无支蝎 *Ananteris elisabethae* Lourenço, 2003 [Elisabeth Nogueira Ferroni Schwartz]^{ep}
- 爱氏无支蝎 *Ananteris evellynae* Lourenço, 2004 [Évellyn Christinne Bruehmüller Ramos]^{ep}
- 茂氏无支蝎 *Ananteris faguasi* Botero-Trujillo, 2009 [Giovanny Fagua]^{ep}
- 菲氏无支蝎 *Ananteris festae* Borelli, 1899 [Enrico Festa]^{ep}
- 弗氏无支蝎 *Ananteris franckei* Lourenço, 1982 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
- 戈尔戈纳无支蝎 *Ananteris gorgonae* Lourenço & Flórez, 1989 [Gorgona Island, Colombia]^{to}
- 圭里帕无支蝎 *Ananteris guiripaensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Güiripa, a town in Aragua State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 圭亚那无支蝎 *Ananteris guyanensis* Lourenço & Monod, 1999 [French Guiana]^{to}
- 黑褐无支蝎 *Ananteris infuscata* Lourenço, Giupponi & Leguin, 2013 [obscured, perfect passive participle of *infusco* (darken)]^{chr}
- 因氏无支蝎 *Ananteris inoae* González-Sponga, 2006 [*Inocencia* Delgado, abbreviated first name]^{ep}
- 中介无支蝎 *Ananteris intermedia* Lourenço, 2012 [*inter-* (between) + *media* (middle)]^{ta}
- 卡里那无支蝎 *Ananteris kalina* Ythier, 2018 [Kali’na, ethnic group of Mana, French Guiana]^{et}
- 库氏无支蝎 *Ananteris kuryi* Giupponi, Vasconcelos & Lourenço, 2009 [Adriano Brillhante Kury]^{ep}
- 雷氏无支蝎 *Ananteris leilae* Lourenço, 1999 [Leila Aparecida Souza Kury]^{ep}
- 卢氏无支蝎 *Ananteris luciae* Lourenço, 1984 [Lucia H. Rapp Py-Daniel]^{ep}
- 马德拉无支蝎 *Ananteris madeirensis* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [Madeira River]^{to}
- 马米利班无支蝎 *Ananteris mamilihpan* Ythier, Chevalier & Lourenço, 2020 [Mamilihpan Inselberg, French Guiana]^{to}
- 马尼亚普尔无支蝎 *Ananteris maniapurensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Maniapure River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 马拉尼昂无支蝎 *Ananteris maranhensis* Lourenço, 1987 [Maranhão State, Brazil]^{to}
- 玛氏无支蝎 *Ananteris mariaelenae* Lourenço, 1999 [Maria Elena de Lima Perez Garcia]^{ep}
- 瑪氏无支蝎 *Ananteris mariaterezae* Lourenço, 1987 [Maria Tereza Jorge Padua]^{ep}
- 马氏无支蝎 *Ananteris martensi* Lourenço, 2021 [Jochen Martens]^{ep}
- 毛氏无支蝎 *Ananteris mauryi* Lourenço, 1982 [Emilio Antonio Maury]^{ep}
- 梅里达无支蝎 *Ananteris meridana* González-Sponga, 2006 [Mérida Municipality, Venezuela]^{to}
- 迈氏无支蝎 *Ananteris michaelae* Lourenço, 2013 [Michael W. Webber]^{ep}
- 弥氏无支蝎 *Ananteris myriamae* Botero-Trujillo, 2007 [Myriam Trujillo]^{ma}
- 奈氏无支蝎 *Ananteris nairae* Lourenço, 2004 [Nair Otaviano Aguiar]^{ep}
- 娜氏无支蝎 *Ananteris norae* González-Sponga, 2006 [Nora Ferstadt]^{ep}
- 黯色无支蝎 *Ananteris obscura* Lourenço & Motta, 2021 [dark]^{chr}
- 欧氏无支蝎 *Ananteris ochoai* Botero-Trujillo & Flórez, 2011 [José Antonio Ochoa]^{ep}
- 奥氏无支蝎 *Ananteris otaviano* Lira, Pordeus & Ribeiro de Albuquerque, 2017 [Otaviano Pereira de Araújo]^{ep}
- 帕尔马里无支蝎 *Ananteris palmari* Botero-Trujillo & Noriega, 2011 [Palmari Natural Reserve, Brazilian Amazonia, Brazil]^{to}
- 埃尔堡无支蝎 *Ananteris paoensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [El Pao, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 帕拉考托无支蝎 *Ananteris paracotoensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Paracotos, a town in Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 皮氏无支蝎 *Ananteris pierrekondre* Lourenço, Chevalier, Gangadin & Ythier, 2020 [Pierre Kondre, a town in Para District, Suriname]^{ep}
- 普拉塔无支蝎 *Ananteris plataensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Caño La Plata, a tributary of Guaniamo River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 菩氏无支蝎 *Ananteris platnicki* Lourenço, 1993 [Norman Ira Platnick]^{ep}
- 故氏无支蝎 *Ananteris polleti* Lourenço, 2016 [Marc Pollet]^{ep}
- 首要无支蝎 *Ananteris principalis* González-Sponga, 2006 [important (the most numerous species in number in this region)]^{ax}
- 匹氏无支蝎 *Ananteris pydanieli* Lourenço, 1982 [Victor Py-Daniel]^{ep}
- 考拉河无支蝎 *Ananteris riocauensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Caura River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 奇科河无支蝎 *Ananteris riochicoi* González-Sponga, 2006 [Chico River, Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}

- 马埃河无支蝎 *Ananteris riomachensis* Rojas-Runjaic, Portillo-Quintero & Borges, 2008 [Maché River, Venezuela]^{lo}
- 罗赖马无支蝎 *Ananteris roraima* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [Mt. Roraima, the Guianas region, South America]^{lo}
- 萨氏无支蝎 *Ananteris sabineae* Lourenço, 2001 [Sabine Jourdan]^{ep}
- 珊氏无支蝎 *Ananteris sanchezi* González-Sponga, 2006 [Julio C. Sánchez]^{ep}
- 瑟氏无支蝎 *Ananteris sepulvedai* González-Sponga, 2006 [Sigifrido Sepúlveda]^{ep}
- 独特无支蝎 *Ananteris singularis* González-Sponga, 2006 [unique, refers to its unique lateroventral carinae of metasoma V]^{mo}
- 卡里那语无支蝎 *Ananteris sipilili* Ythier, Chevalier & Lourenço, 2020 [Kali'na language for "scorpion"]^{au}
- 琐氏无支蝎 *Ananteris solimariae* Botero-Trujillo & Flórez, 2011 [Solimary Garcia]^{ep}
- 苏里南无支蝎 *Ananteris surinamensis* Lourenço, 2012 [Suriname]^{lo}
- 特氏无支蝎 *Ananteris terueli* Kovařík, 2006 [Rolando Teruel Ochoa]^{ep}
- 托利马无支蝎 *Ananteris tolimana* Teruel & Garcia, 2007 [Tolima Department, Colombia]^{lo}
- 特里索无支蝎 *Ananteris tresor* Ythier, Chevalier & Lourenço, 2020 [Trésor Regional Natural Reserve, Mt. Kaw, French Guiana]^{lo}
- 图仑班无支蝎 *Ananteris turumbanensis* Gonzáles-Sponga, 1990 [San Martín de Turumbán, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{lo}
- 委内瑞拉无支蝎 *Ananteris venezuelensis* Gonzáles-Sponga, 1972 [Venezuela]^{lo}
- 佛氏无支蝎 *Ananteris volschenki* Botero-Trujillo, 2009 [Erich S. Volschenk]^{ep}
- 苏利亚无支蝎 *Ananteris zuliana* González-Sponga, 2006 [Zulia State, Venezuela]^{lo}
- 似无支蝎属 Genus *Ananteroides* Borelli, 1911 [*Ananteris* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
- 斐氏似无支蝎 *Ananteroides feae* Borelli, 1911 [Leonardo Fea]^{ep}
- 意外似无支蝎 *Ananteroides inexpectatus* Lourenço, 2013 [unexpected]^{ax}
- 杀人蝎属 Genus *Androctonus* Ehrenberg, 1828 [*andro* (man) + *-ctonus* (killer)]^{er}
- 英雄杀人蝎 *Androctonus aeneas* C. L. Koch, 1839 [Αἰνείας (Aeneas), a Trojan hero]^{my}
- 阿富汗杀人蝎 *Androctonus afghanus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Afghanistan]^{lo}
- 哈桑尼亚杀人蝎 *Androctonus agrab* Ythier & Lourenço, 2022 [*agrab*, Arabic dialect Ḥassāniyya for "scorpion"]^{au}
- 阿莱氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus aleksandrplotkini* Lourenço & Qi, 2007 [Aleksandr Plotkin]^{ep}
- 阿氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus amoreuxi* (Audouin, 1826)
- 模式亚种 *A. amoreuxi amoreuxi* (Audouin, 1826) [Pierre-Joseph Amoreux]^{ep}
- 利氏亚种 *A. amoreuxi levyi* Fet, 1997 [Gershom Levy]^{ep}
- 南方杀人蝎 *Androctonus australis* (Linnaeus, 1758) [southern (*auster* (south) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 俾路支杀人蝎 *Androctonus baluchicus* (Pocock, 1900) [Baluchistan Province, now in Pakistan]^{lo}
- 布氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus bourdoni* Vachon, 1948 [Bourdon]^{ep}
- 巴伯氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus barbouri* (Werner, 1932) [nomen dubium] [Thomas Barbour]^{ep}
- 双色杀人蝎 *Androctonus bicolor* Ehrenberg, 1828
- 模式亚种 *A. bicolor bicolor* Ehrenberg, 1828 [two-colored]^{mo}
- 长棱亚种 *A. bicolor longecarinatus* (Di Caporiacco, 1932) [nomen dubium] [*longe-* (long) + *carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 布基纳法索杀人蝎 *Androctonus burkinensis* Ythier, 2021 [Burkina Faso]^{lo}
- 乔里斯坦杀人蝎 *Androctonus cholistanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2013 [Cholistan Desert, Punjab Province, Pakistan]^{lo}
- 肥尾杀人蝎 *Androctonus crassicauda* (Olivier, 1807) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 德氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus dekeyseri* Lourenço, 2005 [Pierre Louis Dekeyser]^{ep}
- 多氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus donairei* Rossi, 2015 [David Donaire Barroso]^{ep}
- 乳色杀人蝎 *Androctonus eburneus* (Pallary, 1928) [ivory-colored (*ebur* (ivory, elephant) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of))]^{chr}
- 亲缘杀人蝎 *Androctonus inimitus* (Pocock, 1897) [neighboring, closely related, alike (*ini-* (end, border))]^{ta}
- 贡氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus gonneti* Vachon, 1948 [Gonnet]^{ep}
- 霍加尔杀人蝎 *Androctonus hoggarensis* (Pallary, 1929) [Mt. Hoggar, Algeria]^{lo}
- 留氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus liouvillei* (Pallary, 1924) [Jacques Liouville]^{ep}
- 迈氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus maelfaiti* Lourenço, 2005 [Jean-Pierre Maelfait]^{ep}
- 毛里塔尼亚杀人蝎 *Androctonus mauritanicus* (Pocock, 1902) [either the Kingdom of Mauretania or the Roman province, Mauretania Tingitana]^{pal}
- 摩洛哥杀人蝎 *Androctonus maroccanus* Lourenço, Ythier & Leguin, 2009 [Morocco]^{lo}
- 淡色杀人蝎 *Androctonus pallidus* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
- 强壮杀人蝎 *Androctonus robustus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2013 [strong, robust]^{mo}
- 珊氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus santi* Lourenço, 2015 [Sebastian Sant]^{ep}
- 瑟氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus sergenti* Vachon, 1948 [Etienne Sergent]^{ep}
- 西氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus simonettai* Rossi, 2015 [Alberto Mario Simonetta]^{ep}
- 纤细杀人蝎 *Androctonus tenuissimus* Teruel, Kovařík & Turiel, 2013 [*tenui-* (slender) + *-issimus* (superlative suffix)]^{mo}
- 提格雷杀人蝎 *Androctonus tigrari* Lourenço, Rossi & Sadine 2015 [Tigray Province, Ethiopia]^{lo}
- 多哥杀人蝎 *Androctonus togolensis* Lourenço, 2008 [Togo]^{lo}

- 特氏杀人蝎 *Androctonus tropeai* Rossi, 2015 [Gioele Tropea]^{ep}
 土耳其杀人蝎 *Androctonus turkiyensis* Yağmur, 2021 [Turkey; “Türkiye” in Turkish]
 奇杀牛蝎属 Genus *Anomalobuthus* Kraepelin, 1900 [*anomalo-* (abnormal) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
 克氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus krivochatskyi* Teruel, Kovařík & Fet, 2018 [Victor Anatolyevich Krivokhatsky]^{ep}
 洛氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus lowei* Teruel, Kovařík & Fet, 2018 [Graeme Lowe]^{ep}
 帕氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus pavlovskyi* Teruel, Kovařík & Fet, 2018 [Evgenii Nikanorovich Pavlovsky]^{ep}
 里氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus rickmersi* Kraepelin, 1900 [Willy Rickmer Rickmers]^{ep}
 塔氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus talebii* Teruel, Kovařík, Navidpour & Fet, 2014 [Amir Talebi Gol]^{ep}
 扎氏奇杀牛蝎 *Anomalobuthus zarudnyi* (Birula, 1911) [Nikolai Alekseyevich Zarudny]^{ep}
 伪杀牛蝎属 Genus *Apistobuthus* Finnegan, 1932 [*apisto-* (uncertain, faithless) + *Buthus*]^{ta}
 翼尾伪杀牛蝎 *Apistobuthus pterygocercus* Finnegan, 1932 [*pterygo-* (winged) + *cercus* (tail)]^{mo}
 苏氏伪杀牛蝎 *Apistobuthus susanae* Lourenço, 1998 [Susan Finnegan]^{ep}
 澳杀牛蝎属 Genus *Australobuthus* Locket, 1990 [*australo-* (Australia) + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
 盐湖澳杀牛蝎 *Australobuthus xerolimniorum* Locket, 1990 [*xero-* (dry) + *limni-* (lake) + *-orum* (a form of *-us* (suffix forming adjectives))]^{bi}
 棒尾蝎属 Genus *Babycurus* Karsch, 1886 @
 [unknown; translated by junior syn., *Rhoptrurus*: *rhoptr-* (club) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 安氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus ansorgei* Hirst, 1911 [William Jorge Ansorge]^{ep}
 步氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus brignolii* Lourenço & Rossi, 2017 [nomen dubium] [Paolo Marcello Brignoli]^{ep}
 布氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus buettneri* Karsch, 1886
 模式亚种 *B. buettneri buettneri* Karsch, 1886 [Richard Büttner]^{ep}
 草原亚种 *B. buettneri savanicola* Lourenço, Bruehmueller Ramos & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2005 [*savani-* (savannah) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
 刺形棒尾蝎 *Babycurus centrurimorphus* Karsch, 1886 [*centruri-* (spike + tail, from *Centrurus*) + *morphus* (form, morph)]^{mo/ta}
 邓氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus dunlopi* Kovařík, Lowe, Seiter, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2015 [Jason Andrew Dunlop]^{ep}
 巨人棒尾蝎 *Babycurus gigas* Kraepelin, 1896 [a giant]^{mo}
 杰氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus jacksoni* (Pocock, 1890) [Frederick John Jackson]^{ep}
 克氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus kirki* (Pocock, 1890) [John Kirk]^{ep}
 黑棒尾蝎 *Babycurus melanicus* Kovařík, 2000 [exhibiting melanism]^{chr}
 多刺棒尾蝎 *Babycurus multisubaculeatus* Kovařík, 2000 [*multi-* (multiple) + *subaculeatus* (with sub-aculear)]^{mo}
 着色棒尾蝎 *Babycurus pictus* Pocock, 1896 [colored, colorful]^{mo}
 索氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus solegladi* Lourenço, 2005 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
 塔氏棒尾蝎 *Babycurus taramassoi* Borelli, 1919 [Lieutenant Taramasso]^{ep}
 维图棒尾蝎 *Babycurus wituensis* Kraepelin, 1913 [Witu, a town in Kenya]^{to}
 俾路支直钳蝎属 Genus *Baloorthochirus* Kovařík, 1996 [*balo-* (Baluchistan) + *Orthochirus*]^{to&ta}
 贝氏俾路支直钳蝎 *Baloorthochirus becvari* Kovařík, 1996 [Stanislav Bečvář]^{ep}
 芭氏棒尾蝎属 Genus *Barbaracurus* Kovařík, 2018 @ [Barbara York Main + *Babycurus*]^{ep&ta}
 费氏芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus feti* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský & Hurre, 2019 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
 优雅芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus exquisitus* (Lowe, 2000) [careful (behavior), delicate (morphology)]^{er&mo}
 璞氏芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus prudenti* (Lourenço, 2013) [Patrick Prudent]^{ep}
 索马里亚芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus somalicus* (Hirst, 1907) [Somalia]^{to}
 索夫奥马尔芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus sofomarensis* (Kovařík, Lowe, Seiter, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2015)
 [Sof Omar, Arsi Province, Oromia State, Ethiopia]^{to}
 弱斑芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus subpunctatus* (Borelli, 1925) [*sub-* (slightly) + *punct-* (spot, point) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 乌氏芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus ugartei* (Kovařík, 2000) [Alfredo Ugarte]^{ep}
 温氏芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus winklerorum* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Alexander Winkler and Birgit Winkler]^{ep}
 也门芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus yemenensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Seiter, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2015 [Yemen]^{to}
 赞氏芭氏棒尾蝎 *Barbaracurus zambonellii* (Borelli, 1902) [Lodovico Zambonelli]^{ep}
 比氏蝎属 Genus *Birulatus* Vachon, 1974 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
 地神比氏蝎 *Birulatus astartiae* Stathi & Lourenço, 2003 [Astarte, ancient goddess of earth and fertility]^{de}
 哈氏比氏蝎 *Birulatus haasi* Vachon, 1974 [Georg Haas]^{ep}
 以色列比氏蝎 *Birulatus israelensis* Lourenço, 2002 [Israel]^{to}
 约旦比氏蝎 *Birulatus jordanensis* Lourenço, Al-Saraireh, Afifeh, Baker, Bader-Katbeh & Amr, 2021 [Jordan]^{to}
 螫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthacus* Birula, 1908 [*Buthus* + *acus* (aculeus, needle)]^{rad&mo}
 俄氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus agarwali* Zambre & Lourenço, 2010 [Ishan Agarwal]^{ep}
 阿哈加尔螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus ahaggar* Lourenço, Kourim & Sadine, 2017 [El Ahaggar, Algeria]^{to}
 阿氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus amitaii* Cain, Gefen & Prendini, 2021 [Pinchas Amitai]^{ep}

- 阿拉瓦螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus arava* Cain, Gefen & Prendini, 2021 [Arava Valley, between Israel and Jordan]^{io}
- 沙栖螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus arenicola* (Simon, 1885)
- 模式亚种 *B. arenicola arenicola* (Simon, 1885) [*areni-* (sand) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 摩洛哥亚种 *B. arenicola maroccanus* Lourenço, 2006 [Morocco]^{io}
- 阿马斯氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus armasi* Lourenço, 2013 [Luis F. de Armas]^{ep}
- 比氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus birulai* Lourenço, 2006 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
- 克氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus clevai* Lourenço, 2001 [Régis Cleva]^{ep}
- 迈尼耶螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus elmenia* Lourenço & Sadine, 2017 [El Menia, a town in Algeria]^{io}
- 佛氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus foleyi* Vachon, 1948 [Henry Foley]^{ep}
- 前额螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus frontalis* Werner, 1936 [nomen dubium] [of forehead/front (*frons* (forehead, front) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{mo}
- 黯褐螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus fuscata* Pallary, 1929 [darkened, perfect passive participle of *fusco* (darken)]^{chr}
- 勾氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus golovatchi* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Sergei Ilyich Golovatch]^{ep}
- 瘦螫螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus leptochelys* (Ehrenberg, 1829) [*lepto-* (narrow) + *chelys* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
- 利氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus levyi* Cain, Gefen & Prendini, 2021 [Gershom Levy]^{ep}
- 尼日利亚螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus nigerianus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Nigeria]^{io}
- 黑刺螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus nigroaculeatus* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [*nigro-* (black) + *aculeatus* (with aculeus)]^{chr&mo}
- 尼氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus nitzani* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Menachem Nitzan-Tishler]^{ep}
- 西部螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus occidentalis* Lourenço, 2000 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 巴基斯坦螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus pakistanensis* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Pakistan]^{io}
- 萨氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus samiae* Lourenço & Sadine, 2015 [Samia Bissati]^{ep}
- 斯氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus spatzi* (Birula, 1911) [Paul Spatz]^{ep}
- 棘刺螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus spinatus* Lourenço, Bissati & Sadine, 2016 [*spin-* (spine) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 施氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus stockmanni* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský 2016 [Mark Stockmann]^{ep}
- 史氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus striffleri* Lourenço, 2004 [Boris Striffler]^{ep}
- 塔德莫螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus tadmorensis* (Simon, 1892) [Tadmor (now Palmyra), a city in Syria]^{pal}
- 维氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus villiersi* Vachon, 1949 [André Villiers]^{ep}
- 威氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus williamsi* Lourenço & Leguin, 2009 [Stanley C. Williams]^{ep}
- 约特瓦塔螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus yotvatensis* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Yotvata, Arava Valley, Israel]^{io}
- 齐氏螫杀牛蝎 *Buthacus zieglerei* Lourenço, 2000 [Thomas Ziegler]^{ep}
- 似小杀牛蝎属 Genus *Butheoloides* Hirst, 1925 [*Butheolus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
- 安氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides annieae* Lourenço, 1986 [Annie Prieur Lourenço]^{ep}
- 亚氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides aymerichi* Lourenço, 2002 [Michel Aymerich]^{ep}
- 莎氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides charlotteae* Lourenço, 2000 [Charlotte Rouaud]^{ep}
- 擎氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides cimrmani* Kovařík, 2003 [Jára Cimrman]^{ep}
- 具疣似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides granulatus* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 格氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides grosseri* Kovařík, 2016 [Walter Grosser]^{ep}
- 赫氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides hirsti* Lourenço, 1996 [Arthur Stanley Hirst]^{ep}
- 海岸似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides littoralis* Lourenço, Touloun & Boumezzough, 2011 [*littor-* (shore) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 摩洛哥似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides maroccanus* Hirst, 1925 [Morocco]^{io}
- 米氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides milloti* Vachon, 1948 [Jacques Millot]^{ep}
- 莫氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides monodi* Vachon, 1950 [Lionel Monod]^{ep}
- 努尔似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides nuer* Kovařík, 2015 [Nuer people of Ethiopia]^{et}
- 西部似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides occidentalis* Lourenço, Slimani & Berahou, 2003 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 珀氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides polisi* Lourenço, 1996 [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}
- 草原似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides savanicola* Lourenço, 2013 [*savani-* (savannah) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 施氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides schwendingeri* Lourenço, 2002 [Peter J. Schwendinger]^{ep}
- 斯氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides slimanii* Lourenço, 2010 [Tahar Slimani]^{ep}
- 凡氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides vanderberghi* Lourenço, 2015 [Christian Vanderbergh]^{ep}
- 威氏似小杀牛蝎 *Butheoloides wilsoni* Lourenço, 1995 [Edward Osborne Wilson]^{ep}
- 小杀牛蝎属 Genus *Butheolus* Simon, 1882 [*Buthus* + *-olus* (diminutive suffix)]^{ta&mo}
- 安氏小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus andersoni* (Pocock, 1895) [John Anderson]^{ep}
- 伽氏小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus gallagheri* Vachon, 1980 [Michael D. Gallagher]^{ep}
- 豪氏小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus hallani* Lourenço & Rossi, 2017 [Joel Hallan]^{ep}
- 哈氏小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus harrisoni* Lowe, 2018 [Ian D. Harrison]^{ep}
- 海绿小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus thalassinus* Simon, 1882 [sea-green colored (*thalassi-* (sea) + *-inus* (pertaining to))]^{chr}
- 多绒小杀牛蝎 *Butheolus villosus* Hendrixson, 2006 [*villo-* (hair) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}

- 弱杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthiscus* Birula, 1905 [*Buthus* + *-iscus* (diminutive suffix)]^{ta&mo}
- 双刺弱杀牛蝎 *Buthiscus bicalcaratus* Birula, 1905 [*bi-* (two) + *calcar-* (spur) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 似杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthoscorpio* Werner, 1936 [*Buthus* + *scorpio* (scorpion)]^{ta}
- 齐纳似杀牛蝎 *Buthoscorpio chinnarensis* Aswathi, Sureshan & Lourenço, 2015 [Chinnar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala State, India]^{lo}
- 印度似杀牛蝎 *Buthoscorpio indicus* Lourenço, 2012 [India]^{lo}
- 光滑似杀牛蝎 *Buthoscorpio politus* (Pocock, 1899) [polished, perfect passive participle of *polio* (polish)]^{mo}
- 雷雅拉似杀牛蝎 *Buthoscorpio rayalensis* Javed, Rao, Mirza, Sanap & Tampal, 2010 [Rayalaseema Region, India]^{lo}
- 萨氏似杀牛蝎 *Buthoscorpio sarasinorum* (Karsch, 1891) [Paul Benedict Sarasin and Karl Friedrich Sarasin]^{ep}
- 杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthus* Leach, 1815
- [βουθος (*Buthos*), an ancient Greek athlete who devoured an ox] (*u-* (ox) + *-thus* (sacrifice))^{ep}
- 阿氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus adrianae* Rossi, 2013 [Adriana Ratto Politi]^{ep}
- 阿哈加尔杀牛蝎 *Buthus ahaggar* Ythier, Sadine, Haddadi & Lourenço, 2021 [El Ahaggar, Algeria]^{lo}
- 英雄杀牛蝎 *Buthus ajax* (C. L. Koch, 1839) [Αἴας (*Ajax*), a Greek hero in the Trojan war]^{ep}
- 阿利坎特杀牛蝎 *Buthus alacanti* Teruel & Turiel, 2020 [the natives of Alicante]^{et}
- 艾氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus albengai* Lourenço, 2003 [Laurent Albenga]^{ep}
- 阿穆叙氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus amri* Lourenço, Yağmur & Duhem, 2010 [Zuhair Sami Amr]^{ep}
- 长纹杀牛蝎 *Buthus apiatus* Lourenço, El Bouhissi & Sadine, 2020 [*api-* (a long mark) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 亚特兰蒂斯杀牛蝎 *Buthus atlantis* Pocock, 1889 [Atlantic Ocean]^{lo}
- 奥雷斯杀牛蝎 *Buthus aures* Lourenço & Sadine, 2016 [Aous Mts., Algeria]^{lo}
- 阿瓦什杀牛蝎 *Buthus awashensis* Kovařík, 2011 [Awash, a town in Ethiopia]^{lo}
- 巴埃提卡杀牛蝎 *Buthus baeticus* Teruel & Turiel, 2020 [Baetica, an ancient Roman Province]^{pal}
- 巴尔卡杀牛蝎 *Buthus barcaeus* Birula, 1909 [Barca, an ancient city in Libya]^{pal}
- 柏培拉杀牛蝎 *Buthus berberensis* Pocock, 1900 [Berbera, a city in Somalia]^{lo}
- 博博杀牛蝎 *Buthus bobo* Ythier, 2021 [the Bobo ethnic group of Burkina Faso]^{et}
- 绚丽杀牛蝎 *Buthus bonito* Lourenço & Geniez, 2005 [Spanish for “beautiful”]^{au(mo)}
- 博马里尼杀牛蝎 *Buthus boumalenii* Touloun & Boumezzough, 2011 [Boumalene Region, Morocco]^{lo}
- 布萨达杀牛蝎 *Buthus boussaadi* Lourenço, Chichi & Sadine, 2018 [Bou-Sâada, a town in Algeria]^{lo}
- 步氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus brignolii* Lourenço, 2003 [Paolo Marcello Brignoli]^{ep}
- 中非杀牛蝎 *Buthus centroafricanus* Lourenço, 2016 [*centro-* (center) + *afrianus* (of Africa)]^{lo}
- 察安比杀牛蝎 *Buthus chambiensis* Kovařík, 2006 [Mt. Jebel ech Chambi, Tunisia]^{lo}
- 连斑杀牛蝎 *Buthus confluens* Lourenço, Touloun & Boumezzough, 2012 [refers to the confluent disposition of spots on tergites]^{chr}
- 丹氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus danyii* Rossi, 2017 [László Danyi]^{ep}
- 弗氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus delafuentei* Teruel & Turiel 2020 [Félix Samuel Rodríguez de la Fuente]^{ep}
- 德拉河杀牛蝎 *Buthus draa* Lourenço & Slimani, 2004 [Draa River Valley, Morocco]^{lo}
- 邓氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus dunlopi* Kovařík, 2006 [Jason Andrew Dunlop]^{ep}
- 杜氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus duprei* Rossi & Tropea, 2016 [Gérard Dupré]^{ep}
- 埃及杀牛蝎 *Buthus egyptiensis* Lourenço, 2012 [Egypt]^{lo}
- 厄氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus elhennawy* Lourenço, 2005 [Hisham Kamal El-Din El-Hennawy]^{ep}
- 伊氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus elizabethae* Lourenço, 2005 [Elizabeth Victoria Fet]^{ep}
- 埃氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus elmoutaouakili* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Bouchaib Elmoutaouakil]^{ep}
- 狭长杀牛蝎 *Buthus elongatus* Rossi, 2012 [prolonged, perfect passive participle of *elongo* (prolong)]^{mo}
- 伽氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus gabani* Ythier, 2021 [David (Dave) Gaban]^{ep}
- 咖氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus garcialorcai* Teruel & Turiel, 2020 [Federico García Lorca]^{ep}
- 戈氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus goyffoni* Abidi, Sadine & Lourenço, 2021 [Max Goyffon]^{ep}
- 兵士杀牛蝎 *Buthus halius* (C. L. Koch, 1839) [Ἁλίον (*Halius*), a Trojan soldier]^{my}
- 哈氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus hassanini* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Alexandre Hassanin]^{ep}
- 伊比利亚杀牛蝎 *Buthus ibericus* Lourenço & Vachon, 2004 [Iberia]^{lo}
- 中介杀牛蝎 *Buthus intermedius* (Ehrenberg, 1829) [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta}
- 渐肿杀牛蝎 *Buthus intumescens* (Ehrenberg in Hemprich & Ehrenberg, 1829) [swelled, becoming swollen]^{mo}
- 以色列杀牛蝎 *Buthus israelis* Shulov & Amitai, 1959 [Israel]^{lo}
- (戚氏/) 建新杀牛蝎 *Buthus jianxinae* Lourenço, 2005 [Qi Jianxin (戚建新)]^{ep}
- 卡拉拉杀牛蝎 *Buthus karoraensis* Rossi & Tropea, 2016 [Karora Enclave (within Sudan), Eritrea]^{lo}
- 昆氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus kunti* Yağmur, Koc & Lourenço, 2011 [Kadir Bogaç Kunt]^{ep}
- 拉氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus labuschagnei* Lourenço, 2015 [Rian Labuschagne]^{ep}
- 林氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus lienhardi* Lourenço, 2003 [Charles Lienhard]^{ep}
- 路氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus lourencoi* Rossi, Tropea & Yağmur, 2013 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}

- 卢西坦杀牛蝎 *Buthus lusitanus* Lourenço, 2021 [Lusitani, ancient inhabitants of Portugal]^{et}
- 迈氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus malhommei* Vachon, 1949 [Jean Malhomme]^{ep}
- 曼切戈杀牛蝎 *Buthus manchego* Teruel & Turiel 2020 [a Spanish word used locally for the natives of Castilla-La Mancha]^{au(et)}
- 马氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus mardochei* Simon, 1878 [Mardochée Aby Serour]^{ep}
- 玛氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus mariefranceae* Lourenço, 2003 [Marie-France Martin-Eauclaire]^{ep}
- 摩洛哥杀牛蝎 *Buthus maroccanus* Birula, 1903 [Morocco]^{to}
- 山地杀牛蝎 *Buthus montanus* Lourenço & Vachon, 2004 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 纳巴泰杀牛蝎 *Buthus nabataeus* Lourenço, Abu Afifeh & Al-Sarairoh, 2021 [the Nabataeans, ancient Arab people who inhabited northern Arabia and the southern Levant]^{et}
- 黑囊杀牛蝎 *Buthus nigrovesiculosus* Hirst, 1925 [*nigro-* (black) + *vesiculosus* (here as “vesicle”)]^{chr&mo}
- 西部杀牛蝎 *Buthus occidentalis* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2009 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 欧西塔尼亚杀牛蝎 *Buthus occitanus* (Amoreux, 1789) [Occitania Region, France]^{to}
- 东部杀牛蝎 *Buthus orientalis* Lourenço & Simon, 2012 [eastern (*oriens* (east) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 欧氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus oudjanii* Lourenço, 2017 [David Oudjan]^{ep}
- 王子杀牛蝎 *Buthus paris* (C. L. Koch, 1839) [Πάρις (Paris), the prince of Troy]^{my}
- 帕氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus parroti* Vachon, 1949 [Louis Parrot]^{ep}
- 裴氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus pedrosousai* Teruel & Turiel, 2021 [Pedro Reis de Sousa]^{ep}
- 波氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus pococki* Kovařík, Štáhlavský & Elmi, 2020 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
- 璞氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus prudenti* Lourenço & Leguin, 2012 [Patrick Prudent]^{ep}
- 微小杀牛蝎 *Buthus pusillus* Lourenço, 2013 [tiny]^{mo}
- 庇里牛斯杀牛蝎 *Buthus pyrenaes* Ythier, 2021 [Pyrénées-Orientales Department, France]^{to}
- 侯氏杀牛蝎 *Buthus rochati* Lourenço, 2003 [Hervé Rochat]^{ep}
- 撒哈拉杀牛蝎 *Buthus saharicus* Sadine, Bissati & Lourenço, 2015 [Sahara Desert]^{to}
- 山杀牛蝎 *Buthus serrano* Teruel & Turiel 2020 [Spanish for “belonging to a mountain range”]^{au(bi)}
- 索马里兰杀牛蝎 *Buthus somalilandus* Kovařík, Štáhlavský & Elmi, 2020 [Somaliland]^{to}
- 塔西里杀牛蝎 *Buthus tassili* Lourenço, 2002 [Tassili n’Ajjjer, Algeria]^{to}
- 特里纳克里亚杀牛蝎 *Buthus trinacrius* Lourenço & Rossi, 2013 [Τρινάκρια (Trinacria), an ancient name of Sicily]^{pal}
- 突尼斯杀牛蝎 *Buthus tunetatus* (Herbst, 1800) [Tunisia]^{to}
- 也门杀牛蝎 *Buthus yemenensis* Lourenço, 2008 [Yemen]^{to}
- 齐拉杀牛蝎 *Buthus zeylensis* Pocock, 1900 [Zeila, a town in Somalia]^{to}
- 似刺尾蝎属 Genus *Centruroides* Marx, 1890 [*Centrurus*?; reason for naming after this genus is unknown; *centr-* (spine) + *urus* (tail)) + *-oides* (resembling)]^{mo/ta}
- 阿氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides alayoni* Armas, 1999 [Giraldo Alayón Garcia]^{ep}
- 阿塔格蕾霞似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides altagraciae* Teruel, Armas & Kovařík, 2015 [La Altagracia Province, Dominican Republic]^{to}
- 安克利塔斯似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides anchorellus* Armas, 1976 [Cayo Anclitas Island, Cuba]^{to}
- 瘦螯似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides arctimanus* Armas, 1976 [*arcti-* (narrow, fitted, confined) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 贝氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides baergi* Hoffmann, 1932 [William J. Baerg]^{ep}
- 巴尔萨斯似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides balsasensis* Ponce & Francke, 2004 [Balsas Basin, Michoacan State, Mexico]^{to}
- 巴尼似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides bani* Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1987 [Bani, a city in the Dominican Republic]^{to}
- 巴拉克阿似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides baracoae* Armas, 1976 [Baracoa Municipality, Oriente Province, Cuba]^{to}
- 巴布达似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides barbudensis* Pocock, 1898 [Barbuda Island, Lesser Antilles]^{to}
- 柏氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides berstoni* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Hyman Maxwell Berston]^{ep}
- 伯氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides bertholdii* Thorell, 1876 [Arnold Adolph Berthold]^{ep}
- 双色似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides bicolor* Pocock, 1898 [two-colored]^{mo}
- 绚丽似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides bonito* Quijano-Ravell, Teruel & Ponce-Saavedra, 2016 [Spanish for “beautiful”]^{au(mo)}
- 卡劳尔似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides caral* Armas & Trujillo, 2013 [Caral Mts., Guatemala]^{to}
- 加勒比似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides caribbeanus* Teruel & Myers, 2017 [Caribbean]^{to}
- 卡特马科似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides catemacoensis* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Catemaco Municipality, Mexico]^{to}
- 查梅拉似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides chamela* Ponce-Saavedra & Francke, 2011 [Biological Station of Chamela, Jalisco State, Mexico]^{to}
- 查穆拉似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides chamulaensis* Hoffmann, 1932 [San Juan Chamula Municipality, Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 乾氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides chanae* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Kendra Chan]^{ep}
- 恰帕斯似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides chiapanensis* Hoffmann, 1932 [Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 康科迪亚似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides concordia* Armas & Teruel, 2021 [La Concordia Municipality, Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 树栖似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides cuauhmapan* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Nahuatl for “up in a tree”]^{au(bi)}
- 埃氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides edwardsii* (Gervais, 1843) [Henri Milne-Edwards]^{ep}
- 秀丽似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides elegans* (Thorell, 1876)

- 模式亚种 *C. elegans elegans* (Thorell, 1876) [elegant]^{mo}
 缺齿亚种 *C. elegans edentulous* Werner, 1939 [*e-* (without) + *dent-* (tooth) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
 岛屿亚种 *C. elegans insularis* Pocock, 1902 [*insul-* (island) + *-aris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
 细尾似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides exilicauda* Wood, 1863 [*exili-* (spindly) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
 细螯似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides exilimanus* Teruel & Stockwell, 2002 [*exili-* (spindly) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 孤岛似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides exsul* Meise, 1933 [exiled, isolated, insular]^{bi}
 迷惑似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides fallassisimus* Armas & Trujillo, 2010 [*fallass-* (deceitful) + *-isimus* (superlative suffix)]^a
 珙氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides farri* Armas, 1976 [Thomas Farr]^{ep}
 黄色似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides flavopictus* (Pocock, 1898)
 模式亚种 *C. flavopictus flavopictus* (Pocock, 1898) [*flavo-* (yellow) + *pictus* (colored)]^{chr}
 南部亚种 *C. flavopictus meridionalis* Hoffmann, 1932 [southern (*meridio-* (south) + *-alis* (pertaining to))] ^{cho}
 弗氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides franckei* Santibáñez-López & Contreras-Félix, 2013 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
 黄足似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides fulvipes* Pocock, 1898 [*fulvi-* (yellow) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
 加拉诺似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides galano* Teruel, 2001 [Cerro Galano Mts., Cuba]^{to}
 纤细似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides gracilis* (Latreille, 1804) [gracile]^{mo}
 多疣似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides granosus* Thorell, 1876 [*gran-* (grain) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 浅灰似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides griseus* C. L. Koch, 1844 [*gris-* (grey) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
 瓜内似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides guanensis* Franganillo, 1930 [Guane Municipality, Pinar del Rio Province, Cuba]^{to}
 树精似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides hamadryas* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Ἠμαδρύας (Hamadryas), mother of tree-dwelling nymphs in Greek mythology]^{my}
 亨氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides hentzi* Banks, 1900 [Nicholas Marcellus Hentz]^{ep}
 鬃尾似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides hirsuticauda* Teruel, 2011 [*hirsuti-* (hairy, bristled) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
 鬃肢似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides hirsutipalpus* Ponce-Saavedra & Francke, 2009 [*hirsuti-* (hairy, bristled) + *-palpus* (here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
 霍氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides hoffmanni* Armas, 1996 [Carlos Cristian Hoffmann]^{ep}
 惠乔尔似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides huichol* Teruel, Ponce-Saavedra & Quijano-Ravell, 2015 [Huichol people of Nayarit State, Mexico]^{et}
 恶名似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides infamatus* C. L. Koch, 1844 [infamous]^{cha}
 岛屿似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides insulanus* Thorell, 1876 [*insula-* (island) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
 伊西尔似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides ixil* Trujillo & Armas, 2016 [Ixil, a Maya people indigenous to Guatemala]^{et}
 雅拉瓜似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides jaragua* Armas, 1999 [Jaragua National Park, Dominican Republic]^{to}
 候氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides jorgeorum* Santiago-Blay, 2009 [Jorge Santiago-Velázquez and Jorge Luis de León]^{pat&ep}
 库氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides koesteri* Kraepelin, 1912 [H. Köster]^{ep}
 劳阿氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides lauriadnae* Ponce-Saavedra & Francke, 2019 [Laura and Ariadna Ponce Saavedra]^{ep}
 缘纹似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides limbatus* Pocock, 1898 [*limb-* (edge, border) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 明澈似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides limpidus* Karsch, 1879 [clear, bright, limpid]^{mo}
 卢氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides luceorum* Armas, 1999 [Henry Christopher and Leila Hadley Luce]^{ep}
 光亮似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides lucidus* Teruel, Armas & Kovařík, 2015 [*luci-* (light) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 马氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides marcanoi* Armas, 1981 [Eugenio de Jesus Marcano Fondeur]^{ep}
 珠粒似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides margaritatus* (Gervais, 1841) [*margarit-* (pearl) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 马斯科塔似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides mascota* Ponce-Saavedra & Francke, 2011 [Mascota, a town in Jalisco State, Mexico]^{to}
 埋氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides meisei* Hoffmann, 1939 [Wilhelm Meise]^{ep}
 黑指似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides melanodactylus* Teruel, 2001 [*melano-* (black) + *dactylus* (finger)]^{mo}
 纳氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides navarroi* Teruel, 2001 [Nils Navarro Pacheco]^{ep}
 渐黑似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides nigrescens* Pocock, 1898 [*nigr-* (black) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}
 黑掌似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides nigrimanus* Pocock, 1898 [*nigri-* (black) + *manus* (hand)]^{chr&mo}
 黑斑似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides nigropunctatus* Teruel, 2006 [*nigri-* (black) + *punct-* (spot, point) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 黑异似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides nigrovariatus* Pocock, 1898 [*nigro-* (black) + *variatus* (varied, perfect passive participle of *vario* (vary))] ^{chr}
 光泽似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides nitidus* Thorell, 1876 [*nit-* (to shine) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 剧毒似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides noxius* Hoffman, 1932 [noxious, harmful]^{cha}
 黄褐似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides ochraceus* Pocock, 1898 [*chra* (yellow ochre) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
 奥里萨巴似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides orizaba* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2003 [Orizaba, a city in Veracruz State, Mexico]^{to}
 饰装似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides ornatus* Pocock, 1902 [decorated, perfect passive participle of *orno* (adorn)]^{mo/chr}
 浅首似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides pallidiceps* Pocock, 1902 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idi-* (tending to) + *-iceps* (head)]^{chr&mo}
 巴拿马似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides panamensis* Arias & Esposito, 2014 [Panama]^{to}
 菩氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides platnicki* Armas, 1981 [Norman Ira Platnick]^{ep}
 波氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides pococki* Sissom & Francke, 1983 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
 泊氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides polito* Teruel, 2007 [Leopoldo Viña Dávila (“Polito”)]^{ep}

- 庞氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides poncei* Teruel, Kovařík, Baldazo-Monsivais & Hoferek, 2015 [Javier Ponce-Saavedra]^{ep}
- 珀氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides possanii* González-Santillán, Galán-Sánchez & Valdez-Velázquez, 2019 [Lourival Domingos Possani Posta]^{ep}
- 里氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides rileyi* Sissom, 1995 [Edward G. Riley]^{ep}
- 罗氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides robertoi* Armas, 1976 [Luis Roberto Hernández]^{ep}
- 欢愉似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides rodolfoi* Santibáñez-López & Contreras-Félix, 2013 [Rodolfo, Spanish for “Rudolph”, the red-nose reindeer that brings happiness]^{au(ep)}
- 柔氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides romeroi* Quijano-Ravell, Armas, Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2019 [Manuel E. Romero]^{ep}
- 鲁亚纳似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides ruana* Quijano-Ravell & Ponce-Saavedra, 2016 [La Ruana (Felipe Carrillo Puerto), a town in Buenavista Municipality, Michoacan State, Mexico]^{to}
- 圣安德烈斯岛似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides sanandres* Armas, Sarmiento & Flórez 2012 [San Andres Island, Colombia]^{to}
- 萨氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides sasae* Santiago-Blay, 2009 [nickname (“Sasa”) of Rosangie Maria Santiago-Blay]^{ep}
- 施氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides schmidti* Sissom, 1995 [Karl Patterson Schmidt]^{ep}
- 雕纹似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides sculpturatus* Ewing, 1928 [sculptured, perfect passive participle of *sculptura* (sculpture)]^{mo}
- 山似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides serrano* Santibáñez-López & Ponce-Saavedra, 2009 [Spanish for “belonging to a mountain range”]^{au(bi)}
- 朴素似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides simplex* Thorell, 1876 [simple]^{mo}
- 西氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides sissomi* Armas, 1996 [William David Sissom]^{ep}
- 预期似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides spectatus* Teruel, 2006 [expected, perfect passive participle of *specto* (observe)]^{ax}
- 斯氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides stockwelli* Teruel, 2001 [Scott Allen Stockwell]^{ep}
- 腥红似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides suffusus* Pocock, 1902 [reddened, perfect passive participle of *suffendo* (suffuse)]^{chr}
- 塔帕丘拉似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides tapachulaensis* Hoffmann, 1932 [Tapachula, a city in Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 特克曼似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides tecomanus* Hoffmann, 1932 [Tecomán, a city in Colima State, Mexico]^{to}
- 纤弱似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides tenuis* Thorell, 1876 [slender]^{mo}
- 砖红似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides testaceus* DeGeer, 1778 [*testa* (brick) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
- 托氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides thorellii* Kraepelin, 1891 [Tord Tamerlan Teodor Thorell]^{ep}
- 图斯特拉似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides tuxtla* Armas, 1999 [Tuxtla Gutiérrez, a city in Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 恩氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides underwoodi* Armas, 1976 [Garth Underwood]^{ep}
- 维氏似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides villegasi* Baldazo-Monsivaiz, Ponce-Saavedra & Flores-Moreno, 2013 [Ascencio Villegas Arrizôn]^{ep}
- 条纹似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides vittatus* Say, 1821 [*vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 尤卡坦似刺尾蝎 *Centruroides yucatanensis* Goodman, Prendini, Francke & Esposito, 2021 [Yucatán Peninsula, Mexico]^{to}
- 精灵蝎属** Genus *Chaneke* Francke, Teruel & Santibáñez-López, 2014
[chaneque or chanekeh, a legendary creature in Mexican folklore]^{my}
- 爱氏精灵蝎 *Chaneke aliciae* (Armas & Frias, 1998) [Maria de Lourdes Alicia Laguerenne]^{ep}
- 巴氏精灵蝎 *Chaneke baldazoi* Kovařík, Teruel & Lowe, 2016 [José Guadalupe Baldazo Monsivaiz]^{ep}
- 佛戈斯精灵蝎 *Chaneke fogoso* Francke, Teruel & Santibáñez-López, 2014 [Spanish for “feisty” and Microondas Fogos, Mexico]^{au&to}
- 霍氏精灵蝎 *Chaneke hofereki* Kovařík, Teruel & Lowe, 2016 [David Hoferek]^{ep}
- 迷蝎属** Genus *Charmus* Karsch, 1879 #
[unknown; Charma (a character in Hindu myth) or *carmen* (spell, charm)]^{my/mo}
- 步氏迷蝎 *Charmus brignolii* Lourenço, 2000 [Paolo Marcello Brignoli]^{ep}
- 印度迷蝎 *Charmus indicus* Hirst, 1915 [India]^{to}
- 绒迷蝎 *Charmus laneus* Karsch, 1879 [woolly (*lan-* (wool) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of))]^{mo}
- 萨氏迷蝎 *Charmus saradieli* Kovařík, Loewe, Ranawana, Hoferek & Jayarathne 2016 [Deekirikevage Saradiel]^{ep}
- 辛哈加德迷蝎 *Charmus sinhagadensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Sinhadag Hill Fortress, Maharashtra State, India]^{to}
- 西氏滑尾蝎属** Genus *Cicileiurus* Teruel, 2007 [*Cicileus* + *Leiurus*]^{ta}
- 山栖西氏滑尾蝎 *Cicileiurus monticola* Teruel, 2007 [*monti-* (mountain) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 西氏蝎属** Genus *Cicileus* Vachon, 1948 [Dr. Cicile]^{ep}
- 瘦西氏蝎 *Cicileus exilis* (Pallary, 1928) [spindly]^{mo}
- 克氏西氏蝎 *Cicileus cloudsleythompsoni* Lourenço, 1999 [John Leonard Cloudsley-Thompson]^{ep}
- 霍加尔西氏蝎 *Cicileus hoggarensis* Lourenço & Rossi, 2015 [Hoggar Mts., Algeria]^{to}
- 拉氏西氏蝎 *Cicileus latellai* Lourenço & Rossi, 2015 [Leonardo Latella]^{ep}
- 山地西氏蝎 *Cicileus montanus* Lourenço & Rossi, 2015 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 秀杀牛蝎属** Genus *Compsobuthus* Vachon, 1949 [*compso-* (elegant) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 阿比西尼亚秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus abyssinicus* (Birula, 1903) [Abyssinia]^{to}
- 锐棱秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus acutecarinatus* (Simon, 1882) [*acute-* (sharp) + *carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 阿富汗秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus afghanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2007 [Afghanistan]^{to}
- 埃尔秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus air* Lourenço & Rossi, 2018 [Aïr Mts., Niger]^{to}
- 安氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus andresi* Lourenço, 2004 [Andrés Alejandro Ojangurren-Affilastro]^{ep}

- 阿拉伯秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus arabicus* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Saudi Arabia]¹⁰
 亚美尼亚秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus armenicus* Lourenço, Leguin & Duhem, 2015 [Armenia]¹⁰
 黑纹秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus atrostriatus* (Pocock, 1897) [*atro-* (black) + *stri-* (stripe) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 伯氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus berlandi* Vachon, 1950 [Lucien Berland]^{ep}
 比氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus birulai* Lourenço, Leguin & Duhem, 2010 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
 博氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus boucheti* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Philippe Bouchet]^{ep}
 短掌秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus brevimanus* (Werner, 1936) [*brevi-* (short) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 卡梅尔秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus carmelitis* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Mt. Carmel, Israel]¹⁰
 厄立特里亚秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus eritreaensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2016 [Eritrea]¹⁰
 埃及秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus egyptiensis* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2009 [Egypt]¹⁰
 盖氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus garyi* Lourenço & Vachon, 2001 [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}
 休马氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus humae* Amir, Kamaluddin & Kahn, 2005 [nomen dubium] [Huma]^{ep}
 杰氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus jakesi* Kovařík, 2003 [Oldřich Jakeš]^{ep}
 约旦秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus jordanensis* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Jordan]¹⁰
 卡氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus kabateki* Kovařík, 2003 [Petr Kabátek]^{ep}
 喀氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus kaftani* Kovařík, 2003 [Milan Kaftan]^{ep}
 海巴尔秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus khaybari* Abu Afifeh, Aloufi & Al-Saraireh, 2021 [Khaybar, a city in Saudi Arabia]¹⁰
 柯氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus klaptoczi* (Birula, 1909) [Bruno Klaptocz]^{ep}
 克氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus krali* Kovařík, 2012 [David Král]^{ep}
 利氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus levyi* Kovařík, 2012 [Gershom Levy]^{ep}
 长肢秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus longipalpis* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [*longi-* (long) + *-palpis* (here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
 梅德秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus maidensis* Kovařík, 2018 [Maid, a village in Somaliland]¹⁰
 曼氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus maindroni* (Kraepelin, 1900) [Maurice Maindron]^{ep}
 缙氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus manzonii* (Borelli, 1915) [Renzo Manzoni]^{ep}
 马氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus matthiesseni* (Birula, 1905) [A.A. Matthiessen]^{ep}
 细指秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus nematodactylus* Lowe, 2009 [*nemato-* (thread) + *dactylus* (finger)]^{mo}
 巴基斯坦秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus pakistanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2007 [Pakistan]¹⁰
 淡色秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus pallidus* Hendrixson, 2006 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
 波斯秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus persicus* Navidpour, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2008 [Persia (now Iran)]^{pal}
 佩氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus petrioli* Vignoli, 2005 [Andrea Petrioli]^{ep}
 浦氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus plutenkoi* Kovařík, 2003 [Andrei Plutenko]^{ep}
 珀氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus polisi* Lowe, 2001 [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}
 细褶秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus rugosulus* (Pocock, 1900) [*rug-* (wrinkle) + *-osu* (full of, overly) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
 萨德布尔秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus satpuraensis* Waghe, Gangalmale & Khandekar, 2022 [Satpura Mts., India]¹⁰
 施氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus schmiedeknechti* Vachon, 1949 [Otto Schmiedeknecht]^{ep}
 赛氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus seichertii* Kovařík, 2003 [Václav Seichert]^{ep}
 多毛秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus setosus* Hendrixson, 2006 [*set-* (seta) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 昔氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus simoni* Lourenço, 1999 [Eugène Simon]^{ep}
 信德秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus sindicus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2011 [Sind Province, Pakistan]¹⁰
 索马里兰秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus somalilandus* Kovařík, 2012 [Somaliland]¹⁰
 塔西里秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus tassili* Lourenço, 2010 [Tassili n’Ajjjer, Algeria]¹⁰
 托氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus toftii* Lourenço, 2001 [Soren Toft]^{ep}
 通布图秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus tombouctou* Lourenço, 2009 [Tombouctou Administrative Region, Mali]¹⁰
 徒氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus turieli* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Carlos Turiel]^{ep}
 乌氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus ullrichi* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Alex Ullrich]^{ep}
 瓦氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus vachoni* Sissom, 1994 [Max Vachon]^{ep}
 维氏秀杀牛蝎 *Compsobuthus weneri* (Birula, 1908) [Franz Werner]^{ep}
 刚果杀牛蝎属 Genus *Congobuthus* Lourenço, 1999 [Congo + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
 法氏刚果杀牛蝎 *Congobuthus fagei* Lourenço, 1999 [Louis Fage]^{ep}
 达氏蝎属 Genus *Darchenia* Vachon, 1977 [Bernadette Darchen]^{ep&ty}
 模式达氏蝎 *Darchenia bernadettae* Vachon, 1977 [* same as the genus]^{ep}
 埃及杀牛蝎属 Genus *Egyptobuthus* Lourenço, 1999 [Egypt + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
 威氏埃及杀牛蝎 *Egyptobuthus vaissadei* Lourenço, 1999 [Alain Vaissade]^{ep}
 毫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Femtobuthus* Lowe, 2010 [*femto-* (factor of 10⁻¹⁵ in SI Units) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
 风神毫杀牛蝎 *Femtobuthus shutuae* Lowe, 2010 [Shutu, Babylonian goddess of the south wind]^{de}
 费氏蝎属 Genus *Fetilia* Lowe & Kovařík, 2021 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
 齿尾费氏蝎 *Fetilia dentator* Lowe & Kovařík, 2021 [*dent-* (tooth) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{mo}

- 阿穆哈拉蝎属 Genus *Gint* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2013 [Amharian for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 阿穆德阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint amoudensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Just, Awale, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Amoud University, Somaliland]^{to}
- 班氏阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint banfasae* Kovařík & Lowe, 2019 [Huda Ali Banfas]^{ep}
- 秃首阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint calviceps* (Pocock, 1900) [*calvi-* (bald) + *-ceps* (head)]^{mo}
- 柴氏阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint childsi* Kovařík, 2018 [Anthony Childs]^{ep}
- 袖珍阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint dabakalo* Kovařík & Mazuch, 2015 [*dabaqallooc*, Somali language for “small scorpion”]^{au}
- 查迈阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint gaitako* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2013 [Tsamai for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 古班阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint gubanensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Just, Awale, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Guban Area, Somaliland]^{to}
- 奇异阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint insolitus* (Borelli, 1925) [nomen dubium] [*in-* (not) + *solitus* (usual)]^{mo}
- 梅德阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint maidensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Just, Awale, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Maid, a village in Somaliland]^{to}
- 玛莉亚氏阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint marialuisae* Rossi, 2015 [nomen dubium] [Maria Luisa Tavano]^{ep}
- 莫尼卡氏阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint monicae* Rossi, 2015 [nomen dubium] [Monica Leonardi]^{ep}
- 邦特兰阿穆哈拉蝎 *Gint puntlandus* Kovařík & Mazuch, 2015 [Puntland State, Somalia]^{to}
- 矛蝎属 Genus *Grosphus* Simon, 1880 #
- [unknown, a character in *Odes* by Horace, or γρόσφος (point of a javelin)]^{ep/mo}
- 琥珀山矛蝎 *Grosphus ambre* Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2018 [Ambre Special Reserve, Madagascar]^{to}
- 达瑞纳矛蝎 *Grosphus darainensis* Lourenço, Goodman & Ramilijaona, 2004 [Daraina, a town in Madagascar]^{to}
- 勾氏矛蝎 *Grosphus goudoti* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [Jules Goudot]^{ep}
- 多毛矛蝎 *Grosphus hirtus* Kraepelin, 1900 [hairy]^{mo}
- 马达加斯加矛蝎 *Grosphus madagascariensis* (Gervais, 1843) [Madagascar]^{to}
- 黄矛蝎 *Grosphus mavo* Lourenço & Rossi, 2020 [Malagasy for “yellow”]^{au(chr)}
- 马约特矛蝎 *Grosphus mayottensis* Lourenço & Goodman, 2009 [Mayotte Archipelago]^{to}
- 敏氏矛蝎 *Grosphus polskyi* Lourenço, Qi & Goodman, 2007 [Michael Polsky]^{ep}
- 拉氏矛蝎 *Grosphus rakotoarivelei* Lourenço, Wilmé, Soarimalala & Waeber, 2017 [Caleb Rakotoarivele]^{ep}
- 北部矛蝎 *Grosphus tavaratra* Lourenço, Soarimalala & Goodman, 2009 [Malagasy for “from the north”]^{au(cho)}
- 沃氏矛蝎 *Grosphus voahangyae* Lourenço & Wilmé, 2015 [Voahangy Soarimalala]^{ep}
- 异栉蝎属 Genus *Heteroctenus* Pocock, 1893 [*hetero-* (different) + *-ctenus* (here as “pectine”)]^{mo}
- 阿布德氏异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus abudi* (Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1987) [Abraham José Abud Antún]^{ep}
- 旱栖异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus aridicola* (Teruel & Armas, 2012) [*aridi-* (dry, arid) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 伯氏异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus bonettii* (Armas, 1999) [Mario Bonetti]^{ep}
- 加氏异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus garridoi* (Armas, 1974) [Orlando Hilario Garrido Calleja]^{ep}
- 希瓦拉异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus gibarae* (Teruel, 2006) [Gibara Mts., Cuba]^{to}
- 疣螯异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus granulimanus* (Teruel, 2006) [*granuli-* (small grain) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 木色异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus junceus* (Herbst, 1800) [*junc-* (rush, reed) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
- 梅氏异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus melloleitaoi* (Teruel & Armas, 2006) [Cândido Firmino de Mello-Leitão]^{ep}
- 太子港异栉蝎 *Heteroctenus princeps* (Karsch, 1879) [Port-au-Prince, Haiti]^{to}
- 半杀牛蝎属 Genus *Hemibuthus* Pocock, 1900 [*hemi-* (half) + *Buthus*]^{ta}
- 粗螯半杀牛蝎 *Hemibuthus crassimanus* (Pocock, 1897) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 乌氏半杀牛蝎 *Hemibuthus umarii* Amir, Kamaluddin & Khan, 2004 [Umar Niaz]^{ep}
- 半信使蝎属 Genus *Hemilychas* Hirst, 1911 [*hemi-* (half) + *Lychas*]^{ta}
- 亚历山大半信使蝎 *Hemilychas alexandrinus* (Hirst, 1911) [Alexandria, a city in Australia]^{to}
- 喜山戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Himalayotityobuthus* Lourenço, 1997 [*himalayo-* (Himalaya) + *Tityobuthus*]^{to&ta}
- 阿氏喜山戾杀牛蝎 *Himalayotityobuthus alejandrae* Lourenço, 2003 [Alejandra Ceballos]^{ep}
- 马氏喜山戾杀牛蝎 *Himalayotityobuthus martensi* Lourenço, 1997 [Jochen Martens]^{ep}
- 霍屯督蝎属 Genus *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908 [Hottentots (Khoikhoi), nomads of Namibia and South Africa]^{et&ty}
- 阿氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta akbarii* Yağmur, Moradi, Tabatabaei & Jafari, 2022 [Abolfazl Akbari]^{ep}
- 高地霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta alticola* (Pocock, 1895) ○
- 模式亚种 *H. alticola alticola* (Pocock, 1895) [*alti-* (high) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 黑额亚种 *H. alticola nigrifrons* (Pocock, 1900) [*nigri-* (black) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 砂霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta arenaceus* (Purcell, 1902) [*arena* (sand) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{mo}
- 阿西姆氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta asimii* Amir, Kamaluddin & Khan, 2004 [nomen dubium] [Asim Iftikhar]^{ep}
- 布哈里亚霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta buchariensis* (Birula, 1897) [Bukhara Emirate; until 1920 included territories of modern Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan]^{pal}
- 雀斑霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta conspersus* (Thorell, 1876) [spotted]^{chr}
- 芬氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta finneganae* Kovařík, 2007 [Susan Finnegan]^{ep}
- 浅黄霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta flavidulus* Teruel & Rein, 2010 [light yellow (*flavidu-* (yellowish) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix))]^{chr}
- 弗氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta franzwernerii* (Birula, 1914) [Franz Werner]^{ep}

- 黯躬霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta fuscitruncus* (Di Caporiacco, 1936) [*fusci-* (dark brown) + *truncus* (trunk)]^{chr&mo}
- 甘贝拉霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta gambelaensis* Kovařík, 2015 [Gambela State, Ethiopia]^{to}
- 詹氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta gentili* (Pallary, 1924) [Gentil]^{ep}
- 吉巴霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta gibaensis* Kovařík, 2015 [Giba Valley, Ethiopia]^{to}
- 豪德霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta haudensis* Kovařík & Lowe, 2021 [Haud Area, Somaliland]^{to}
- 霍加尔霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta hoggarensis* Lourenço & Leguin, 2014 [Hoggar Mts., Algeria]^{to}
- 模式霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta hottentotta* (Fabricius, 1787) [* same as the genus]^{et&tau}
- 贾巴尔普尔霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta jabalpurensis* Kovařík, 2007 [Jabalpur, a city in Madhya Pradesh State, India]^{to}
- 贾拉拉巴德霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta jalalabadensis* Kovařík, 2007 [Jalalabad, a city in Nangarhar Province, Afghanistan]^{to}
- 贾氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta jayakari* (Pocock, 1895) [Atmaram Sadashiv Grandin (Grovindin) Jayakar]^{ep}
- 犹太霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta judaicus* (Simon, 1872) [Judea, now Israel]^{pal}
- 朱氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta juliae* Kovařík, Yağmur & Fet, 2019 [Julia V. Samartseva]^{ep}
- 喀拉拉霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta keralaensis* Aswhati, Sureshan & Lourenço, 2016 [Kerala State, India]^{to}
- 胡齐斯坦霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta khoozestanus* Navidpour, Kovařík, Soleglad & Fet, 2008 [Khoozestan Province, Iran]^{to}
- 克氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta krivokhatskyi* Kovařík, Yağmur & Fet, 2019 [Viktor Anatolyevich Krivokhatsky]^{ep}
- 拉氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta lacroixi* Ythier & Dupre, 2021 [Jean-Bernard Lacroix]^{ep}
- 洛斯坦霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta lorestanus* Navidpour, Nayebzadeh, Soleglad, Fet, Kovařík & Kayedi, 2010 [Lorestan Province, Iran]^{to}
- 马氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta mazuchi* Kovařík, 2013 [Tomas Mazuch]^{ep}
- 美索不达米亚霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta mesopotamicus* Lourenço & Qi, 2007 [Mesopotamia]^{pal}
- 恐吓霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta minax* (L. Koch, 1875)
- 模式亚种 *H. minax minax* (L. Koch, 1875) [threatening (*min-* (jut forth) + *-ax* (inclined to))]^{er}
- 西部亚种 *H. minax occidentalis* (Vachon & Stockmann, 1968) [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 半高地霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta minusalta* Vachon, 1959 [*minus-* (less) + *alta* (high)]^{bi}
- 纳氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta navidpouri* Kovařík, Yağmur & Moradi, 2018 [Shahrokh Navidpour]^{ep}
- 黑山霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta nigrimontanus* Kovařík & Lowe, 2021 [Cal Madow (“Black Mountains”) Mts., Somaliland]^{to}
- 诺氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta novaki* Kovařík, 2015 [Pavel Novák]^{ep}
- 厚尾霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta pachyurus* (Pocock, 1897) [*pachy-* (thick, large) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 通透霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta pellucidus* Lowe, 2010 [translucent (*pe-* (through) + *lucidus* (light))]^{mo}
- 班贾布霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta penjabensis* Kovařík, 2007 [Punjab State, India]^{to}
- 多斑霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta polystictus* (Pocock, 1896) [*poly-* (many) + *stictus* (spotted)]^{chr}
- 雷氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta reddyi* Lourenço, 2015 [R. P. Sreenivasa-Reddy]^{ep}
- 皱壳霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta rugiscutis* (Pocock, 1897) [*rugi-* (wrinkle) + *scutis* (sheild)]^{mo}
- 萨氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta salei* (Vachon, 1980) [John Benjamin Sale]^{ep}
- 索氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta saulcyi* (Simon, 1880) [Félix de Saulcy]^{ep}
- 泳石霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta saxinatans* Lowe, 2010 [*saxin-* (rock) + *-atans* (swim)]^{er}
- 粗糙霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta scaber* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [rough]^{mo}
- 国王霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta schach* (Birula, 1905) [*shah*, king in Farsi]^{ep}
- 锡斯坦霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta sistansensis* Kovařík, Yağmur & Moradi, 2018 [Sistan Province, Iran]^{to}
- 索科特拉霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta socotrensensis* (Pocock, 1889) [Socotra Island, Yemen]^{to}
- 索马里亚霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta somalicus* Kovařík, 2018 [Somalia]^{to}
- 宋氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta songi* (Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005) ★ [Song Daxiang (宋大祥)]^{ep}
- 叟氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta sousai* Turiel, 2014 [Pedro Reis de Sousa]^{ep}
- 斯氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta stockwelli* Kovařík, 2007 [Scott Allen Stockwell]^{ep}
- 锡尔特霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta syrticus* (Borelli, 1914) [nomen dubium] [Gulf of Syrte, Libya]^{to}
- 塔木尔霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta tamulus* (Fabricius, 1798) [archaic form of “Tamil”, Tamil people]^{et}
- 特氏霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta trailini* Kovařík, 2013 [Vladimir Trailin]^{ep}
- 三线霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta trilineatus* (Peters, 1861) [*tri-* (three) + *linea* (line) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 乌干达霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta ugandaensis* Kovařík, 2013 [Uganda]^{to}
- 马拉提霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta vinchu* Mirza, Ambekar & Kulkarni, 2019 [Marathi for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 扎格罗斯霍屯督蝎 *Hottentotta zagrosensis* Kovařík, 1997 [Zagros Mts., Iran]^{to}
- 伊朗杀牛蝎属 Genus *Iranobuthus* Kovařík, 1997 [Iran + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
- 克氏伊朗杀牛蝎 *Iranobuthus krali* Kovařík, 1997 [David Král]^{ep}
- 纤螫蝎属 Genus *Ischnotelson* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017
- [*ischno-* (thin) + *telson*]^{mo}
- 瓜南比纤螫蝎 *Ischnotelson guanambiensis* (Lenarducci, Pinto-da-Rocha & Lucas, 2005) [Guanambi Municipality, Bahia State, Brazil]^{to}
- 佩鲁阿苏纤螫蝎 *Ischnotelson peruassu* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017 [Cavernas do Peruçu National Park, Brazil]^{to}

似等蝎属 Genus *Isometroides* Keyserling, 1885 [*Isometrus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ia}

瘦弱似等蝎 *Isometroides vescus* (Karsch, 1880) [attenuated]^{mo}

等蝎属 Genus *Isometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 [*iso-* (equal) + *metrus* (measurement)]^{mo}

安波利等蝎 *Isometrus amboli* Sulakhe, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020 [Amboli, a village in Maharashtra State, India]^{io}

阿瑟氏等蝎 *Isometrus atherii* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2008 [Ather]^{ep}

华丽等蝎 *Isometrus formosus* Pocock, 1894 [beautiful (*form-* (beauty) + *-osus* (full of, overly))]^{mo}

伊萨德等蝎 *Isometrus isadensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [nomen dubium] [Isad, a village in Maharashtra State, India]^{io}

寇氏等蝎 *Isometrus kovariki* Sulakhe, Dandekar, Mukherjee, Pandey, Ketkar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020 [František Kovařík]^{ep}

里亚卡特氏等蝎 *Isometrus liaqatii* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2008 [Liaqat]^{ep}

斑等蝎 *Isometrus maculatus* (DeGeer, 1778) ☆ [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

塔米尼等蝎 *Isometrus tamhini* Sulakhe, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020 [Tamhini, a village in Maharashtra State, India]^{io}

瑟氏等蝎 *Isometrus thurstoni* Pocock, 1893 [Edgar Thurston]^{ep}

思氏等蝎 *Isometrus thwaitesi* Pocock, 1897 [George Henry Kendrick Thwaites]^{ep}

图皮蝎属 Genus *Jaguajir* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017

[Tupi for “scorpion”]^{au}

统帅图皮蝎 *Jaguajir agamemnon* (C. L. Koch, 1839) [Ἀγαμέμνων (Agamemnon), king of Mycenae, leader of the Greek army in the Trojan War]^{my}

平氏图皮蝎 *Jaguajir pinto* (Mello-Leitão, 1932)

模式亚种 *J. pinto pinto* (Mello-Leitão, 1932) [Cezar Pinto]^{ep}

库鲁亚种 *J. pinto kourouensis* (Lourenço, 2008) [Kourou Commune, French Guiana]^{io}

柔氏图皮蝎 *Jaguajir rochae* (Borelli, 1910) [Francisco Diaz da Rocha]^{ep}

雅氏信使蝎属 Genus *Janalychas* Kovařík, 2019 [Jana Štundlová *Lychas*]^{ep&ta}

白掌雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas albimanus* (Henderson, 1919) [*albi-* (white) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}

珐氏雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas farkasi* (Kovařík, 1997) [Balázs Farkas]^{ep}

具疣雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas granulatus* Mirza, 2020 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

艾氏雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas heurtaultae* (Kovařík, 1997) [Jacqueline Heurtault]^{ep}

喀拉拉雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas keralaensis* Mirza, 2020 [Kerala State, India]^{io}

滑额雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas laevifrons* (Pocock, 1897) [*laevi-* (smooth) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}

邵氏雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas shoplanti* (Oates, 1888) [Edwin Rew Shopland]^{ep}

斯里兰卡雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas srilankensis* (Lourenço, 1997) [Sri Lanka]^{io}

三棱雅氏信使蝎 *Janalychas tricarinatus* (Simon, 1884) [*tri-* (three) + *carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

卡拉斯山蝎属 Genus *Karasbergia* Hewitt, 1913 [Karasberg Hill, Northern Cape, South Africa]^{io}

麦氏卡拉斯山蝎 *Karasbergia methueni* Hewitt, 1913 [Paul Ayshford Methuen]^{ep}

克氏蝎属 Genus *Kraepelinia* Vachon, 1974 [Karl Kraepelin]^{ep}

壮肢克氏蝎 *Kraepelinia palpator* (Birula, 1903) [*palp-* (here as “pedipalp”) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{mo}

兰氏蝎属 Genus *Lanzatus* Kovařík, 2001 [Benedetto “Bettino” Lanza]^{ep}

胡鲁尔兰氏蝎 *Lanzatus huluul* Kovařík & Lowe, 2021 [Huluul, a village in Somaliland]^{io}

索马里亚兰氏蝎 *Lanzatus somalicus* Kovařík, 2001 [Somalia]^{io}

索马里兰兰氏蝎 *Lanzatus somalilandus* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2016 [Somaliland]^{io}

滑尾蝎属 Genus *Leiurus* Ehrenberg, 1828 [*lei-* (smooth) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}

阿氏滑尾蝎 *Leiurus abdullahbayrami* Yağmur, Koc & Kunt, 2009 [Abdullah Bayram]^{ep}

阿拉伯滑尾蝎 *Leiurus arabicus* Lowe, Yağmur & Kovařík, 2014 [Saudi Arabia]^{io}

黯黑滑尾蝎 *Leiurus ater* Lourenço, 2019 [black]^{chr}

短针滑尾蝎 *Leiurus brachycentrus* (Ehrenberg, 1829) [*brachy-* (short) + *centrus* (here as “aculeus”)]^{mo}

德氏滑尾蝎 *Leiurus dekeyseri* Lourenço, 2020 [Pierre Louis Dekeyser]^{ep}

古班滑尾蝎 *Leiurus gubanensis* Kovařík & Lowe, 2020 [Guban Area, Somaliland]^{io}

韩氏滑尾蝎 *Leiurus haenggii* Lowe, Yağmur & Kovařík, 2014 [Ambros Hänggi]^{ep}

埃氏滑尾蝎 *Leiurus heberti* Lowe, Yağmur & Kovařík, 2014 [Blaine Hébert]^{ep}

希伯来滑尾蝎 *Leiurus hebraeus* (Birula, 1908) [Hebrew]^{et}

霍加尔滑尾蝎 *Leiurus hoggarensis* Lourenço, Kourim & Sadine, 2018 [Hoggar Mts., Algeria]^{io}

科威特滑尾蝎 *Leiurus kuwaiti* Lourenço, 2020 [Kuwait]^{io}

约旦滑尾蝎 *Leiurus jordanensis* Lourenço, Modr & Amr, 2002 [Jordan]^{io}

长栉滑尾蝎 *Leiurus macroctenus* Lowe, Yağmur & Kovařík, 2014 [*marco-* (long) + *-ctenus* (here as “pectine”)]^{mo}

尼日利亚滑尾蝎 *Leiurus nigerianus* Lourenço, 2021 [Nigeria]^{io}

五线滑尾蝎 *Leiurus quinquestriatus* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [*quinque-* (five) + *stri-* (stripe) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

撒哈拉滑尾蝎 *Leiurus saharicus* Lourenço, 2020 [Sahara Desert]^{io}

- 草原滑尾蝎 *Leiurus savanicola* Lourenço, Qi & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2006 [*savani-* (savannah) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 索马里亚滑尾蝎 *Leiurus somalicus* Lourenço, & Rossi, 2016 [Somalia]^{to}
- 光滑杀牛蝎属 Genus *Liobuthus* Birula, 1898 [*lio-* (smooth) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 凯氏光滑杀牛蝎 *Liobuthus kessleri* Birula, 1898 [Karl Fedorovich Kessler]^{ep}
- 润杀牛蝎属 Genus *Lissothus* Vachon, 1948 [*lisso-* (smooth) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 伯氏润杀牛蝎 *Lissothus bernardi* Vachon, 1948 [Francis Bernard]^{ep}
- 尚巴润杀牛蝎 *Lissothus chaambi* Lourenço & Sadine, 2014 [Châamba tribe of North Sahara]^{et}
- 西部润杀牛蝎 *Lissothus occidentalis* Vachon, 1950 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 信使蝎属 Genus *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845 [Λίχας (Lichas), Hercules's servant]^{my}
- 阿氏信使蝎 *Lychas aberlenci* Lourenço, 2013 [Henri-Pierre Aberlenc]^{ep}
- 阿马斯氏信使蝎 *Lychas armasi* Kovařík, 2013 [Luis F. de Armas]^{ep}
- 具链信使蝎 *Lychas armillatus* Gervais, 1841 [*armilla-* (bracelet) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr/mo}
- 粗糙信使蝎 *Lychas asper* (Pocock, 1891) [rough]^{mo}
- 比哈尔信使蝎 *Lychas biharensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Bihar State, India]^{to}
- 步氏信使蝎 *Lychas brehieri* Lourenço, 2017 [Franck Bréhier]^{ep}
- 布氏信使蝎 *Lychas buchari* Kovařík, 1997 [Jan Buchar]^{ep}
- 庄他武里信使蝎 *Lychas chanthaburiensis* Ythier & Lourenço, 2022 [Chanthaburi Province, Thailand]^{to}
- 瑟氏信使蝎 *Lychas cernickai* Kovařík, 2013 [Martin Cernicka]^{ep}
- 黄掌信使蝎 *Lychas flavimanus* (Thorell, 1888) [*flavi-* (yellow) + *manus* (hand)]^{chr&mo}
- 格氏信使蝎 *Lychas gravelyi* Henderson, 1913 [Frederic Henry Gravely]^{ep}
- 亨氏信使蝎 *Lychas hendersoni* (Pocock, 1897) [John Robertson Henderson]^{ep}
- 希氏信使蝎 *Lychas hillyardi* Kovařík, 1997 [Paul D. Hillyard]^{ep}
- 意外信使蝎 *Lychas inexpectatus* Lourenço, 2011 [unexpected]^{ex}
- 卡姆谢特信使蝎 *Lychas kamshetensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Kamshet, a village in Maharashtra State, India]^{to}
- 哈尔帕迪信使蝎 *Lychas kharpadi* Bastawade, 1986 [Kharpada, a village in Maharashtra State, India]^{to}
- 涛岛信使蝎 *Lychas kotao* Lourenço, 2020 [Ko Tao Island, Thailand]^{to}
- 克氏信使蝎 *Lychas krali* Kovařík, 1995 [David Král]^{ep}
- 路氏信使蝎 *Lychas lourencoi* Kovařík, 1997 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
- 石纹信使蝎 *Lychas marmoreus* (C. L. Koch, 1844) [*marmor-* (marble) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
- 约氏信使蝎 *Lychas mjobergi* Kraepelin, 1916 [Eric Georg Mjöberg]^{ep}
- 尖刺信使蝎 *Lychas mucronatus* (Fabricius, 1798) ☆ [*mucron-* (pointed end) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 黑胸信使蝎 *Lychas nigristeris* (Pocock, 1899) [*nigri-* (black) + *sternis* (sternum)]^{chr&mo}
- 欧氏信使蝎 *Lychas obsti* Kraepelin, 1913 [Erich Obst]^{ep}
- 奇异信使蝎 *Lychas perfidus* (Keyserling, 1885) [perfidious]^{mo}
- 菴氏信使蝎 *Lychas rackae* Kovařík, 1997 [Gisela Rack]^{ep}
- 多褶信使蝎 *Lychas rugosus* (Pocock, 1897) [*rug-* (wrinkle) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 桑托信使蝎 *Lychas santoensis* Lourenço, 2009 [Espiritu Santo Island, Vanuatu]^{to}
- 粗糙信使蝎 *Lychas scaber* (Pocock, 1893) [rough]^{mo}
- 纤细信使蝎 *Lychas scutilus* C. L. Koch, 1845 ☆ (extinct in China) [slender]^{mo}
- 锯齿信使蝎 *Lychas serratus* (Pocock, 1891) [*serra-* (sawtooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 赦氏信使蝎 *Lychas shelfordi* (Borelli, 1904) [Robert Walter Campbell Shelford]^{ep}
- 多变信使蝎 *Lychas variatus* (Thorell, 1876)
- 模式亚种 *L. variatus variatus* (Thorell, 1876) [varied, perfect passive participle of *vario* (to vary)]^{mo/chr}
- 冠层亚种 *L. variatus canopensis* Lourenço & Qi, 2007 [refers to the habitat, canopy]^{bi}
- 似信使蝎属 Genus *Lychasioides* Vachon, 1974 [*Lychas* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
- 阿氏似信使蝎 *Lychasioides amieti* Vachon, 1974 [Jean-Louis Amiet]^{ep}
- 毛里塔尼亚杀牛蝎属 Genus *Mauritanobuthus* Qi & Lourenço, 2007 [Mauritania + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
- 詹氏毛里塔尼亚杀牛蝎 *Mauritanobuthus geniezi* Qi & Lourenço, 2007 [Philippe Geniez]^{ep}
- 中杀牛蝎属 Genus *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950 [*meso-* (middle, median) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 阿富汗中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus afghanus* (Pocock, 1889) [Afghanistan]^{to}
- 巴氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus barszczewskii* (Birula, 1904) [Lev Semyonovich Barszczewsky]^{ep}
- 比氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus birulai* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Št'áhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
- 伯格多中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus bogdoensis* (Birula, 1896) [Maloe Bogdo Hill, now in West Kazakhstan Region, Kazakhstan]^{pal}
- 克氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus crucittii* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Št'áhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Pierangelo Crucitti]^{ep}

- 兵士中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus eupeus* (C. L. Koch, 1839) [Ἐπειός (Epeus), a Greek soldier in the Trojan War]^{my}
 法氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus farleyi* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Roger Dean Farley]^{ep}
 佛氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus fomichevi* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Alexander Anatolyevich Fomichev]^{ep}
 伽氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus galinae* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Galina N. Fet]^{ep}
 哈氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus haarlovi* Vachon, 1958 [Niels Lorentz Haarlov]^{ep}
 伊朗中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus iranensis* (Birula, 1917) [Iran]^{to}
 喀氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus kaftani* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Milan Kaftan]^{ep}
 克尔曼中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus kirmanensis* (Birula, 1900) [Kerman Province, Iran]^{to}
 麦氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus macmahoni* (Pocock, 1900) [Henry MacMahon]^{ep}
 马氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus marusiki* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Yuri Mikhailovich Marusik]^{ep}
 美索不达米亚中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus mesopotamicus* (Penther, 1912) [Mesopotamia]^{pal}
 米氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus mirshamsii* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Omid Mirshamsi]^{ep}
 纳氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus navidpourii* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Shahrokh Navidpour]^{ep}
 波斯中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus persicus* (Pocock, 1899) [Persia, now Iran]^{pal}
 斐氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus philippovitschi* (Birula, 1905) [E. M. Filippovich]^{ep}
 菲氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus phillipsii* (Pocock, 1889) [Ethelbert Lort Phillips]^{ep}
 菴氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus rahsenae* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Rahşen S. Kaya]^{ep}
 斗士中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839) ☆ [Θεσπίτης (Thersites), a Greek soldier in the Trojan War]^{my}
 土耳其中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus turcicus* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Turkey]^{to}
 硕螯中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus vesiculatus* (Pocock, 1899) [with developed vesicle]^{mo}
 维氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus vignolii* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Valerio Vignoli]^{ep}
 亚氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus yağmuri* Kovařík & Fet in Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Ersen Aydin Yağmur]^{ep}
 扎氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus zarudnyi* Novruzov, Kovařík & Fet, 2022 [Nikolai Alekseyevich Zarudnyi]^{ep}
 宗氏中杀牛蝎 *Mesobuthus zonsteini* Kovařík, Fet, Gantenbein, Graham, Yağmur, Štáhlavský, Poverennyi & Novruzov, 2022 [Sergei Zonstein]^{ep}
- 中戾蝎属 Genus *Mesotityus* González-Sponga, 1981 [*meso-* (middle, median) + *Tityus*]^{mod&ta}
 丹氏中戾蝎 *Mesotityus vondangeli* González-Sponga, 1981 [Miguel von Dangel]^{ep}
- 微无支蝎属 Genus *Microananteris* Lourenço, 2003 [*micro-* (small) + *Ananteris*]^{mod&ta}
 阿博纳米微无支蝎 *Microananteris abounami* Lourenço & Chevalier, 2022 [Abounami River, French Guiana]^{to}
 米塔拉卡丘微无支蝎 *Microananteris inselberg* Lourenço, 2021 [Mitaraka Inselberg, French Guiana]^{to}
 小型微无支蝎 *Microananteris minor* Lourenço, 2003 [small-sized]^{mo}
 锯齿微无支蝎 *Microananteris serrulata* Lourenço, 2021 [*serr-* (serration) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix) + *-ata* (with)]^{mo}
- 微杀牛蝎属 Genus *Microbuthus* Kraepelin, 1898 [*micro-* (small) + *Buthus*]^{mod&ta}
 法氏微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus fagei* Vachon, 1949 [Louis Fage]^{ep}
 黄褐微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus flavorufus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2007 [*flavo-* (yellow) + *rufus* (rufous)]^{chr}
 伽氏微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus gardneri* Lowe, 2010 [Andrew S. Gardner]^{ep}
 克氏微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus kristensenorum* Lowe, 2010 [Charles and Anita Kristensen]^{ep}
 海岸微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus litoralis* (Pavesi, 1885) [*litor-* (shore) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
 摩洛哥微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus maroccanus* Lourenço, 2002 [Morocco]^{to}
 精灵微杀牛蝎 *Microbuthus satyrus* Lowe, Kovařík, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2018 [satyr, a male nature spirit in Greek mythology]^{my}
- 微戾蝎属 Genus *Microtityus* Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966 [*micro-* (small) + *Tityus*]^{mod&ta}
 安氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus angelaerosae* González-Sponga, 2001 [Angela Rosa Delgado de González]^{ep}
 巴拉奥纳微戾蝎 *Microtityus barahona* Armas & Teruel, 2012 [Barahona Province, Dominican Republic]^{to}
 彼氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus biordi* González-Sponga, 1970 [Luis Enrique Biord]^{ep}
 维氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus bivcentorum* Botero-Trujillo, Erazo-Moreno & Perez, 2009 [José Vicente Rodríguez-Mahecha and José Vicente Rueda-Almonacid]^{ep}

- 波多黎各微戾蝎 *Microtityus borincanus* Teruel, Rivera & Sánchez, 2014 [Borikén, Spanish word for the people native to Puerto Rico]^{aut(ep)}
- 卡帕亚微戾蝎 *Microtityus capayaensis* González-Sponga, 2001 [Capaya, a town in Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 康氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus consuelo* Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1987 [Consuelo de Marcano]^{ep}
- 苏氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus desuzeae* González-Sponga, 2001 [Gina D'Suze]^{ep}
- 疑难微戾蝎 *Microtityus difficilis* Teruel & Armas, 2006 [difficult, problematic]^{ca}
- 多米尼加微戾蝎 *Microtityus dominicanensis* Santiago-Blay, 1985 [Dominican Republic]^{to}
- 尤斯特歇斯微戾蝎 *Microtityus eustatia* Armas, 2018 [Eustatia Island, British Virgin Islands]^{to}
- 法氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus farleyi* Teruel, 2000 [Roger Dean Farley]^{ep}
- 渐黄微戾蝎 *Microtityus flavescens* Teruel, 2001 [*flav-* (yellow) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}
- 弗氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus franckei* Botero-Trujillo & Noriega, 2008 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
- 冯氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus fundorai* Armas, 1974 [Carlos Fundora]^{ep}
- 关塔那摩微戾蝎 *Microtityus Guantanamo* Armas, 1984 [Guantanamo Province, Cuba]^{to}
- 艾氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus iviei* Armas, 1999 [Vaine Wilton Ivie]^{ep}
- 乔氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus jaumei* Armas, 1974 [Miguel Luis Jaime García]^{ep}
- 何氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus joseantonioi* González-Sponga, 1981 [José Antonio González Delgado]^{ep}
- 寇氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus kovariki* Teruel & Infante, 2007 [František Kovařík]^{ep}
- 兰氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus lantiguai* Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1992 [Domingo Lantigua]^{ep}
- 海岸微戾蝎 *Microtityus litoralensis* González-Sponga, 2001 [littoral]^{bi}
- 路氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus lourencoi* Armas & Teruel, 2012 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
- 迷你微戾蝎 *Microtityus minimus* Kovařík & Teruel, 2014 [smallest]^{mo}
- 寡齿微戾蝎 *Microtityus paucidentatus* Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1992 [*pauci-* (few) + *dent-* (tooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 普氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus prendinii* Armas & Teruel, 2012 [Lorenzo Prendini]^{ep}
- 微小微戾蝎 *Microtityus pusillus* Teruel & Kovařík, 2012 [tiny]^{mo}
- 瑞氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus reini* Armas & Teruel, 2012 [Jan Ove Rein]^{ep}
- 里氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus rickyi* Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966 [Ricky Waering]^{ep}
- 珊氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus santosi* Teruel, Rivera & Sánchez, 2014 [Carlos José Santos Flores]^{ep}
- 赛氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus sevciki* González-Sponga, 2001 [Carlos Sevcik]^{ep}
- 索氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus solegladi* Armas & Teruel, 2012 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
- 斯氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus starri* Lourenço & Huber, 1999 [Christopher K. Starr]^{ep}
- 特立尼达微戾蝎 *Microtityus trinitensis* Armas, 1974 [Trinidad, a town in Sancti Spíritus Province, Cuba]^{to}
- 凡氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus vanzolinii* Lorenzo & Eickstedt, 1983 [Paulo Emilio Vanzolini]^{ep}
- 维埃克斯微戾蝎 *Microtityus vieques* Teruel, Rivera & Santos, 2015 [Vieques Island, Puerto Rico]^{to}
- 薇氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus virginiae* Armas, 1999 [Virginia Heinsen de Freitas]^{ep}
- 火山土微戾蝎 *Microtityus vulcanicus* Teruel, 2019 ["volcanic", alludes to the type of soil where this species lives]^{bi}
- 韦氏微戾蝎 *Microtityus waeringi* Francke & Sissom, 1980 [Erik Kjellesvig-Waering]^{ep}
- 亚拉奎微戾蝎 *Microtityus yaracuyan* González-Sponga, 2001 [Yaracuy State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 新杀牛蝎属 Genus *Neobuthus* Hirst, 1911 [*neo-* (new) + *Buthus*]^{ca}**
- 阿穆德新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus amoudensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Amoud University, Somaliland]^{to}
- 阿瓦什新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus awashensis* Kovařík & Lowe, 2012 [Awash, a town in Ethiopia]^{to}
- 柏培拉新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus berberensis* (Hirst, 1911) [Berbera, a city in Somaliland]^{to}
- 克氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus cloudsleythompsoni* Lourenço, 2001 [John Leonard Cloudsley-Thompson]^{ep}
- 埃里加博新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus erigavoensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Erigavo City, Somaliland]^{to}
- 厄立特里亚新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus eritreaensis* Lowe & Kovařík, 2016 [Eritrea]^{to}
- 米氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus factorio* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Factorio, a computer game created by Michal Kovařík, the son of the first author]^{ep}
- 锈色新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus ferrugineus* (Kraepelin, 1898) [*ferrugin-* (rust) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
- 古班新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus gubanensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Guban Area, Somaliland]^{to}
- 亥氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus haeckeli* Kovařík, 2019 [Martin Häckel]^{ep}
- 柯氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus kloppersi* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Johan Kloppers]^{ep}
- 库氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus kutcheri* Lowe & Kovařík, 2016 [Steven R. Kutcher]^{ep}
- 梅德新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus maidensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [Maid, a village in Somaliland]^{to}
- 山地新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus montanus* Kovařík, Lowe, Awale, Elmi & Hurre, 2018 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 索氏新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus solegladi* Kovařík, 2019 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
- 苏丹新杀牛蝎 *Neobuthus sudanensis* Lourenço, 2005 [Sudan]^{to}

新矛蝎属 Genus *Neogrosphus* Lourenço, 1995 # [*neo-* (new) + *Grosphus*]^{ta}

安德拉斐亚巴新矛蝎 *Neogrosphus andrafiabe* Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber 2015 [Andrafiabe Cave, Ankarana Special Reserve, Madagascar]^{to}

布氏新矛蝎 *Neogrosphus blanci* Lourenço, 1996 [Charles Pierre Blanc]^{ep}

格氏新矛蝎 *Neogrosphus griveaudi* (Vachon, 1969) [Paul Griveaud]^{ep}

齿杀牛蝎属 Genus *Odontobuthus* Vachon, 1950 [*odonto-* (tooth) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}

俾路支齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus baluchicus* Barahoei, Prendini, Navidpour, Tahir, Aliabadian, Siahsarvie & Mirshamsi, 2021 [Baluchistan Province, Pakistan]^{to}

双齿齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus bidentatus* (Lourenço & Pezier, 2002) [*bi-* (two) + *dent-* (tooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

短指齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus brevidigitus* Lowe, 2010 [*brevi-* (short) + *digitus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}

恰巴哈尔齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus chabaharensis* Barahoei, Prendini, Navidpour, Tahir, Aliabadian & Siahsarvie, 2021 [Chabahar, a city in Iran]^{to}

多氏齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus doriae* (Thorell, 1876) [Giacomo Doria]^{ep}

克尔曼齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus kermanus* Barahoei, Prendini, Navidpour, Tahir, Aliabadian & Siahsarvie, 2021 [Kerman Province, Iran]^{to}

齿尾齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus odonturus* (Pocock, 1897) [*odont-* (tooth) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}

塔氏齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus tavighiae* Navidpour, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2013 [Mitra Tavighi]^{ep}

提氏齿杀牛蝎 *Odontobuthus tirgari* Mirshamsi, Azghadi, Navidpour, Aliabadian & Kovařík, 2013 [Siavash Tirgari]^{ep}

齿尾蝎属 Genus *Odonturus* Karsch, 1879 [*odont-* (tooth) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}

具齿齿尾蝎 *Odonturus dentatus* Karsch, 1879 [*dent-* (tooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

奥氏蝎属 Genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987 [Guillaume-Antoine Olivier]^{ep}

博乐奥氏蝎 *Olivierus bolensis* (Sun, Zhu & Lourenço, 2010) ★ [Bole, a city in Xinjiang Autonomous Province, China]^{to}

布鲁图斯奥氏蝎 *Olivierus brutus* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Brutus, a famous Czech rock band]^{ep}

高加索奥氏蝎 *Olivierus caucasicus* (Nordmann, 1840) [Caucasian, of the Caucasus Mts.]^{cho}

艾氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus elenae* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Elena Kreuzberg-Mukhina]^{ep}

极端奥氏蝎 *Olivierus extremus* (Werner, 1936) [extreme, outermost]^{cho?}

黯褐奥氏蝎 *Olivierus fuscus* (Birula, 1897) [dark brown]^{chr}

格氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus gorelovi* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Yuri Konstantinovich Gorelov]^{ep}

海南奥氏蝎 *Olivierus hainanensis* (Birula, 1904) ★ [Hainan Province, China]^{to}

中介奥氏蝎 *Olivierus intermedius* (Birula, 1897) [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta}

喀什奥氏蝎 *Olivierus karshius* (Sun & Sun, 2011) ★ [Karshi, a city in Xinjiang Autonomous Province, China]^{to}

卡氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus kaznakovi* (Birula, 1904) [Alexander Nikolaevich Kaznakov]^{ep}

克氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus kreuzbergi* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Alexander Voldemar-Alexandrovich Kreuzberg]^{ep}

长螯奥氏蝎 *Olivierus longichelus* (Sun & Zhu, 2010) ★ [*longi-* (long) + *chelus* (hand, chela)]^{mo}

马氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879) ☆ [von Martens]^{ep}

弥氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus mikhailovi* Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein & Graham, 2021 [Kirill Glebovich Mikhailov]^{ep}

米氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus mischi* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Michael Misch]^{ep}

尼氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus nenilini* (Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein, Kaiser, Stewart & Graham, 2018) [Andrei Borisovich Nenilin]^{ep}

帕提亚奥氏蝎 *Olivierus parthorum* (Pocock, 1889) [Parthia, ancient region of what is now north-eastern Iran]^{pal}

普氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus przewalskii* (Birula, 1897) ☆ [Nikolai Mikhailovich Przewalsky]^{ep}

塔氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus tarabaevi* Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein & Graham, 2021 [Chingis Karimovich Tarabaev]^{ep}

沃氏奥氏蝎 *Olivierus voldemari* Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein & Graham, 2021 [Voldemar-Alexander Emilyevich Kreuzberg]^{ep}

似直钳蝎属 Genus *Orthochiroides* Kovařík, 1998 [*Orthochirus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}

岛屿似直钳蝎 *Orthochiroides insularis* (Pocock, 1889) [*insul-* (island) + *-aris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}

索科特拉似直钳蝎 *Orthochiroides socotrensis* Kovařík, 2004 [Socotra Island, Yemen]^{to}

索马里兰似直钳蝎 *Orthochiroides somalilandus* Kovařík & Lowe, 2022 [Somaliland]^{to}

瓦氏似直钳蝎 *Orthochiroides vachoni* Kovařík, 1998 [Max Vachon]^{ep}

直钳蝎属 Genus *Orthochirus* Karsch, 1891 [*ortho-* (straight) + *chirus* (hand, pincer)]^{mo}

阿法尔直钳蝎 *Orthochirus afar* Kovařík, Lowe & Šťáhlavský, 2016 [Afar, people of Ethiopia, Djibouti and Eritrea]^{et}

阿富汗直钳蝎 *Orthochirus afghanus* Kovařík, 2004 [Afghanistan]^{to}

阿氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus aristidis* (Simon, 1882) [Aristide Letourneux]^{ep}

阿塔耳直钳蝎 *Orthochirus atarensis* Lourenço & Leguin, 2011 [Atar, a town in Mauritania]^{to}

巴氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus bastawadei* Zambre, Mirza, Sanap, Upadhye & Javed, 2011 [Deshbhushan Bastawade]^{ep}

双色直钳蝎 *Orthochirus bicolor* (Pocock, 1897) [two-colored]^{mo}

比氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus birulai* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Alexei Andreevich Bialynitskii-Birula]^{ep}

- 具棱直钳蝎 *Orthochirus carinatus* Navidpour, Kovařík, Soleglad & Fet, 2019 [*carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 克氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus cloudsleythompsoni* Lourenço & Leguin, 2011 [John Leonard Cloudsley-Thompson]^{ep}
- 丹氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus danielleae* (Lourenço & Vachon, 1997) [Danielle Defaye]^{ep}
- 伐氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus farzanpayi* (Vachon & Farzanpay, 1987) [Reza Farzanpay]^{ep}
- 费氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus feti* Kovařík, 2004 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
- 渐黄直钳蝎 *Orthochirus flavescens* (Pocock, 1897) [*flav-* (yellow) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}
- 佛氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus fomichevi* Kovařík, Yağmur, Fet & Hussen, 2019 [Alexander Anatolyevich Fomichev]^{ep}
- 仉氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus formozovi* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Nikolay Aleksandrovich Formozov]^{ep}
- 黯足直钳蝎 *Orthochirus fuscipes* (Pocock, 1900) [*fusci-* (dark brown) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 甘氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus gantenbeini* Kovařík, Yağmur, Fet & Hussen, 2019 [Benjamin Gantenbein]^{ep}
- 秃额直钳蝎 *Orthochirus glabrifrons* (Kraepelin, 1903) [*glabri-* (bald, smooth) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 葛氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus gromovi* Kovařík, 2004 [Alexander Viktorovich Gromov]^{ep}
- 格氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus grosseri* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Walter Grosser]^{ep}
- 戈氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus gruberi* Kovařík & Fet, 2006 [Jürgen Gruber]^{ep}
- 赫拉特直钳蝎 *Orthochirus heratensis* Kovařík, 2004 [Herat Province, Afghanistan]^o
- 霍尔木兹甘直钳蝎 *Orthochirus hormozganensis* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Hormozgan Province, Iran]^o
- 因氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus innesi* Simon, 1910 [Walter Innes Bey]^{ep}
- 伊朗直钳蝎 *Orthochirus iranus* Kovařík, 2004 [Iran]^o
- 伊拉克直钳蝎 *Orthochirus iraqus* Kovařík, 2004 [Iraq]^o
- 贾拉拉巴德直钳蝎 *Orthochirus jalalabadensis* Kovařík, 2004 [Jalalabad, a city in Nangarhar Province, Afghanistan]^o
- 卡氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus kasparki* (Lourenço & Huber, 2000) [Max Kasperek]^{ep}
- 克尔曼直钳蝎 *Orthochirus kermanensis* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Kerman Province, Iran]^o
- 金氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus kinzelbachi* (Lourenço & Huber, 2000) [Ragnar Kinzelbach]^{ep}
- 印神直钳蝎 *Orthochirus krishnai* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Krishna, a Hindu deity]^{de}
- 克氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus kryzhanovskiyi* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Oleg Leonidovich Kryzhanovskiy]^{ep}
- 库氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus kucerai* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Pavel Kučera]^{ep}
- 摩洛哥直钳蝎 *Orthochirus maroccanus* Lourenço & Leguin, 2011 [Morocco]^o
- 马氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus mashipouri* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Behzad Mashipour]^{ep}
- 黑尾直钳蝎 *Orthochirus melanurus* (Kessler, 1874) [*melan-* (black) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 美索不达米亚直钳蝎 *Orthochirus mesopotamicus* Birula, 1918 [Mesopotamia]^{pal}
- 米氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus milloti* Lourenço, 2021 [Jacques Millot]^{ep}
- 小型直钳蝎 *Orthochirus minor* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [small-sized]^{mo}
- 莫氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus monodi* (Lourenço & Vachon, 1997) [Lionel Monod]^{ep}
- 纳氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus navidpouri* Kovařík, Yağmur, Fet & Hussen, 2019 [Shahrokh Navidpour]^{ep}
- 御氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus nordmanni* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Alexander von Nordmann]^{ep}
- 橄榄直钳蝎 *Orthochirus olivaceus* (Karsch, 1881) [*oliv-* (olive) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
- 淡色直钳蝎 *Orthochirus pallidus* (Pocock, 1897) [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
- 波斯直钳蝎 *Orthochirus persa* (Birula, 1900) [Persia (now Iran)]^{pal}
- 萨姆谢尔直钳蝎 *Orthochirus samrchelsis* Kovařík, 2004 [Samrchel, Afghanistan]^o
- 多孔直钳蝎 *Orthochirus scrobiculosus* (Grube, 1873)
- 模式亚种 *O. scrobiculosus scrobiculosus* (Grube, 1873) [*scrobi-* (fossa) + *-ulo* (diminutive suffix) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 内盖夫亚种 *O. scrobiculosus negebensis* (Shulov & Amitai, 1960) [Negev Desert, Israel]^o
- 塞氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus sejnai* Kovařík, Fet & Yağmur, 2020 [Vladimir Šejna]^{ep}
- 塞姆南直钳蝎 *Orthochirus semnanensis* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Semnan Province, Iran]^o
- 埃尔伍德直钳蝎 *Orthochirus soufiensis* Lourenço & Sadine, 2021 [“Souf”, an Arabic name for the region of El-Oued]^{au(to)}
- 斯氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus stockwelli* (Lourenço & Vachon, 1995) [Scott Allen Stockwell]^{ep}
- 塔西里直钳蝎 *Orthochirus tassili* Lourenço & Leguin, 2011 [Tassili n’Ajjer, Algeria]^o
- 提贝斯提直钳蝎 *Orthochirus tibesti* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Tibesti Region, Chad]^o
- 多变直钳蝎 *Orthochirus varius* Kovařík, 2004 [varied]^{mo/chr}
- 维氏直钳蝎 *Orthochirus vignolii* Kovařík & Navidpour, 2020 [Valerio Vignoli]^{ep}
- 扎格罗斯直钳蝎 *Orthochirus zagrosensis* Kovařík, 2004 [Zagros Mts., Iran]^o
- 泛杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pantobuthus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009 [*panto-* (all (the characters)) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 复杂泛杀牛蝎 *Pantobuthus complicatus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009 [complicate]^{mo}
- 副杀牛蝎属 Genus *Parabuthus* Pocock, 1890 [*para-* (close to, near) + *Buthus*]^{ta}
- 阿比西尼亚副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus abyssinicus* (Pocock, 1901) [Abyssinia, now Ethiopia]^{pal}
- 短掌副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus brevimanus* (Thorell, 1876) [*brevi-* (short) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}

- 无毛副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus calvus* Purcell, 1898 [hairless]^{mo}
- 好望角副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus capensis* (Ehrenberg, 1831) [Cape of Good Hope, South Africa]^{to}
- 擎氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus cimrmani* Kovařík, 2004 [Jára Cimrman]^{ep}
- 散鸣副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus distridor* Lamoral, 1980 [*dis-* (separately) + *stridor* (a hissing sound)]^{er}
- 埃里加博副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus erigavoensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Erigavo, a city in Somaliland]^{to}
- 厄立特里亚副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus eritreaensis* Kovařík, 2003 [Eritrea]^{to}
- 秃螯副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus glabrimanus* Prendini & Esposito, 2010 [*glabri-* (bald, smooth) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 纤细副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus gracilis* Lamoral, 1979 [*gracile*]^{mo}
- 疣螯副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus granimanus* Pocock, 1895 [*grani-* (grain) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 具疣副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus granulatus* (Ehrenberg, 1831) [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 哈麦尔副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus hamar* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2016 [Hamar people, Ethiopia]^{er}
- 异尾副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus heterurus* Pocock, 1899 [*heter-* (different) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 亨氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus hunteri* Pocock, 1895 [Archibald Hunter]^{ep}
- 卡氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus kabateki* Kovařík, Lowe, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Petr Kabátek]^{ep}
- 奥罗米亚副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus kajibu* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2016 [Oromia for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 卡拉哈里副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus kalaharicus* Lamoral, 1977 [Kalahari Gemsbock National Park, Namibia]^{to}
- 克氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus kraepelini* Werner, 1902 [Karl Kraepelin]^{ep}
- 宽亚玛副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus kuanyamarum* Monard, 1937 [Kuanyama, language of Namibia and Angola]^{li}
- 滑额副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus laevifrons* (Simon, 1888) [*laevi-* (smooth) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 滑体副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus liosoma* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [*lio-* (smooth) + *soma* (body)]^{mo}
- 极巨副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus maximus* Werner, 1913 [greatest]^{mo}
- 马氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus mazuchi* Kovařík, Lowe, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Tomas Mazuch]^{ep}
- 莫桑比克副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus mossambicensis* (Peters, 1861) [Mozambique]^{to}
- 穆氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus muelleri* Prendini, 2000 [Gerbus J. Müller]^{ep}
- 纳米布副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus namibensis* Lamoral, 1979 [Namib Desert]^{to}
- 侏儒副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus nanus* Lamoral, 1979 [dwarf]^{mo}
- 淡色副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus pallidus* Pocock, 1895 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
- 扁尾副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus planicauda* (Pocock, 1889) [*plani-* (flat) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 铜色副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus raudus* (Simon, 1888) [copper-colored]^{chr}
- 强壮副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus robustus* Kovařík, Lowe, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2019 [strong, robust]^{mo}
- 施氏副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus schlechteri* Purcell, 1899 [Max Schlechter]^{ep}
- 鬃腹副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus setiventer* Prendini & Esposito, 2010 [*seti-* (seta) + *venter* (belly)]^{mo}
- 索马里兰副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus somalilandus* Kovařík, Lowe, Elmi & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Somaliland]^{to}
- 嘶鸣副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus stridulus* Hewitt, 1913 [hissing, emitting a particularly shrill sound]^{er}
- 德兰士瓦副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus transvaalicus* Purcell, 1899 [Transvaal Province, South Africa]^{to}
- 多绒副杀牛蝎 *Parabuthus villosus* (Peters, 1862) [*villo-* (hair) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 栉杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pectinibuthus* Fet in Orlov & Vasilyev, 1984 [pectine + *Buthus*]^{mod&ta}
- 比氏栉杀牛蝎 *Pectinibuthus birulai* Fet in Orlov & Vasilyev, 1984 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
- 膨戮蝎属 Genus *Physoctonus* Mello-Leitão, 1934 [*physo-* (air, inflate) + *-ctonus* (killer)]^{mod&er}
- 亚马孙膨戮蝎 *Physoctonus amazonicus* Lourenço, 2017 [Amazon River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
- 脆弱膨戮蝎 *Physoctonus debilis* (C. L.Koch, 1840) [feeble, weak, disabled]^{mo}
- 线纹膨戮蝎 *Physoctonus striatus* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017 [*stri-* (stripe) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 侏杀牛蝎属 Genus *Picobuthus* Lowe, 2010 [*pico-* (small) + *Buthus*]^{mod&ta}
- 鄧氏侏杀牛蝎 *Picobuthus dundoni* Lowe, 2010 [Jim Dundon]^{ep}
- 沃希拜侏杀牛蝎 *Picobuthus wahibaensis* Lowe, 2010 [Ramlat Al Wahiba, Oman]^{to}
- 邻杀牛蝎属 Genus *Plesiobuthus* Pocock, 1900 [*plesio-* (near) + *Buthus*]^{ta}
- 奇异邻杀牛蝎 *Plesiobuthus paradoxus* Pocock, 1900 [extraordinary (*para-* (beyond) + *doxus* (expectation))]^{mo}
- 珀氏蝎属 Genus *Polisius* Fet, Capes & Sissom, 2001 [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}
- 波斯珀氏蝎 *Polisius persicus* Fet, Capes & Sissom, 2001 [Persia (now Iran)]^{pal}
- 拟润杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pseudolissothus* Lourenço, 2001 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Lissothus*]^{ta}
- 微小拟润杀牛蝎 *Pseudolissothus pusillus* Lourenço, 2001 [tiny]^{mo}
- 拟信使蝎属 Genus *Pseudolychas* Kraepelin, 1911 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Lychas*]^{ta}
- 黄褐拟信使蝎 *Pseudolychas ochraceus* (Hirst, 1911) [*ochra* (yellow ochre) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
- 佩氏拟信使蝎 *Pseudolychas pegleri* (Purcell, 1901) [Alice Pegler]^{ep}
- 德兰士瓦拟信使蝎 *Pseudolychas transvaalicus* Lawrence, 1961 [Transvaal Province, South Africa]^{to}

拟织尾蝎属 Genus *Pseudouroplectes* Lourenço, 1995 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Uroplectes*]^{1a}

- 贝氏拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes betschi* Lourenço, 1995 [Jean-Marie Betsch]^{ep}
 雅氏拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes jacki* Lourenço, 2021 [Jack Wilson de Wilde]^{ep}
 菴氏拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes lalyae* Lourenço & Ythier, 2010 [Laly Ythier]^{ep}
 斑拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes maculatus* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 皮氏拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes pidgeoni* Lourenço & Goodman, 1999 [Mark Pidgeon]^{ep}
 岩峰拟织尾蝎 *Pseudouroplectes tsingy* Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2016 [Antsingy formations, a zone of limestone outcrops, Mahajanga, Madagascar]^{ge}

拉兹蝎属 Genus *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987 [Institute Razi, Hessarak-Karodj, Iran]^{1a}

- 比氏拉兹蝎 *Razianus birulai* Tahir, Navidpour & Prendini, 2014 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
 伐氏拉兹蝎 *Razianus farzanpayi* Tahir, Navidpour & Prendini, 2014 [Reza Farzanpay]^{ep}
 新疆拉兹蝎 *Razianus xinjianganus* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010 ★ [Xinjiang Autonomous Province, China]^{1a}
 扎氏拉兹蝎 *Razianus zarudnyi* (Birula, 1903) [Nikolai Alekseyevich Zarudny]^{ep}

雷氏蝎属 Genus *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972 [R. P. Sreenivasa-Reddy]^{ep}

- 亚雷雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus aareyensis* (Mirza & Sanap, 2010) [Aarey Milk Colony, Maharashtra State, India]^{1a}
 棘尾雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus acanthurus* (Pocock, 1899) [*acanth-* (spine, thorn) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 阿萨姆雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus assamensis* (Oates, 1888) [Assam State, India]^{1a}
 绚丽雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus basilicus* (Karsch, 1879) [royal, magnificent, splendid]^{mo}
 贝氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus besucheti* (Vachon, 1982) [Claude Besuchet]^{ep}
 彼氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus bilyi* (Kovařík, 2003) [Svatopluk Bílý]^{ep}
 短针雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus brachycentrus* (Pocock, 1899) [*brachy-* (short) + *centrus* (here as “aculeus”)]^{mo}
 锡兰雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus ceylonensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Ranawana, Hoferek, Jayarathne, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2016 [Ceylon (now Sri Lanka)]^{pal}

- 科比特雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus corbeti* (Tikader & Batawade, 1983) [Corbett National Park, Uttar Pradesh State, India]^{1a}
 德氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus deharvengi* (Lourenço & Duhem, 2010) [Louis Deharveng]^{ep}
 费氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus feti* (Kovařík, 2013) [Victor Fet]^{ep}
 夫氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus furai* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Vladimír Fura]^{ep}
 亥氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus heimi* (Vachon, 1976) [Roger Heim]^{ep}
 海南雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus hainanensis* (Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005) ★ [Hainan Province, China]^{1a}
 霍氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus hofereki* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 [David Hoferek]^{ep}
 贾氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus jayarathnei* Kovařík, 2016 [V. A. Sanjeewa Jayarathne]^{ep}
 詹氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus jendeki* (Kovařík, 2013) [Eduard Jendek]^{ep}
 朱氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus justii* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Pavel Just]^{ep}
 坎曼雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus khammamensis* (Kovařík, 2003) [Khammam, a city in Andhra Pradesh State, India]^{1a}
 克氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus krasenskyi* (Kovařík, 1998) [Pavel Krásenský]^{ep}
 库氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus kurkai* (Kovařík, 1997) [Antonín Kúrka]^{ep}
 吕氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus loebli* (Vachon, 1982) [Ivan Löbl]^{ep}
 马氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus majkusi* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Roman Majkus]^{ep}
 黑指雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus melanodactylus* (C. L. Koch, 1867) [*melano-* (black) + *dactylus* (finger)]^{moc}
 纳氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus navaiae* (Kovařík, 1998) [Shahin Navai]^{ep}
 内氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus neradi* (Kovařík, 2013) [Ladislav Nerad]^{ep}
 佩氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus petrzelkai* (Kovařík, 2003) [Karel Petrzelka]^{ep}
 疑难雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus problematicus* (Kovařík, 2003) [problematic]^{1a}
 拉氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus ranawanai* Kovařík, 2016 [Kithsiri B. Ranawana]^{ep}
 坚硬雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus rigidulus* (Pocock, 1897) [*rigid-* (stiff, hard) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
 柔氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus rolciki* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Jakub Rolčík]^{ep}
 施氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus schwotti* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 [Petr Schwott]^{ep}
 西藏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus tibetanus* (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008) ★ [Tibet Autonomous Region, China]^{1a}
 条纹雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus vittatus* (Pocock, 1900) [*vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 齐氏雷氏蝎 *Reddyanus zideki* (Kovařík, 1994) [Jiří Zidek]^{ep}

棍尾蝎属 Genus *Rhopalurus* Thorell, 1876 [*rhopal-* (club, stick) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}

- 加勒比棍尾蝎 *Rhopalurus caribensis* Teruel & Roncallo, 2008 [Caribbean]^{1a}
 宽尾棍尾蝎 *Rhopalurus laticauda* Thorell, 1876 [*lati-* (wide) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
 欧氏棍尾蝎 *Rhopalurus ochoai* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017 [José Antonio Ochoa]^{ep}

撒哈拉杀牛蝎属 Genus *Saharobuthus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009 [Sahara Desert + *Buthus*]^{1a&1a}

- 秀丽撒哈拉杀牛蝎 *Saharobuthus elegans* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009 [elegant]^{mo}

- 萨珊蝎属 Genus *Sassanidotus* Farzanpay, 1987 [Sassanid Dynasty of Persia]^{pal}
 纤细萨珊蝎 *Sassanidotus gracilis* (Birula, 1900) [gracile]^{mo}
 扎氏萨珊蝎 *Sassanidotus zarudnyi* (Birula, 1900) [Nikolai Alekseyevich Zarudny]^{ep}
 索马里杀牛蝎属 Genus *Somalibuthus* Kovařík, 1998 [Somalia + *Buthus*]^{to&ta}
 戴氏索马里杀牛蝎 *Somalibuthus demisi* Kovařík, 1998 [René Demis]^{ep}
 萨氏索马里杀牛蝎 *Somalibuthus sabae* Kovařík & Njoroge, 2021 [Saba Douglas-Hamilton]^{ep}
 索迷蝎属 Genus *Somalicharmus* Kovařík, 1998 # [Somalia + *Charmus*]^{to&ta}
 帷氏索迷蝎 *Somalicharmus whitmanae* Kovařík, 1998 [Sarah Whitman]^{ep}
 穴信使蝎属 Genus *Spelaolychas* Kovařík, 2019 [*spelaeo-* (cave) + *Lychas*]^{bi&ta}
 霍氏穴信使蝎 *Spelaolychas hosei* (Pocock, 1891) [Charles Hose]^{ep}
 特氏蝎属 Genus *Teruelius* Lowe & Kovařík, 2019 [Rolando Teruel Ochoa]^{ep}
 安卡拉凡兹卡特氏蝎 *Teruelius ankarafantsika* (Lourenço, 2003) [Ankarafantsika Reserve, Madagascar]^{to}
 安卡瑞纳特氏蝎 *Teruelius ankarana* (Lourenço & Goodman, 2003) [Ankarana Massif, Madagascar]^{to}
 缀环特氏蝎 *Teruelius annulatus* (Fage, 1929) [*annul-* (a rin-shaped structure) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 贝马拉哈特氏蝎 *Teruelius bemaraha* (Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2018) [Bemaraha National Park, Madagascar]^{to}
 双色特氏蝎 *Teruelius bicolor* (Lourenço, 2012) [two-colored]^{mo}
 双线特氏蝎 *Teruelius bistriatus* (Kraepelin, 1900) [*bi-* (two) + *stri-* (stripe) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 艾氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius eliseanneae* (Lourenço & Wilmé, 2016) [Elise-Anne Leguin]^{ep}
 费氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius feti* (Lourenço, 1996) [Victor Fet]^{ep}
 黄黑特氏蝎 *Teruelius flavopiceus* (Kraepelin, 1900) [*flavo-* (yellow) + *pic-* (pitch) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
 甘氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius ganzhorni* (Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2016) [Jörg Ulrich Ganzhorn]^{ep}
 格氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius grandidieri* (Kraepelin, 1900) [Alfred Grandidier]^{ep}
 潮间特氏蝎 *Teruelius intertidalis* (Lourenço, 1999) [Intertidal zone (*inter-* (between) + *tidalis* (pertaining to the tide))] ^{bi}
 缘纹特氏蝎 *Teruelius limbatus* (Pocock, 1889) [*limb-* (edge, border) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 玛氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius magalieae* (Lourenço, 2014) [Magalie Castelin]^{ep}
 马哈法利特氏蝎 *Teruelius mahafaliensis* (Lourenço, Goodman & Ramilijaona, 2004) [Mahafaly Plateau, Madagascar]^{to}
 奥氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius olgae* (Lourenço, 2004) [Olga Ramilijaona]^{ep}
 萨氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius sabineae* (Lourenço & Wilmé, 2016) [Sabine Jourdan]^{ep}
 韦氏特氏蝎 *Teruelius waeberi* (Lourenço & Wilmé, 2016) [Patrick O. Waeber]^{ep}
 泰迷蝎属 Genus *Thaicharmus* Kovařík, 1995 # [Thailand + *Charmus*]^{to&ta}
 古氏泰迷蝎 *Thaicharmus guptai* Mirza, Sanap & Kunte, 2016 [Atul Gupta]^{ep}
 印度泰迷蝎 *Thaicharmus indicus* Kovařík, 2013 [India]^{to}
 洛氏泰迷蝎 *Thaicharmus lowei* Kovařík, Soleglad & Fet, 2007 [Graeme Lowe]^{ep}
 马氏泰迷蝎 *Thaicharmus mahunkai* Kovařík, 1995 [Sándor Mahunka]^{ep}
 戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Tityobuthus* Pocock, 1893 [*Tityus* + *Buthus*]^{ta}
 岩峰戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus antsingy* Lourenço & Goodman, 2004 [Antsingy formations, zone of limestone outcrops, Mahajanga, Madagascar]^{se}
 巴氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus baroni* (Pocock, 1890) [Richard Baron]^{ep}
 贝氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus betschi* Lourenço, Qi & Goodman, 2008 [Jean-Marie Betsch]^{ep}
 切氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus chelbergorum* Lourenço, Qi & Goodman, 2008 [Bruce S. and Joyce E. Chelberg]^{ep}
 达瑞纳戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus darainensis* Lourenço & Goodman, 2002 [Daraina, a town in Madagascar]^{to}
 达氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus dastychi* Lourenço, 1997 [Hieronymus Dastych]^{ep}
 格氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus griswoldi* Lourenço, 2000 [Charles Edward Griswold]^{ep}
 吉氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus guillaumeti* Lourenço, 1995 [Jean-Louis Guillaumet]^{ep}
 伊武希贝戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus ivohibe* Lourenço & Goodman, 1999 [Ivohibe Special Reserve, Madagascar]^{to}
 朱氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus judsoni* Lourenço, 1996 [Mark L. I. Judson]^{ep}
 洛克贝戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus lokobe* Lourenço, Waeber & Wilmé, 2016 [Lokobe Strict Reserve, Nose Be Island, Madagascar]^{to}
 曼氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus manonae* Lourenço, 2000 [Manon Vincelette]^{ep}
 玛氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus mariejeanneae* Lourenço, Waeber & Wilmé, 2018 [Marie Jeanne Raherilalao]^{ep}
 麦氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus mccarteri* Lourenço, Qi & Goodman, 2008 [John W. McCarter Jr.]^{ep}
 莫氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus monodi* Lourenço, 2000 [Lionel Monod]^{ep}
 淡色戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus pallidus* Lourenço, 2004 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
 帕氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus parrilloi* Lourenço, 1996 [Philip Parrillo]^{ep}
 佩氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus petrae* Lourenço, 1996 [Petra Sierwald]^{ep}
 波氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus pococki* Lourenço, 1995 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
 拉氏戾杀牛蝎 *Tityobuthus rakotondravonyi* Lourenço, 2003 [Daniel Rakotondravony]^{ep}

仿戾蝎属 Genus *Tityopsis* Armas, 1974 [*Tityus* + *-opsis* (appearance)]^{1a}

堪氏仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis canizaresorum* Teruel & Rodríguez-Cabrera, 2020 [Caizares brothers (Maikel and Maydiel)]^{ep}

异仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis inaequalis* (Armas, 1974) [*in-* (not) + *aequalis* (equal)]^{mo}

意外仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis inexpectata* (Moreno, 1940) [unexpected]^{ax}

棕褐仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis mulata* Teruel & Rodríguez-Cabrera, 2020 [Spanish for “brown-colored woman”]^{au(chr)}

侏儒仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis pumila* Teruel & Rodríguez-Cabrera, 2020 [dwarf]^{mo}

谢氏仿戾蝎 *Tityopsis sheylae* Teruel & Rodríguez-Cabrera, 2020 [Sheyla Yong]^{ep}

戾蝎属 Genus *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836

[Τῖτυός (Tityos), a giant in Greek mythology, from *tisis* (one who who suffers retribution)]^{my}

和平戾蝎 *Tityus aba* Candido, Lucas, de Souza, Diaz & Lira-da-Silva, 2005 [Afro-Brazilian for “hope of peace”]^{au}

阿布德氏戾蝎 *Tityus abudi* Armas, 1999 [Abraham José Abud Antún]^{ep}

阿卡纳纳戾蝎 *Tityus acananensis* González-Sponga, 2009 [Acanaa, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{1o}

阿迪斯氏戾蝎 *Tityus adisi* Lourenço, 2002 [Joachim Adis]^{ep}

阿德氏戾蝎 *Tityus adrianoi* Lourenço, 2003 [Adriano Monteiro de Castro Pimenta]^{ep}

阿尼科戾蝎 *Tityus ahincoi* González-Sponga, 2001 [AHINCO, “Grupo ecologista de la población de Ejido”, Mérida Municipality, Venezuela]^{1o}

阿里氏戾蝎 *Tityus alejandroi* Teruel, Rivera & Santos, 2015 [Alejandro J. Sánchez]^{ep}

高山戾蝎 *Tityus altithronus* Armas, 1999 [*alti-* (high) + *thronus* (throne, high seat), refers to high altitude]^{bi}

似印皇戾蝎 *Tityus androcottoides* (Karsch, 1879) [*Androcottus*, from a Latin name for Chandragupta Maurya; jun. syn. of *Tityus*] + *-oides* (resembling)]^{1a}

佞氏戾蝎 *Tityus anduzei* González-Sponga, 1997 [Pablo Anduze]^{ep}

安氏戾蝎 *Tityus angelesae* Santiago-Blay, 2009 [Angeles Blay]^{ma}

安妮氏戾蝎 *Tityus anneae* Lourenço, 1997 [Jessie Anne Cloudsley-Thompson]^{ep}

阿诺里戾蝎 *Tityus anori* Lourenço, Rossi & Wilmé, 2019 [Anori Municipality, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{1o}

安蒂奥基亚戾蝎 *Tityus antioquiensis* Lourenço & Otero Patio, 1998 [Antioquia Department, Colombia]^{1o}

阿皮亚卡斯戾蝎 *Tityus apiacas* Lourenço 2002 [Apiácas Municipality, Mato Grosso State, Brazil]^{1o}

阿雷氏戾蝎 *Tityus arellanoparra* González-Sponga, 1985 [Manuel Antonio Arellano Parra]^{ep}

阿根廷戾蝎 *Tityus argentinus* Borelli, 1899 [Argentina]^{1o}

脆弱戾蝎 *Tityus asthenes* Pocock, 1893 [feeble, weak]^{mo}

黑腹戾蝎 *Tityus atriventer* Pocock, 1897 [*atri-* (black) + *venter* (belly)]^{chr&mo}

巴伊亚戾蝎 *Tityus bahiensis* (Perty, 1833)

模式亚种 *T. bahiensis bahiensis* (Perty, 1833) [Bahia State, Brazil]^{1o}

埃氏亚种 *T. bahiensis eickstedtae* Lourenço, 1982 [Vera Regina Dessimoni von Eickstedt]^{ep}

巴基西梅托戾蝎 *Tityus barquisimetanus* González-Sponga, 1994 [Barquisimeto, a city in Venezuela]^{1o}

巴氏戾蝎 *Tityus bastosi* Lourenço, 1984 [Eduardo Kunze Bastos]^{ep}

贝氏戾蝎 *Tityus betschi* Lourenço, 1992 [Jean-Marie Betsch]^{ep}

丽戾蝎 *Tityus bellulus* Armas, 1999 [*bellu-* (pretty) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}

彼氏戾蝎 *Tityus birabeni* Abalos, 1955 [Max Birabén]^{ep}

布氏戾蝎 *Tityus blanci* Lourenço, 1994 [Charles Pierre Blanc]^{ep}

卜氏戾蝎 *Tityus blaseri* Mello-Leitão, 1931 [José Blaser]^{ep}

博科诺戾蝎 *Tityus boconoensis* González-Sponga, 1981 [Bocon, a city in Trujillo State, Venezuela]^{1o}

玻利维亚戾蝎 *Tityus bolivianus* Kraepelin, 1895 [Bolivia]^{1o}

步氏戾蝎 *Tityus brazilae* Lourenço & Eickstedt, 1984 [Tnia Brazil Nunes]^{ep}

蒔氏戾蝎 *Tityus breweri* González-Sponga, 1997 [Charles Brewer Carías]^{ep}

卡其帕戾蝎 *Tityus cachipalensis* González-Sponga, 2002 [Cachipal, a village in Sucre State, Venezuela]^{1o}

凯氏戾蝎 *Tityus caesarbarrioi* González-Sponga, 2001 [César Barrio]^{ep}

冠层戾蝎 *Tityus canopensis* Lourenço & Pezier, 2002 [refers to the ecological niche, canopy]^{bi}

卡拉沃沃戾蝎 *Tityus carabobensis* González-Sponga, 1987 [Carabobo State, Venezuela]^{1o}

似具脊戾蝎 *Tityus carinatoides* Mello-Leitão, 1945 [*Tityus carinatus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{1a}

卡里皮托戾蝎 *Tityus caripitensis* Quiroga, de Sousa & Parrilla-Ivarez, 2000 [Caripito, a city in Monagas State, Venezuela]^{1o}

卡氏戾蝎 *Tityus carolineae* Kovařík, Teruel, Cozijn & Seiter, 2013 [Caroline Pepermans]^{ep}

卡氏戾蝎 *Tityus carrilloi* Ojanguren Affilastro, 2021 [Ramm Carrillo]^{ep}

喀氏戾蝎 *Tityus carvalhoi* Mello-Leitão, 1945 [Antenor Leito de Carvalho]^{ep}

阿苏尔山戾蝎 *Tityus cerroazul* Lourenço, 1986 [Cerro Azul, Panama]^{1o}

尚氏戾蝎 *Tityus championi* Pocock, 1898 [George Charles Champion]^{ep}

查臘拉戾蝎 *Tityus charalaensis* Mello-Leitão, 1940 [nomen nudum] [Charalá, a town in Colombia]^{1o}

- 查氏炭蝎 *Tityus charreyroni* Vellard, 1932 [Jacques Charreyron]^{ep}
- 智利炭蝎 *Tityus chilensis* Lourenço, 2005 [Chile]^{fo}
- 乔科炭蝎 *Tityus choco* Lourenço & Flórez, 2019 [Choco Region, Colombia]^{fo}
- 安第斯炭蝎 *Tityus cisandinus* Lourenço & Ythier, 2017 [*cis-* (on the same side) + *andinus* (Andes Mts.)]^{fo}
- 格纹炭蝎 *Tityus clathratus* C. L. Koch, 1844 [*clathri-* (lattice) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 哥伦比亚炭蝎 *Tityus columbianus* (Thorell, 1876) [Colombia]^{fo}
- 连纹炭蝎 *Tityus confluens* Borelli, 1899
- 模式亚种 *T. confluens confluens* Borelli, 1899 [confluent]^{chr}
- 博多克纳亚种 *T. confluens bodoquena* Lourenço, Cabral & Ramos, 2004 [Serra da Bodoquena National Park, Brazil]^{fo}
- 具肋炭蝎 *Tityus costatus* (Karsch, 1879) [*cost-* (rib) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 粗尾炭蝎 *Tityus crassicauda* Lourenço, 2013 [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 粗螯炭蝎 *Tityus crassimanus* (Thorell, 1876) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 奎氏炭蝎 *Tityus cuellari* Lourenço, 1994 [Orlando Cuellar]^{ep}
- 库莱布拉炭蝎 *Tityus culebrensis* González-Sponga, 1994 [Culebra, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{fo}
- 精灵炭蝎 *Tityus curupi* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Adilardi, Cajade, Ramirez, Ceccarelli & Mola, 2017 [Curupí, a goblin in Guaraní myth]^{my}
- 柱形炭蝎 *Tityus cylindricus* (Karsch, 1879) [cylindrical]^{mo}
- 鬃尾炭蝎 *Tityus dasyurus* Pocock, 1897
- 模式亚种 *T. dasyurus dasyurus* Pocock, 1897 [*dasy* (hair, bristle) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 黄足亚种 *T. dasyurus fulvipes* Mello-Leitão, 1945 [*fulvi-* (yellow) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 长指炭蝎 *Tityus dedoslargos* Francke & Stockwell, 1987 [Spanish for “long fingers”]^{au(mo)}
- 德氏炭蝎 *Tityus demangei* Lourenço, 1981 [Jean-Marie Demange]^{ep}
- 狄氏炭蝎 *Tityus dillerorum* Kovařík, Teruel, Lowe & Friedrich, 2015 [Juliane and Erich Diller]^{ep}
- 迪氏炭蝎 *Tityus dinizi* Lourenço, 1997 [Carlos Diniz]^{ep}
- 异炭蝎 *Tityus discrepans* (Karsch, 1879) [discrepant]^{mo}
- 多氏炭蝎 *Tityus dorae* González-Sponga, 2001 [Dora Padrón de Gracia]^{ep}
- 杜阿卡炭蝎 *Tityus duacaensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [Duaca Settlement, Lara State, Venezuela]^{fo}
- 杜氏炭蝎 *Tityus dulcea* González-Sponga, 2006 [Dulce Alvarez de Alarcón]^{ep}
- 督氏炭蝎 *Tityus dupouyi* González-Sponga, 1987 [Don Walter Dupouy]^{ep}
- 厄瓜多尔炭蝎 *Tityus ecuadorensis* Kraepelin, 1896 [Ecuador]^{fo}
- 艾氏炭蝎 *Tityus elii* (Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1992) [Eli Rafael Martinez]^{ep}
- 伊氏炭蝎 *Tityus elizabethae* Lourenço & Ramos, 2004 [Elizabeth Franklin]^{ep}
- 依氏炭蝎 *Tityus elizabethebravo* González-Sponga & Wall González, 2007 [Elizabeth Bravo]^{ep}
- 恩氏炭蝎 *Tityus engelkei* Pocock, 1902 [Charles Engelke]^{ep}
- 佞氏炭蝎 *Tityus estherae* Santiago-Blay, 2009 [Esther Arroyo]^{ep}
- 埃氏炭蝎 *Tityus evandroi* Mello-Leitão, 1945 [Evandro Chagas]^{ep}
- 束带炭蝎 *Tityus fasciolatus* Pessôa, 1935 [*fasci-* (band) + *-ola* (diminutive suffix) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 菲氏炭蝎 *Tityus festae* Borelli, 1899 [Enrico Festa]^{ep}
- 凤梨炭蝎 *Tityus filodendron* González-Sponga, 1981 [living in filodendrons (bromeliads), *filo-* (love) + *dendron* (tree)]^{bi}
- 孚氏炭蝎 *Tityus footei* Chamberlin, 1916 [H. W. Foote]^{ep}
- 小爪炭蝎 *Tityus forcipula* (Gervais, 1843) [*forcip-* (claw) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
- 富氏炭蝎 *Tityus fuhrmanni* Kraepelin, 1914 [Otto Fuhrmann]^{ep}
- 致命炭蝎 *Tityus funestus* Hirst, 1911 [deadly, lethal]^{cha}
- 伽氏炭蝎 *Tityus gaffini* Lourenço, 2000 [Douglas D. Gaffin]^{ep}
- 咖氏炭蝎 *Tityus gasci* Lourenço, 1982 [Jean-Pierre Gasc]^{ep}
- 悉氏炭蝎 *Tityus generaltheophilo* Lourenço, 2017 [General Guilherme Cals Theophilo Gaspar de Oliveira]^{ep}
- 冈氏炭蝎 *Tityus gonzalespongai* Quiroga, de Sousa, Parrilla-Álvarez & Manzanilla, 2004 [Manuel Angel González-Sponga]^{ep}
- 葛氏炭蝎 *Tityus grahami* Lourenço, 2012 [Matthew R. Graham]^{ep}
- 伊登洞炭蝎 *Tityus grottoedensis* Botero-Trujillo & Flórez, 2014 [*grotto* for “cave” and El Edén Cave, Colombia]^{au&to}
- 瓜尼炭蝎 *Tityus guane* Moreno-González, González & Flórez, 2019 [the Guane people, a Pre-Columbian native tribe]^{et}
- 瓜里科炭蝎 *Tityus guariconesis* González-Sponga, 2004 [Guárico State, Venezuela]^{fo}
- 海地炭蝎 *Tityus haetianus* Teruel & Santos, 2018 [Haiti]^{fo}
- 霍氏炭蝎 *Tityus horacioi* Lourenço & Leguin, 2011 [Horacio Raúl Pérez-García]^{ep}
- 医研所炭蝎 *Tityus imei* Borges, de Sousa & Manzanilla, 2006 [Instituto de Medicina Experimental, Venezuela]^{fo}
- 未定炭蝎 *Tityus indecisus* Mello-Leitão, 1934 [undecided]^{fa}
- 独特炭蝎 *Tityus insignis* (Pocock, 1889) [remarkable, distinguished]^{mo}
- 中介炭蝎 *Tityus intermedius* Borelli, 1899 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{fa}

- 伊莎贝尔氏戾蝎 *Tityus isabelceciliae* González-Sponga, D'Suze & Sevcik, 2001 [Isabel Cecilia Itriago Viso]^{ne}
- 伊凡氏戾蝎 *Tityus ivani* González-Sponga, 2008 [Ivan Daniel Alarcón]^{ep}
- 委内瑞拉科研所戾蝎 *Tityus ivicnancor* González-Sponga, 1997 [Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas + *nancor* (found)]^{to}
- 亥氏戾蝎 *Tityus jaimiei* Miranda, Bermudez, Flórez & Armas, 2020 [Jaime González Medina]^{ep}
- 简氏戾蝎 *Tityus jeanvillardii* Lourenço, 2001 [Jean Albert Vellard]^{ep}
- 琥氏戾蝎 *Tityus julianae* Lourenço, 2005 [Juliana de Souza Araújo]^{ep}
- 胡氏戾蝎 *Tityus juliorum* Santiago-Blay, 2009 [Julio Santiago-Ortega]^{ep}
- 茹氏戾蝎 *Tityus jussarae* Lourenço, 1988 [Jussara Lourenço]^{ep}
- 柯氏戾蝎 *Tityus kaderkai* Kovařík, 2005 [Radan Kaderka]^{ep}
- 什氏戾蝎 *Tityus kalettai* González-Sponga, 2007 [Polaco Francisco Kaletta]^{ep}
- 卡拉哈戾蝎 *Tityus karaja* Lourenço, 2016 [Karajá people of Brazilian Amazon]^{et}
- 金氏戾蝎 *Tityus kindli* Kovařík & Teruel, 2014 [Pavel Kindl]^{ep}
- 恩迪乌卡戾蝎 *Tityus kukututee* Ythier, Chevalier & Gangadin, 2020 [Ndyuka language for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 库氏戾蝎 *Tityus kuryi* Lourenço, 1997 [Adriano Brilhante Kury]^{ep}
- 兰氏戾蝎 *Tityus lancinii* González-Sponga, 1972 [Abden Lancini]^{ep}
- 芦氏戾蝎 *Tityus lokiae* Lourenço, Adis & Araujo, 2005 [Hannelore “Loki” Schmidt]^{ep}
- 长趾戾蝎 *Tityus longidigitus* González-Sponga, 2008 [*longi-* (long) + *digitus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}
- 路氏戾蝎 *Tityus lourencoi* Flórez, 1996 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
- 卢氏戾蝎 *Tityus lutzi* Giltay, 1928 [Adolfo Lutz]^{ep}
- 长螯戾蝎 *Tityus macrochirus* Pocock, 1897 [*macro-* (long) + *chirus* (hand, pincer)]^{mo}
- 硕螯戾蝎 *Tityus magnimanus* Pocock, 1897 [*magni-* (large) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 迈米尔戾蝎 *Tityus maimirensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [Maimire, Yaracuy State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 马纳戾蝎 *Tityus mana* Lourenço, 2012 [Mana Commune, French Guiana]^{to}
- 马纳卡戾蝎 *Tityus manakai* González-Sponga, 2004 [Campamento Manaka, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 马尼亚普尔戾蝎 *Tityus maniapurensis* González-Sponga, 2009 [Maniapure River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 马拉若戾蝎 *Tityus marajoensis* Lourenço & da Silva, 2007 [Marajó Island, Pará State, Brazil]^{to}
- 马拉尼昂戾蝎 *Tityus maranhensis* Lourenço, de Jesus Junior & Limeira-de-Oliveira, 2006 [Maranhão State, Brazil]^{to}
- 马赫沙氏戾蝎 *Tityus marechali* Lourenço, 2013 [Patrick Maréchal]^{ep}
- 马汀氏戾蝎 *Tityus martinpaechi* Lourenço, 2001 [Martin Paech]^{ep}
- 马氏戾蝎 *Tityus matthieseni* Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 2000 [Fabio Aranha Matthiesen]^{ep}
- 马图格卢苏戾蝎 *Tityus mattogrossensis* Borelli, 1901 [Matto Grosso State, Brazil]^{to}
- 马图林戾蝎 *Tityus maturinensis* González-Sponga, 2008 [San Antonio de Maturín, Monagas State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 黑斑戾蝎 *Tityus melanostictus* Pocock, 1893 [*melano-* (black) + *stictus* (spotted, tattooed)]^{chr}
- 梅氏戾蝎 *Tityus melici* Lourenço, 2003 [Antonio Melic]^{ep}
- 怖戾蝎 *Tityus metuendus* Pocock, 1897 [to be feared, future passive participle of *metuo* (fear)]^{cha}
- 米氏戾蝎 *Tityus michelii* Armas, 1982 [Julio Micheli]^{ep}
- 微螯戾蝎 *Tityus microcystis* Lutz & Mello, 1922 [*micro-* (small) + *cystis* (here as “vesicle, telson”)]^{mo}
- 莫纳加斯戾蝎 *Tityus monaguensis* González-Sponga, 1974 [Monagas State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 蒙氏戾蝎 *Tityus mongei* Lourenço, 1996 [Julian Monge-Najera]^{ep}
- 穆库孙戾蝎 *Tityus mucusunamensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Mucusún, Mérida Municipality, Venezuela]^{to}
- 穆氏戾蝎 *Tityus munozii* Lourenço, 1997 [Arturo Muñoz-Cuevas]^{ep}
- 内布利纳戾蝎 *Tityus neblina* Lourenço, 2008 [Pico da Neblina National Park, Brazil-Venezuela]^{to}
- 漠视戾蝎 *Tityus neglectus* Mello-Leitão, 1932 [neglected]^{ax}
- 内巴戾蝎 *Tityus neibae* Armas, 1999 [Neyba Mts., Dominican Republic]^{to}
- 尼氏戾蝎 *Tityus nelsoni* Lourenço 2005 [Nelson F. Fé]^{ep}
- 细螯戾蝎 *Tityus nematochirus* Mello-Leitão, 1940 [*nemato-* (thread) + *chirus* (hand, pincer)]^{mo}
- 新埃斯帕塔戾蝎 *Tityus neoespartanus* González-Sponga, 1996 [Nueva Esparta State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 东北戾蝎 *Tityus nororientalis* González-Sponga, 1996 [type locality in northeastern Venezuela]^{cho}
- 奥比斯波戾蝎 *Tityus obispoii* González-Sponga, 2006 [Agua de Obispo, Trujillo State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 黯色戾蝎 *Tityus obscurus* (Gervais, 1843) [dark]^{chr}
- 钝戾蝎 *Tityus obtusus* (Karsch, 1879) [blunt, obtuse]^{mo?er?}
- 豹斑戾蝎 *Tityus ocelote* Francke & Stockwell, 1987 [Spanish for “ocelot”, *Felis pardalis*]^{au(chr)}
- 奥斯马戾蝎 *Tityus osmanus* González-Sponga, 1996 [Osma River, Federal District, Venezuela]^{to}
- 奥特罗氏戾蝎 *Tityus oteroi* Lourenço, 1998 [Rafael Otero Patiño]^{ep}
- 欧氏戾蝎 *Tityus ottenwalderi* Armas, 1999 [José A. Ottenwalder]^{ep}

- 厚尾戾蝎 *Tityus pachyurus* Pocock, 1897 [*pachy-* (thick, large) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 庞潘戾蝎 *Tityus pampanensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [Pampán Municipality, Trujillo State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 潘古纳戾蝎 *Tityus panguana* Kovařík, Teruel, Lowe & Friedrich, 2015 [Panguana Biological Research Station, Peru]^{to}
- 巴拉圭戾蝎 *Tityus paraguayensis* Kraepelin, 1895 [Paraguay]^{to}
- 侏儒戾蝎 *Tityus parvulus* Kraepelin, 1914 [*parv-* (dwarf, small) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
- 圣保罗戾蝎 *Tityus paulistorum* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [São Paulo State, Brazil]^{to}
- 佩里哈戾蝎 *Tityus perijanensis* González-Sponga, 1994 [Sierra de Perijá National Park, Colombia]^{to}
- 着色戾蝎 *Tityus pictus* Pocock, 1893 [colored, colorful]^{mo}
- 平氏戾蝎 *Tityus pintodarochai* Lourenço, 2005 [Ricardo Pinto da Rocha]^{ep}
- 皮氏戾蝎 *Tityus pittieri* González-Sponga, 1981 [Henri Pittier]^{ep}
- 波氏戾蝎 *Tityus pococki* Hirst, 1907 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
- 银港省戾蝎 *Tityus portoplatensis* Armas & Marcano Fondeur, 1992 [Puerto Plata Province, Dominican Republic]^{to}
- 河戾蝎 *Tityus potameis* Lourenço & Leão Giupponi, 2004 [river (*potamos*)]^{bi}
- 浦氏戾蝎 *Tityus prancei* Lourenço, 2000 [Ghillelan Tolmie Prance]^{ep}
- 朴氏戾蝎 *Tityus proseni* Abalos, 1954 [Alberto F. Prosen]^{ep}
- 拳击手戾蝎 *Tityus pugilator* Pocock, 1898 [*pugil-* (boxer) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
- 微小戾蝎 *Tityus pusillus* Pocock, 1893 [tiny]^{mo}
- 基里基雷戾蝎 *Tityus quiriquirensis* González-Sponga, 2008 [Quiriquire, Punceres Municipality, Monagas State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 基氏戾蝎 *Tityus quirogae* De Sousa et al., 2006 [Mercedes Quiroga]^{ep}
- 基斯克亚戾蝎 *Tityus quisqueyanus* (Armas, 1982) [Quisqueya, the native name for Hispaniola Island]^{au(to)}
- 拉米雷兹氏戾蝎 *Tityus ramirezi* Esquivel de Verde, 1969 [nomen dubium] [Martin Ramirez]^{ep}
- 菴氏戾蝎 *Tityus raquelae* Lourenço, 1988 [Raquel Sampaio]^{ep}
- 何氏戾蝎 *Tityus rebieri* Lourenço, 1997 [Jacques Rebière]^{ep}
- 考拉河戾蝎 *Tityus riocaurensis* González-Sponga, 1996 [Caura River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 内格罗河戾蝎 *Tityus rionegrensis* Lourenço, 2006 [Negro River, Brazil]^{to}
- 里氏戾蝎 *Tityus riverai* Teruel & Sánchez, 2009 [Mel José Rivera]^{ep}
- 珞氏戾蝎 *Tityus roigi* Maury & Lourenço, 1987 [Arturo Roig Alsina]^{ep}
- 罗氏戾蝎 *Tityus rojasi* González-Sponga, 1996 [Pastor Rojas]^{ep}
- 萝氏戾蝎 *Tityus romeroi* González-Sponga, 2008 [Manuel E. Romero]^{ep}
- 荣氏戾蝎 *Tityus rondonorum* Rojas-Runjaic & Armas, 2007 [the Rondón family]^{ep}
- 柔氏戾蝎 *Tityus rosenbergi* Pocock, 1898 [Rosenberg]^{ep}
- 赤褐戾蝎 *Tityus rufofuscus* Pocock, 1897 [*rufo-* (rufous) + *fuscus* (dark brown)]^{chr}
- 石栖戾蝎 *Tityus rupestre* Lourenço, 2019 [*rupe-* (rock) + *-stre* (pertaining to), Campo Rupestres biotype]^{bi}
- 多褶戾蝎 *Tityus rugosus* Schenkel, 1932 [*rug-* (wrinkle) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 露氏戾蝎 *Tityus rasmelyae* González-Sponga, D'Suze & Sevcik, 2001 [Rasmely López]^{ep}
- 萨氏戾蝎 *Tityus sabinae* Lourenço, 1994 [Sabine Jourdan]^{ep}
- 萨纳雷戾蝎 *Tityus sanarensis* González-Sponga, 1997 [Sanare, a city in Lara State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 圣费尔南多戾蝎 *Tityus sanfernandoi* González-Sponga, 2008 [San Fernando, a city in Sucre State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 萨里萨里尼亚马戾蝎 *Tityus sarisarinamensis* González-Sponga, 2002 [Tepui Sarisariñama, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 掌氏戾蝎 *Tityus sastrei* Lourenço & Flórez, 1990 [Claude Sastre]^{ep}
- 施氏戾蝎 *Tityus schrammi* Teruel & Santos, 2018 [Frederic Schramm]^{ep}
- 锯齿戾蝎 *Tityus serrulatus* Lutz & Mello, 1922 [*serr-* (serration) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 奥里诺科戾蝎 *Tityus shiriana* González-Sponga, 1991 [Makiritare name for Indians living along High Orinoco River, Venezuela]^{et}
- 林戾蝎 *Tityus silvestris* Pocock, 1897 [*silv-* (forest) + *-estris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 塞氏戾蝎 *Tityus simonsi* Pocock, 1900 [Perry Oveitt Simons]^{ep}
- 斯氏戾蝎 *Tityus smithii* Pocock, 1893 [Herbert Huntingdon Smith]^{ep}
- 索拉塔戾蝎 *Tityus soratensis* Kraepelin, 1912 [Sorata, Bolivia]^{to}
- 穴戾蝎 *Tityus spelaeus* Moreno-Gonzalez, Pinto-da-Rocha & Gallão, 2021 [*spelaeus* (pertaining to cave)]^{bi}
- 棘刺戾蝎 *Tityus spinatus* Pocock, 1898 [*spin-* (spine) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 斑尾戾蝎 *Tityus stigmurus* (Thorell, 1876) [*stigm-* (spot) + *urus* (tail)]^{chr&mo}
- 思氏戾蝎 *Tityus strandi* Werner, 1939 [Embrik Strand]^{ep}
- 南梅里达戾蝎 *Tityus surimeridensis* González-Sponga, 2002 [*sur-* (South) + Mérida Municipality, Venezuela]^{to}
- 东南戾蝎 *Tityus surorientalis* González-Sponga, 1996 [Type locality (Paso Nuevo) in southeastern Venezuela]^{cho}
- 茜氏戾蝎 *Tityus sylviae* Lourenço, 2005 [Sylvia Marlene Lucas]^{ep}
- 塔氏戾蝎 *Tityus tamayoi* González-Sponga, 1987 [Francisco Tamayo]^{ep}
- 泰罗纳戾蝎 *Tityus tayrona* Lourenço, 1991 [Tayrona National Park, Colombia]^{to}

- 细尾戾蝎 *Tityus tenuicauda* Prendini, 2001 [*tenui-* (slender) + *cauda* (tail)]
- 惧戾蝎 *Tityus timendus* Pocock, 1898 [to be feared, future passive participle of *timeo* (fear)]^{cha}
- 特立尼达戾蝎 *Tityus trinitatis* Pocock, 1897 [Trinidad Island]^{to}
- 三线戾蝎 *Tityus trivittatus* Kraepelin, 1898 [*tri-* (three) + *vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 图库鲁伊戾蝎 *Tityus tucurui* Lourenço, 1988 [Tucuruí Municipality, Pará State, Brazil]^{to}
- 简朴戾蝎 *Tityus uniformis* Mello-Leitão, 1931 [*uni-* (single) + *formis* (form)]^{mo}
- 黑戾蝎 *Tityus unus* Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 2000 [Tupi indian for “black”]^{au(chr)}
- 尤基雷戾蝎 *Tityus uquirensis* González-Sponga, 2001 [Uquire, a hamlet in Sucre State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 乌拉奇切戾蝎 *Tityus urachichensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [Urachiche Municipality, Yaracuy State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 乌氏戾蝎 *Tityus urbinai* Scorza, 1952 [Mario Urbina]^{ep}
- 乌拉圭戾蝎 *Tityus uruguayensis* Borelli, 1901 [Uruguay]^{to}
- 崑氏戾蝎 *Tityus vaissadei* Lourenço, 2002 [Alain Vaissade]^{ep}
- 巴莱拉戾蝎 *Tityus valerae* Scorza, 1954 [Valera, a city in Trujillo State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 本纳莫戾蝎 *Tityus venamensis* González-Sponga, 1981 [Venamo Mts., Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 本图阿里戾蝎 *Tityus ventuarensis* González-Sponga, 2009 [Ventuari River, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 耶氏戾蝎 *Tityus wachteli* Kovařík, Teruel, Lowe & Friedrich, 2015 [Franz Wachtel]^{ep}
- 沃氏戾蝎 *Tityus walli* González-Sponga & Wall González, 2007 [Victor Wall]^{ep}
- 耶氏戾蝎 *Tityus yerenai* González-Sponga, 2009 [Edgard Yerena]^{ep}
- 苏利亚戾蝎 *Tityus zulianus* González-Sponga, 1981 [Zulia State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 穴棍尾蝎属 Genus *Troglohopalurus* Lourenço, Baptista & Giupponi, 2004 [*troglo-* (cave) + *Rhopalurus*]^{bi&ta}
- 通透穴棍尾蝎 *Troglohopalurus translucidus* Lourenço, Baptista & Giupponi, 2004 [*trans-* (through) + *luci-* (light) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
- 葡语穴棍尾蝎 *Troglohopalurus lacrau* (Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 1997) [Portuguese for “scorpion” used in the past in Brazil]^{au}
- 穴戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Troglotityobuthus* Lourenço, 2000 [*troglo-* (cave) + *Tityobuthus*]^{bi&ta}
- 纤细穴戾杀牛蝎 *Troglotityobuthus gracilis* (Fage, 1946) [*gracile*]^{mo}
- 穴螫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Trypanothacus* Lowe, Kovařík, Stockmann & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [*trypano-* (to drill) + *Buthacus*]^{er&ta}
- 阿兹拉克穴螫杀牛蝎 *Trypanothacus azraqensis* Al-Sarairh, Afifeh, Aloufi, Amr & Lourenço, 2021 [Azraq, a town in Zarqa Governorate, Jordan]^{to}
- 巴氏穴螫杀牛蝎 *Trypanothacus barnesi* Lowe, Kovařík, Stockmann & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [J. Neil Barnes]^{ep}
- 布氏穴螫杀牛蝎 *Trypanothacus buettikeri* (Hendrixson, 2006) [Willi Büttiker]^{ep}
- 织尾蝎属 Genus *Uroplectes* Peters, 1861 [*uro-* (tail) + *plectes* (braided, twisted)]^{mo}
- 安氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes ansiedippenaarae* Prendini, 2015 [Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman]^{ep}
- 具棱织尾蝎 *Uroplectes carinatus* (Pocock, 1890)
- 模式亚种 *U. carinatus carinatus* (Pocock, 1890) [*carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 南方亚种 *U. carinatus australis* Hewitt, 1918 [southern (*auster* (south) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 丘氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes chubbi* Hirst, 1911 [Charles Chubb]^{ep}
- 艾氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes emiliae* (Werner, 1916) [Emilie Messinger]^{ep}
- 勐氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes ischeri* (Karsch, 1879) [Fischer]^{ep}
- 黄绿织尾蝎 *Uroplectes lavoviridis* Peters, 1861 [*lavo-* (yellow) + *viridis* (green)]^{chr}
- 华丽织尾蝎 *Uroplectes formosus* Pocock, 1890
- 模式亚种 *U. formosus formosus* Pocock, 1890 [beautiful (*form-* (beauty) + *-osus* (full of, overly))]^{mo}
- 巴苏陀兰亚种 *U. formosus basuticus* Hewitt, 1927 [Basutoland (now Lesotho)]^{pal}
- 斑足亚种 *U. formosus maculipes* Hewitt, 1918 [*maculi-* (spot, stain) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 斯氏亚种 *U. formosus spenceri* Pocock, 1896 [H. A. Spencer]^{ep}
- 纤细织尾蝎 *Uroplectes gracilior* Hewitt, 1914 [*graciler* (comparative of *gracilis*)]^{mo}
- 独特织尾蝎 *Uroplectes insignis* Pocock, 1890 [remarkable, distinguished]^{mo}
- 加丹加织尾蝎 *Uroplectes katangensis* Prendini, 2015 [Katanga Province, Republic of Congo]^{to}
- 线纹织尾蝎 *Uroplectes lineatus* (C. L. Koch, 1844) [*linea* (line) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 长掌织尾蝎 *Uroplectes longimanus* Werner, 1936 [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 玛氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes machadoi* Lourenço, 2000 [Antóni de Barros Machado]^{ep}
- 马拉维织尾蝎 *Uroplectes malawicus* Prendini, 2015 [Malawi Lake, Africa]^{to}
- 马氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes marlothi* Purcell, 1901 [Rudolph Marloth]^{ep}
- 恩加拉织尾蝎 *Uroplectes ngangelarum* Monard, 1930 [Ngangela, people of Angola]^{et}
- 西部织尾蝎 *Uroplectes occidentalis* Simon, 1876
- 模式亚种 *U. occidentalis occidentalis* Simon, 1876 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}

- 莫氏亚种 *U. occidentalis monardi* Vachon, 1950 [Alfred Monard]^{ep}
- 橄绿织尾蝎 *Uroplectes olivaceus* Pocock, 1896 [*oliv-* (olive) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
- 奥吉斌织尾蝎 *Uroplectes otjimbinguensis* (Karsch, 1879)
- 模式亚种 *U. otjimbinguensis otjimbinguensis* (Karsch, 1879) [Otjimbingue, a settlement in Erongo Region, Namibia]^{to}
- 马萨卡亚种 *U. otjimbinguensis massacarum* Monard, 1937 [Massaca, Angola]^{to}
- 豹纹织尾蝎 *Uroplectes pardalis* Werner, 1913 [*pard-* (leopard) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{chr}
- 帕氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes pardii* Kovařík, 2003 [Leo Pardi]^{ep}
- 着色织尾蝎 *Uroplectes pictus* Werner, 1913 [colored, colorful]^{mo}
- 多毛织尾蝎 *Uroplectes pilosus* (Thorell, 1876) [*pil-* (hair) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 平掌织尾蝎 *Uroplectes planimanus* (Karsch, 1879)
- 模式亚种 *U. planimanus planimanus* (Karsch, 1879) [*plani-* (flat) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 宽亚玛亚种 *U. planimanus kuanyamarus* Monard, 1937 [Kuanyama, language of Namibia and Angola]^{li}
- 施氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes schlechteri* Purcell, 1901 [Max Schlechter]^{ep}
- 舒氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes schubotzi* Kraepelin, 1929 [Johann G. Hermann Schubotz]^{ep}
- 锡氏织尾蝎 *Uroplectes silvestrii* Borelli, 1913 [Filippo Silvestri]^{ep}
- 细足织尾蝎 *Uroplectes teretipes* Lawrence, 1966 [*teret-* (slim) + *-ips* (foot)]^{mo}
- 三角织尾蝎 *Uroplectes triangulifer* (Thorell, 1876) [*tri-* (three) + *angul-* (angle) + *-ifer* (bearing)]^{mo/chr}
- 突掌织尾蝎 *Uroplectes tumidimanus* Lamoral, 1979 [*tumidi-* (swollen) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 杂色织尾蝎 *Uroplectes variegatus* (C. L. Koch, 1844) [variegated, perfect passive participle of *variego* (variegate)]^{chr}
- 条纹织尾蝎 *Uroplectes vittatus* (Thorell, 1876) [*vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 黄纹织尾蝎 *Uroplectes xanthogrammus* Pocock, 1897 [*xantho-* (yellow) + *grammus* (line)]^{chr}
- 赞比西织尾蝎 *Uroplectes zambezicus* Prendini, 2015 [Zambezi River Valley, Africa]^{to}
- 小瓦氏蝎属 Genus *Vachoniolus* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [Max Vachon + *-olus* (diminutive suffix)]^{ep&mo}
- 巴提纳小瓦氏蝎 *Vachoniolus batinahensis* Lowe, 2010 [Al Batinah Plain, Oman]^{to}
- 伽氏小瓦氏蝎 *Vachoniolus gallagheri* Lowe, 2010 [Michael D. Gallagher]^{ep}
- 球螯小瓦氏蝎 *Vachoniolus globimanus* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973 [*globi-* (globe) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 伊朗小瓦氏蝎 *Vachoniolus iranus* Navidpour, Kovařík, Soleglad & Fet, 2008 [Iran]^{to}
- 瓦氏蝎属 Genus *Vachonus* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Max Vachon]^{ep}
- 阿西亚氏瓦氏蝎 *Vachonus asiyaee* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009 [nomen dubium] [Asiyyaa]^{ep}
- 意外瓦氏蝎 *Vachonus inexpectatus* Lourenço, 2015 [unexpected]^{ax}
- 伊克巴尔氏瓦氏蝎 *Vachonus iqbali* Amir & Kamaluddin, 2009 [nomen dubium] [Iqbal]^{ep}
- 拉贾斯坦瓦氏蝎 *Vachonus rajasthanicus* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Rajasthan State, India]^{to}
- 诡杀牛蝎属 Genus *Xenobuthus* Lowe, 2018 [*xeno-* (alien, foreign, strange) + *Buthus*]^{mo&ta}
- 煤色诡杀牛蝎 *Xenobuthus anthracinus* (Pocock, 1895) [*anthrac-* (charcoal) + *-inus* (pertaining to)]^{chr}
- 阿拉伯诡杀牛蝎 *Xenobuthus arabicus* (Lourenço & Qi, 2006) [Saudi Arabia]^{to}
- 黄诡杀牛蝎 *Xenobuthus xanthus* Lowe, 2018 [yellow]^{chr}
- 国君蝎属 Genus *Zabius* Thorell, 1893 [the king of Hyperborea in Greek myth]^{my}
- 彼氏国君蝎 *Zabius birabeni* Mello-Leitão, 1938 [Max Birabén]^{ep}
- 黯褐国君蝎 *Zabius fuscus* (Thorell, 1876) [dark brown]^{chr}
- 高乔国君蝎 *Zabius gaucho* Acosta, Candido, Buckup & Brescovit, 2008 [*gauchos*, inhabitants of River Grande do Sul State, Brazil]^{et}
- 寇里蝎科 Family *Chaerilidae* Pocock, 1893
- 寇里蝎属 Genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 [Χοιρίλος (Choerilus), a Greek epic poet]^{ep}
- 敏捷寇里蝎 *Chaerilus agilis* Pocock, 1899 [agile]^{er}
- 阿凡氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus agnellivanniorum* Lourenço & Rossi, 2018 [Paolo Agnelli and Stefano Vanni]^{ep}
- 艾氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus alberti* Kovařík, 2019 [A. Albert]^{ep}
- 安达曼寇里蝎 *Chaerilus andamanensis* Lourenço, Duhem & Leguin, 2011 [Andaman Islands, India]^{to}
- 安娜普娜寇里蝎 *Chaerilus annapurna* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [Mt. Annapurna, Nepal]^{to}
- 阿萨姆寇里蝎 *Chaerilus assamensis* Kraepelin, 1913 ☆ [Assam State, India]^{to}
- 婆罗洲寇里蝎 *Chaerilus borneensis* Simon, 1880 [Borneo Island (Indonesia/Malaysia/Brunei)]^{to}
- 洞栖寇里蝎 *Chaerilus cavernicola* Pocock, 1894 [*caverni-* (cave) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 西里伯斯寇里蝎 *Chaerilus celebensis* Pocock, 1894 [Celebes (now Sulawesi) Island, Indonesia]^{to}
- 锡兰寇里蝎 *Chaerilus ceylonensis* Pocock, 1894 [Ceylon (now Sri Lanka)]^{pal}
- 柴氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus chapmani* Vachon & Lourenço, 1985 [Philippe Chapman]^{ep}
- 丘布鲁克寇里蝎 *Chaerilus chubluk* Lourenço, Tran & Pham, 2020 [ChuBluk Volcano, Vietnam]^{to}
- 擎氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus cimrmani* Kovařík, 2012 [Jára Cimrman]^{ep}
- 贝形寇里蝎 *Chaerilus conchiformis* Zhu, Han & Lourenço, 2008 ★ [*conchi-* (shell) + *formus* (form)]^{mo}

- 具疣寇里蝎 *Chaerilus granulatus* Kovařík, Lowe, Hoferek, Forman & Král, 2015 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 霍氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus hofereki* Kovařík, Král, Kořínková & Lerma, 2014 [David Hoferek]^{ep}
- 洪巴寇里蝎 *Chaerilus honba* Lourenço, 2019 [Hon Bà Nature Reserve, Khánh Hòa Province, Vietnam]^{to}
- 独特寇里蝎 *Chaerilus insignis* Pocock, 1894 [remarkable, distinguished]^{mo}
- 朱氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus juliettae* Lourenço, 2011 [Juliette Arab]^{ep}
- 柬埔寨寇里蝎 *Chaerilus kampuchea* Lourenço, 2012 [nomen dubium] [Khmer language for “Cambodia”]^{au(to)}
- 考氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus kautti* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Peter Kautt]^{ep}
- 滑螯寇里蝎 *Chaerilus laevimanus* Pocock, 1899 [*laevi-* (smooth) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 老挝寇里蝎 *Chaerilus laoticus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008 [Laos]^{to}
- 雷特拉寇里蝎 *Chaerilus lehrarensis* Khatoon, 1999 [nomen dubium] [Lehtrar Bala, Punjab Province, Pakistan]^{to}
- 长掌寇里蝎 *Chaerilus longimanus* Kovařík, Lowe, Hoferek, Forman & Král, 2015 [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 米林寇里蝎 *Chaerilus mainlingensis* Di & Zhu, 2009 ★ [Mainling County, Tibet Autonomous Region, China]^{to}
- 马氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus majkusi* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Zdeněk Majkus]^{ep}
- 内氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus neradorum* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Ladislav Nerad and his wife Hana]^{ep}
- 佩氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus petrzekai* Kovařík, 2000 [Karel Petrzelka]^{ep}
- 欧氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus ojangureni* Kovařík, 2005 [Andrès Ojanguren-Affilastro]^{ep}
- 菲律宾寇里蝎 *Chaerilus philippinus* Lourenço & Ythier, 2008 [Philippine]^{to}
- 帕托姆寇里蝎 *Chaerilus pathom* Lourenço & Pham, 2014 [Pa Thom Cave, Vietnam]^{to}
- 着色寇里蝎 *Chaerilus pictus* (Pocock, 1890) [colored, colorful]^{mo}
- 拟贝形寇里蝎 *Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis* Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015 ★ [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Chaerilus conchiformis*]^{ta}
- 极艳寇里蝎 *Chaerilus pulcherrimus* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [*pulcher-* (beautiful) + *-imus* (superlative suffix)]^{mo}
- 直螯寇里蝎 *Chaerilus rectimanus* Pocock, 1899 [*recti-* (straight) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 罗氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus robinsoni* Hirst, 1911 [Herbert Christopher Robinson]^{ep}
- 萨氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus sabinae* Lourenço, 1995 [Sabine Jourdan]^{ep}
- 赛氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus seiteri* Kovařík, 2012 [Michael Seiter]^{ep}
- 塞氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus sejnai* Kovařík, 2005 [Vladimir Šejna]^{ep}
- 索氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus solegladi* Kovařík, 2012 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
- 棘刺寇里蝎 *Chaerilus spinatus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [*spin-* (spine) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 施氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus stockmannorum* Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2018 [Mark Stockmann and his wife Britta]^{ep}
- 泰氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus telnovi* Lourenço, 2009 [Dmitry Telnov]^{ep}
- 特氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus terueli* Kovařík, 2012 [Rolando Teruel Ochoa]^{ep}
- 格纹寇里蝎 *Chaerilus tessellatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005 ★ [*tessell-* (a small cube of stone) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 泰国寇里蝎 *Chaerilus thai* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010 [Thailand]^{to}
- 提氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus tichyi* Kovařík, 2000 [Vladimír Tichý]^{ep}
- 三肋寇里蝎 *Chaerilus tricostatus* Pocock, 1899 ☆ [*tri-* (three) + *cost-* (rib) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 截形寇里蝎 *Chaerilus truncatus* Karsch, 1879 [truncated, perfect passive participle of *trunco* (maim, mutilate)]^{mo}
- 忒氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus tryznai* Kovařík, 2000 ★ [Miloš Trýzna]^{ep}
- 杂色寇里蝎 *Chaerilus variegatus* Simon, 1877 [variegated, perfect passive participle of *variego* (variegate)]^{chr}
- 越南寇里蝎 *Chaerilus vietnamicus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008 [nomen dubium] [Vietnam]^{to}
- 瑞氏寇里蝎 *Chaerilus wrzecionkoi* Kovařík, 2012 ★ [Antonin Wrzecionko]^{ep}
- 微迷蝎科 Family **Microcharmidae** Lourenço, 1996
- 微迷蝎属 Genus **Microcharmus** Lourenço, 1995 # [*micro-* (small) + *Charmus*]^{mo&ta}
- 安氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus andrei* Lourenço, Waeber & Wilmé, 2019 [André Peyrieras]^{ep}
- 安通吉尔微迷蝎 *Microcharmus antongil* Lourenço, Waeber & Wilmé, 2019 [Antongil Bay, Madagascar]^{to}
- 贝马拉哈微迷蝎 *Microcharmus bemaraha* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [Bemaraha National Park, Madagascar]^{to}
- 克氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus cloudsleythompsoni* Lourenço, 1995 [John Leonard Cloudsley-Thompson]^{ep}
- 连纹微迷蝎 *Microcharmus confluenciatatus* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [*confluenci-* (confluence) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 姜戈阿微迷蝎 *Microcharmus djangoa* Lourenço, Waeber & Wilmé, 2019 [Djangoa Municipality, Madagascar]^{ep}
- 杜氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus duhemi* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [Bernard Duhem]^{ep}
- 勐氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus fisheri* Lourenço, 1998 [Brian L. Fisher]^{ep}
- 豪氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus hauseri* Lourenço, 1996 [Bernd Hauser]^{ep}
- 茹氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus jussarae* Lourenço, 1996 [Jussara Lourenço]^{ep}
- 斑微迷蝎 *Microcharmus maculatus* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 马达加斯加微迷蝎 *Microcharmus madagascariensis* Lourenço, 1999 [Madagascar]^{to}
- 珀氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmus pauliani* (Lourenço, 2004)

- 模式亚种 *M. pauliani pauliani* (Lourenço, 2004) [Renaud Paulian]^{ep}
 琥珀山亚种 *M. pauliani ambre* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [Ambre Special Reserve, Madagascar]^{fo}
 纳莫罗卡亚种 *M. pauliani namoroka* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [Namoroka National Park, Madagascar]^{fo}
 萨氏微迷蝎 *Microcharmum sabineae* Lourenço, 1996 [Sabine Jourdan]^{ep}
 杂色微迷蝎 *Microcharmum variegatus* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [variegated, perfect passive participle of *variego* (variegate)]^{chr}
 紫罗兰微迷蝎 *Microcharmum violaceous* Lourenço, Goodman & Fisher, 2006 [*viol-* (violet) + *-aceous* (forming, having the nature of)]^{chr}
- 新原杀牛蝎属 Genus *Neoprotobuthus* Lourenço 2000 [*neo-* (new) + *proto-* (first) + *Buthus*]^{ta}
 中介新原杀牛蝎 *Neoprotobuthus intermedius* Lourenço, 2000 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta}
- 拟蛮蝎科 Family **Pseudochactidae** Gromov, 1998
- 老挝蝎属 Genus *Aemngvantom* Prendini, Ehrental & Loria, 2021 [Lao for “scorpion”]^{au&ty}
 模式老挝蝎 *Aemngvantom lao* (Lourenço, 2012) [Laos]^{fo}
 苏安洞老挝蝎 *Aemngvantom thamnongpaseuam* Prendini, Ehrental & Loria, 2021 [Tham Nong Pa Seuam, Khammouane Province, Laos]^{fo}
- 拟蛮蝎属 Genus *Pseudochactas* Gromov, 1998 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Chactas*]^{ta}
 米氏拟蛮蝎 *Pseudochactas mischi* Soleglad, Kovařík & Fet, 2012 [Michael Misch]^{ep}
 奥氏拟蛮蝎 *Pseudochactas ovchinnikovi* Gromov, 1998 [Sergei Vladimirovich Ovchinnikov]^{ep}
- 穴甘蒙蝎属 Genus *Troglokhammouanus* Lourenço, 2007 [*troglo-* (cave) + Khammouane, Laos]^{bi&to}
 施氏穴甘蒙蝎 *Troglokhammouanus steineri* Lourenço, 2007 [Helmut Steiner]^{ep}
- 越南蝎属 Genus *Vietbocap* Lourenço & Pham, 2010 [Vietnam + “*bocap*”, Vietnamese for “scorpion”]^{to&au}
 堪氏越南蝎 *Vietbocap canhi* Lourenço & Pham, 2010 [Le Xuan Canh]^{ep}
- 毒尾蝎小目 Parvorder **Iurida** Soleglad & Fet, 2003
- 圣经蝎科 Family **Akravidae** Levy, 2007
- 圣经蝎属 Genus *Akrav* Levy, 2007 [Biblical Hebrew for “scorpion”]^{au}
 以色列沙氏圣经蝎 *Akrav israchanani* Levy, 2007 [*isra-* (Israel; also Israel Na’aman) + Chanan (Dimentman)]^{to&ep}
- 将军蝎科 Family **Belisariidae** Lourenço, 1998
- 将军蝎属 Genus *Belisarius* Simon, 1879 [Βελισάριος (Belisarius), a general of the Byzantine Empire]^{ep}
 伊比利亚将军蝎 *Belisarius ibericus* Lourenço, 2015 [Iberia]^{pal}
 格氏将军蝎 *Belisarius xambeui* Simon, 1879 [Pierre-Joseph Vincent Xambeu]^{ep}
- 萨丁蝎属 Genus *Sardoscorpium* Tropea & Onnis, 2020
 [*sardo-* (Sardinian) + *scorpius* (Latin for “scorpion”)]^{fo}
- 喜穴萨丁蝎 *Sardoscorpium troglophilus* Tropea & Onnis, 2020 [*troglo-* (cave) + *-philus* (lover)]^{bi}
- 沟尾蝎科 Family **Bothriuridae** Simon, 1880
- 沟尾蝎属 Genus *Bothriurus* Peters, 1861 [*bothri-* (trench, pit) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 阿巴伊拉沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus aguardente* Santos-da-Silva, Carvahlo & Brescovit, 2017 [Abaíra (city of “aguardente”), a city in Bahia State, Brazil]^{fo}
 阿拉瓜亚沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus araguayae* Vellard, 1934 [Araguya (= Araguaia) River, Goiás State, Brazil]^{fo}
 粗糙沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus asper* Pocock, 1893 [rough]^{mo}
 伯氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus bertae* Abalos, 1955 [Berta Juárez Heredia]^{ep}
 博氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus bocki* Kraepelin, 1911 [Charles Bock]^{ep}
 博纳瑞亚沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus bonariensis* (C. L. Koch, 1842) [Bonaria, Buenos Aires, Argentina]^{fo}
 布氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus buecherli* San Martín, 1963 [Wolfgang Bücherl]^{ep}
 步氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus burmeisteri* Kraepelin, 1894 [Karl Hermann Konrad Burmeister]^{ep}
 塞氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus ceii* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2007 [José Miguel Alfredo María Cei]^{ep}
 塞拉多沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus cerradoensis* Lourenço, Motta, Godoi & Araújo 2004 [Cerrados Region, Brazil]^{fo}
 查科沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus chacoensis* Maury & Acosta, 1993 [Chaco Region of Paraguay and Argentina]^{fo}
 智利沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus chilensis* (Molina, 1782) [Chile]^{fo}
 科尔多瓦沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus cordubensis* Acosta, 1995 [Córdoba Province, Argentina]^{fo}
 革质沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus coriaceus* Pocock, 1893 [*cori-* (leather) + *-aceus* (forming, having the nature of)]^{mo}
 戴氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus delmari* Santos-da-Silva, Carvahlo & Brescovit, 2017 [Delmar Lopes Alvim]^{ep}
 杜氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus dumayi* Cekalovic, 1974 [Alejandro Dumay Deramond]^{ep}
 黄沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus flavidus* Kraepelin, 1911 [*flav-* (yellow) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
 戈亚斯沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus goiano* Lovato, Anker & Lourenço, 2021 [Goiás State, Brazil]^{fo}
 黄褐沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus guarani* Maury, 1984 [tawny-colored]^{chr}
 山岭沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus huincul* Mattoni, 2007 [Mapuche for “mountain”]^{au(bi)}

欺詐沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus illudens* Mello-Leitão, 1947

模式亚种 *B. illudens illudens* Mello-Leitão, 1947 [mocking, deceiving]^{la}

阿拉蓬加斯亚种 *B. illudens araponguensis* Bücherl, San Martín, da Cunha, Matthiesen & Zimmer, 1963 [Arapongas Municipality, Paraná State, Brazil]^o

无武沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus inermis* Maury, 1981 [*in-* (not) + *erm-* (*arma*, armed) + *-is* (combined form with *in-*)]^{mo}

耶稣沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus jesuita* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 [Spanish for “Jesuit”]^{au(ep)}

凯氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus keyserlingi* Pocock, 1893 [Eugen von Keyserling]^{ep}

斑沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus maculatus* Kraepelin, 1911 [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

摩卡沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus mochaensis* Cekalovic, 1982 [Mocha Island, Arauco, Chile]^o

穆氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus moojeni* Mello-Leitão, 1945 [João Moojen]^{ep}

南氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus nendai* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Garcia-Mauro, 2010 [Santiago Nenda]^{ep}

西北阿根廷沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus noa* Maury, 1984 [“Noroeste Argentina”]^{to}

奥拉恩沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus olaen* Acosta, 1997 [Olaen Pampa, Argentina]^o

潘帕沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus pampa* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2002 [Achal Pampa, Argentina]^o

巴塔哥尼亚沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus patagonicus* Maury, 1968 [Patagonia, Argentina]^o

皮奇库伊沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus pichicuy* Mattoni, 2002 [Pichicuy, Petorca Province, Chile]^o

皮昆切沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus picunche* Mattoni, 2002 [Mapuche tribe from south-central Chile]^{et}

波拉沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus pora* Mattoni & Acosta, 2005 [Ponta Porã, Mato Grosso do Sul State, Brazil]^{to}

显著沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus conspicuus* Mello-Leitão, 1934 [conspicuous, remarkable]^{mo}

柔氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus rochai* Mello-Leitão, 1932

模式亚种 *B. rochai rochai* Mello-Leitão, 1932 [Francisco Diaz da Rocha]^{ep}

西部亚种 *B. rochai occidentalis* Lourenço, 2003 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}

罗恰沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus rochensis* San Martín, 1965 [Rocha Department, Uruguay]^{to}

渐红沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus rubescens* Mello-Leitão, 1947 [*rub-* (red) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}

圣克鲁斯沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus sanctaerucis* Mattoni, 2007 [Puerto Santa Cruz, a town in Argentina]^{to}

独特沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus signatus* Pocock, 1893 [marked, distinguished, perfect passive participle of *signo* (mark, sign)]^{mo}

索奥雷塔马沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus sooretamensis* San Martín, 1966 [Sooretama National Park, Brazil]^o

三线沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus trivittatus* Werner, 1939 [*tri-* (three) + *vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

瓦氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus vachoni* San Martín, 1968 [Max Vachon]^{ep}

条纹沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus vittatus* (Guerin Meneville, 1838) [*vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

佛氏沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus voyati* Maury, 1973 [Raymart Voyat]^{ep}

辛古沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus xingu* Lourenço, 2016 [Rio Xingu, Pará State, Brazil]^o

岔脊沟尾蝎 *Bothriurus ypsilon* Mello-Leitão, 1935 [Greek “Y” formed by denticles on metasoma V]^{mo}

短胸蝎属 Genus *Brachistosternus* Pocock, 1893 [*brachisto-* (shortest) + *sternus* (sternum)]^{mo}

阿空加瓜短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus aconcagua* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Luisa-Scioscia, 2007 [Mt. Aconcagua, Chile]^{to}

异短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus alienus* Linnberg, 1898 [strange, foreign]^{mo}

缺腺短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus anandrovestigia* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Ochoa, 2018 [androvestigia on metasoma V]^{mo}

安第斯短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus andinus* Chamberlin, 1916 [Andes Mts.]^o

窄螯短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus angustimanus* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Roig Alsina, 2001 [*angusti-* (strait) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}

阿氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus artigasi* Cekalovic, 1974 [Jorge Narciso José Artigas Coch]^{ep}

巴氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus barrigai* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Pizarro-Araya, 2014 [Juan Enrique Barriga Tuñón]^{ep}

卡斯特罗氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus castroi* Mello-Leitão, 1940 [nomen dubium] [Raul Castro]^{ep}

塞氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus cekalovici* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2005 [Tomás Cekalovic Kushevich]^{ep}

赛氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus cepedai* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Augusto, Pizarro-Araya & Mattoni, 2007 [Jorge Cepeda-Pizarro]^{ep}

羌戈斯短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus chango* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2007 [Changos Indian tribe from Peru and Chile]^{et}

智利短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus chilensis* Kraepelin, 1911 [Chile]^o

秦巴短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus chimba* Ojanguren Affilastro, Alfaro & Pizarro-Araya, 2021 [La Chimba National Reserve, Chile]^{to}

西南短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus contisuyu* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Ochoa, 2018 [Conti Suyu, Quechua for “southwestern region” in Peru]^{au(cho)}

科金博短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus coquimbo* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Augusto, Pizarro-Araya & Mattoni, 2007 [Coquimbo Region, Chile]^{to}

多氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus donosoi* Cekalovic, 1974 [Roberto Donoso-Barros]^{ep}

埃氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus ehrenbergii* (Gervais, 1841) [Christian Gottfried Ehrenberg]^{ep}

锈色短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus ferrugineus* (Thorell, 1876) [*ferrugin-* (rust) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}

盖氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus gayi* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Ochoa, 2018 [Claudio Gay Mouret]^{ep}

伽氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus galianoae* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2002 [Maria Elena Galiano]^{ep}

霍姆伯格氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus holmbergi* Carbonell, 1923 [nomen dubium] [Eduardo Ladislao Holmberg]^{ep}

- 中介短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus intermedius* Lnnberg, 1902 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{aa}
- 海岸短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus kamanchaca* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2007 [local name for “sea fog” along the coastline]^{au(bi)}
- 寇氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus kovariki* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 [František Kovářik]^{fp}
- 尤耶亚科短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus llullaillaco* Ojanguren Affilastro, Alfaro & Pizarro-Araya, 2021 [Lullaillaco Volcano, Chile]^{to}
- 马氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus mattonii* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2005 [Camilo Iván Mattoni]^{fp}
- 米斯蒂短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus misti* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Ochoa, 2018 [Misti Volcano, Peru]^{to}
- 山地短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus montanus* Roig Alsina, 1977 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 多齿短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus multidentatus* Maury, 1984 [*multi-* (many) + *dent-* (tooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 尼氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus negrei* Cekalovic, 1975 [Jacques Negré]^{ep}
- 火山短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus ninapo* Ochoa, 2004 [*nina poqchiq orco*, Quechua for “volcano”]^{au(bi)}
- 欧氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus ochoai* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2004 [José Antonio Ochoa]^{fp}
- 帕波索短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus paposo* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Pizarro-Araya, 2014 [Paposo Area, Chile]^{to}
- 葆氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus paulae* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 [Paula Korob]^{fp}
- 佩氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus pognai* Cekalovic, 1969 [Luis Peña]^{ep}
- 潘氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus petheri* Mello-Leitão, 1931 [Arnold Penther]^{ep}
- 琵氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus perettii* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Mattoni, 2006 [Alfredo V. Peretti]^{ep}
- 秘鲁短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus peruvianus* Toledo Piza, 1974 [Peruvian]^{cho}
- 菲氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus philippii* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Ochoa, 2018 [Rodolfo Amando Philippi Krumwiede]^{ep}
- 匹氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus piacentinii* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 [Luis Norberto Piacentini]^{fp}
- 普氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus prendinii* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003 [Lorenzo Prendini]^{fp}
- 棘丛短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus quiscapata* Ochoa & Acosta, 2002 [Quechua for “spine (quisca)” and “spiny place (pata)”]^{au(bi)}
- 罗氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus roigalsinai* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2002 [Arturo Roig Alsina]^{fp}
- 茜氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus sciosciae* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2002 [Cristina Scioscia]^{fp}
- 西蒙纳氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus simoneae* Lourenço, 2000 [nomen dubium] [Simone Largura]^{ep}
- 特尔卡短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus telteca* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2000 [Telteca Reserve, Argentina]^{to}
- 提提卡卡短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus titicaca* Ochoa & Acosta, 2002 [Lake Titicaca, Peru]^{to}
- 侵螫短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus turpuq* Ochoa, 2002 [Quechua for “aggressive sting”]^{au(er)}
- 魏氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus weyenberghi* (Thorell, 1876) [Hendrik Weyenbergh]^{ep}
- 赞氏短胸蝎 *Brachistosternus zambrunoi* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2002 [Mario Zambruno]^{ep}
- 布兰德山蝎属 Genus *Brandbergia* Prendini, 2003 [Brandberg Massif, Namibia]^{to}
- 哈氏布兰德山蝎 *Brandbergia haringtoni* Prendini, 2003 [Alexis Harington]^{ep}
- 巴西沟尾蝎属 Genus *Brazilobothriurus* Lourenço & Monod, 2000 [Brazil + *Bothriurus*]^{to&ta}
- 潘塔纳尔巴西沟尾蝎 *Brazilobothriurus pantanalensis* Lourenço & Monod, 2000 [Pantanal Region, Brazil]^{to}
- 刺勇蝎属 Genus *Centromachetes* Lönnerberg, 1897 [*centro-* (spike) + *machetes* (fighter, warrior)]^{mo&er}
- 黯色刺勇蝎 *Centromachetes obscurus* Mello-Leitão, 1932 [dark]^{chr}
- 波氏刺勇蝎 *Centromachetes pocockii* (Kraepelin, 1894) [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
- 提氏刺勇蝎 *Centromachetes titschaki* (Werner, 1939) [Erich Titschak]^{ep}
- 尾屠蝎属 Genus *Cercophonius* Peters, 1861 [*cerco-* (tail) + *phonius* (murderer)]^{mo&er}
- 多疣尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius granulatus* Kraepelin, 1908 [*granul-* (granule) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 克氏尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius kershawi* Glauert, 1930 [James Andrew Kershaw]^{ep}
- 迈氏尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius michaelsoni* Kraepelin, 1908 [Wilhelm Michaelson]^{ep}
- 昆士兰尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius queenslandae* Acosta, 1990 [Queensland State, Australia]^{to}
- 鳞纹尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius squama* (Gervais, 1843) [scale]^{chr,mo}
- 具沟尾屠蝎 *Cercophonius sulcatus* Kraepelin, 1908 [*sulc-* (furrow, ditch, track) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 滑体蝎属 Genus *Lisposoma* Lawrence, 1928 [*lispo-* (smooth) + *soma* (body)]^{mo}
- 秀丽滑体蝎 *Lisposoma elegans* Lawrence, 1928 [elegant]^{mo}
- 休赫氏滑体蝎 *Lisposoma josehermana* Lamoral, 1979 [Marie-Josée and Herman Lamoral]^{ma&pat}
- 毛氏蝎属 Genus *Mauryius* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Mattoni, 2017 [Emilio Antonio Maury]^{ep}
- 库约毛氏蝎 *Mauryius cuyanus* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Mattoni, 2017 [Cuyo Area (Mendoza, San Luis and San Juan) in Argentina]^{to}
- 山沟尾蝎属 Genus *Orobothriurus* Maury, 1975 [*oro-* (mountain) + *Bothriurus*]^{bi&ta}
- 高地山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus alticola* (Pocock, 1899) [*alti-* (high) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 安佩山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus ampay* Ochoa & Acosta, 2003 [Ampay National Sanctuary, Peru]^{to}
- 阿提奎帕山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus atiquipa* Ochoa & Acosta, 2002 [Lomas de Atiquipa, Peru]^{to}
- 卡尔恰基斯山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus calchaqui* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Mt. Cumbres Calchaquis, Argentina]^{to}

- 康氏山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus compagnucci* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Luis Compagnucci]^{ep}
- 曲指山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus curvidigitus* (Kraepelin, 1911) [*curvi-* (curved) + *digitus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}
- 法玛提纳山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus famatina* Acosta & Ochoa, 2001 [Famatina Mts., Argentina]^{lo}
- 格氏山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus grismadoi* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Campon, Silnik & Mattoni, 2009 [Cristian José Grismado]^{ep}
- 瓦斯卡兰山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus huascaran* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Huascaran National Park, Peru]^{lo}
- 佩氏山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus paessleri* (Kraepelin, 1911) [Carl Richard Paessler]^{ep}
- 侏儒山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus parvus* Maury, 1975 [dwarf]^{mo}
- 弯指山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus quewerukana* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Quechua for “curved (quewe)” and “finger (rukana)”]^{au(mo)}
- 拉氏山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus ramirezi* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Perez Ramirez]^{ep}
- 塔马鲁加尔山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus tamarugal* Ochoa, Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni & Prendini, 2011 [Tamarugal Pampa, Chile]^{lo}
- 婴小山沟尾蝎 *Orobothriurus wawita* Acosta & Ochoa, 2000 [Quechua for “little baby”]^{au(mo)}
- 君主蝎属** Genus *Pachakutej* Ochoa, 2004
[the ninth Sapa Inca of the Kingdom of Cusco, Pachakuti Inca Yupanqui, 15th century]^{ep}
- 粗螯君主蝎 *Pachakutej crassimanus* (Maury, 1975) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 印加君主蝎 *Pachakutej inca* (Maury, 1975) [Inca civilization, South America]^{et}
- 第二君主蝎 *Pachakutej iskay* (Acosta & Ochoa, 2001) [Quechua for “two” (the second species from Peru)]^{au(ax)}
- 最小君主蝎 *Pachakutej juchuicha* Ochoa, 2004 [Quechua for “the smallest”]^{au(mo)}
- 奥氏君主蝎 *Pachakutej oscari* Ochoa, 2004 [Oscar Ochoa Mendieta]^{ep}
- 秘鲁君主蝎 *Pachakutej peruvianus* (Mello-Leitão, 1948) [Peruvian]^{lo}
- 弑尾蝎属** Genus *Phoniocercus* Pocock, 1893 [*phonio-* (murderer) + *cercus* (tail)]^{er&mo}
- 着色弑尾蝎 *Phoniocercus pictus* Pocock, 1893 [colored, colorful]^{mo}
- 圣马丁氏弑尾蝎 *Phoniocercus sanmartini* Cekalovic, 1968 [Pablo R. San Martín]^{ep}
- 石栖巨齿蝎属** Genus *Rumikiru* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni, Ochoa & Prendini, 2012
[Quechua for “stone (rumi)” and “tooth (kiru)”]^{au(bi&mo)}
- 阿塔卡马石栖巨齿蝎 *Rumikiru atacama* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni, Ochoa & Prendini, 2012 [Atacama Desert, Chile]^{lo}
- 路氏石栖巨齿蝎 *Rumikiru lourencoi* (Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2003) [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
- 阿拉乌咖那蝎属** Genus *Tehuankea* Cekalovic, 1973 [*tehuanque*, Araucan for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 谟氏阿拉乌咖那蝎 *Tehuankea moyanoi* Cekalovic, 1973 [Hugo Iván Moyano González]^{ep}
- 尖刺蝎属** Genus *Thestylus* Simon, 1880 # [unknown, translated by its “*stylus*” part and the “*centrus*” part in its jun. syn. *Maecocentrus*, which both mean “pillar” or “spike”]^{mo?ep?my?}
- 橙尾尖刺蝎 *Thestylus aurantiurus* Yamaguti & Pinto-da-Rocha, 2003 [*auranti-* (orange) + *urus* (tail)]^{chr&mo}
- 格氏尖刺蝎 *Thestylus glasioui* Bertkau, 1880 [Auguste François Marie Glaziou]^{ep}
- 独特尖刺蝎 *Thestylus signatus* Mello-Leitão, 1931 [nomen dubium] [marked, distinguished, perfect passive participle of *signo* (mark, sign)]^{mo}
- 提玛蝎属** Genus *Timogenes* Simon, 1880 [Τιμαγένης (Timagenes), a Greek historian from 1st century B.C.]^{ep}
- 奥氏提玛蝎 *Timogenes dorbignyi* (Guérin Méneville, 1843) [Alcide d’Orbigny]^{ep}
- 秀丽提玛蝎 *Timogenes elegans* (Mello-Leitão, 1931) [elegant]^{mo}
- 简手提玛蝎 *Timogenes haplochirus* Maury & Roig Alsina, 1977 [*haplo-* (simple) + *chirus* (hand, pincer)]^{mo}
- 马普切提玛蝎 *Timogenes mapuche* Maury, 1975 [Mapuche people from northern Patagonia, Argentina]^{et}
- 苏门答腊提玛蝎 *Timogenes sumatranus* Simon, 1880 [Sumatra (incorrect type locality for this Argentinian species)]^{lo}
- 尾弑蝎属** Genus *Urophonius* Pocock, 1893 [*uro-* (tail) + *phonius* (murderer)]^{mo&er}
- 阿恰拉尾弑蝎 *Urophonius achalensis* Abalos & Hominal, 1974 [Achala Pampa, Argentina]^{lo}
- 阿劳卡尾弑蝎 *Urophonius araucano* Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2020 [the Araucano indigenous people who occupied southern and central Chile]^{et}
- 短针尾弑蝎 *Urophonius brachycentrus* (Thorell, 1876) [*brachy-* (short) + *centrus* (here as “aculeus”)]^{mo}
- 主教尾弑蝎 *Urophonius eugenicus* (Mello-Leitão, 1931) [Marcus Eugenius, an archbishop of Ephesus]^{ep}
- 独特尾弑蝎 *Urophonius exochus* (Penther, 1913) [distinct]^{mo}
- 具疣尾弑蝎 *Urophonius granulatus* Pocock, 1898 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 伊氏尾弑蝎 *Urophonius iheringi* Pocock, 1893 [Hermann Friedrich Albrecht von Ihering]^{ep}
- 山岭尾弑蝎 *Urophonius mahuidensis* Maury, 1973 [Mahuida, Mapuche for “sierra”]^{au(bi)}
- 马氏尾弑蝎 *Urophonius martinezi* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Cheli, 2009 [Juan José Martínez]^{ep}
- 蒙氏尾弑蝎 *Urophonius mondacai* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Pizarro-Araya & Prendini, 2011 [José Mondaca Escudero]^{ep}
- 佩文切尾弑蝎 *Urophonius pehuenche* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Pizarro-Araya, 2020 [the pass between Argentina and Chile, “Paso Pehuenche”, also the indigenous people that inhabited this area]^{lo&et}

- 皮氏尾絨蝎 *Urophonius pizarroi* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Ochoa, Mattoni & Prendini, 2010 [Jaime Pizarro Araya]^{ep}
 索蒙库拉尾絨蝎 *Urophonius somuncura* Acosta, 2003 [Meseta de Somuncurá, Argentina]^{to}
 跨安第斯尾絨蝎 *Urophonius transandinus* Acosta, 1998 [*trans-* (across) + *andinus* (Andes)]^{po}
 特里瓜尔姆尾絨蝎 *Urophonius tregualemuensis* Cekalovic, 1981 [Tregualemu, Maule Province, Chile]^{to}
 杜比斯尾絨蝎 *Urophonius tumbensis* Cekalovic, 1981 [Tumbes Península, Concepción Province, Chile]^{to}
 瓦氏沟尾蝎属 Genus *Vachonia* Abalos, 1954 [Max Vachon]^{ep}
 马氏瓦氏沟尾蝎 *Vachonia martinezi* Abalos, 1954 [Antonio Martinez]^{ep}
 猎舟甲蝎科 Family **Caraboctonidae** Kraepelin, 1905
 猎舟甲蝎属 Genus *Caraboctonus* Pocock, 1893
 [*carabo-* (carabid beetles, from *carabus* (an ancient small boat covered with leather)) + *-ctonus* (killer)]^{er}
 凯氏猎舟甲蝎 *Caraboctonus keyserlingi* Pocock, 1893 [Eugen von Keyserling]^{ep}
 似厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hadruioides* Pocock, 1893 [*Hadrurus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
 阿氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides adrianae* Rossi, 2012 [Adriana Ratto Politi]^{ep}
 阿吉拉氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides aguilar* Francke & Soleglad, 1980 [Pedro G. Aguilar Fernández]^{ep}
 布氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides bustamantei* Ochoa & Chaparro, 2008 [Javier Bustamante]^{ep}
 具棱似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides carinatus* Pocock, 1900 [*carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 查尔卡斯似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides charcasus* (Karsch, 1879) [Charcas (now Sucre), Bolivia]^{pal}
 钦查苏尤似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides chinchaysuyu* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Chinchay Suyu, Quechua for an administrative region of Inca Empire]^{au(to)}
 多氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides doriai* Rossi, 2014 [Giuliano Doria]^{ep}
 艾氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides elenae* Rossi, 2014 [Elena Gavetti]^{ep}
 加拉帕戈斯似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides galapagoensis* Maury, 1975 [Galápagos Islands]^{to}
 盖氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides geckoi* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Roberto Gecko Gutiérrez]^{ep}
 葛氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides graceae* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Grace Servat]^{ep}
 太阳神似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides inti* Ythier, 2021 [Inti, the Incan sun god]^{de}
 胡氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides juanchaparro* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Juan Carlos Chaparro]^{ep}
 豹斑似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides leopardus* Pocock, 1900 [leopard (*leo-* (lion) + *pardus* (male panther))]^{chr}
 路氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides lourencoi* Rossi, 2012 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
 弧形似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides lunatus* (L. Koch, 1867) [curved, crescent-shaped, perfect passive participle of *luno* (curve)]^{mo/chr}
 斑似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides maculatus* (Thorell, 1876) [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 毛氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides mauryi* Francke & Soleglad, 1980 [Emilio Antonio Maury]^{ep}
 摩氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides moreti* Rossi, 2014 [Pierre Moret]^{ep}
 地神似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides pachamama* Ythier, 2021 [Pachamama, the Incan earth goddess]^{de}
 岛屿似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides tishqu* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Quechua for “island” (Santa Island, Peru)]^{au(bi)}
 汤氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides tongiorgii* Rossi, 2012 [Paolo Tongiorgi]^{ep}
 乌氏似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides udvardyi* Lourenço, 1995 [Miklos Dezso Ferenc Udvardy]^{ep}
 维查依托似厚尾蝎 *Hadruioides vichayitos* Ochoa & Prendini, 2010 [Playa Vichayitos, Piura Department, Peru]^{to}
 蛮蝎科 Family **Chaetidae** Pocock, 1893
 假尾戮蝎属 Genus *Anuroctonus* Pocock, 1893 [*a-* (not) + *Uroctonus*]^{ta}
 波氏假尾戮蝎 *Anuroctonus pococki* Soleglad & Fet, 2004
 模式亚种 *A. pococki pococki* Soleglad & Fet, 2004 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
 下加州亚种 *A. pococki bajae* Soleglad & Fet, 2004 [Baja California State, Mexico]^{to}
 黑指假尾戮蝎 *Anuroctonus phaiodactylus* (Wood, 1863) [*phai-* (dark) + *dactylus* (finger)]^{chr&mo}
 魔屋山蝎属 Genus *Auyantepuia* González-Sponga, 1978 [Auyán-tepui (“Devil’s House”, in the local Pemón language), Venezuela]^{to}
 阿鲁库魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia aluku* Ythier, 2018 [Aluku, an ethnic group of Apatou, French Guiana]^{et}
 阿马帕魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia amapaensis* Lourenço & Qi, 2007 [Amapá State, Brazil]^{to}
 金矿魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia aurum* Ythier, 2018 [gold, alluding to the village of Saül, founded at the beginning of the 19th century]^{to}
 芙氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia fravalae* Lourenço, 1983 [Jacqueline Fraval Kovoov]^{ep}
 盖氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia gaillardi* Lourenço, 1983 [Maurice Gaillard]^{ep}
 凯氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia kelleri* (Lourenço, 1997) [Albert Keller]^{ep}
 劳氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia laurae* Ythier, 2015 [Laura Ythier]^{ep}
 墨氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia mottai* Lourenço & Araujo, 2004 [Paulo César Motta]^{ep}
 侏儒魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia parvulus* (Pocock, 1897) [*parv-* (dwarf, small) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
 罗氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia royi* Ythier, 2018 [Grégory Roy]^{ep}
 司氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia scorzai* (Dagert, 1957) [José Vicente Scorza]^{ep}

- 西氏魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia sissomi* Lourenço, 1983 [William David Sissom]^{ep}
 苏里南魔屋山蝎 *Auyantepuia surinamensis* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [Suriname]^{to}
 猎人蛮蝎属 Genus *Broteochactas* Pocock, 1893 [*Brotheas* + *Chactas*]^{ta}
 考阿布里猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas cauaburi* Lourenço, Araujo & Franklin, 2010 [Cauaburi River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
 科奎猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas cocuyensis* González-Sponga, 2004 [Piedra del Cocuy, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 丹氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas danielleae* Lourenço, 2007 [Danielle Defaye]^{ep}
 高氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas gollmeri* (Karsch, 1879) [Julius Gollmer]^{ep}
 马尼萨潘猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas manisapanensis* (González-Sponga, 1992) [Manisapân Mts., Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
 毛氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas mauriciodiasi* Lourenço, 2017 [Mauricio Dias]^{ep}
 尼氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas niemeyerae* Lourenço, Ponce de Leão Giupponi & Pedroso, 2011 [Helyanne De Niemeyer]^{ep}
 光泽猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas nitidus* Pocock, 1893 [*niti-* (to shine) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 帕里马猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas parimensis* González-Sponga, 2004 [Parima Mts., Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 多孔猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas porosus* (Pocock, 1900) [*poro-* (callosity) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 普鲁斯猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas purus* Lourenço, 2017 [Rio Purus, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
 司氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas scorzai* Dagert, 1957 [José Vicente Scorza]^{ep}
 锡尔维斯猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas silves* Lourenço, 2014 [Silves Municipality, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
 忒氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas trezzii* (Vignoli & Kovařík, 2003) [Giuliano Trezzi]^{ep}
 委内瑞拉猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas venezuelensis* (González-Sponga, 1996) [Venezuela]^{to}
 贝氏猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas verneti* (González-Sponga, 1992) [Pedro Vernet]^{ep}
 弱脊猎人蛮蝎 *Broteochactas vestigialis* González-Sponga, 1978 [vestigial, refers to the lateral keels and ventral half of metasoma V]^{mo}
 猎人蝎属 Genus *Brotheas* C. L. Koch, 1837 [Βροθέας (Brotheas), son of Tantalus in Greek mythology, a hunter]^{my}
 亚马孙猎人蝎 *Brotheas amazonicus* Lourenço, 1988 [Amazon River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
 玻利维亚猎人蝎 *Brotheas bolivianus* Lourenço, 2008 [Bolivia]^{to}
 堪氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas camposi* González-Sponga, 1972 [Arquimedes Campos]^{ep}
 卡氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas caramaschii* Lourenço, Ponce de Leão Giupponi & Pedroso, 2011 [Ulisses Caramaschi]^{ep}
 卡塔尼亚波猎人蝎 *Brotheas cataniapensis* González-Sponga, 1997 [Rio Cataniapo, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 克氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas cristinae* Lourenço, 2007 [Cristina A Rheims]^{ep}
 库努库努马猎人蝎 *Brotheas cunucunumensis* González-Sponga, 1984 [Cunucunuma River, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 达氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas dasilvai* González-Sponga, 1978 [Abilio Da Silva]^{ep}
 疣螯猎人蝎 *Brotheas granimanus* Pocock, 1898 [*grani-* (grain) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 具疣猎人蝎 *Brotheas granulatus* Simon, 1877 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 翰氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas henriquesi* Lourenço & Machado, 2004 [Augusto Loureiro Henriques]^{ep}
 亨氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas humboldti* González-Sponga, 1980 [Alexander von Humboldt]^{ep}
 乔氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas jourdani* Lourenço, 1997 [Raymond Jourdan]^{ep}
 利氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas libinallyi* González-Sponga, 1978 [Radamés Libinally]^{ep}
 里氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas lichyi* González-Sponga, 1980 [René Lichy]^{ep}
 马瓦里努马猎人蝎 *Brotheas mawarinumensis* González-Sponga, 1991 [Mawarinuma River, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 敏氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas mingueti* González-Sponga, 1973 [Luis Minguet]^{ep}
 穆氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas munozii* González-Sponga, 1997 [Arturo Muñoz-Cuevas]^{ep}
 诺氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas noguerai* González-Sponga, 1993 [Félix Nogueira]^{ep}
 奥卡莫猎人蝎 *Brotheas ocamoi* González-Sponga, 2004 [Ocamo River, Mts. Parima, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 瓠氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas overali* Lourenço, 1988 [William Leslie Overal]^{ep}
 帕拉猎人蝎 *Brotheas paraensis* Simon, 1880 [Pará State, Brazil]^{to}
 琵氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas perezramirezi* González-Sponga, 1996 [Perez Ramirez]^{ep}
 里约尼格罗猎人蝎 *Brotheas rionegroensis* González-Sponga, 1996 [San Carlos de Rio Negro, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{to}
 萨氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas sanabriai* González-Sponga, 1997 [Lewis Sanabria]^{ep}
 林猎人蝎 *Brotheas silvestris* Lourenço, 1988 [*silv-* (forest) + *-estris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
 塔帕若斯猎人蝎 *Brotheas tapajos* Lourenço, 2012 [Tapajos River, Pará State, Brazil]^{to}
 瓦雷帕猎人蝎 *Brotheas wareipai* González-Sponga, 2004 [Wareipa Indian Community, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
 威氏猎人蝎 *Brotheas wilmeri* González-Sponga, 1980 [Wilmer Pérez]^{ep}
 蛮蝎属 Genus *Chactas* Gervais, 1844 [a Natchez Indian in François-René de Chateaubriand's novel *Atala*]^{ep}
 阿朵氏蛮蝎 *Chactas adornellae* Rossi, 2014 [Adornella Politi]^{ep}
 赤道蛮蝎 *Chactas aequinoctialis* (Karsch, 1879) [equinoctial]^{cho?}
 阿氏蛮蝎 *Chactas alarconi* González-Sponga, 2003 [Rigoberto Alarcón]^{ep}
 巴瓦科阿斯蛮蝎 *Chactas barbacoensis* González-Sponga, 1987 [Barbacoas, Lara State, Venezuela]^{to}
 巴氏蛮蝎 *Chactas barravierai* Lourenço, 1997 [Benedito Barraviera]^{ep}
 巴西蛮蝎 *Chactas braziliensis* Lourenço, Aguiar & Franklin, 2005 [Brazil]^{to}

- 短尾蛮蝎 *Chactas brevicaudatus* (Karsch, 1879) [*brevi-* (short) + *caud-* (tail) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 布氏蛮蝎 *Chactas brownelli* Lourenço, 1997 [Phillip H. Brownell]^{ep}
- 坎波埃利亚斯蛮蝎 *Chactas campoeliasensis* González-Sponga, 2006 [Campo Elias, Mérida Municipality, Venezuela]^{to}
- 查瓦斯肯蛮蝎 *Chactas chabasquensis* González-Sponga & Wall-González, 2007 [Chabasquén, Portuguesa State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 克罗尼蛮蝎 *Chactas chironiensis* González-Sponga, 1978 [Altos de Chironi, Henri Pittier National Park, Venezuela]^{to}
- 金足蛮蝎 *Chactas chrysopus* Pocock, 1893 [*chryso-* (gold) + *-pus* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 孤岛蛮蝎 *Chactas exsul* (Werner, 1939) [exiled, isolated, insular]^{bi}
- 锈色蛮蝎 *Chactas ferruginosus* González-Sponga, 1984 [*ferrugin-* (rust) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{chr}
- 甘氏蛮蝎 *Chactas gansi* González-Sponga, 1974 [Carl Gans]^{ep}
- 捷氏蛮蝎 *Chactas gestroi* Kraepelin, 1912 [Raffaello Gestro]^{ep}
- 多疣蛮蝎 *Chactas granulatus* González-Sponga, 2007 [*granul-* (granule) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 吉科氏蛮蝎 *Chactas guinandcortesi* González-Sponga, 2003 [Alejandro Guinand and Hernando Cortés]^{ep}
- 阿蒂约蛮蝎 *Chactas hatilloensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [El Hatillo, Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 豪氏蛮蝎 *Chactas hauseri* Lourenço, 1997 [Bernd Hauser]^{ep}
- 间斑蛮蝎 *Chactas interpuncta* González-Sponga, 1987 [*inter-* (between) + *puncta* (spot, point)]^{chr}
- 埃希多蛮蝎 *Chactas iutensis* González-Sponga, 2008 [Instituto Universitario Tecnológico de Ejido, Venezuela]^{to}
- 卡氏蛮蝎 *Chactas karschii* Pocock, 1893 [Ferdinand Karsch]^{ep}
- 凯氏蛮蝎 *Chactas keyserlingii* Pocock, 1893 [Eugen von Keyserling]^{ep}
- 鄂氏蛮蝎 *Chactas koepcke* Lourenço & Dastych, 2001 [Hans-Wilhelm Koepcke]^{ep}
- 滑足蛮蝎 *Chactas laevipes* (Karsch, 1879) [*laevi-* (smooth) + *-pes* (foot)]^{mo}
- 拉氏蛮蝎 *Chactas latuffi* González-Sponga, 1976 [Felipe Latuff]^{ep}
- 纤尾蛮蝎 *Chactas lepturus* Thorell, 1876 [*lept-* (narrow) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 大型蛮蝎 *Chactas major* Kraepelin, 1914 [large-sized]^{mo}
- 马氏蛮蝎 *Chactas mahnerti* Lourenço, 1995 [Volker Mahnert]^{ep}
- 迈米尔蛮蝎 *Chactas maimirensis* González-Sponga & Wall-González, 2007 [Maimire, Yaracuy State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 玛氏蛮蝎 *Chactas marinae* González-Sponga, 1987 [Marina González Lander]^{ep}
- 毛氏蛮蝎 *Chactas mauriesi* Lourenço & Flórez, 1990 [Jean-Paul Mauries]^{ep}
- 摩氏蛮蝎 *Chactas moreti* Lourenço, 2014 [Pierre Moret]^{ep}
- 牛津蛮蝎 *Chactas oxfordi* González-Sponga, 1978 [collectors of the “Club de Exploradores de la Universidad de Oxford”]^{ep}
- 瓠氏蛮蝎 *Chactas ozendai* Lourenço, 1999 [Paul Ozenda]^{ep}
- 普拉提雨蛮蝎 *Chactas platillonensis* González-Sponga & Wall-González, 2007 [Cerro Platillón Natural Monument, Guárico State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 瑞翰氏蛮蝎 *Chactas raymondhansi* Francke & Boos, 1986 [Raymond A. Mendez and Hans E. A. Boos]^{ep}
- 网纹蛮蝎 *Chactas reticulatus* Kraepelin, 1912 [*ret-* (net) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 罗氏蛮蝎 *Chactas rogelioi* González-Sponga, 1972 [Rogelio Delgado]^{ep}
- 红线蛮蝎 *Chactas rubrolineatus* Simon, 1880 [*rubro-* (red) + *linea* (line) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 糙螯蛮蝎 *Chactas scabrimanus* Kraepelin, 1912 [*scabri-* (rough) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 多毛蛮蝎 *Chactas setosus* Kraepelin, 1912 [*set-* (seta) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 昔氏蛮蝎 *Chactas simonii* Pocock, 1893 [Eugène Simon]^{ep}
- 图马盖蛮蝎 *Chactas tumaquensis* González-Sponga & Wall-González, 2007 [Tumaque, Lara State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 勃氏蛮蝎 *Chactas vanbenedenii* (Gervais, 1843) [Pierre-Joseph van Beneden]^{ep}
- 贝氏蛮蝎 *Chactas venegasi* González-Sponga, 2008 [Leonardo Venegas]^{ep}
- 薇氏蛮蝎 *Chactas viloriai* Rojas-Runjaic, 2004 [Angel Luis Viloría Petit]^{ep}
- 图尔瓜蛮蝎 *Chactas turguaensis* González-Sponga, 2007 [Turgua, Miranda State, Venezuela]^{to}
- 尤皮蛮蝎 *Chactas yaupi* Lourenço, 2014 [Yaupi, a village in Morona-Santiago Province, Ecuador]^{to}
- 余帕蛮蝎 *Chactas yupai* González-Sponga, 1994 [Yupa Indians of western Venezuela]^{et}
- 仿蛮蝎属** Genus *Chactopsis* Kraepelin, 1912 [*Chactas* + *-opsis* (appearance)]^{ta}
- 亚马孙仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis amazonica* Lourenço & Francke, 1986 [Amazon River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{to}
- 帕里马仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis barajuri* González-Sponga, 1982 [Karinja language for the Indians of the high Parima Mts., Venezuela]^{ti}
- 布氏仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis buhrnheimi* Lourenço, 2003 [Paulo Bührnheim]^{ep}
- 森妖仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis chullachaqui* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjaic, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013 [Quechua for a mythical spirit of the forest with unequal feet]^{au(my)}
- 森卫仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis curupira* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjaic, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013 [a mythical inhabitant and protector of the forest from the folklore of Brazilian Amazonia]^{my}
- 独特仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis insignis* Kraepelin, 1912 [remarkable, distinguished]^{mo}
- 锡亚帕仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis siapaensis* González-Sponga, 1991 [Siapa River, which takes its source in the Tepui La Neblina, Venezuela]^{to}
- 苏吉里马仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsis sujirima* González-Sponga, 1982 [a character from Kalina mythology, identity unknown]^{my}

似仿蛮蝎属 Genus *Chactopsoides* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjac, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013
[*Chactopsis* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}

- 佞氏似仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsoides anduzei* (González-Sponga, 1982) [Pablo Anduze]^{ep}
冈氏似仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsoides gonzalezspingai* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjaic, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013 [González-Sponga]^{ep}
马拉华卡似仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsoides marahuacaensis* (González-Sponga, 2004) [Mt. Marahuaca, Venezuela]^{to}
亚诺马米似仿蛮蝎 *Chactopsoides yanomami* (Lourenço, Ponce de Leão Giupponi & Pedroso, 2011) [Yanomami people of Brazilian Amazonia]^{et}

圭亚那蛮蝎属 Genus *Guyanochactas* Lourenço, 1998 [Guyana + *Chactas*]^{to&ta}

- 黄圭亚那蛮蝎 *Guyanochactas flavus* Lourenço & Ythier, 2011 [yellow]^{chr}
冈氏圭亚那蛮蝎 *Guyanochactas gonzalezspingai* (Lourenço, 1983) [Manuel Ángel González-Sponga]^{ep}
古氏圭亚那蛮蝎 *Guyanochactas goujei* (Vellard, 1932) [Maurice Gouge]^{ep}
马氏圭亚那蛮蝎 *Guyanochactas mascarenhasi* (Lourenço, 1988) [Bento Mascarenhas]^{ep}
图氏圭亚那蛮蝎 *Guyanochactas touroulti* Lourenço, 2018 [Julien Touroult]^{ep}

厚尾蛮蝎属 Genus *Hadrurochactas* Pocock, 1893

[*hadr-* (thick, strong) + *uro-* (tail)]/?*Hadrurus* + *Chactas*]^{mo&ta}

- 阿拉里皮厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas araripe* (Lourenço, 2010) [Chapada do Araripe, Permanbuco State, Brazil]^{to}
布雷茹厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas brejo* (Lourenço, 1988) [Brejo formation, Maranguape, Ceará State, Brazil]^{to}
克氏厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas cristinae* Ythier, 2018 [Cristina Benros-Ythier]^{ep}
马氏厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas machadoi* González-Sponga, 1993 [Antonio Machado Allison]^{ep}
马普埃拉厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas mapuera* (Lourenço, 1988) [Mapuera River Region, Brazil]^{to}
奥氏厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas odoardi* González-Sponga, 1985 [Odoardo Ravelo]^{ep}
珀氏厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas polisi* (Monod & Lourenço, 2001) [Gary Allan Polisi]^{ep}
绍氏厚尾蛮蝎 *Hadrurochactas schaumii* (Karsch, 1880) [Hermann Rudolf Schaum]^{ep}

硕仿蛮蝎属 Genus *Megachactops* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjac, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013

[*mega-* (large) + *Chactopsis*]^{ta}

- 革质硕仿蛮蝎 *Megachactops coriaceo* (González-Sponga, 1991) [*cori-* (leather) + *-aceo* (forming, having the nature of)]^{mo}
毒神硕仿蛮蝎 *Megachactops kuemoui* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjaic, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013 [an Amazonian deity who created all dangerous and poisonous creatures of the night, from the folklore of the Piaroa of Venezuelan Amazonia]^{my}
库里帕克硕仿蛮蝎 *Megachactops kurripako* Ythier, 2019 [the Kurripako ethnic group of Colombia]^{et}

新蛮蝎属 Genus *Neochactas* Soleglad & Fet 2003 [*neo-* (new) + *Chactas*]^{ta}

- 瓦里亚新蛮蝎 *Neochactas bariensis* (González-Sponga, 1991) [Baría River, Venezuela]^{to}
彼氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas bilbaoi* (González-Sponga, 1978) [Maite Bilbao]^{ep}
布氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas bruzuali* (González-Sponga, 1980) [Gustavo Bruzual Pérez]^{ep}
卡罗尼新蛮蝎 *Neochactas caroniensis* (González-Sponga, 1996) [Caroni River, Venezuela]^{to}
哥伦比亚新蛮蝎 *Neochactas colombiensis* (González-Sponga, 1976) [Colombia]^{to}
精致新蛮蝎 *Neochactas delicatus* (Karsch, 1879) [delicate, charming]^{mo}
埃氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas efreni* (González-Sponga, 1978) [Efrén Toro]^{ep}
媛氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas eliasilvai* (González-Sponga, 1980) [Elías Silva]^{ep}
蒂氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas fei* (Pinto-da-Rocha, Gasnier, Brescovit & Apolinario, 2002) [Nelson Fé]^{ep}
伽氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas garciai* (González-Sponga, 1978) [Gerardo Garcia Herrero]^{ep}
多疣新蛮蝎 *Neochactas granosus* (Pocock, 1900) [*gran-* (grain) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
瓜伊基尼马新蛮蝎 *Neochactas guaiquinimensis* (González-Sponga, 1997) [Mt. Guaiquinima, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
雅氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas jaspei* (González-Sponga, 1993) [Luis Jaspe]^{ep}
何氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas josemanueli* (González-Sponga, 1992) [José Manuel Ayala]^{ep}
齐氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas kjellesvigi* (González-Sponga, 1974) [Erik Norman Kjellesvig-Waering]^{ep}
劳氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas laui* (Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966) [Edgar Lau]^{ep}
里氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas leoneli* (González-Sponga, 1978) [Leonel Hernández]^{ep}
长螯新蛮蝎 *Neochactas macrochela* (González-Sponga, 2004) [*macro-* (long) + *chela* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
内布利纳新蛮蝎 *Neochactas neblinensis* (González-Sponga, 1991) [Tepui “La Neblina”, Venezuela]^{to}
奥里诺科新蛮蝎 *Neochactas orinocensis* (Scorza, 1954) [High Orinoco River, Venezuela]^{to}
帕那瑞新蛮蝎 *Neochactas panarei* (González-Sponga, 1980) [Panare Indians, Venezuela]^{et}
埃尔堡新蛮蝎 *Neochactas paoensis* (González-Sponga, 1996) [El Pao, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
拉氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas racenisi* (González-Sponga, 1975) [Janis Racenis]^{ep}
比涅阿河新蛮蝎 *Neochactas riopinensis* (González-Sponga, 1992) [La Pina River, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{to}
鲁氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas ruizpittoli* (González-Sponga, 1993) [Antonio Ruiz Pittol]^{ep}
圣马丁氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas sanmartini* (González-Sponga, 1974) [Pablo R. San Martin]^{ep}

- 珊氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas santanai* (González-Sponga, 1978) [Miguel Santana]^{ep}
 萨里萨里尼亚马新蛮蝎 *Neochactas sarisarinamensis* (González-Sponga, 1985) [Tepui Sarisariñama, Bolívar State, Venezuela]^{lo}
 西马拉沃奇新蛮蝎 *Neochactas simarawochensis* (González-Sponga, 1980) [Simarawochi, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{lo}
 斯氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas skuki* (Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 2000) [Gabriel Skuk]^{ep}
 贝拉氏新蛮蝎 *Neochactas verai* (González-Sponga, 1993) [Mario Vera]^{ep}
 亚夸纳新蛮蝎 *Neochactas yekuanae* (González-Sponga, 1984) [Ya'kuana people of Venezuela and Brazil]^{et}
 伪猎人蝎属 Genus *Nullibrotheas* Williams, 1974 [*nulli-* (not) + *Brotheas*]^{la}
 艾氏伪猎人蝎 *Nullibrotheas allenii* (Wood, 1863) [Harrison Allen]^{ep}
 刺蛮蝎属 Genus *Spinochactas* Lourenço, 2016 [*spino-* (spine) + *Chactas*]^{mo&ta}
 米塔拉卡刺蛮蝎 *Spinochactas mitaraka* Lourenço, 2016 [Mitaraka Massif, French Guiana]^{lo}
 国王蝎属 Genus *Teuthraustes* Simon, 1878 [Τεῦθρας (Teuthras), king of Mysia in Greek mythology]^{my} [阿
 氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes adrianae* González-Sponga, 1975 [Adriana, wife of José Manuel Ayala]^{ep}
 阿卡纳纳国王蝎 *Teuthraustes akananensis* González-Sponga, 1984 [Akanaña, Amazonas State, Venezuela]^{lo}
 亚马孙国王蝎 *Teuthraustes amazonicus* (Simon, 1880) [Amazon River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{lo}
 墨色国王蝎 *Teuthraustes atramentarius* Simon, 1878 [*atra-* (black) + *-ament-* (suffix forming nouns) + *-arius* (suffix forming
 adjectives)]^{chr}
 巴西国王蝎 *Teuthraustes braziliensis* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010 [Brazil]^{lo}
 堪氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes camposi* (Mello-Leitão, 1939) [Francisco Campos]^{ep}
 卡氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes carmelinae* Scorza, 1954 [unknown, probably a feminine name]^{ep?}
 咖氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes castiglii* Rossi, 2015 [Francesco Massimo Castigli]^{ep}
 疑惑国王蝎 *Teuthraustes dubius* (Borelli, 1899) [dubious]^{la}
 菲氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes festae* (Borelli, 1899) [Enrico Festa]^{ep}
 杰氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes gervaisii* (Pocock, 1893) [François Louis Paul Gervais]^{ep}
 吉氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes giupponii* Ythier & Lourenço, 2017 [Alessandro Ponce de Leão Giupponi]^{ep}
 光滑国王蝎 *Teuthraustes glaber* Kraepelin, 1912 [smooth]^{mo}
 格氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes guerdouxi* Lourenço, 1995 [Jean Guerdoux]^{ep}
 科氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes khodayarii* Ythier & Lourenço, 2017 [Khosro Khodayari]^{ep}
 库氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes kuryi* Ythier & Lourenço, 2017 [Adriano Brillhante Kury]^{ep}
 利氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes lisei* Lourenço, 1994 [Arno Antonio Lise]^{ep}
 洛哈国王蝎 *Teuthraustes lojanus* (Pocock, 1900) [Loja, a city in Ecuador]^{lo}
 马图拉卡国王蝎 *Teuthraustes maturaca* González-Sponga, 1991 [name of a canal linking Baría River (Venezuela) to Cabauri
 River (Brazil)]^{lo}
 厄灵国王蝎 *Teuthraustes newaribe* Lourenço, Ponce de Leão Giupponi & Pedroso, 2011 [in Yanomami folklore, mischievous
 entities, “nè waribè” or “nè waripè”]^{my}
 具眼国王蝎 *Teuthraustes oculatus* Pocock, 1900 [*ocul-* (eye) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 瓠氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes ohausi* Kraepelin, 1912 [Friedrich Ohaus]^{ep}
 网纹国王蝎 *Teuthraustes reticulatus* González-Sponga, 1991 [*ret-* (net) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 柔氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes rosenbergi* (Pocock, 1898) [William Frederick Henry Rosenberg]^{ep}
 塞氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes simonsi* (Pocock, 1900) [Perry Oveitt Simons]^{ep}
 温氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes whympersi* (Pocock, 1893) [Edward Whympers]^{ep}
 帷氏国王蝎 *Teuthraustes wittii* (Kraepelin, 1896) [Ernesto Witt]^{ep}
 尾戮蝎属 Genus *Uroctonus* Thorell, 1876 [*uro-* (tail) + *-ctonus* (killer)]^{er}
 弗氏尾戮蝎 *Uroctonus franckei* Williams, 1986 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
 葛氏尾戮蝎 *Uroctonus grahami* Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972 [Richard Edward Graham]^{ep}
 辛螫尾戮蝎 *Uroctonus mordax* Thorell, 1876
 模式亚种 *U. mordax mordax* Thorell, 1876 [sting, tart (*mordeo* (bite) + *-ax* (inclined to))]^{er}
 多齿亚种 *U. mordax pluridens* Hjelle, 1972 [*pluri-* (many) + *-dens* (tooth)]^{mo}
 瓦氏蛮蝎属 Genus *Vachoniochactas* González-Sponga, 1978 [Max Vachon + *Chactas*]^{ep&ta}
 亚马孙瓦氏蛮蝎 *Vachoniochactas amazonicus* González-Sponga, 1991 [Amazon River, Amazonas State, Brazil]^{lo}
 爱氏瓦氏蛮蝎 *Vachoniochactas ashleeae* Lourenço, 1994 [Ashlee Hedgecock Rowe]^{ep}
 亨氏瓦氏蛮蝎 *Vachoniochactas humboldti* Flórez, Botero-Trujillo & Acosta, 2008 [Alexander von Humboldt]^{ep}
 拉萨尔瓦氏蛮蝎 *Vachoniochactas lasallei* González-Sponga, 1978 [Sociedad de Ciencias “La Salle”, Venezuela]^{lo}
 罗赖马瓦氏蛮蝎 *Vachoniochactas roraima* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009 [Mt. Roraima, the Guianas region, South America]^{lo}
 双棘蝎科 Family **Diplocentridae** Karsch, 1880
 双目蝎属 Genus *Bioculus* Stahnke, 1968 [*bi-* (two) + *oculus* (eye)]^{mo}
 卡沃双目蝎 *Bioculus caboensis* (Stahnke, 1968) [San José del Cabo, Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{lo}
 塞拉尔沃双目蝎 *Bioculus cerralvensis* Stahnke, 1968 [Cerralvo Island, Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{lo}

- 科蒙杜双目蝎 *Bioculus comondae* Stahnke, 1968 [Comond Municipality, Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{lo}
 圣克鲁斯双目蝎 *Bioculus cruzensis* Stahnke, 1968 [Santa Cruz Island, Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{lo}
 侏儒双目蝎 *Bioculus parvulus* Martín-Frias, 2004 [*parv-* (dwarf, small) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
 凯氏蝎属 Genus *Cazierius* Francke, 1978 [Mont Adelbert Cazier]^{ep}
 阿氏凯氏蝎 *Cazierius alayoni* Armas, 1999 [Giraldo Alayón García]^{ep}
 粗糙凯氏蝎 *Cazierius asper* Teruel, 2006 [rough]^{mo}
 酋长凯氏蝎 *Cazierius cayacoa* Teruel, Jiménez & Santos, 2021 [Cayacoa, the last Taino cacique that ruled the Higey Chiefdom]^{ep}
 金耀凯氏蝎 *Cazierius chryseus* Teruel & Armas, 2006 [*chry-* (gold) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
 希瓜乔凯氏蝎 *Cazierius ciguayo* Teruel, Jiménez & Santos, 2021 [Ciguayo people of the type locality, Cueva de los Murciélagos, Puerto Plata Province, Dominican Republic]^{et}
 加氏凯氏蝎 *Cazierius garridoi* Armas, 2005 [Orlando Hilario Garrido Calleja]^{ep}
 多疣凯氏蝎 *Cazierius granulatus* Teruel, 2013 [*granul-* (granule) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 袞氏凯氏蝎 *Cazierius gundlachii* (Karsch, 1880) [Johann Christoph Gundlach]^{ep}
 内巴凯氏蝎 *Cazierius neibae* Kovařík & Teruel, 2014 [Neyba Mts., Dominican Republic]^{lo}
 奇异凯氏蝎 *Cazierius paradoxus* Teruel & Diaz, 2004 [extraordinary (*para-* (beyond) + *doxus* (expectation))]^{mo}
 侏儒凯氏蝎 *Cazierius parvus* Armas, 1984 [dwarf]^{mo}
 光滑凯氏蝎 *Cazierius politus* (Pocock, 1898) [polished, perfect passive participle of *polio* (polish)]^{mo}
 托氏凯氏蝎 *Cazierius torrei* (Moreno, 1938) [Carlos de la Torre]^{ep}
 隐君王蝎属 Genus *Cryptoichlus* Teruel & Kovařík, 2012 [*crypt-* (hidden) + *Oichlus*]^{bi&ta}
 罗氏隐君王蝎 *Cryptoichlus rodriguezii* Teruel & Kovařík, 2012 [Tomas Michel Rodriguez Cabrera]^{ep}
 二棘蝎属 Genus *Didymocentrus* Kraepelin, 1905 [*didymo-* (twin) + *centrus* (spike)]^{mo}
 阿马斯氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus armasi* Teruel & Rodriguez, 2008 [Luis F. de Armas]^{ep}
 哈氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus hasethi* (Kraepelin, 1896) [C. G. de Haseth]^{ep}
 胡氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus hummelincki* Francke, 1978 [Pieter Wagenaar Hummelinck]^{ep}
 乔氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus jaumei* Armas, 1976 [Miguel Luis Jaime García]^{ep}
 克氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus krausi* Francke, 1978 [Otto Kraus]^{ep}
 路氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus lesueurii* (Gervais, 1844) [Charles-Alexandre Lesueur]^{ep}
 马提尼克二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus martinicae* Teruel & Questel, 2020 [Martinique]^{lo}
 小型二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus minor* Francke, 1978 [small-sized]^{mo}
 光泽二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus nitidus* (Hirst, 1907) [*niti-* (to shine) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 圣费利佩二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus sanfelipensis* Armas, 1976 [Sabanas de San Felipe, Cuba]^{lo}
 特立尼达二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus trinitarius* (Franganillo, 1930) [Trinidad Island]^{lo}
 韦氏二棘蝎 *Didymocentrus waeringi* Francke, 1978 [Erik Norman Kjellesvig-Waering]^{ep}
 双棘蝎属 Genus *Diplocentrus* Peters, 1861 [*diplo-* (double) + *centrus* (spike)]^{mo}
 玛雅洞穴双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus actun* Armas & Palacios-Vargas, 2002 [Mayan for “cave”]^{au(bi)}
 无眼双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus anophthalmus* Francke, 1977 [*an-* (without) + *ophthalmus* (eye)]^{mo}
 斗士双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus bellator* Teruel, 2003 [*bell-* (fight) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
 伯氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus bereai* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2004 [Pablo Berea]^{ep}
 双色双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus bicolor* Contreras-Félix & Santibáñez-López, 2011 [two-colored]^{mo}
 恰帕斯双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus chiapasensis* Beutelspacher & Armas, 1998 [Chiapas State, Mexico]^{lo}
 乔尔双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus chol* Francke, 2007 [Chol people from the region of type locality, Chiapas State, Mexico]^{et}
 丘鲁穆科双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus churumuco* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2005 [Churumuco Municipality, Michoacán State, Mexico]^{lo}
 科氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus coddingtoni* Stockwell, 1988 [Jonathan Coddington]^{ep}
 寇氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus colwelli* Sissom, 1986 [Christopher S. Colwell]^{ep}
 敏氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus coylei* Fritts & Sissom, 1996 [Frederick A. Coyle]^{ep}
 科苏梅尔双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus cozumel* Beutelspacher & Armas, 1998 [Cozumel Island, Mexico]^{lo}
 洞穴双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus cueva* Francke, 1978 [Spanish for “cave”]^{au(bi)}
 恶魔双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus diablo* Stockwell & Nilsson, 1987 [Spanish for “devil”]^{au}
 精灵双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus duende* Santibáñez-López & González-Santillán, 2017 [Spanish for “goblin”]^{au}
 锈色双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus ferrugineus* Fritts & Sissom, 1996 [*ferrugin-* (rust) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
 华丽双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus formosus* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2003 [beautiful (*form-* (beauty) + *-osus* (full of, overly))]^{mo}
 弗氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus franckei* Santibáñez-López, 2014 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
 哲氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus gertschi* Sissom & Walker, 1992 [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}
 剑士双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus gladiator* Beutelspacher & Trujillo, 1999 [*gladi-* (sword) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
 霍氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus hoffmanni* Francke, 1977 [Carlos Cristian Hoffmann]^{ep}
 岛屿双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus insularis* Sagastume-Espinoza, Longhorn & Santibáñez-López, 2015 [*insul-* (island) + *-aris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}

- 伊萨瓦尔双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus izabal* Armas & Trujillo, 2016 [Izabal Department, Guatemala]¹⁰
- 雅卡双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus jaca* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2000 [Santa María Jacatepec, a town in Oaxaca State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 凯氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus keyserlingii* Karsch, 1880 [Eugen von Keyserling]^{ep}
- 克氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus kraepelini* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2013 [Karl Kraepelin]^{ep}
- 拉楚阿双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus lachua* Armas, Trujillo & Agreda, 2011 [Lachuà Lake, Guatemala]¹⁰
- 兰氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus landelinoi* Trujillo & Armas, 2012 [Roni Landelino Trujillo Leon]^{pat}
- 美丽双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus lindo* Stockwell & Baldwin, 2001 [Spanish for “pretty”]^{au(mo)}
- 长掌双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus longimanus* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Athanasiadis, 2011 [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 路氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus lourencoi* Stockwell, 1988 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço]^{ep}
- 光亮双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus lucidus* Stockwell, 1988 [*luci-* (light) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
- 露氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus luisae* Guijosa, 1973 [Maria Luisa Bolaños de Guijosa]^{ma}
- 马加瓦双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus majahuensis* Baldazo Monsivaiz, 2003 [La Majahua, Guerrero State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 莫塔瓜双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus motagua* Armas & Trujillo, 2009 [Motagua River Valley, Zacapa Municipality, Guatemala]¹⁰
- 玛雅双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus maya* Francke, 1977 [inhabitants of the Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico]^{et}
- 梅氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus melici* Armas, Martín-Frias & Berea, 2004 [Antonio Melic]^{ep}
- 墨西哥双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus mexicanus* Peters, 1861
模式亚种 *D. mexicanus mexicanus* Peters, 1861 [Mexico]¹⁰
- 卡氏亚种 *D. mexicanus karschi* Sissom & Francke, 1998 [Ferdinand Karsch]^{ep}
- 米氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus mitchelli* Francke, 1977 [Robert Wetsel Mitchell]^{ep}
- 米特拉双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus mitlae* Francke, 1977 [Ruins of Mitla near the type locality, Mexico]¹⁰
- 蒙特克里斯托双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus montecristo* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2000 [Montecristo, a town in Villaflores Municipality, Chiapas State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 奥氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus ochoterenai* Hoffmann, 1931 [Isaac Ochoterena]^{ep}
- 饰装双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus ornatus* Stockwell, 1988 [decorated, perfect passive participle of *orno* (adorn)]^{mo}
- 历法双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus oxlajujbaktun* Trujillo & Armas, 2012 [Oxlajuj B’ak’tun, 394-year cycle in the Mayan calendar, a metonym for the type locality]^{au(to)}
- 佩隆西略双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus peloncillensis* Francke, 1975 [Peloncillo Mts., New Mexico and Arizona, USA]¹⁰
- 琵氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus perezii* Sissom, 1991 [Gonzalo Pérez-Higareda]^{ep}
- 珀普提双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus popti* Trujillo & Armas, 2016 [Maya Popti community, Guatemala]¹⁰
- 直螯双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus rectimanus* Pocock, 1898 [*recti-* (straight) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 雷氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus reddelli* Francke, 1977 [James R. Reddell]^{ep}
- 罗奥双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus roo* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2005 [Quintana Roo State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 箭肢双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus sagittipalpus* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2013 [*sagitti-* (arrow) + *palpus* (here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
- 珊氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus santiagoi* Stockwell, 1988 [Jorge A. Santiago-Blay]^{ep}
- 郝氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus silanesi* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2000 [Juan López Silanes]^{ep}
- 玛语双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus sinaan* Armas & Martín-Frias, 2000 [Mayan for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 西氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus sissomi* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2013 [William David Sissom]^{ep}
- 斯氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus spitzeri* Stahnke, 1970 [Carl Spitzer]^{ep}
- 思氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus steeleae* Stockwell, 1988 [June M. Steele]^{ep}
- 泰氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus taibeli* (Di Caporiacco, 1938) [Alulah Taibel]^{ep}
- 特瓦坎双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus tehuacanus* Hoffmann, 1931 [Tehuacán State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 提万诺双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus tehuano* Francke, 1977 [Tehuano, ethnic group from Mexico]^{et}
- 提南戈双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus tenango* Santibáñez-López & Francke, 2008 [Atenango del Rio, Guerrero State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 怀氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus whitei* (Gervais, 1844) [Adam White]^{ep}
- 威氏双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus williamsi* Sissom & Wheeler, 1995 [Stanley C. Williams]^{ep}
- 萨卡特卡双棘蝎 *Diplocentrus zacatecanus* Hoffmann, 1931 [Zacatecas State, Mexico]¹⁰
- 异尼博山蝎属 Genus *Heteronebo* Pocock, 1899 [*hetero-* (different) + *Nebo*]^{1a}
- 巴拉奥纳异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo barahonae* Teruel, Armas & Kovařík, 2015 [Barahona Province, Dominican Republic]¹⁰
- 伯氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo bermudezi* (Moreno, 1938) [P. J. Bermdez]^{ep}
- 开曼异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo caymanensis* Francke, 1978 [Grand Cayman, Cayman Island, West Indies]¹⁰
- 奚氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo cicero* Armas & Marcano-Fondeur, 1987 [Julio Cicero]^{ep}
- 克氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo clareae* Armas, 2001 [Clare Flemming]^{ep}
- 多米尼加异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo dominicus* Armas, 1981 [Dominican Republic]^{tochr&mo}
- 秀丽异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo elegans* Francke, 1978 [elegant]^{mo}
- 佛氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo forbesii* Pocock, 1899 [Henry Ogg Forbes]^{ep}
- 格氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo granti* Pocock, 1899 [William Robert Ogilvie-Grant]^{ep}

- 牙买加异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo jamaicae* Francke, 1978 [Jamaica]^{to}
 山栖异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo monticola* (Armas, 1999) [*monti-* (mountain) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
 摹氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo morenoi* (Armas, 1973) [Abelardo Moreno Bonilla]^{ep}
 尼布琼异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo nibujon* Armas, 1984 [Nibujón, a village in Baracoa Municipality, Guantánamo Province, Cuba]^{to}
 奥维耶多异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo oviedo* (Armas, 1999) [Oviedo, a city in Pedernales Province, Dominican Republic]^{to}
 波多黎各异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo portoricensis* Francke, 1978 [Puerto Rico]^{to}
 侏儒异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo pumilus* Armas, 1981 [dwarf]^{mo}
 粗糙异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo scaber* (Pocock, 1893) [rough]^{mo}
 瓦氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo vachoni* Francke, 1978 [Max Vachon]^{ep}
 因氏异尼博山蝎 *Heteronebo yntemai* Francke & Sissom, 1980 [John A. Yntema]^{ep}
 纳瓦蝎属 Genus *Kolotl* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2014 [Nahuatl for “scorpion”]^{au}
 巨型纳瓦蝎 *Kolotl magnus* (Beutelspacher & López-Forment, 1991) [great]^{mo}
 旁氏纳瓦蝎 *Kolotl poncei* (Francke & Quijano-Ravell, 2009) [Javier Ponce-Saavedra]^{ep}
 尼博山蝎属 Genus *Nebo* Simon, 1878 [Mt. Nebo, Jordan]^{to}
 黄足尼博山蝎 *Nebo lavipes* Simon, 1882 [*lavi-* (yellow) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
 弗氏尼博山蝎 *Nebo franckei* Vachon, 1980 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
 大尼博山蝎 *Nebo grandis* Francke, 1980 [grand]^{mo}
 亨加姆尼博山蝎 *Nebo henjamicus* Francke, 1980 [Henjam Island, Iran]^{to}
 耶利哥尼博山蝎 *Nebo hierichonticus* (Simon, 1872) [Jericho]^{to}
 阿曼尼博山蝎 *Nebo omanensis* Francke, 1980 [Oman]^{to}
 敏氏尼博山蝎 *Nebo poggesii* Sissom, 1994 [Maria Poggesi]^{ep}
 怀氏尼博山蝎 *Nebo whitei* Vachon, 1980 [P. Granville White]^{ep}
 也门尼博山蝎 *Nebo yemenensis* Francke, 1980 [Yemen]^{to}
 君王蝎属 Genus *Oiclus* Simon, 1880 [Οικλῆς (Oicles), father of Amphiarus in Greek mythology]^{my}
 热泉君王蝎 *Oiclus ardens* Ythier, 2019 [ardent; alluding to the geothermal activity and numerous hot springs in the type locality]^{bi}
 库氏君王蝎 *Oiclus cousteau* Ythier, 2019 [JacquesYves Cousteau]^{ep}
 侏儒君王蝎 *Oiclus nanus* Teruel & Chazal, 2010 [dwarf]^{mo}
 裴氏君王蝎 *Oiclus purvesii* (Becker, 1880)
 模式亚种 *O. purvesii purvesii* (Becker, 1880) [J. Purves]^{ep}
 萨巴亚种 *O. purvesii sabae* Francke, 1978 [Saba Island, Lesser Antilles]^{ep}
 奎氏君王蝎 *Oiclus questeli* Teruel, 2008 [Karl Questel]^{ep}
 瓜德罗普君王蝎 *Oiclus tipunch* Ythier, 2019 [the national drink (ti' punch) particularly of the Guadeloupe Island, a metonym for the type locality]^{au(to)}
 孔跗蝎属 Genus *Tarsoporosus* Francke, 1978 [*tarso-* (tarsus) + *poro-* (callosity) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 安奇卡亚孔跗蝎 *Tarsoporosus anchicaya* Lourenço & Flórez, 1990 [Anchicayá River, Valle del Cauca Department, Colombia]^{to}
 黄孔跗蝎 *Tarsoporosus lavus* (González-Sponga, 1984) [yellow]^{chr}
 库氏孔跗蝎 *Tarsoporosus kugleri* (Schenkel, 1932) [Hans Gottfried Kugler]^{ep}
 马库伊拉孔跗蝎 *Tarsoporosus macuira* Teruel & Roncallo, 2007 [Serrania de Macuira, Colombia]^{to}
 尤氏孔跗蝎 *Tarsoporosus yustizi* (González-Sponga, 1984) [Enrique Yustiz]^{ep}
 真蝎科 Family **Euscorpiidae** Laurie, 1896
 山蝎属 Genus *Alpiscorpius* Gantenbein, Fet, Largiadèr & Scholl, 1999
 [*alpis-* (the Alps) + *scorpius* (Latin for “scorpion”)]^{to}
 阿尔法山蝎 *Alpiscorpius alpha* (Di Caporiacco, 1950) [Greek letter alpha (α)]^{ord}
 贝塔山蝎 *Alpiscorpius beta* (Di Caporiacco, 1950) [Greek letter beta (β)]^{ord}
 卡氏山蝎 *Alpiscorpius caporiaccoi* (Bonacina, 1980) [Lodovico di Caporiacco]^{ep}
 克罗地亚山蝎 *Alpiscorpius croaticus* (Di Caporiacco, 1950) [Croatia]^{to}
 德尔塔山蝎 *Alpiscorpius delta* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter delta (δ)]^{ord}
 狄那里克山蝎 *Alpiscorpius dinaricus* (Di Caporiacco, 1950) [Dinaric Alps, Balkans]^{to}
 伽马山蝎 *Alpiscorpius gamma* (Di Caporiacco, 1950) [Greek letter gamma (γ)]^{ord}
 日耳曼尼亚山蝎 *Alpiscorpius germanus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Germania australis (now Tyrol State, Austria)]^{pal}
 卡帕山蝎 *Alpiscorpius kappa* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter kappa (κ)]^{ord}
 喀氏山蝎 *Alpiscorpius karamani* Tropea, 2021 [Ivo Karaman]^{ep}
 拉姆达山蝎 *Alpiscorpius lambda* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter lambda (λ)]^{ord}
 明戈瑞利亚山蝎 *Alpiscorpius mingrelicus* (Kessler, 1874) [Mingrelia Region, Georgia]^{pal}
 欧米茄山蝎 *Alpiscorpius omega* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter omega (ω)]^{ord}
 奥米克戎山蝎 *Alpiscorpius omikron* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter omikron (ο)]^{ord}

- 帕氏山蝎 *Alpiscorpius pavicevici* Tropea, 2021 [Dragan Pavićević]^{ep}
- 弗里吉亚山蝎 *Alpiscorpius phrygius* (Bonacina, 1980) [Phrygia, an ancient kingdom in the west central part of Anatolia (now Turkey)]^{pal}
- 西格玛山蝎 *Alpiscorpius sigma* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter sigma (σ/ς)]^{ord}
- 乌卢达山蝎 *Alpiscorpius uludagensis* (Lacroix, 1995) [Mt. Uludağ, Turkey]^{io}
- 艾普西龙山蝎 *Alpiscorpius ypsilon* Kovařík, Štundlová, Fet & Šťáhlavský, 2019 [Greek letter ypsilon (υ)]^{ord}
- 兹氏山蝎 *Alpiscorpius zlorubovici* Tropea, 2021 [Matija Zlorubović]^{ep}
- 真蝎属** Genus *Euscorpium* Thorell, 1876 [*eu-* (real, good, beautiful) + *scorpius* (Latin for “scorpion”)]^{mo}
- 阿拉达戈拉真蝎 *Euscorpium aladaglarenis* Tropea & Yağmur, 2016 [Aladağlar Mts., Turkey]^{io}
- 阿拉尼亚真蝎 *Euscorpium alanyaensis* Tropea, Yağmur, Parmakelis & Kunt, 2016 [Alanya District, Antalya Province, Turkey]^{io}
- 阿氏真蝎 *Euscorpium altadonnai* Tropea, 2017 [Giovanni Altadonna]^{ep}
- 阿莫尔戈斯真蝎 *Euscorpium amorgensis* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2017 [Amorgos Island, Greece]^{io}
- 阿奎利亚真蝎 *Euscorpium aquilejensis* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Aquileienses, inhabitants of Aquileia, Italy]^{io}
- 阿勒坎氏真蝎 *Euscorpium arikani* Yağmur & Tropea, 2015 [Hüseyin Arikani]^{ep}
- 阿弗吉氏真蝎 *Euscorpium avcii* Tropea, Yağmur, Koç, Yeşilyurt & Rossi, 2012 [Aziz Avci]^{ep}
- 巴利阿里真蝎 *Euscorpium balearicus* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Balearic Islands, Spain]^{io}
- 彼欧阔沃真蝎 *Euscorpium biokovensis* Tropea & Ozimec, 2020 [Biokovo Mts., Croatia]^{io}
- 比氏真蝎 *Euscorpium birulai* Fet, Soleglad, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2014 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
- 博氏真蝎 *Euscorpium bonacinai* Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [Alberto Bonacina]^{ep}
- 伯洛瓦格拉瓦真蝎 *Euscorpium borovaglavaensis* Tropea, 2015 [Borova Glava Mts., Bosnia-Herzegovina]^{io}
- 卡拉布里亚真蝎 *Euscorpium calabriae* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Calabria, Italy]^{io}
- 干地亚真蝎 *Euscorpium candiota* Birula, 1903 [Candia (now Heraklion), a city in the Crete Island, Greece]^{pal}
- 堪氏真蝎 *Euscorpium canestrinii* (Fanzago, 1872) [Giovanni Canestrini]^{ep}
- 喀尔巴阡真蝎 *Euscorpium carpathicus* (Linnaeus, 1767) [Carpathian Mts., Romania]^{io}
- 切拉诺真蝎 *Euscorpium celanus* Tropea, 2012 [Celano, a town in Abruzzo Region, Italy]^{io}
- 奇里乞亚真蝎 *Euscorpium ciliciensis* Birula, 1898 [Cilicia (now Çukurova), southern coastal region of Asia Minor of the central Anatolian Plateau]^{pal}
- 秀雅真蝎 *Euscorpium concinnus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [elegant, neat]^{mo}
- 科孚真蝎 *Euscorpium corcyraeus* Tropea & Rossi, 2012 [Corcyra, the Latin name of Corfu Island, Greece]^{io}
- 丘氏真蝎 *Euscorpium curcici* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2017 [Božidar P. M. Ćurčić]^{ep}
- 戴氏真蝎 *Euscorpium deltshevi* Fet, Graham, Webber & Blagoev, 2014 [Christo Deltshev]^{ep}
- 德氏真蝎 *Euscorpium drenskii* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2015 [Pencho Drenski]^{ep}
- 埃里曼索斯真蝎 *Euscorpium erymanthius* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2013 [Mt. Erymanthos, Greece]^{io}
- 埃斯基谢希尔真蝎 *Euscorpium eskisehrensensis* Tropea & Yağmur, 2015 [Eskişehir Province, Turkey]^{io}
- 费氏真蝎 *Euscorpium feti* Tropea, 2013 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
- 加尔加诺真蝎 *Euscorpium garganicus* Di Caporiacco, 1950
- 模式亚种 *E. garganicus garganicus* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Gargano Promontory, Foggia Region, Italy]^{io}
- 莫利塞亚种 *E. garganicus molisanus* Tropea, 2017 [Molise Region, Italy]^{io}
- 吉氏真蝎 *Euscorpium giachinoi* Tropea & Fet, 2015 [Pier Mauro Giachino]^{ep}
- 革氏真蝎 *Euscorpium gocmeni* Tropea, Yağmur & Yesilyurt, 2014 [Bayram Göçmen]^{ep}
- 哈氏真蝎 *Euscorpium hadzii* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Jovan Hadži]^{ep}
- 哈坎氏真蝎 *Euscorpium hakani* Tropea & Yağmur, 2016 [Hakan Durmuş]^{ep}
- 霍纳兹真蝎 *Euscorpium honazicus* Tropea, Yağmur, Karampatsou, Parmakelis & Yesilyurt, 2016 [Mt. Honaz, Denizli, Turkey]^{io}
- 希布莱乌斯真蝎 *Euscorpium hyblaicus* Tropea, 2016 [Hyblaean Mts., Sicily Region, Italy]^{io}
- 伊达真蝎 *Euscorpium idaicus* Yağmur & Tropea, 2017 [Mt. Ida, Balıkesir Province, Turkey]^{io}
- 意大利真蝎 *Euscorpium italicus* (Herbst, 1800) [Italy]^{io}
- 简氏真蝎 *Euscorpium janstai* Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [Petr Janšta]^{ep}
- 卡氏真蝎 *Euscorpium kabateki* Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [Petr Kabatek]^{ep}
- 金氏真蝎 *Euscorpium kinzelbachi* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2014 [Ragnar Kinzelbach]^{ep}
- 寇氏真蝎 *Euscorpium koci* Tropea & Yağmur, 2015 [Halil Koç]^{ep}
- 柯氏真蝎 *Euscorpium koschewnikovi* Birula, 1900 [Grigory Alexandrovich Kozhevnikov]^{ep}
- 克氏真蝎 *Euscorpium kritscheri* Fet, Soleglad, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2013 [Erich Kritscher]^{ep}
- 拉丁真蝎 *Euscorpium latinus* Tropea & Parmakelis, 2022 [Latium vetus, an ancient region in Italy]^{io}
- 莱斯沃斯真蝎 *Euscorpium lesbiacus* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi, Stathi & Zafeiriou, 2020 [Lesvos Island, Greece]^{io}
- 利西亚真蝎 *Euscorpium lycius* Yağmur, Tropea & Yeşilyurt, 2013 [Lycia Region (now Turkey)]^{pal}

- 弥氏真蝎 *Euscorpium mylonasi* Fet, Soleglad, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2014 [Moysis Mylonas]^{ep}
 拿波里真蝎 *Euscorpium naupliensis* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Nafplio, a city in Greece]^{lo}
 尼斯真蝎 *Euscorpium niciensis* (C.L. Koch, 1841) [Nice, a city in France]^{lo}
 基督山岛真蝎 *Euscorpium oglasae* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Oglasa Island (now Montecristo Island), Italy]^{pal}
 奥萨真蝎 *Euscorpium ossae* Di Caporiacco, 1950 [Mt. Ossa, Greece]^{lo}
 帕耳忒诺珀真蝎 *Euscorpium parthenopeius* Tropea, Parmakelis, Sziszkosz, Balanika & Boudierka, 2014 [Parthenöpe, an ancient name of Naples, Italy]^{pal}
 攸氏真蝎 *Euscorpium popovi* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2015 [Alexi Popov]^{ep}
 萨氏真蝎 *Euscorpium sadileki* Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [David Sadílek]^{ep}
 萨兰托真蝎 *Euscorpium salentinus* Tropea, 2017 [Salento, a region in Apulia, Italy]^{lo}
 粗糙真蝎 *Euscorpium scaber* Birula, 1900 [rough]^{mo}
 施氏真蝎 *Euscorpium scheraboni* Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [Bernhard Scherabon]^{ep}
 西坎尼真蝎 *Euscorpium sicanus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Sicani, ancient people of Sicily]^{et}
 索氏真蝎 *Euscorpium solegladi* Fet, Graham, Webber & Blagoev, 2014 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
 斯氏真蝎 *Euscorpium stahlavskyi* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2014 [František Šťáhlavský]^{ep}
 思氏真蝎 *Euscorpium stefaniae* Tropea & Parmakelis, 2022 [Stefania Tropea]^{ep}
 学徒真蝎 *Euscorpium studentium* Karaman, 2020 [a group of college students of Faculty of Sciences in Novi Sad, Serbia]^{ep}
 素丹真蝎 *Euscorpium sultanensis* Tropea & Yağmur, 2016 [Sultan Mts., Denizli, Turkey]^{lo}
 陶里亚真蝎 *Euscorpium tauricus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Tauria, ancient name of the Crimean Peninsula]^{pal}
 的里雅斯特真蝎 *Euscorpium tergestinus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [Tergeste (now Trieste), Italy]^{pal}
 色雷斯真蝎 *Euscorpium thracicus* Kovařík, Lowe, Byronová & Šťáhlavský, 2020 [Thracia (Thrace) region, Bulgaria]^{pal}
 特雷亚真蝎 *Euscorpium trejaensis* Tropea & Parmakelis, 2022 [Treja River, Italy]^{lo}
 崑氏真蝎 *Euscorpium vailatii* Tropea & Fet, 2015 [Dante Vailati]^{ep}
 维氏真蝎 *Euscorpium vignai* Tropea, Fet, Parmakelis, Kotsakiozi & Stathi, 2014 [Augusto Vigna Taglianti]^{ep}
 亚氏真蝎 *Euscorpium yagmuri* Kovařík, Fet & Soleglad, 2014 [Ersen Aydin Yağmur]^{ep}
硕躯蝎属 Genus *Megacormus* Karsch, 1881 [*mega-* (large) + *cormus* (trunk)]^{mo}
 弗氏硕躯蝎 *Megacormus franckei* Kovařík, 2019 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
 哲氏硕躯蝎 *Megacormus gertschi* Díaz Nájera, 1966 [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}
 多疣硕躯蝎 *Megacormus granosus* (Gervais, 1843) [*gran-* (grain) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 戈氏硕躯蝎 *Megacormus grubbsi* Sissom, 1994 [Andrew Grubbs]^{ep}
 饰缘硕躯蝎 *Megacormus segmentatus* Pocock, 1900 [*segment-* (segment) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 希丘硕躯蝎 *Megacormus xichu* González-Santillán, González-Ruiz & Escobedo-Morales, 2017 [Xichú, a city in Guanajuato State, Mexico]^{lo}
邻蛮蝎属 Genus *Plesiochactas* Pocock, 1900 [*plesio-* (near) + *Chactas*]^{ta}
 瘦弱邻蛮蝎 *Plesiochactas dilutus* (Karsch, 1881) [weak, diluted, perfect passive participle of *diluo* (dilute)]^{mo}
 米氏邻蛮蝎 *Plesiochactas mitchelli* Soleglad, 1976 [Robert Wetsel Mitchell]^{ep}
 巴氏邻蛮蝎 *Plesiochactas vasquezi* Trujillo & Armas, 2012 [Carlos Vásquez Almazán]^{ep}
四孔蝎属 Genus *Tetratrichobothrius* Birula, 1917 [*tetra-* (four) + *trichobothrius* (trichobothria)]^{mo}
 黄尾四孔蝎 *Tetratrichobothrius flavicaudis* (DeGeer, 1778) [*flavi-* (yellow) + *cauda* (tail)]^{chr&mo}
穴硕躯蝎属 Genus *Troglocormus* Francke, 1981 [*troglo-* (cave) + *Megacormus*]^{bi&ta}
 盲穴硕躯蝎 *Troglocormus ciego* Francke, 1981 [Spanish for “blind”]^{au(mo)}
 威氏穴硕躯蝎 *Troglocormus willis* Francke, 1981 [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}
厚尾蝎科 Family *Hadruridae* Stahnke, 1974
厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hadrurus* Thorell, 1876 [*hadr-* (thick, strong) + *uro-* (tail)]^{mo}
 安沙波利哥厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus anzaborrego* Soleglad, Fet & Lowe, 2011 [Anza-Borrego Desert State Park, California, USA]^{lo}
 亚利桑那厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus arizonensis* Ewing, 1928
 模式亚种 *H. arizonensis arizonensis* Ewing, 1928 [Arizona, USA]^{lo}
 南方亚种 *H. arizonensis austrinus* Williams, 1970 [*austr-* (south) + *-inus* (pertaining to)]^{cho}
 同色厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus concolorous* Stahnke, 1969 [*con-* (same) + *colorous* (colored)]^{mo}
 鬃毛厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus hirsutus* (Wood, 1863) [hairy, bristled]^{mo}
 黯色厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus obscurus* Williams, 1970 [dark]^{chr}
 平氏厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus pinteri* Stahnke, 1969 [P. J. Pinter]^{ep}
 栗色厚尾蝎 *Hadrurus spadix* Stahnke, 1940 [chestnut-colored]^{chr}
霍氏厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hoffmannihadrurus* Fet & Soleglad, 2004 [Carlos Cristian Hoffmann + *Hadrurus*]^{ep&ta}
 阿兹特克霍氏厚尾蝎 *Hoffmannihadrurus aztecus* (Pocock, 1902) [Aztecs, people of Mexico at the time of the Spanish conquest]^{et}
 哲氏霍氏厚尾蝎 *Hoffmannihadrurus gertschi* (Soleglad, 1976) [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}

半蝎科 Family **Hemiscorpiidae** Pocock, 1893半蝎属 Genus **Hemiscorpius** Peters, 1861 [*hemi-* (half) + *scorpius* (Latin for “scorpion”)]^{mo}

- 棘尾半蝎 *Hemiscorpius acanthocercus* Monod & Lourenço, 2005 [*acantho-* (spine, thorn) + *cercus* (tail)]^{mo}
 阿拉伯半蝎 *Hemiscorpius arabicus* Pocock, 1899 [Arabian Peninsula]^{to}
 埃及半蝎 *Hemiscorpius egyptiensis* Lourenço, 2011 [Egypt]^{to}
 瘦螯半蝎 *Hemiscorpius enischnochela* Monod & Lourenço, 2005 [*enishno-* (thin) + *chela* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
 镰指半蝎 *Hemiscorpius falcifer* Lowe, 2010 [*falc-* (sickle) + *-ifer* (bearing)]^{mo}
 鞭尾半蝎 *Hemiscorpius flagelliraptor* Lowe, 2010 [*flagelli-* (whip) + *raptor* (ravisher)]^{mo&er}
 盖氏半蝎 *Hemiscorpius gaillardi* (Vachon, 1974) [Maurice Gaillard]^{ep}
 卡什凯半蝎 *Hemiscorpius kashkayi* Karatas & Gharkheloo, 2013 [Kashkay, or Qashqai, nomadic Turks living in Iran]^{et}
 纤尾半蝎 *Hemiscorpius lepturus* Peters, 1861 [*lept-* (narrow) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 曼氏半蝎 *Hemiscorpius maindroni* Kraepelin, 1900 [Maurice Maindron]^{ep}
 诺氏半蝎 *Hemiscorpius novaki* Kovařík & Mazuch, 2011 [Pavel Novák]^{ep}
 波斯半蝎 *Hemiscorpius persicus* Birula, 1903 [Persia (now Iran)]^{pal}
 沙氏半蝎 *Hemiscorpius shahii* Kovařík, Navidpour & Soleglad, 2017 [Mehran Shahi]^{ep}
 索科特拉半蝎 *Hemiscorpius socotranus* Pocock, 1899 [Socotra Island, Yemen]^{to}
 索马里半蝎 *Hemiscorpius somalicus* Lourenço, 2011 [Somalia]^{to}
 泰氏半蝎 *Hemiscorpius tellinii* Borelli, 1904 [Achilles Tellini]^{ep}

异蝎科 Family **Heteroscorpionidae** Kraepelin, 1905异蝎属 Genus **Heteroscorpion** Birula, 1903 [*hetero-* (different) + *scorpion*]^{mo}

- 古氏异蝎 *Heteroscorpion goodmani* Lourenço, 1996 [Steven Goodman]^{ep}
 凯氏异蝎 *Heteroscorpion kaii* Lourenço & Goodman, 2009 [Kai Schütte]^{ep}
 克氏异蝎 *Heteroscorpion kraepelini* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [Karl Kraepelin]^{ep}
 巨型异蝎 *Heteroscorpion magnus* Lourenço & Goodman, 2002 [great]^{mo}
 似后棘异蝎 *Heteroscorpion opisthacanthoides* (Kraepelin, 1896) [*Opisthacanthus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{aa}
 拉氏异蝎 *Heteroscorpion raselimananai* Lourenço & Goodman, 2004 [Achille Raselimanana]^{ep}

链尾蝎科 Family **Hormuridae** Laurie, 1896螯戮蝎属 Genus **Cheloctonus** Pocock, 1892 [*chelo-* (hand, chela) + *-ctonus* (killer)]^{mo&er}

- 煤色螯戮蝎 *Cheloctonus anthracinus* Pocock, 1899
 模式亚种 *C. anthracinus anthracinus* Pocock, 1899 [*anthrac-* (charcoal) + *-inus* (pertaining to)]^{chr}
 沃氏亚种 *C. anthracinus warreni* Hewitt, 1931 [Warren G. Rump]^{ep}
 粗螯螯戮蝎 *Cheloctonus crassimanus* (Pocock, 1896)
 模式亚种 *C. crassimanus crassimanus* (Pocock, 1896) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 扁平亚种 *C. crassimanus depressus* Hewitt, 1918 [flattened]^{mo}
 光滑螯戮蝎 *Cheloctonus glaber* Kraepelin, 1896 [smooth]^{mo}
 中介螯戮蝎 *Cheloctonus intermedius* Hewitt, 1912 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{aa}
 琼氏螯戮蝎 *Cheloctonus jonesii* Pocock, 1892
 模式亚种 *C. jonesii jonesii* Pocock, 1892 [C. R. Jones]^{ep}
 雕纹亚种 *C. jonesii sculpturatus* Hewitt, 1914 [sculptured; perfect passive participle of *sculptura* (sculpture)]^{mo}

螯猛蝎属 Genus **Chiromachetes** Pocock, 1899 [*chiro-* (hand, pincer) + *machetes* (fighter, warrior)]^{mo&er}

- 斐氏螯猛蝎 *Chiromachetes fergusonii* Pocock, 1899 [Harold Stuart Ferguson]^{ep}
 英勇螯猛蝎 *Chiromachetes parakrami* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Ketkar, Gowande, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020 [*parakram*, Sanskrit for “act of valour”; Baji Prabhu Deshpande and his army defended his king against the Sultanate of Bijapur at Pavan Khind, near the type locality; a metonym]^{au(to)}
 拉氏螯猛蝎 *Chiromachetes ramdasswamii* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Ketkar, Gowande, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020 [Samartha Ramdas Swami]^{ep}
 萨亚德里螯猛蝎 *Chiromachetes sahyadriensis* Mirza, Sanap & Zambre, 2015 [Sahyadri Hills, Mts. Western Ghats, India]^{to}
 蒂鲁帕蒂螯猛蝎 *Chiromachetes tirupati* Lourenço, 1997 [Tirupati, a city in Andhra Pradesh State, India]^{to}

螯勇蝎属 Genus **Chiromachus** Pocock, 1893 [*chiro-* (hand, pincer) + *machus* (fighter, warrior)]^{mo&er}

- 黄足螯勇蝎 *Chiromachus ochropus* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [*chro-* (yellow ochre) + *-pus* (foot)]^{chr&mo}

冥神蝎属 Genus **Hadogenes** Kraepelin, 1894 [Ἅδης (Hades), god of the underworld in Greek mythology]^{de}

- 南非冥神蝎 *Hadogenes austroafricanus* Penther, 1900 [*austro-* (south) + *africanus* (African)]^{to}
 双色冥神蝎 *Hadogenes bicolor* Purcell, 1899 [two-colored]^{mo}
 纤细冥神蝎 *Hadogenes gracilis* Hewitt, 1909 [gracile]^{mo}
 具疣冥神蝎 *Hadogenes granulatus* Purcell, 1901 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 根氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes gunningi* Purcell, 1899 [Jan Willem Boudewijn Gunning]^{ep}
 哈氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes hahni* (Peters, 1862) [Carl Wilhelm Hahn]^{ep}

- 劳氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes lawrencei* Newlands, 1972 [Reginald Frederick Lawrence]^{ep}
 长掌冥神蝎 *Hadogenes longimanus* Prendini, 2001 [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 小型冥神蝎 *Hadogenes minor* Purcell, 1899 [small-sized]^{mo}
 纽氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes newlandsi* Prendini, 2001 [Gerald Newlands]^{ep}
 寡齿冥神蝎 *Hadogenes paucidens* Pocock, 1896 [*pauci-* (few) + *dens* (tooth)]^{mo}
 叶形冥神蝎 *Hadogenes phyllodes* (Thorell, 1876) [*phyll-* (leaf) + *-odes* (resembling)]^{mo}
 多孔冥神蝎 *Hadogenes polytrichobothrius* Prendini, 2006 [*poly-* (many) + *trichobothrius* (trichobothria)]^{mo}
 索特潘斯山冥神蝎 *Hadogenes soutpansbergensis* Prendini, 2006 [Soutpansberg District, South Africa]^{io}
 牧者冥神蝎 *Hadogenes tityrus* (Simon, 1888) [*Tityrus*, name of a sheperd in Greek mythology]^{my}
 鬃尾冥神蝎 *Hadogenes trichiurus* (Gervais, 1843)
 模式亚种 *H. trichiurus trichiurus* (Gervais, 1843) [*trichi-* (hair) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 南非亚种 *H. trichiurus caffer* Hewitt, 1918 [from *ka ir*, Arabic for “non-believer”, a historic term, now derogatory for black South Africans]^{au(ce)}
 似纤细亚种 *H. trichiurus gracilioides* Hewitt, 1918 [*Hadogenes gracilis* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
 淡色亚种 *H. trichiurus pallidus* Pocock, 1898 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
 侏儒亚种 *H. trichiurus parvus* Hewitt, 1925 [dwarf]^{mo}
 维氏亚种 *H. trichiurus wernerii* Fet, 1997 [Franz Werner]^{ep}
 怀氏亚种 *H. trichiurus whitei* Purcell, 1899 [George White]^{ep}
 穴居冥神蝎 *Hadogenes troglodytes* (Peters, 1861)
 模式亚种 *H. troglodytes troglodytes* (Peters, 1861) [cave-dweller (*troglo-* (cave) + *-dytes* (enterer))]^{bi}
 粗尾亚种 *H. troglodytes crassicaudatus* Hewitt, 1918 [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *caud-* (tail) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 具齿亚种 *H. troglodytes dentatus* Hewitt, 1918 [*dent-* (tooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 莱塔巴亚种 *H. troglodytes letabensis* Werner, 1933 [Letaba Camp, Kruger National Park, South Africa]^{io}
 马托波斯亚种 *H. troglodytes matoppoanus* Hewitt, 1918 [Matopos Hills, Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe)]^{io}
 魏氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes weygoldti* Stáhlavský, Štundlová, Lowe, Stockmann & Kovařík, 2018 [Peter Weygoldt]^{ep}
 祖鲁冥神蝎 *Hadogenes zuluanus* Lawrence, 1937 [Zululand Municipality, KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa]^{io}
 藏氏冥神蝎 *Hadogenes zumpti* Newlands & Cantrell, 1985 [Fritz Konrad Ernst Zump]^{ep}
 类链尾蝎属 Genus *Hormiops* Fage, 1933 [*hormi-* (necklace) + *-ops* (eye)? *Hormurus* + *-ops* (resembling)]^{mo/ta}
 戴氏类链尾蝎 *Hormiops davidovi* Fage, 1933 [Konstantin Nikolaevich Davydoff (Dawydoff, Davydov)]^{ep}
 无支类链尾蝎 *Hormiops infulcra* Monod, 2014 [*in-* (without) + *fulcra* (fulcrum)]^{mo}
 链尾蝎属 Genus *Hormurus* Thorell, 1876 [*horm-* (necklace) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 薄荷岛链尾蝎 *Hormurus boholiensis* Kraepelin, 1914 [Bohol Island, Philippines]^{io}
 瘦肢链尾蝎 *Hormurus ischnoryctes* Monod & Prendini, 2013 [*ischn-* (thin) + *oryctes* (digger, here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
 卡氏链尾蝎 *Hormurus karschii* (Keyserling, 1885) [Ferdinand Karsch]^{ep}
 筒指链尾蝎 *Hormurus litodactylus* (Monod & Volschenk, 2004) [*lito-* (simple) + *dactylus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}
 长掌链尾蝎 *Hormurus longimanus* (Locket, 1995) [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 长螯链尾蝎 *Hormurus macrochela* Monod, 2013 [*macro-* (long) + *chela* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
 新喀里多尼亚链尾蝎 *Hormurus neocaledonicus* (Simon, 1877) [New Caledonia]^{io}
 强肢链尾蝎 *Hormurus ochyroscapter* Monod, 2013 [*ochyro-* (strong) + *scapter* (digger, here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
 五孔链尾蝎 *Hormurus penta* (Francke & Lourenço, 1991) [five; refers to five ventral trichobothria on the pedipalp patella]^{mo}
 珀氏链尾蝎 *Hormurus polisorum* (Volschenk, Locket & Harvey, 2001) [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}
 卫格岛链尾蝎 *Hormurus waigiensis* (Gervais 1843) [Waigi Island (now Waigeo), western New Guinea, Indonesia]^{nal}
 毒勇蝎属 Genus *Iomachus* Pocock, 1893 [*i (os)-* (poison, venom) + *machus* (fighter, warrior)]^{chad&er}
 博拉纳毒勇蝎 *Iomachus borana* (Di Caporiacco, 1939) [Borana Zone, Ethiopia]^{io}
 因氏毒勇蝎 *Iomachus ineichi* Lourenço, 2020 [Ivan Ineich]^{ep}
 滑首毒勇蝎 *Iomachus laeviceps* (Pocock, 1890) [*laevi-* (smooth) + *-ceps* (head)]^{mo}
 马拉巴毒勇蝎 *Iomachus malabarensis* Pocock, 1900 [Malabar Region, India]^{io}
 光泽毒勇蝎 *Iomachus nitidus* Pocock, 1900 [*niti-* (to shine) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 光滑毒勇蝎 *Iomachus politus* Pocock, 1896
 模式亚种 *I. politus politus* Pocock, 1896 [polished, perfect passive participle of *polio* (polish)]^{mo}
 西部亚种 *I. politus occidentalis* Lourenço, 2003 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
 小斑毒勇蝎 *Iomachus punctulatus* Pocock, 1897 [*punct-* (spot, point) + *-ula* (diminutive suffix) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 苏尔加纳毒勇蝎 *Iomachus surgani* (Bastawade, 1986) [Surgana, a town in Maharashtra State, India]^{io}
 滑螯蝎属 Genus *Liocheles* Sundevall, 1833 [*lio-* (smooth) + *cheles* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
 南亚滑螯蝎 *Liocheles australasiae* (Fabricius, 1775) ☆ [*austral-* (southern) + *asiae* (Asia)]^{cho}
 长掌滑螯蝎 *Liocheles longimanus* (Werner, 1939) [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 黑足滑螯蝎 *Liocheles nigripes* (Pocock, 1897) [*nigri-* (black) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}

- 猩红滑螫蝎 *Liocheles oranghutan* Ythier & Richard, 2020 [pun on the sympatric orangutan and color of the holotype male]^{bi&mo}
 沙氏滑螫蝎 *Liocheles schalleri* Mirza, 2017 [George Beals Schaller]^{ep}
- 后棘蝎属 Genus *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861 [*opisth-* (behind) + *acanthus* (spine, thorn)]^{mo}
- 非洲后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus africanus* Simon, 1876
 模式亚种 *O. africanus africanus* Simon, 1876 [Africa]^{lo}
 淡色亚种 *O. africanus pallidus* Lourenço, 2003 [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
- 安班加后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus ambanja* Lourenço, 2014 [Ambanja, Madagascar]^{lo}
 安多亚耶拉后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus andohahela* Lourenço, 2014 [Andohahela National Park, Madagascar]^{lo}
 安齐拉纳纳后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus antsiranana* Lourenço, 2014 [Antsiranana Province, Madagascar]^{lo}
 粗糙后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus asper* (Peters, 1861) [rough]^{mo}
 奥塔纳后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus autanensis* González-Sponga, 2004 [Autana River, Venezuela]^{lo}
 巴苏陀兰后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus basutus* Lawrence, 1955 [Basutoland (now Lesotho)]^{pal}
 玻氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus borboremai* Lourenço & Fé, 2003 [Carlos Augusto Telles de Borborema]^{ep}
 短尾后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus brevicauda* Rojas-Runjaic, Borges & Armas, 2008 [*brevi-* (short) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
 好望角后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus capensis* Thorell, 1876 [Cape of Good Hope, South Africa]^{lo}
 卡雅布后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus cayaporum* Vellard, 1932 [Kayapo people from Brazil]^{et}
 达瑞纳后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus darainensis* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [Daraina town in Madagascar]^{lo}
 分离后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus diremptus* (Karsch, 1879) [separated, perfect passive participle of *dirimo* (separate)]^{mo/cho}
 高突后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus elatus* (Gervais, 1844) [elevated, perfect passive participle of *effero* (lift up)]^{mo}
 法氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus faillei* Lourenço & Wilmé, 2019 [Arnaud Faille]^{ep}
 艾氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus heurtaultae* Lourenço, 1980 [Jacqueline Heurtault]^{ep}
 滑足后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus laevipes* (Pocock, 1893) [*laevi-* (smooth) + *-pes* (foot)]^{mo}
 拉氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus lamorali* Lourenço, 1981 [Bruno Ho Lamoral]^{ep}
 拉瓦索阿后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus lavasoa* Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2016 [Lavasoa humid forest, Toliara Province, Madagascar]^{lo}
 卢氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus lecomtei* (Lucas, 1858) [Aubry Lecomte]^{ep}
 纤尾后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus lepturus* (Beauvois, 1805) [*lept-* (narrow) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 卢氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus lucienneae* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [Lucienne Wilmé]^{ep}
 斑后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus maculatus* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [*macula-* (spot, stain) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 马达加斯加后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus madagascariensis* Kraepelin, 1894 [Madagascar]^{lo}
 米氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus milloti* Lourenço & Goodman, 2008 [Jacques Millot]^{ep}
 珀氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus pauliani* Lourenço & Goodman, 2008 [Renaud Paulian]^{ep}
 黑后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus piceus* Lourenço & Goodman, 2006 [*pic-* (pitch) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
 捕鱼者后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus piscatorius* Lawrence, 1955 [*pisc-* (fish) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns) + *-ius* (suffix forming adjectives)]^{er}
 皱首后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus rugiceps* Pocock, 1897 [*rugi-* (wrinkle) + *-ceps* (head)]^{mo}
 多褶后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus rugulosus* Pocock, 1896 [*rug-* (wrinkle) + *-ulo* (diminutive suffix) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 苏里南后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus surinamensis* Lourenço, 2017 [Suriname]^{lo}
 泰坦后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus titanus* Lourenço, Wilmé & Waeber, 2018 [titanic]^{mo}
 巴氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus valerioi* Lourenço, 1980 [Carlos E. Valerio]^{ep}
 强壮后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus validus* Thorell, 1876 [*val-* (be strong) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
 魏氏后棘蝎 *Opisthacanthus weyrauchi* Mello-Leitão, 1948 [Wolfgang Karl Weyrauch]^{ep}
- 古螫戮蝎属 Genus *Palaeocheloctonus* Lourenço, 1996 [*palaeo-* (ancient) + *Cheloctonus*]^{ta}
- 珀氏古螫戮蝎 *Palaeocheloctonus pauliani* Lourenço, 1996 [Renaud Paulian]^{ep}
 北方古螫戮蝎 *Palaeocheloctonus septentrionalis* Lourenço & Wilmé, 2015 [northern (*septentrio-* (north) + *-alis* (pertaining to))] ^{cho}
- 藏毒勇蝎属 Genus *Tibetiomachus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Tibet + *Iomachus*]^{to&ta}
- 喜山藏毒勇蝎 *Tibetiomachus himalayensis* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 ★ [Himalaya Mts.]^{lo}
- 毒尾蝎科 Family *Iuridae* Thorell, 1876
- 祭司蝎属 Genus *Calchas* Birula, 1899
 [Κάλχας (Calchas), the famous soothsayer among the Greeks at the time of the Trojan War]^{my}
- 安氏祭司蝎 *Calchas anlasi* Yağmur, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2013 [Sinan Anlaş]^{ep}
 比氏祭司蝎 *Calchas birulai* Fet, Soleglad & Kovařík, 2009 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
 寇氏祭司蝎 *Calchas kosswigi* Yağmur, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2013 [Curt Kosswig]^{ep}
 佩氏祭司蝎 *Calchas nordmanni* Birula, 1899 [Alexander von Nordmann]^{ep}
- 毒尾蝎属 Genus *Iurus* Thorell, 1876 [*i (os)-* (poison, venom) + *urus* (tail)]^{cha&mo}
- 德干毒尾蝎 *Iurus dekanum* (Roewer, 1943) [Deccan Plateau, India]^{lo}
 杜氏毒尾蝎 *Iurus dufourei* (Brullé, 1832) [Jean-Marie Léon Dufour]^{ep}
 金氏毒尾蝎 *Iurus kinzelbachi* Kovařík, Fet, Soleglad & Yağmur, 2010 [Ragnar Kinzelbach]^{ep}

- 新祭司蝎属 Genus *Neocalchas* Yağmur, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2013 [*neo-* (new) + *Calchas*]^{ta}
 戈氏新祭司蝎 *Neocalchas gruberi* (Fet, Soleglad & Kovařík, 2009) [Jürgen Gruber]^{ep}
- 原毒尾蝎属 Genus *Protoiurus* Soleglad, Fet, Kovařík & Yağmur, 2012 [*proto-* (first) + *Iurus*]^{ta}
 亚洲原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus asiaticus* (Birula, 1903) [Asian]^{cho}
 卡氏原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus kadleci* (Kovařík, Fet, Soleglad & Yağmur, 2010) [Stanislav Kadlec]^{ep}
 克氏原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus kraepelini* (von Ubisch, 1922) [Karl Kraepelin]^{ep}
 昆氏原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus kumhutasu* Yağmur, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík 2015 [Yusuf Kumlutaş]^{ep}
 罗德岛原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus rhodiensis* Soleglad, Fet, Kovařík & Yağmur, 2012 [Rhodes Island, Greece]^{to}
 斯氏原毒尾蝎 *Protoiurus stathiae* Soleglad, Fet, Kovařík & Yağmur, 2012 [Iasmi Stathi]^{ep}
- 皱齿蝎科 Family **Rugodentidae** Bastawade, Sureshan & Radhakrishnan, 2005
 皱齿蝎属 Genus *Rugodentus* Bastawade, Sureshan & Radhakrishnan, 2005 [*rugo-* (wrinkle) + *dent* (tooth)]^{mo}
 喀拉拉皱齿蝎 *Rugodentus keralaensis* Bastawade, Sureshan & Radhakrishnan, 2005 [Kerala State, India]^{to}
- 蝎科 Family **Scorpionidae** Latreille, 1802
 半岛异距蝎属 Genus *Chersonesometrus* Couzijn, 1978 [*chersoneso-* (peninsula) + *Heterometrus*]^{bi&ta}
 巴氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus bastawadei* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Deshbhushan Bastawade]^{ep}
 贝氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2004) [Janet Beccaloni]^{ep}
 黄足半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus fulvipes* (C. L. Koch, 1837) [*fulvi-* (yellow) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
 亨氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus hendersoni* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [John Robertson Henderson]^{ep}
 马德拉斯半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus madraspatensis* (Pocock, 1900) [Madras (Chenna), Tamil Nadu State, India]^{to}
 纳氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus nathanorum* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Prabala Susai Nathan]^{ep}
 盔掌半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus pelekomanus* (Couzijn, 1981) [*peleko-* (helmet) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 希氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus shivashankari* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Tirumani Shivashankar]^{ep}
 黯色半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus tristis* (Henderson, 1919) [melancholic, dark]^{chr}
 罗氏半岛异距蝎 *Chersonesometrus wroughtoni* (Pocock, 1899) [Robert Charles Wroughton]^{ep}
- 德干异距蝎属 Genus *Deccanometrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Deccan Plateau + *Heterometrus*]^{to&ta}
 孟加拉德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus bengalensis* (C. L. Koch, 1841) ☆ [Bengal, now in India and Bangladesh]^{to}
 宽掌德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus latimanus* (Pocock, 1894) [*lati-* (wide) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 滑尾德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus liurus* (Pocock, 1897) [*li-* (smooth) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
 黯色德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus obscurus* (Couzijn, 1981) [dark]^{chr}
 勒氏德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus phipsoni* (Pocock, 1893) [Emma Phipson]^{ep}
 尤氏德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus ubicki* (Kovařík, 2004) [Darrell Ubick]^{ep}
 黄足德干异距蝎 *Deccanometrus xanthopus* (Pocock, 1897) [*xantho-* (yellow) + *-pus* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 巨异距蝎属 Genus *Gigantometrus* Couzijn, 1978 [*giganto-* (giant) + *Heterometrus*]^{mo&ta}
 斯氏巨异距蝎 *Gigantometrus swammerdami* (Simon, 1872) [Jan Swammerdam]^{ep}
 泰坦巨异距蝎 *Gigantometrus titanicus* (Couzijn, 1981) [titanic]^{mo}
- 异距蝎属 Genus *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 [*hetero-* (different) + *metrus* (measurement)]^{mo}
 蓝灰异距蝎 *Heterometrus glaucus* (Thorell, 1876) [glaucous, blue-grey]^{chr}
 光滑异距蝎 *Heterometrus laevigatus* (Thorell, 1876) [lightened, perfect passive participle of *levigo* (lighten)]^{mo}
 老挝异距蝎 *Heterometrus laoticus* Couzijn, 1981 [Laos]^{to}
 长掌异距蝎 *Heterometrus longimanus* (Herbst, 1800) [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 佩氏异距蝎 *Heterometrus petersii* (Thorell, 1876) [Wilhelm Carl Hartwig Peters]^{ep}
 林神异距蝎 *Heterometrus silenus* (Simon, 1884) ◉ [Σειληνός (Silenus), god of the forests in Greek mythology]^{de}
 携刺异距蝎 *Heterometrus spinifer* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [*spin-* (spine) + *-ifer* (bearing)]^{mo}
 托氏异距蝎 *Heterometrus thorellii* (Pocock, 1892) [Tord Tamerlan Teodor Thorell]^{ep}
- 爪哇异距蝎属 Genus *Javanimetrus* Couzijn, 1981 [Java + *Heterometrus*]^{to&ta}
 蓝青爪哇异距蝎 *Javanimetrus cyaneus* (C. L. Koch, 1836) [*cyan* (greenish blue) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
- 后目蝎属 Genus *Opisththalmus* C. L. Koch, 1837 [*opist-* (behind) + *ophthalamus* (eye)]^{mo}
 灼色后目蝎 *Opisththalmus adustus* Kraepelin, 1908 [burnt-colored, perfect passive participle of *aduro* (scorch)]^{chr}
 沙足后目蝎 *Opisththalmus ammopus* Lamoral, 1980 [*ammo-* (sand) + *-pus* (foot)]^{mo}
 黯黑后目蝎 *Opisththalmus ater* Purcell, 1898 [black]^{chr}
 旱地后目蝎 *Opisththalmus austerus* Karsch, 1879 [austere, harsh, dry]^{bi}
 伯氏后目蝎 *Opisththalmus boehmi* (Kraepelin, 1896) [Richard Boehm]^{ep}
 短尾后目蝎 *Opisththalmus brevicauda* Lawrence, 1928 [*brevi-* (short) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
 好望角后目蝎 *Opisththalmus capensis* (Herbst, 1800) [Cape of Good Hope, South Africa]^{to}
 具棱后目蝎 *Opisththalmus carinatus* (Peters, 1861) [*carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
 凹掌后目蝎 *Opisththalmus cavimanus* Lawrence, 1928 [*cavi-* (concave) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 查氏后目蝎 *Opisththalmus chaperi* Simon, 1880 [Chaper]^{ep}

- 金耀后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus chrysites* Lawrence, 1967 [gold]^{chr}
- 寇氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus coetzei* Lamoral, 1979 [Cornelius Gerhardus Coetzee]^{ep}
- 秀雅后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus concinnus* Newlands, 1972 [elegant, neat]^{mo}
- 粗螯后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus crassimanus* Purcell, 1899 [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 菲氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus fitsimensi* Hewitt, 1935 [Frederick William FitzSimons]^{ep}
- 渐黄后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus flavescens* Purcell, 1898 [*flav-* (yellow) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}
- 掘洞者后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus fossor* Purcell, 1898 [*foss-* (dig) + *-or* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
- 黯足后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus fuscipes* Purcell, 1898 [*fusci-* (dark brown) + *-pes* (foot)]^{mo}
- 隆尾后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus gibbericauda* Lamoral, 1979 [*gibberi-* (gibbous) + *-cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 巨人后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus gigas* Purcell, 1898 [a giant]^{mo}
- 秃额后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus glabrifrons* Peters, 1861 [*glabri-* (bald, smooth) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 疣尾后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus granicauda* Purcell, 1898 [*grani-* (grain) + *-cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 疣额后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus granifrons* Pocock, 1896 [*grani-* (grain) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 哈克氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus haackei* Lawrence, 1966 [Wulf Dietrich Haacke]^{ep}
- 哈氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus harpei* Harington, 2001 [Micajah Harpe]^{ep}
- 霍氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus holmi* (Lawrence, 1969) [Erik Holm]^{ep}
- 中间后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus intercedens* Kraepelin, 1908 [interceding, present active participle of *intercedo* (intercede)]^{ta}
- 中介后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus intermedius* Kraepelin, 1894 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta}
- 詹氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus jenseni* (Lamoral, 1972) [M. K. and Rolf A. C. Jensen]^{ep}
- 卡鲁后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus karrooensis* Purcell, 1898 [Great Karroo, South Africa]^{to}
- 凯兰后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus keilandsi* Hewitt, 1914 [Keilands, South Africa]^{to}
- 拉氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus lamorali* Prendini, 2000 [Bruno Ho Lamoral]^{ep}
- 宽尾后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus laticauda* Purcell, 1898 [*lati-* (wide) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 宽掌后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus latimanus* C. L. Koch, 1841 [*lati-* (wide) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 吼鸣后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus latro* Thorell, 1876 [to howl, bark, roar]^{er}
- 劳氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus lawrencei* Newlands, 1969 [Reginald Frederick Lawrence]^{ep}
- 莱氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus leipoldti* Purcell, 1898 [Christiaan Frederik Louis Leipoldt]^{ep}
- 海岸后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus litoralis* Lawrence, 1955 [*litor-* (shore) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 长尾后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus longicauda* Purcell, 1899 [*longi-* (long) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 萝氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus lornae* Lamoral, 1979 [Lorna Ferguson]^{ep}
- 卢西拉后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus luciranus* Lawrence, 1959 [Lucira Commune, Angola]^{to}
- 枯瘦后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus macer* Thorell, 1876 [lean, skinny]^{mo}
- 光首后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus nitidiceps* Pocock, 1896 [*niti-* (to shine) + *-idi-* (tending to) + *-ceps* (head)]^{mo}
- 期望后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus opinatus* (Simon, 1888) [supposed, expected, perfect participle of *opinor* (imagine, deem)]^{ta}
- 淡足后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pallipes* C. L. Koch, 1842 [*pall-* (pale) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
- 派氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pattisoni* Purcell, 1899 [R. Pattison]^{ep}
- 潘氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus penrithorum* Lamoral, 1979 [Mary-Lou and Mike Penrith]^{ep}
- 琵氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus peringueyi* Purcell, 1898 [Louis Péringuey]^{ep}
- 着色后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pictus* Kraepelin, 1894 [colored, colorful]^{mo}
- 多齿后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pluridens* Hewitt, 1918 [*pluri-* (many) + *dens* (tooth)]^{mo}
- 掠夺者后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus praedo* Thorell, 1876 [robber]^{er}
- 好斗后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pugnax* Thorell, 1876 [pugnacious, *pug-* (fight) + *-ax* (inclined to)]^{er}
- 侏儒后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus pygmaeus* Lamoral, 1979 [*pygma-* (pygmy) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{mo}
- 糙额后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus scabrifrons* Hewitt, 1918 [*scabri-* (rough) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 施氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus schlechteri* Purcell, 1898 [Max Schlechter]^{ep}
- 舒氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus schultzei* Kraepelin, 1908 [Leonhard Schultze]^{ep}
- 鬃额后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus setifrons* Lawrence, 1961 [*seti-* (seta) + *frons* (forehead)]^{mo}
- 乌加后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus ugabensis* Hewitt, 1934 [Ugab River, Namibia]^{to}
- 耶氏后目蝎 *Opisthophthalmus wahlbergii* Thorell, 1876 [Johan August Wahlberg]^{ep}
- 博氏惧蝎属 Genus *Pandiborellius* Rossi, 2015 [*Pandinus* + Giovanni Alfredo Borelli]^{ta&ep}
- 阿拉伯博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius arabicus* (Kraepelin, 1894) [Saudi Arabia]^{to}
- 阿瓦什博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius awashensis* (Kovářik, 2012) [Awash, a town in Ethiopia]^{to}
- 阿法尔博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius igdu* Kovářik, Lowe, Soleglad & Plíšková, 2017 [Afar for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 岛屿博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius insularis* Kovářik, Lowe, Soleglad & Plíšková, 2017 [*insul-* (island) + *-aris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 兰氏博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius lanzai* (Rossi, 2015) [Benedetto (“Bettino”) Lanza]^{ep}
- 玛氏博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius magretti* (Borelli, 1901) [Paolo Magretti]^{ep}
- 梅德博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius meidensis* (Karsch, 1879) [Meid, a village in Somalia]^{to}

- 尼氏博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius nistriae* (Rossi, 2014) [Annamaria Nistri]^{ep}
 珀氏博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius percivali* (Pocock, 1902) [Arthur Blayney Percival]^{ep}
 索马里兰博氏惧蝎 *Pandiborellius somalilandus* (Kovařík, 2012) [Somaliland]^{eo}
 似惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinoides* Fet, 1997 [*Pandinus* + *-oides* (resembling)]^{ta}
 凹掌似惧蝎 *Pandinoides cavimanus* (Pocock, 1888) [*cavi-* (concave) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
 杜氏似惧蝎 *Pandinoides duffmackayi* Prendini, 2016 [Alexander Duff-Mackay]^{ep}
 军人似惧蝎 *Pandinoides militaris* (Pocock, 1900) [*mili-* (soldier) + *-arius* (suffix forming adjectives)]^{er}
 类惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinops* Birula, 1913 [*Pandinus* + *-ops* (appearance)]^{ta}
 好斗类惧蝎 *Pandinops bellicosus* (L. Koch, 1875) [*bellic-* (warlike, bellicose) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{er}
 克氏类惧蝎 *Pandinops cole* (Pocock, 1896) [Edith Cole]^{ep}
 厄立特里亚类惧蝎 *Pandinops eritreaensis* (Kovařík, 2003) [Eritrea]^{eo}
 弗氏类惧蝎 *Pandinops friedrichi* Kovařík, 2016 [Stefan Friedrich]^{ep}
 宽螯类惧蝎 *Pandinops platycheles* (Werner, 1916) [*platy-* (wide) + *cheles* (hand, chela)]^{mo}
 波氏类惧蝎 *Pandinops pococki* (Kovařík, 2000) [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
 拳击手类惧蝎 *Pandinops pugilator* (Pocock, 1900) [*pugil-* (boxer) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
 徒氏类惧蝎 *Pandinops turieli* Kovařík, 2016 [Carlos Turiel]^{ep}
 仿惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinopsis* Vachon, 1974 [*Pandinus* + *-opsis* (appearance)]^{ta}
 独裁者仿惧蝎 *Pandinopsis dictator* (Pocock, 1888) [*dict-* (dictate) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
 尾惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinurus* Fet, 1997 [*Pandinus* + *urus* (tail)]^{ta&mo}
 阿法尔尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus afar* Kovařík, Lowe, Soleglad & Plíšková, 2017 [Afar, people of Ethiopia, Djibouti and Eritrea]^{et}
 阿氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus awalei* Kovařík, Lowe & Elmi, 2020 [Ahmed Ibrahim Awale]^{ep}
 奚氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus citernii* (Borelli, 1919) [Carlo Citerni]^{ep}
 致命尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus exitialis* (Pocock, 1888) [fatal, lethal, *exiti-* (destruction) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{cha}
 黄足尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus fulvipes* Kovařík, Lowe & Mazuch, 2019 [*fulvi-* (yellow) + *-pes* (foot)]^{chr&mo}
 格氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus gregoryi* (Pocock, 1896) [John Walter Gregory]^{ep}
 索马里尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus hangarale* Kovařík, Lowe, Mazuch, Awale, Štundlová & Šťáhlavský, 2017 [Somali for “big black scorpion”]^{au}
 中介尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus intermedius* (Borelli, 1919) [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta}
 柯氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus kmoniceki* Kovařík, Lowe, Mazuch, Plíšková & Šťáhlavský, 2017 [Hynek Kmoníček]^{ep}
 马氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus mazuchi* (Kovařík, 2011) [Tomas Mazuch]^{ep}
 奥罗莫尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus oromo* Kovařík, Lowe, Soleglad & Plíšková, 2017 [Oromo people of Ethiopia, northern Kenya and Somalia]^{et}
 淡色尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus pallidus* (Kraepelin, 1894) [*pall-* (pale) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
 菲氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus phillipsii* (Pocock, 1896) [Ethelbert Lort Phillips]^{ep}
 里氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus riccardoi* Rossi, 2015 [Riccardo Rossi]^{ep}
 斯氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus smithi* (Pocock, 1899) [Arthur Donaldson Smith]^{ep}
 苏丹尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus sudanicus* (Hirst, 1911) [Sudan]^{eo}
 特氏尾惧蝎 *Pandinurus trailini* (Kovařík, 2013) [Vladimir Trailin]^{ep}
 惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinus* Thorell, 1876 [*pandeious*, Greek for “fearsome, quite terrible”]^{cha}
 冈比亚惧蝎 *Pandinus gambiensis* Pocock, 1899 [Gambia]^{eo}
 统治者惧蝎 *Pandinus imperator* (C. L. Koch, 1841) [*imper-* (command) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns)]^{er}
 乌干达惧蝎 *Pandinus ugandaensis* Kovařík, 2011 [Uganda]^{eo}
 奥氏惧蝎 *Pandinus ulderigo* Rossi, 2014 [Ulderigo Rossi]^{ep}
 肢惧蝎属 Genus *Pandipalpus* Rossi, 2015 [*Pandinus* + *palpus* (here as “pedipalp”)]^{ta&mo}
 洛氏肢惧蝎 *Pandipalpus lowei* (Kovařík, 2012) [Graeme Lowe]^{ep}
 旅行者肢惧蝎 *Pandipalpus viatoris* (Pocock, 1890) [*via-* (travel) + *-ator* (suffix forming agent nouns) + *-is* (singular genitive suffix)]^{er}
 萨亚德里异距蝎属 Genus *Sahyadrimetrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Sahyadri Hills + *Heterometrus*]^{to&ta}
 巴氏萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus barberi* (Pocock, 1900) [Barber]^{ep}
 喀那拉萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus kanarensis* (Pocock, 1900) [Kanara Region, India]^{eo}
 马氏萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus mathewi* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [A. P. Mathew]^{ep}
 多褶萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus rugosus* (Couzijn, 1981) [*rug-* (wrinkle) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 粗糙萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus scaber* (Thorell, 1876) [rough]^{mo}
 提氏萨亚德里异距蝎 *Sahyadrimetrus tikaderi* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Binoy Krishna Tikader]^{ep}
 蝎属 Genus *Scorpio* Linnaeus, 1758 [Greek for “scorpion”]
 比氏蝎 *Scorpio birulai* Fet, 1997 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
 恩内迪蝎 *Scorpio ennedi* Lourenço, Duhem & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Ennedi Plateau, Chad]^{eo}

- 烟色蝎 *Scorpio fuliginosus* (Pallary, 1928) [*fuligin-* (soot) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{chr}
- 黯褐蝎 *Scorpio fuscus* (Ehrenberg, 1829) [dark brown]^{chr}
- 西方蝎 *Scorpio hesperus* Birula, 1910 [western]^{cho}
- 克氏蝎 *Scorpio kruglovi* Birula, 1910 [Alexei Fedorovich Kruglov]^{ep}
- 黯蝎/摩尔蝎 *Scorpio maurus* Linnaeus, 1758
- 模式亚种 *S. maurus maurus* Linnaeus, 1758 [dark-skinned or Moorish, probably a pun]^{chr/et}
- 贝氏亚种 *S. maurus behringsi* Schenkel, 1949 [Professor Behrings]^{ep}
- 军团亚种 *S. maurus legionis* Werner, 1936 [a legion]^{ep?}
- 施氏亚种 *S. maurus stemmleri* Schenkel, 1949 [Carl Stemmler]^{ep}
- 汤氏亚种 *S. maurus townsendi* (Pocock, 1900) [Frederick William Townsend]^{ep}
- 特拉拉斯山亚种 *S. maurus trarasensis* Bousisset & Larrouy, 1962 [Traras Massif, Algeria]^{to}
- 也门亚种 *S. maurus yemenensis* Werner, 1929 [Yemen]^{to}
- 摩加多蝎 *Scorpio mogadorensis* Birula, 1910 [Mogador (now Essaouira), a city in Morocco]^{pal}
- 尼日尔蝎 *Scorpio niger* Lourenço & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2012 [Niger]^{to}
- 西部蝎 *Scorpio occidentalis* Werner, 1936 [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}
- 阔掌蝎 *Scorpio palmatus* (Ehrenberg, 1828) [*palma* (palm) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 近形蝎 *Scorpio propinquus* (Simon, 1872) [resembling]^{ta}
- 布匿蝎 *Scorpio punicus* Fet, 2000 [Punic, Carthaginian, from Carthage, now in Tunisia]^{pal}
- 草原蝎 *Scorpio savanicola* Lourenço, 2009 [*savani-* (savanah) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 苏丹蝎 *Scorpio sudanensis* Lourenço & Cloudsley-Thompson, 2009 [Sudan]^{to}
- 塔西里蝎 *Scorpio tassili* Lourenço & Rossi, 2016 [Tassili n' Ajjer, Algeria]^{to}
- 魏氏蝎 *Scorpio weidholzi* Werner, 1929 [Alfred Weidholz]^{ep}
- 斯里兰卡异距蝎属 Genus *Srilankametrus* Couzijn, 1981 [Sri Lanka + *Heterometrus*]^{to&ta}
- 将军斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus caesar* (C. L. Koch, 1841) [Gaius Julius Caesar, a Roman general and statesman]^{ep}
- 库氏斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus couzijni* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Heinrich Wilhelm Cornelius Couzijn]^{ep}
- 沉螯斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus gravimanus* (Pocock, 1894) [*gravi-* (heavy) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 印度斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus indus* (DeGeer, 1778) [India, erroneous type locality]^{to}
- 波氏斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus pococki* Prendini & Loria, 2020 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
- 锯齿斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus serratus* (Pocock, 1900) [*serra-* (sawtooth) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 耶鲁斯里兰卡异距蝎 *Srilankametrus yaleensis* (Kovařík, Ranawana, Jayarathne, Hoferek & Štáhlavský, 2019) [Yala National Park, Sri Lanka]^{to}
- 类蝎科 Family **Scorpiopidae** Kraepelin, 1905
- 副类蝎属 Genus *Parascorpiops* Banks, 1928 [*para-* (close to, near) + *Scorpiops*]^{mo}
- 山地副类蝎 *Parascorpiops montanus* Banks, 1928 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 类蝎属 Genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 [*Scorpio* + *-ops* (appearance)]^{ta}
- 亲缘类蝎 *Scorpiops affinis* Kraepelin, 1898 [related, allied]^{ta}
- 阿富汗类蝎 *Scorpiops afghanus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 [Afghanistan]^{to}
- 阿安氏类蝎 *Scorpiops alexandreaeorum* (Lourenço, 2013) [Alexandre Tynié and Anne Lottier]^{ep}
- 煤色类蝎 *Scorpiops anthracinus* Simon, 1887 [*anthrac-* (charcoal) + *-inus* (pertaining to)]^{chr}
- 月神类蝎 *Scorpiops artemisae* (Kovařík, Košulić, Štáhlavský, Plíšková, Dongkhamfu & Wongprom, 2015) [Ἄρτεμις (Artemis), goddess of the Moon in Greek mythology, associated with Orion who was killed by a giant scorpion (one story among all the legends)]^{de}
- 弱尾类蝎 *Scorpiops asthenurus* Pocock, 1900 ☉ [*asthen-* (feeble, weak) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 黑斑类蝎 *Scorpiops atomatus* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) ★ [*ato-* (black) + *atom-* (particle) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 巴氏类蝎 *Scorpiops bastawadei* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Deshbushan Bastawade]^{ep}
- 贝氏类蝎 *Scorpiops beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2005) [Janet Beccaloni]^{ep}
- 不丹类蝎 *Scorpiops bhutanensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 [Bhutan]^{to}
- 宾氏类蝎 *Scorpiops binghamii* Pocock, 1893 [Charles Thomas Bingham]^{ep}
- 比氏类蝎 *Scorpiops birulai* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Alexei Andreevich Byalynitskii-Birula]^{ep}
- 布氏类蝎 *Scorpiops braunwalderi* Kovařík, 2000 [Matt E. Braunwalder]^{ep}
- 凯氏类蝎 *Scorpiops calmonti* (Lourenço, 2013) [Benjamin Calmont]^{ep}
- 洞栖类蝎 *Scorpiops cavernicola* (Lourenço & Pham, 2013) [*caverni-* (cave) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 清迈类蝎 *Scorpiops chiangmai* (Lourenço, 2019) [nomen dubium] [Chiang Mai, a city in Thailand]^{to}
- 齐氏类蝎 *Scorpiops ciki* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Eduard Čik]^{ep}
- 城堡类蝎 *Scorpiops citadelle* (Kovařík, 2013) [*Citadelle*, a book's title by Antoine de Saint-Exupéry]^{ep}
- 达克荣类蝎 *Scorpiops dakrong* (Lourenço & Pham, 2014) [Dakrong District, Vietnam]^{to}

- 达氏类蝎 *Scorpiops dastychi* Kovařík, 2000 [Hieronymus Dastych]^{ep}
- 德干类蝎 *Scorpiops deccanensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1977 [Deccan Plateau, India]^{io}
- 戴氏类蝎 *Scorpiops demisi* Kovařík, 2005 [René Demis]^{ep}
- 邸氏类蝎 *Scorpiops dii* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Di Zhiyong (邸智勇)]^{ep}
- 邓氏类蝎 *Scorpiops dunlopi* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Jason Andrew Dunlop]^{ep}
- 珐氏类蝎 *Scorpiops farkaci* Kovařík, 1993 [Jan Farkač]^{ep}
- 费氏类蝎 *Scorpiops feti* Kovařík, 2000 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
- 夫氏类蝎 *Scorpiops furai* Kovařík, 2020 [Vladimír Fura]^{ep}
- 葛氏类蝎 *Scorpiops grandjeani* (Vachon, 1974) [François Grandjean]^{ep}
- 格氏类蝎 *Scorpiops grosseri* Kovařík, 2020 [Walter Grosser]^{ep}
- 哈氏类蝎 *Scorpiops hardwickii* (Gervais, 1843) ☆ [General Hardwick]^{ep}
- 哈姆斯氏类蝎 *Scorpiops harmsi* Kovařík, 2020 [Danilo Harms]^{ep}
- 霍氏类蝎 *Scorpiops hofereki* Kovařík, 2020 [David Hoferek]^{ep}
- 硕大类蝎 *Scorpiops ingens* Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015 ★ [huge]^{mo}
- 伊氏类蝎 *Scorpiops irenae* Kovařík, 1994 [Irena Kovaříková]^{ep}
- 詹氏类蝎 *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 1994 ★ [Eduard Jendek]^{ep}
- 喀氏类蝎 *Scorpiops kaftani* Kovařík, 1993 [Milan Kaftan]^{ep}
- 卡蒙类蝎 *Scorpiops kamengensis* (Bastawade, 2006) ○ [West Kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh State, India]^{io}
- 考氏类蝎 *Scorpiops kautti* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Peter Kautt]^{ep}
- 剋氏类蝎 *Scorpiops kejvali* Kovařík, 2020 [Zdeněk Kejval]^{ep}
- 甲米类蝎 *Scorpiops krabiensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Krabi Province, Thailand]^{io}
- 库氏类蝎 *Scorpiops kubani* (Kovařík, 2004) ☆ [Vit Kubáň]^{ep}
- 朗县类蝎 *Scorpiops langxian* Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005 ★ [Lang District, Tibet Autonomous Region, China]^{io}
- 瘦螯类蝎 *Scorpiops leptochirus* Pocock, 1893 ○ [*lepto-* (narrow) + *chirus* (hand, pincer)]^{mo}
- 拉萨类蝎 *Scorpiops lhasa* Di & Zhu, 2009 ★ [Lhasa, a city in Tibet Autonomous Region, China]^{io}
- 李氏类蝎 *Scorpiops lii* (Di & Qiao, 2020) ★ [Li Wenxin (李文鑫)]^{ep}
- 里氏类蝎 *Scorpiops lioneli* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2021 [Lionel Monod]^{ep}
- 林氏类蝎 *Scorpiops lindbergi* Vachon, 1980 [Kurt Lindberg]^{ep}
- 长掌类蝎 *Scorpiops longimanus* Pocock, 1893 ○ [*longi-* (long) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 浅黄类蝎 *Scorpiops luridus* Zhu, Lourenço & Qi, 2005 ★ [*lur-* (paleness, sallowness) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{chr}
- 马哈拉施特拉类蝎 *Scorpiops maharashtraensis* (Mirza, Sanap & Upadhye, 2013) [Maharashtra State, India]^{io}
- 玛氏类蝎 *Scorpiops margerisonae* Kovařík, 2000 ★ [Janet Margerison-Knight]^{ep}
- 山地类蝎 *Scorpiops montanus* Karsch, 1879 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 纳格番尼类蝎 *Scorpiops nagphani* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2021 [Marathi for a steep hilltop with a rocky cliff inside Bhimashankar Wildlife Sanctuary, meaning “cobra’s (nag) hood (phani)”]^{au(io)}
- 尼拉类蝎 *Scorpiops neera* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2021 [Neera River, Varandha Ghat, Maharashtra State, India]^{io}
- 内氏类蝎 *Scorpiops neradi* (Kovařík, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2013) [Ladislav Nerad]^{ep}
- 诺氏类蝎 *Scorpiops novaki* (Kovařík, 2005) ★ [Jindřich Novák]^{ep}
- 小毛类蝎 *Scorpiops oligotrichus* Fage, 1933 [*oligo-* (small) + *trichus* (hair)]^{mo}
- 猎人类蝎 *Scorpiops orioni* (Kovařík, Košulič, Štáhlavský, Plíšková, Dongkhamfu & Wongprom, 2015) [Ὠρίων or Ὠαρίων (Orion), a hunter in Greek mythology who was killed by a giant scorpion]^{my}
- 伯杰默里类蝎 *Scorpiops pachmarhicus* Bastawade, 1992 [Pachmarhi Hill Station, Madhya Pradesh State, India]^{io}
- 巴基斯坦类蝎 *Scorpiops pakistanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2009 [Pakistan]^{io}
- 巴色类蝎 *Scorpiops pakseensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Pakse, a city in Laos]^{io}
- 佩氏类蝎 *Scorpiops petersii* Pocock, 1893 ○ [Wilhelm Carl Hartwig Peters]^{ep}
- 帕尔坦类蝎 *Scorpiops phaltanensis* (Sulakhe, Sayyed, Deshpande, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2020) [Phaltan, a town in Satara District, Maharashtra State, India]^{io}
- 跋都类蝎 *Scorpiops phatoensis* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Phato, a city in Chumphon Province, Thailand]^{io}
- 黑类蝎 *Scorpiops piceus* Lourenço & Ythier, 2022 [*pic-* (pitch) + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of)]^{chr}
- 浦氏类蝎 *Scorpiops prasiti* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Prasit Wongprom]^{ep}
- 疑难类蝎 *Scorpiops problematicus* Kovařík, 2000 [problematic]^{io}
- 多孔类蝎 *Scorpiops profusus* (Lourenço, 2017) [excessive, lavish, profuse, refers to the very high number of trichobothria]^{mo}
- 拟山地类蝎 *Scorpiops pseudomontanus* Kovařík & Ahmed, 2009 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Scorpiops montanus*]^{ia}
- 普洱类蝎 *Scorpiops puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010) ★ [Puer, a city in Yunnan Province, China]^{io}
- 柔堂类蝎 *Scorpiops rohtangensis* Mani, 1959 [Rohtang Pass, Punjab State, India]^{io}

- 萨塔拉类蝎 *Scorpiops satarensis* Pocock, 1900 [Satara District, Maharashtra State, India]^{fo}
- 簕氏类蝎 *Scorpiops scheibae* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Renate Scheibe]^{ep}
- 舒氏类蝎 *Scorpiops schumacheri* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Patrick Schumacher]^{ep}
- 塞氏类蝎 *Scorpiops sejnai* Kovařík, 2000 [Vladimir Šejna]^{ep}
- 舍氏类蝎 *Scorpiops sherwoodae* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Danniella Sherwood]^{ep}
- 施甸类蝎 *Scorpiops shidian* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) ★ [Shidian County, Yunnan Province, China]^{fo}
- 索氏类蝎 *Scorpiops solegladi* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Michael E. Sologlad]^{ep}
- 粗壮类蝎 *Scorpiops solidus* Karsch, 1879 [*sol-* (to be solid) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
- 宋氏类蝎 *Scorpiops songi* Di & Qiao, 2020 ★ [Song Daxiang (宋大祥)]^{ep}
- 斯皮提类蝎 *Scorpiops spitiensis* Zambre, Sanap & Mirza, 2014 [Spiti Valley, Himachal Pradesh State, India]^{fo}
- 塔什库尔干类蝎 *Scorpiops taxkorgan* Lourenço, 2018 ★ [Taxkorgan Natural Reserve, Xinjiang Autonomous Province, China]^{fo}
- 细尾类蝎 *Scorpiops tenuicauda* Pocock, 1894 [*tenui-* (slender) + *cauda* (tail)]^{mo}
- 泰国类蝎 *Scorpiops thailandus* Kovařík, Lowe, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2020 [Thailand]^{fo}
- 陶米氏类蝎 *Scorpiops thaomischi* (Kovařík, 2012) [Thao Ho and Michael Misch]^{ep}
- 西藏类蝎 *Scorpiops tibetanus* Hirst, 1911 ★ [Tibet Autonomous Region, China]^{fo}
- 穴居类蝎 *Scorpiops troglodytes* (Lourenço & Pham, 2015) [cave-dweller (*troglo-* (cave) + *-dytes* (enterer))]^{bi}
- 忒氏类蝎 *Scorpiops tryznai* Kovařík, 2020 [Miloš Trýzna]^{ep}
- 瓦氏类蝎 *Scorpiops vachoni* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) ★ [Max Vachon]^{ep}
- 强壮类蝎 *Scorpiops validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010) ★ [*val-* (to be strong) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{mo}
- 维氏类蝎 *Scorpiops viktoriae* (Lourenço & Košulič, 2018) [Viktorie Košuličová]^{ep}
- 韦氏类蝎 *Scorpiops vonwicki* Birula, 1913 [Sergei Nikolaevich von Wick]^{ep}
- 梵语类蝎 *Scorpiops vrushchik* Sulakhe, Deshpande, Dandekar, Padhye & Bastawade, 2021 [Sanskrit for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 汪氏类蝎 *Scorpiops wongpromi* (Kovařík, Sologlad & Košulič, 2013) [Prasithi Wongprom]^{ep}
- 瑞氏类蝎 *Scorpiops wrzecionkoi* Kovařík, 2020 ★ [Antonin Wrzecionko]^{ep}
- 徐氏类蝎 *Scorpiops xui* (Sun & Zhu, 2010) ★ [Xu Jishan (徐吉山)]^{ep}
- 亚氏类蝎 *Scorpiops yagmuri* Kovařík, 2020 [Ersen Aydin Yağmur]^{ep}
- 杨氏类蝎 *Scorpiops yangi* (Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007) ★ [Yang Zizhong (杨自忠)]^{ep}
- 张氏类蝎 *Scorpiops zhangshuyuan* (Ythier, 2019) ★ [Zhang Shuyuan (张书源)]^{ep}
- 祖氏类蝎 *Scorpiops zubairahmedi* Kovařík, 2009 [Zubair Ahmed]^{ep}
- 祖拜尔氏类蝎 *Scorpiops zubairi* Kovařík, 2020 [Zubair Ahmed]^{ep}
- 迷信山蝎科 Family Superstitioniidae** Stahnke, 1940
- 迷信山蝎属 Genus Superstitionia** Stahnke, 1940 [Superstition Mts., Arizona, USA]^{fo}
- 多恩迷信山蝎 *Superstitionia donensis* Stahnke, 1940 [Don’s Camp Canyon, Arizona, USA]^{fo}
- 盲蛮蝎科 Family Typhlochactidae** Mitchell, 1971
- 西语蝎属 Genus Alacran** Francke, 1982 [Spanish word for “scorpion”]^{au}
- 恶魔西语蝎 *Alacran chamuco* Francke, 2009 [a name given in parts of Mexico to a devil that inhabits the underworld]^{au}
- 地狱西语蝎 *Alacran tartarus* Francke, 1982 [the deep abyss in Greek mythology]^{my}
- 特奎西语蝎 *Alacran triquimera* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2014 [Tres Quimeras Cave, Puebla State, Mexico]^{fo}
- 深洞蛮蝎属 Genus Sotanochactas** Francke, 1986 [Spanish word for “pit” + *Chactas*]^{au(bi)&ta}
- 埃氏深洞蛮蝎 *Sotanochactas elliotti* (Mitchell, 1971) [William Elliott]^{ep}
- 冥河蛮蝎属 Genus Stygochactas** Vignoli & Prendini, 2009
- [Styx (underworld river in Greek mythology) + *Chactas*]^{my&ta}
- 多疣冥河蛮蝎 *Stygochactas granulatus* (Sissom & Cokendolpher, 1998) [*granul-* (granule) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 盲蛮蝎属 Genus Typhlochactas** Mitchell, 1971 [*typhlo-* (blind) + *Chactas*]^{mo&ta}
- 洞栖盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas cavicola* Francke, 1986 [*cavi-* (cave) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 米氏盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas mitchelli* Sissom, 1988 [Robert Wetsel Mitchell]^{ep}
- 雷氏盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas reddelli* Mitchell, 1968 [James R. Reddell]^{ep}
- 柔氏盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas rhodesi* Mitchell, 1968 [William Rhodes]^{ep}
- 西氏盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas sissomi* Francke, Vignoli & Prendini, 2009 [William David Sissom]^{ep}
- 林盲蛮蝎 *Typhlochactas sylvestris* Mitchell & Peck, 1977 [*silv-* (forest) + *-estris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 油鹱洞蝎科 Family Troglotayosicidae** Lourenço, 1998
- 油鹱洞蝎属 Genus Troglotayosicus** Lourenço, 1981 [*troglo-* (troglitic) + Cuevo de Los Tayos, Ecuador]^{bi&to}
- 巴氏油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus ballvei* Botero-Trujillo, Ochoa & Prendini, 2021 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
- 鬃毛油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus hirsutus* Botero-Trujillo, Ochoa, Tovar & Souza, 2012 [hairy]^{mo}
- 地栖油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus humiculum* Botero-Trujillo & Francke, 2009 [leaf litter (*humi-* (ground) + *-culum* (diminutive suffix))]^{bi}
- 梅氏油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus mejideni* Botero-Trujillo, González-Gomez, Valenzuela-Rojas & Garcia, 2017 [Arie van der Meijden]^{ep}

- 穆拉农卡油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus muranunkae* Sánchez-Vialas, Blasco-Arostegui, Garcia-Gila & Lourenço, 2020 [Mura Nunka, Shuar word for the vegetation formations of the sandstone plateaus that characterize the region; Mura (the type of dominant vegetation) + Nunka (region)]^{au(ge)}
- 瓦氏油鹱洞蝎 *Troglotayosicus vachoni* Lourenço, 1981 [Max Vachon]^{ep}
- 螫尾蝎科 Family Urodacidae** Pocock, 1893
- 盲蝎属 Genus Aops** Volschenk & Prendini, 2008 [blind, *a-* (without) + *ops* (eye)]^{mo}
- 钩指盲蝎 *Aops oncodactylus* Volschenk & Prendini, 2008 [*onco-* (hook) + *dactylus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}
- 螫尾蝎属 Genus Urodacus** Peters, 1861 [*uro-* (tail) + *dacus* (bite, sting)]^{mo&er}
- 武装螫尾蝎 *Urodacus armatus* Pocock, 1888 [armed, perfect passive participle of *armo* (arm)]^{mo}
- 布氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus butleri* Volschenk, Harvey & Prendini, 2012 [William Henry Butler]^{ep}
- 具棱螫尾蝎 *Urodacus carinatus* Hirst, 1911 [*carin-* (carina) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 中部螫尾蝎 *Urodacus centralis* L. E. Koch, 1977 [central (*centr-* (center) + *-alis* (pertaining to))] ^{cho}
- 狭长螫尾蝎 *Urodacus elongatus* L. E. Koch, 1977 [prolonged, perfect passive participle of *elongo* (prolong)]^{mo}
- 显赫螫尾蝎 *Urodacus excellens* Pocock, 1888 [distinguished, excellent]^{mo}
- 吉氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus giulianii* L. E. Koch, 1977 [Derham Giuliani]^{ep}
- 哈氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus hartmeyer* Kraepelin, 1908 [Robert Hartmeyer]^{ep}
- 武尾螫尾蝎 *Urodacus hoplurus* Pocock, 1898 [*hopl-* (armed) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 库兰螫尾蝎 *Urodacus koolanensis* L. E. Koch, 1977 [Koolan Island, Australia]^{to}
- 洛氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus lowei* L. E. Koch, 1977 [Graeme Lowe]^{ep}
- 长尾螫尾蝎 *Urodacus macrurus* Pocock, 1899 [*macr-* (long) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}
- 毡毛螫尾蝎 *Urodacus manicatus* (Thorell, 1876) [*manica-* (sleeve) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 麦氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus mckenziei* Volschenk, Smith & Harvey, 2000 [Norman I. McKenzie]^{ep}
- 巨鞭螫尾蝎 *Urodacus megamastigus* L. E. Koch, 1977 [*mega-* (enormous) + *mastigus* (whip)]^{mo}
- 纽荷兰螫尾蝎 *Urodacus novaehollandiae* Peters, 1861 [New Holland, exoethnonym for Western Australia given by Dutch explorers]^{to}
- 平掌螫尾蝎 *Urodacus planimanus* Pocock, 1893 [*plani-* (flat) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 近似螫尾蝎 *Urodacus similis* L. E. Koch, 1977 [similar]^{to}
- 棘刺螫尾蝎 *Urodacus spinatus* Pocock, 1902 [*spin-* (spine) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 多变螫尾蝎 *Urodacus varians* Glauert, 1963 [varying, present participle of *vario* (vary)]^{mo/chr}
- 夏氏螫尾蝎 *Urodacus yaschenkoi* (Birula, 1903) [Alexandr Leonidovich Yashchenko]^{ep}
- 愈神蝎科 Family Vaejovidae** Thorell, 1876
- 光滑巴尔萨斯蝎属 Genus Balsateres** González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
[Balsas Depression (Mexico) + *-teres* (smooth, polished)]^{to&mo}
- 锡氏光滑巴尔萨斯蝎 *Balsateres cisnerosi* (Saavedra & Sissom, 2004) [Socrates Cisnero Paz]^{ep}
- 卡特琳娜岛蝎属 Genus Catalinia** Soleglad, 2017 [Santa Catalina Island, California, USA]^{to}
- 安德烈亚斯卡特琳娜岛蝎 *Catalinia andreas* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Andreas Canyon, California, USA]^{to}
- 艾氏卡特琳娜岛蝎 *Catalinia ayreyi* Teruel & Myers, 2019 [Richard F. Ayrey]^{ep}
- 栗色卡特琳娜岛蝎 *Catalinia castanea* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [chestnut-colored]^{chr}
- 迷你卡特琳娜岛蝎 *Catalinia minima* (Kraepelin, 1911) [smallest]^{mo}
- 汤氏卡特琳娜岛蝎 *Catalinia thompsoni* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Melvin Thompson]^{ep}
- 奇瓦瓦蝎属 Genus Chihuahuanus** González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013 [Chihuahuan Desert]^{to}
- 双线奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus bilineatus* (Pocock, 1898) [*bi-* (two) + *linea* (line) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
- 凯氏奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus cazieri* (Williams, 1968) [Mont Adelbert Cazier]^{ep}
- 科阿韦拉奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus coahuilae* (Williams, 1968) [Coahuila State, Mexico]^{to}
- 粗螫奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus crassimanus* (Pocock, 1898) [*crassi-* (fat, thick) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 秃螫奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus glabrimanus* (Sissom & Hendrixson, 2005) [*glabri-* (bald, smooth) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}
- 球形奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus globosus* (Borelli, 1915) [*glob-* (globe) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
- 寇氏奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus kovariki* (Soleglad & Fet, 2008) [František Kovařík]^{ep}
- 茹氏奇瓦瓦蝎 *Chihuahuanus russelli* (Williams, 1971) [Findlay Russell]^{ep}
- 弗氏蝎属 Genus Franckeus** Soleglad & Fet, 2005 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
- 科氏弗氏蝎 *Franckeus kochi* (Sissom, 1991) [Carl Ludwig Koch]^{ep}
- 敏氏弗氏蝎 *Franckeus minckleyi* (Williams, 1968) [Wendell Lee Minckley]^{ep}
- 光泽弗氏蝎 *Franckeus nitidulus* (C. L. Koch, 1843) [*niti-* (to shine) + *-idu-* (tending to) + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix)]^{mo}
- 半岛弗氏蝎 *Franckeus peninsularis* (Williams, 1980) [peninsula]^{bi}
- 菩氏弗氏蝎 *Franckeus platnicki* (Sissom, 1991) [Norman Ira Platnick]^{ep}
- 红掌弗氏蝎 *Franckeus rubrimanus* (Sissom, 1991) [*rubri-* (red) + *manus* (hand)]^{chr&mo}

哲氏蝎属 Genus *Gertschius* Graham & Soleglad, 2007 [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}

敏捷哲氏蝎 *Gertschius agilis* (Sissom & Stockwell, 1991) [agile]^{er}

粗体哲氏蝎 *Gertschius crassicornus* Graham & Soleglad, 2007 [*crassi-* (fat, thick + *corpus* (body))^{mo}

格氏蝎属 Genus *Graemeloweus* Soleglad, Fet, Graham & Ayrey, 2016 [Graeme Lowe]^{ep}

歌氏格氏蝎 *Graemeloweus glimmi* (Hjelle, 1972) [Thomas M. Glimme]^{ep}

艾氏格氏蝎 *Graemeloweus iviei* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Wilton Ivie]^{ep}

迈杜格氏蝎 *Graemeloweus maidu* (Savary & Bryson, 2016 [Maidu people of northern California])^{et}

科氏蝎属 Genus *Kochius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008 [Carl Ludwig Koch]^{ep}

具须科氏蝎 *Kochius barbatus* (Williams, 1971) [*barba-* (beard + *-atus* (with))^{mo}

棕褐科氏蝎 *Kochius bruneus* (Williams, 1970) [*brun-* (brown + *-eus* (made of, having the quality of))^{chr}

塞拉尔沃科氏蝎 *Kochius cerralvensis* (Williams, 1971) [Cerralvo Island, Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{to}

崩积科氏蝎 *Kochius colluvius* Ayrey, Jones & Myers, 2019 [the colluvial soil where all of the type specimens were found]^{bi}

绒尾科氏蝎 *Kochius hirsuticauda* (Banks, 1910) [*hirsuti-* (hairy, bristled + *cauda* (tail))^{mo}

岛屿科氏蝎 *Kochius insularis* (Williams, 1970) [*insul-* (island + *-aris* (pertaining to))^{bi}

马格达莱纳科氏蝎 *Kochius magdalensis* (Williams, 1971) [Magdalena Plain of Baja California, Mexico]^{to}

斑肢科氏蝎 *Kochius punctipalpi* (Wood, 1863) [*puncti-* (spot, point + *-palpi* (here as “pedipalp”))^{chr&mo}

索诺拉科氏蝎 *Kochius sonorae* (Williams, 1971) [Sonora Desert, USA]^{to}

多绒科氏蝎 *Kochius villosus* (Williams, 1971) [*villo-* (hair) + *-osus* (full of, overly))^{mo}

微纳瓦蝎属 Genus *Konetontli* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013 [Nahuatl for “infant, small creature”]^{au(mo)}

阿卡普尔科微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli acapulco* (Armas & Martín-Frias, 2001) [Acapulco, a city in Guerrero State, Mexico]^{to}

查美拉微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli chamelaensis* (Williams, 1986) [Biological Station of Chamela, Jalisco State, Mexico]^{to}

佛戈斯微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli ignes* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2015 [“fire”; type locality Fogos is the Portuguese for

“fires”]^{to} 雅基微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli ilitchi* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2015 [Yaqui for “small”]^{au(mo)}

胡斯特拉瓦卡微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli juxtlahuaca* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2015 [Juxtlahuaca Cave, Guerrero State, Mexico]^{to}

布雷佩查微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli kuarapu* (Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2005) [Purhepecha for “scorpion”]^{au}

小型微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli migrus* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2015 [small]^{mo}

纳亚里特微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli nayarit* (Armas & Martín-Frias, 2001) [Nayarit State, Mexico]^{to}

派氏微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli pattersoni* (Williams & Haradon in Williams, 1980) [Donald Patterson]^{ep}

芝华塔尼欧微纳瓦蝎 *Konetontli zihuatanejensis* (Baldazo-Monsivaiz, 2003) [Zihuatanejo, a city in Guerrero State, Mexico]^{to}

寇氏蝎属 Genus *Kovarikia* Soleglad, Fet & Graham, 2014 [František Kovařík]^{ep}

洛杉矶寇氏蝎 *Kovarikia angelena* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Los Angeles, California, USA]^{to}

博氏寇氏蝎 *Kovarikia bogerti* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Charles Mitchell Bogert]^{ep}

西方学院寇氏蝎 *Kovarikia oxy* Bryson, Graham & Soleglad, 2018 [nickname for Occidental College]^{to}

萨氏寇氏蝎 *Kovarikia savaryi* Bryson, Graham & Soleglad, 2018 [Warren E. Savary]^{ep}

威氏寇氏蝎 *Kovarikia williamsi* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Stanley C. Williams]^{ep}

布雷佩查蝎属 Genus *Kuarapu* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2010 [Purhepecha for “scorpion”]^{au&ty}

模式布雷佩查蝎 *Kuarapu purhepecha* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2010 [endonym used by the Tarascan Indians of Michoacán State, Mexico]^{et}

战神蝎属 Genus *Maaykuyak* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013 [Kiliwa for “God of the warrior”]^{au(de)}

条纹战神蝎 *Maaykuyak vittatus* (Williams, 1970) [*vitta-* (band) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

沃氏战神蝎 *Maaykuyak waueri* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Roland H. Wauer]^{ep}

中墨愈神蝎属 Genus *Mesomexovis* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013 [*meso-* (middle) + *mex-* (Mexico) + *-ovis* (*Vaejovis*)]^{to&mo}

阿特南戈中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis atenango* (Francke & González-Santillán, 2006) [Atenango del Río, Guerrero, Mexico]^{to}

瓦哈卡中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis oaxaca* (Santibáñez-López & Sissom, 2010) [Oaxaca State, Mexico]^{to}

西部中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis occidentalis* (Hoffmann, 1931) [western (*occidens* (west) + *-alis* (pertaining to))]^{cho}

斑点中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis punctatus* (Karsch, 1879) [*punct-* (spot, point) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr&mo}

栗色中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis spadix* (Hoffmann, 1931) [chestnut-colored]^{chr}

弱脊中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis subcristatus* (Pocock, 1898) [*sub-* (slightly) + *crista-* (keel) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

杂色中墨愈神蝎 *Mesomexovis variegatus* (Pocock, 1898) [variegated, perfect passive participle of *variego* (variegate)]^{chr}

副愈神蝎属 Genus *Paravaejovis* Williams, 1980 [*para-* (close to, near) + *Vaejovis*]^{ta}

迷惑副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis confusus* (Stahnke, 1940) [confusing]^{ta}

迪氏副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis diazi* (Williams, 1970) [Alfonso Díaz-Nájera]^{ep}

壮尾副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis eusthenura* (Wood, 1863) [*eusthen-* (strong + *ura* (tail))^{mo}

黄副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis flavus* (Banks, 1900) [yellow]^{chr}

青黄副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis galbus* (Williams, 1970) [yellow-green]^{chr}

沉尾副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis gravicaudus* (Williams, 1970) [*gravi-* (heavy + *caudus* (tail))^{mo}

- 霍氏副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis hoffmanni* (Williams, 1970) [Carlos Cristian Hoffmann]^{ep}
 侏儒副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis pumilis* (Williams, 1970) [dwarf]^{mo}
 清教徒副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis puritanus* (Gertsch, 1958) [Puritan-American Museum Expedition]^{ep}
 施氏副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis schwenkmeyeri* (Williams, 1970) [Richard C. Schwenkmeyer]^{ep}
 携刺副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis spinigerus* (Wood, 1863) [*spini-* (spine + *-gerus* (bearing))]^{mo}
 韦氏副愈神蝎 *Paravaejovis waeringi* (Williams, 1970) [Erik Norman Kjellesvig-Waering]^{ep}
- 副尾戮蝎属 Genus *Paruroctonus*** Werner, 1934 [*par-* (close to, near) + *Uroctonus*]^{ta}
- 沙慈副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus ammonastes* Haradon, 1984 [*ammo-* (sand + *-nastes* (inhabitant))]^{bi}
 沙栖副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus arenicola* Haradon, 1984
 模式亚种 *P. arenicola arenicola* Haradon, 1984 [*areni-* (sand) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
 裸足亚种 *P. arenicola nudipes* Haradon, 1984 [*nudi-* (nude) + *-pes* (foot)]^{mo}
 阿氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus arnaudi* Williams, 1972 [Paul Henri Arnaud]^{ep}
 贝氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus baergi* (Williams & Hadley, 1967) [William J. Baerg]^{ep}
 下加州副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus bajae* Williams, 1972 [Baja California Peninsula, Mexico]^{to}
 班氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus bantai* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1966)
 模式亚种 *P. bantai bantai* Gertsch & Soleglad, 1966 [Benjamin Harrison Banta]^{ep}
 萨拉托加亚种 *P. bantai saratoga* Haradon, 1985 [Saratoga Springs, California, USA]^{to}
 拜氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus becki* (Gertsch & Allred, 1965) [D. Elen Beck]^{ep}
 博基亚斯副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus boquillas* Sissom & Henson, 1998 [Boquillas Canyon, Texas, USA]^{to}
 北方副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus boreus* (Girard, 1854) [northern]^{cho}
 波利哥副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus borregoensis* Williams, 1972
 模式亚种 *P. borregoensis borregoensis* Williams, 1972 [Borrego Valley, California, USA]^{to}
 海岸亚种 *P. borregoensis actites* Haradon, 1984 [coast-dweller]^{bi}
 科阿韦拉副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus coahuilanus* Haradon, 1985 [Coahuila State, Mexico]^{to}
 纤细副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus gracilior* (Hoffmann, 1931) [more gracile (comparative of *gracilis*)]^{mo}
 绒足副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus hirsutipes* Haradon, 1984 [*hirsuti-* (hairy, bristled + *-pes* (foot))]^{mo}
 浅黄副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus luteolus* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1966) [*lute-* (yellow + *-olus* (diminutive suffix))]^{chr}
 海岸副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus maritimus* Williams, 1987 [maritime]^{bi}
 马氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus marksi* Haradon, 1984 [Joseph L. Marks]^{ep}
 光泽副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus nitidus* Haradon, 1984 [*niti-* (to shine + *-idus* (tending to))]^{mo}
 佩科斯副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus pecos* Sissom & Francke, 1981 [Pecos River, New Mexico, USA]^{to}
 拟侏儒副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus pseudopumilis* (Williams, 1970) [*pseudo-* (false, fake + *Paravaejovis pumilis*)]^{ta}
 舒氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus shulovi* (Williams, 1970)
 模式亚种 *P. shulovi shulovi* (Williams, 1970) [Aharon Shulov]^{ep}
 内华达亚种 *P. shulovi nevadae* Haradon, 1985 [Nevada, USA]^{to}
 锡氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus silvestrii* (Borelli, 1909) [Filippo Silvestri]^{ep}
 近似副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus simulatus* Haradon, 1985 [simulated, imitated, perfect passive participle of *simulo* (simulate)]^{ta}
 斯氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus stahnkei* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1966) [Herbert Ludwig Stahnke]^{ep}
 南副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus surensis* Williams & Haradon, 1980 [Spanish for “south”, as in Baja California Sur, Mexico]^{aud&cho/to}
 犹他副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus utahensis* (Williams, 1968) [Utah, USA]^{to}
 多变副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus variabilis* Hjelle, 1982 [variable]^{mo/chr}
 风地副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus ventosus* Williams, 1972 [*vent-* (wind + *-osus* (full of, overly; refers to the windy type locality))]^{bi}
 威氏副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus williamsi* Sissom & Francke, 1981 [Stanley C. Williams]^{ep}
 黄副尾戮蝎 *Paruroctonus xanthus* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1966) [yellow]^{chr}
- 拟尾戮蝎属 Genus *Pseudouroctonus*** Stahnke, 1974 [*pseudo-* (false, fake) + *Uroctonus*]^{ta}
- 阿帕切拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus apacheanus* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Apache Indians who lived in the range of this species]^{et}
 布氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus brysoni* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2017 [Robert Wilson Bryson Jr.]^{ep}
 凯氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus cazieri* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Mont Adelbert Cazier]^{ep}
 奇卡诺拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus chicano* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [vernacular name for people of Mexican descent born in the United States]^{au(et)}
 克氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus kremani* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2015 [Michael Kreman]^{ep}
 林氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus lindsayi* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Georges Lindsay]^{ep}
 谟氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus moyeri* Ayrey, Kovařik & Myers, 2021 [Ryan Moyer]^{ep}
 罪恶拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus peccatum* Tate, Riddle, Soleglad & Graham, 2013 [Latin for “sin”; type locality near Las Vegas, Nevada, USA, nicknamed “Sin City”]^{to}
 雷氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus reddelli* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [James R. Reddell]^{ep}
 浅红拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus rufulus* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [*rufu-* (red + *-ulus* (diminutive suffix))]^{chr}

萨氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus savvasi* Francke, 2009 [Charles Savvas]^{ep}

桑塔丽塔拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus santarita* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2015 [Santa Rita Mts., Arizona, USA]^{to}

司氏拟尾戮蝎 *Pseudouroctonus sprousei* Francke & Savary, 2006 [Peter Sprouse]^{ep}

锯指蝎属 Genus *Serradigitus* Stahnke, 1974 [*serra-* (sawtooth) + *digitus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}

阿氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus adcocki* (Williams, 1980) [Richard Adcock]^{ep}

武齿锯指蝎 *Serradigitus armadentis* (Williams, 1980) [*arma-* (armed) + *dentis* (tooth)]^{mo}

鲍氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus baueri* (Gertsch, 1958) [Harry Bauer]^{ep}

贝氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus bechteli* (Williams, 1980) [Kenneth Bechtel]^{ep}

炎热锯指蝎 *Serradigitus calidus* (Soleglad, 1974) [*cal-* (hot) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{bi}

德氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus dwyeri* (Williams, 1980) [Richard Dwyer]^{ep}

哲氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus gertschi* (Williams, 1968)

模式亚种 *S. gertschi gertschi* (Williams, 1968) [Willis John Gertsch]^{ep}

线纹亚种 *S. gertschi striatus* (Hjelle, 1972) [*stri-* (stripe) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}

希甘塔锯指蝎 *Serradigitus gigantaensis* (Williams, 1980) [Sierra de la Giganta Mts., Baja California Sur State, Mexico]^{to}

草地锯指蝎 *Serradigitus gramenestris* (Williams, 1970) [*gramen* (grass) + *-estris* (pertaining to)]^{bi}

哈氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus haradoni* (Williams, 1980) [Richard M. Haradon]^{ep}

亥氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus hearnei* (Williams, 1980) [Thomas Powell Hearne]^{ep}

约书亚锯指蝎 *Serradigitus joshuaensis* (Soleglad, 1972) [Joshua Tree National Monument, California, USA]^{to}

海岸锯指蝎 *Serradigitus littoralis* (Williams, 1980) [*littor-* (shore) + *-alis* (pertaining to)]^{bi}

渺小锯指蝎 *Serradigitus minutis* (Williams, 1970) [diminished, perfect passive participle of *minuo* (diminish)]^{mo}

密氏锯指蝎 *Serradigitus miscionei* Ayrey, 2011 [Tom Miscione]^{ep}

太平洋锯指蝎 *Serradigitus pacificus* (Williams, 1980) [Pacific Ocean]^{to}

灼热锯指蝎 *Serradigitus torridus* Williams & Berke, 1986 [*torr-* (scorch, parch) + *-idus* (tending to)]^{bi}

伍帕特基锯指蝎 *Serradigitus wupatkiensis* (Stahnke, 1940) [Wupatki National Monument, Arizona, USA]^{to}

雅基锯指蝎 *Serradigitus yaqui* Sissom & Stockwell, 1991 [Yaqui Indians who lived near Yaqui River Valley, Sonora State, Mexico]^{et}

鬃尾蝎属 Genus *Smeringurus* Haradon, 1983 [*smering-* (bristle, hair) + *urus* (tail)]^{mo}

旱地鬃尾蝎 *Smeringurus aridus* (Soleglad, 1972) [dry, arid]^{bi}

大鬃尾蝎 *Smeringurus grandis* (Williams, 1970) [grand]^{mo}

梅萨鬃尾蝎 *Smeringurus mesaensis* (Stahnke, 1957) [Mesa, a city in Arizona, USA]^{to}

瓦氏鬃尾蝎 *Smeringurus vachoni* (Stahnke, 1961) [Max Vachon]^{ep}

斯氏蝎属 Genus *Stahnkeus* Soleglad & Fet, 2006 [Herbert Ludwig Stahnke]^{ep}

奥氏斯氏蝎 *Stahnkeus allredi* (Sissom & Stockwell, 1991) [Donald M. Allred]^{ep}

漠栖斯氏蝎 *Stahnkeus deserticola* (Williams, 1970) [*deserti-* (desert) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}

哈氏斯氏蝎 *Stahnkeus harbisoni* (Williams, 1970) [Charles Francis Harbison]^{ep}

珀氏斯氏蝎 *Stahnkeus polisi* (Sissom & Stockwell, 1991) [Gary Allan Polis]^{ep}

细螯斯氏蝎 *Stahnkeus subtilimanus* (Soleglad, 1972) [*subtili-* (fine, thin) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}

合棱蝎属 Genus *Syntropis* Kraepelin, 1900 [*syn-* (joint) + *tropis* (keel), refers to the single ventromedian carina on metasoma I-IV]^{mo}

阿氏合棱蝎 *Syntropis aalbui* Lowe, Soleglad & Fet, 2007 [Rolf Lionel Aalbu]^{ep}

长尾合棱蝎 *Syntropis macrura* Kraepelin, 1900 [*macr-* (long) + *ura* (tail)]^{mo}

威氏合棱蝎 *Syntropis williamsi* Soleglad, Lowe & Fet, 2007 [Stanley C. Williams]^{ep}

托氏蝎属 Genus *Thorellius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008 [Tord Tamerlan Teodor Thorell]^{ep}

脊螯托氏蝎 *Thorellius cristimanus* (Pocock, 1898) [*cristi-* (keel) + *manus* (hand)]^{mo}

无畏托氏蝎 *Thorellius intrepidus* (Thorell, 1876) [fearless]^{er}

凶蛮托氏蝎 *Thorellius tekuani* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2018 [Nahuatl for “ferocious”]^{au(er)}

维拉利卡托氏蝎 *Thorellius wixarika* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2018 [endonym used by the Huichol people of the central and western Sierra Madre Occidental, Mexico]^{et}

黑黍托氏蝎 *Thorellius yuyuawi* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2018 [Wixarika for “grains of black maize”, refers to the color and smoothness of the integument, especially the chelae]^{au(mo)}

近尾戮蝎属 Genus *Uroctonites* Williams & Savary, 1991 [*Uroctonus* + *-ites* (suffix indicating relationship)]^{ta}

吉氏近尾戮蝎 *Uroctonites giulianii* William & Savary, 1991 [Derham Giuliani]^{ep}

华楚卡近尾戮蝎 *Uroctonites huachuca* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Huachuca Mts., Arizona, USA]^{to}

蒙特雷近尾戮蝎 *Uroctonites montereus* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Monterey Country, California, USA]^{to}

红杉近尾戮蝎 *Uroctonites sequoia* (Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972) [Sequoia National Park, California, USA]^{to}

愈神蝎属 Genus *Vaejovis* C. L. Koch, 1836 [Vejovis, god of healing in Roman mythology]^{de}

阿华萨塔愈神蝎 *Vaejovis aguzarca* Díaz-Plascencia & González-Santillán, 2022 [Agua Zarca Biological Station, Sierra Fria, San José de Gracia Municipality, Aguascalientes, Mexico]^{to}

- 阿瓜斯卡连特斯愈神蝎 *Vaejovis aquascalentensis* Chávez-Samayoá & González-Santillán, 2022 [Aguascalientes, a city in Mexico]^{to}
- 侏儒愈神蝎 *Vaejovis baggins* Azzinnari, Bryson, Graham, Solis-Rojas & Sissom, 2021 [the fictional hobbit Bilbo Baggins in J. R. R. Tolkien's *The Hobbit*, in reference to small size]^{ep}
- 强盗愈神蝎 *Vaejovis bandido* Graham, Ayrey & Bryson, 2012 [Spanish for “bandits”; Sierra de los Ajos were hideouts for bandits and outlaws during the early 1900s, a metonym]^{au(to)}
- 彼氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis bigelowi* Sissom, 2011 [Joe Bigelow]^{ep}
- 卡罗莱纳愈神蝎 *Vaejovis carolinianus* (Beauvois, 1805) [South Carolina, USA]^{to}
- 卡氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis cashi* Graham, 2007 [Kevin Cash]^{ep}
- 塞博鲁科愈神蝎 *Vaejovis ceboruco* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2019 [Ceboruco Volcano, Jala Municipality, Nayarit State, Mexico]^{to}
- 恰帕斯愈神蝎 *Vaejovis chiapas* Sissom, 1989 [Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 奇索斯愈神蝎 *Vaejovis chisos* Sissom, 1990 [Chisos Mts., Texas, USA]^{to}
- 科尔科曼愈神蝎 *Vaejovis coalcoman* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2014 [Coalcomán Mts., Mexico]^{to}
- 克氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis crumpi* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2011 [Darrell Crump]^{ep}
- 曲指愈神蝎 *Vaejovis curvidigitus* Sissom, 1991 [*curvi-* (curved) + *digitus* (here as “finger”)]^{mo}
- 达氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis darwini* Santibáñez-López & Francke, 2010 [Charles Darwin]^{ep}
- 戴氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis davidi* Soleglad & Fet, 2005 [William David Sissom]^{ep}
- 德氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis deboerae* Ayrey, 2009 [Melinda DeBoer-Ayrey]^{ep}
- 欺诈愈神蝎 *Vaejovis decipiens* Hoffmann, 1931 [deceiving]^{ta}
- 道氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis dugesi* Pocock, 1902 [Alfredo Dugès]^{ep}
- 雨愈神蝎 *Vaejovis dzahui* Santibáñez-López & Francke, 2010 [Mixtec for “rain” (justification not given)]^{au}
- 琥珀愈神蝎 *Vaejovis electrum* Hughes, 2011 [amber-colored]^{chr}
- 艾氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis elii* Ayrey, 2020 [Eli Ayrey]^{ep}
- 费氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis feti* Graham, 2007 [Victor Fet]^{ep}
- 弗氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis franckei* Sissom, 1989 [Oscar Federico Francke Ballvé]^{ep}
- 纤细愈神蝎 *Vaejovis gracilis* Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972 [*gracile*]^{mo}
- 葛氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis grahami* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2014 [Matthew R. Graham]^{ep}
- 具疣愈神蝎 *Vaejovis granulatus* Pocock, 1898 [*granul-* (small grain) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}
- 格氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis grayae* Ayrey, 2014 [Alice Gray]^{ep}
- 浩氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis halli* Ayrey, 2012 [James Hall]^{ep}
- 中介愈神蝎 *Vaejovis intermedius* Borelli, 1915 [*inter-* (between) + *medius* (middle)]^{ta/mo}
- 高地愈神蝎 *Vaejovis islaserrano* Barrales-Alcala, Francke, Van Devender & Contreras-Félix, 2018 [Spanish *isla* for “island” and *sierra* for “mountain range” (being the adjective “serrano”), refers to the highlands of the Sonoran Desert]^{au(to)}
- 简氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis janssi* Williams, 1980 [Edwin Janss Jr.]^{ep}
- 琼氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis jonesi* Stahnke, 1940 [D. J. Jones]^{ep}
- 石栖愈神蝎 *Vaejovis lapidicola* Stahnke, 1940 [*lapidi-* (stone) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 多斑愈神蝎 *Vaejovis maculosus* Sissom, 1989 [*macul-* (spot, stain) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{chr}
- 毛氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis mauryi* Capes, 2001 [Emilio Antonio Maury]^{ep}
- 麦氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis mcwesti* Sissom, Graham, Donaldson & Bryson Jr, 2016 [Kari James McWest]^{ep}
- 门氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis mendozai* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2021 [Jorge Iván Mendoza-Marroquín]^{ep}
- 墨西哥愈神蝎 *Vaejovis mexicanus* C. L. Koch, 1836 [Mexico]^{to}
- 密氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis miscionei* Myers & Ayrey, 2011 [Tom Miscione]^{ep}
- 米氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis mitchelli* Sissom, 1991 [Robert Wetsel Mitchell]^{ep}
- 山地愈神蝎 *Vaejovis montanus* Graham & Bryson, 2010 [*mont-* (mountain) + *-anus* (pertaining to)]^{bi}
- 山栖愈神蝎 *Vaejovis monticola* Sissom, 1989 [*monti-* (mountain) + *-cola* (dweller)]^{bi}
- 莫雷利亚愈神蝎 *Vaejovis morelia* Miranda-López, Ponce-Saavedra & Francke, 2012 [Morelia, a city in Michoacan State, Mexico]^{to}
- 南奇提拉愈神蝎 *Vaejovis nanchititla* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2019 [Sierra de Nanchititla Natural Park, Mexico]^{to}
- 渐黑愈神蝎 *Vaejovis nigrescens* Pocock, 1898 [*nigr-* (black) + *-escens* (becoming)]^{chr}
- 黑髀愈神蝎 *Vaejovis nigrofemoratus* Hendrixson & Sissom, 2001 [*nigro-* (black) + *femor-* (femur) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr&mo}
- 北方愈神蝎 *Vaejovis norteno* Sissom & González-Santillán, 2004 [*norteño*, Spanish for “northern”]^{au(cho)}
- 奥科特愈神蝎 *Vaejovis ocotensis* Zárate-Gálvez & Francke, 2009 [El Ocote, Chiapas State, Mexico]^{to}
- 巴塔哥尼亚愈神蝎 *Vaejovis patagonia* Ayrey, 2018 [Patagonia Region, Argentina]^{to}
- 佩森愈神蝎 *Vaejovis paysonensis* Soleglad, 1973 [Payson, Arizona, USA]^{to}
- 娇小愈神蝎 *Vaejovis pequeno* Hendrixson, 2001 [Spanish for “little one”]^{au(mo)}
- 波氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis pococki* Sissom, 1991 [Reginald Innes Pocock]^{ep}
- 普氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis prendinii* Santibáñez-López & Francke, 2010 [Lorenzo Prendini]^{ep}
- 微小愈神蝎 *Vaejovis pusillus* Pocock, 1898 [tiny]^{mo}

- 柔氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis rossmani* Sissom, 1989 [Douglas Athon Rossman]^{ep}
 珊氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis santibagnezi* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2019 [Carlos Santibáñez López]^{ep}
 多毛愈神蝎 *Vaejovis setosus* Sissom, 1989 [*set-* (seta) + *-osus* (full of, overly)]^{mo}
 茜氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis sierrae* Sissom, Graham, Donaldson & Bryson Jr., 2016 [Sierra Elizabeth Bryson]^{ep}
 斯氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis smithi* Pocock, 1902 [Herbert Huntingdon Smith]^{ep}
 索氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis solegladi* Sissom, 1991 [Michael E. Soleglad]^{ep}
 司氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis sprousei* Sissom, 1990 [Peter Sprouse]^{ep}
 思氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis stetsoni* Ayrey & Myers, 2019 [Eric Stetson]^{ep}
 塔尔帕愈神蝎 *Vaejovis talpa* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2019 [Talpa de Allende, Jalisco State, Mexico]^{fo}
 塔帕尔帕愈神蝎 *Vaejovis tapalpa* Contreras-Félix & Francke, 2019 [Tapalpa, Jalisco State, Mexico]^{fo}
 忒氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis tenamaztlei* Contreras-Félix, Francke & Bryson Jr., 2015 [Francisco Tenamaztle]^{ep}
 细肢愈神蝎 *Vaejovis tenuipalpus* Sissom, Hughes, Bryson Jr. & Prendini, 2012 [*tenui-* (slender) + *palpus* (here as “pedipalp”)]^{mo}
 格纹愈神蝎 *Vaejovis tesselatus* Hendrixson & Sissom, 2001 [*tessel-* (a small cube of stone) + *-atus* (with)]^{chr}
 特雷斯皮科斯愈神蝎 *Vaejovis trespicos* Zarate-Galvez & Francke, 2009 [Tres Picos Mts., Chiapas State, Mexico]^{fo}
 忒氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis trinityae* Ayrey, 2013 [Trinity Frances Ayrey]^{ep}
 特氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis troupi* Ayrey & Soleglad, 2015 [Robert Troup]^{ep}
 牛仔愈神蝎 *Vaejovis vaquero* Gertsch & Soleglad, 1972 [Spanish for “cowboy”]^{au}
 佛氏愈神蝎 *Vaejovis vorhiesi* Stahnke, 1940 [Charles Taylor Vorhies]^{ep}
 萨波特克愈神蝎 *Vaejovis zapoteca* Santibáñez-López & Francke, 2010 [Zapoteca culture, Mexico]^{et}
 似愈神蝎属 Genus *Vejooidus* Stahnke, 1974 [*V[a]ejovis* + *-oidus* (resembling)]^{ta}
 长爪似愈神蝎 *Vejooidus longiunguis* (Williams, 1969) [*longi-* (long) + *unguis* (claw)]^{mo}
 维齐诺蝎属 Genus *Vizcaino* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
 [Vizcaino Desert, Baja California State, Mexico]^{fo&ty}
 模式维齐诺蝎 *Vizcaino viscainensis* (Williams, 1970) [Vizcaino Desert, Baja California State, Mexico]^{fo}
 维氏蝎属 Genus *Wernerius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008 [Franz Werner]^{ep}
 印优维氏蝎 *Wernerius inyoensis* Webber, Graham & Jaeger, 2012 [Inyo Mts., California, USA]^{fo}
 穆氏维氏蝎 *Wernerius mumai* (Sissom, 1993) [Martin Hammond Muma]^{ep}
 顶刺维氏蝎 *Wernerius spicatus* (Haradon, 1974) [*spica-* (spike) + *-atus* (with)]^{mo}

Appendix 2

Currently recognized subgenera

- 微戾蝎属 Genus *Microtityus* Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966
 微戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Microtityus* Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966
 异微戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Parvabsonus* Armas, 1974 [*parva-* (small) + *absonus* (discrepancy)]^{ta&mo}
- 戾蝎属 Genus *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836
 始戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Archaeotityus* Lourenço, 2006 [*archaeo-* (primitive) + *Tityus*]^{ta}
 王戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Atreus* Gervais, 1843 [Ἀτρεΰς (Atreus), king of Mycenae]^{my}
 巴西戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Brazilotityus* Lourenço, 2006 [Brazil + *Tityus*]^{to&ta}
 加勒比戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Caribetityus* Lourenço, 1999 [Caribbean + *Tityus*]^{to&ta}
 戾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836
- 沟尾蝎属 Genus *Bothriurus* Peters, 1861
 安第斯沟尾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Andibothriurus* Maury, 1975 [Andes Mts. + *Bothriurus*]^{to&ta}
 沟尾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Bothriurus* Peters, 1861
- 短胸蝎属 Genus *Brachistosternus* Pocock, 1893
 短胸蝎亚属 Subgenus *Brachistosternus* Pocock, 1893
 小胸蝎亚属 Subgenus *Ministernus* Francke 1985 [*mini-* (tiny) + *sternus* (sternum)]^{mo}
- 山蝎属 Genus *Alpiscorpius* Gantenbein, Fet, Largiadèr & Scholl, 1999
 山蝎亚属 Subgenus *Alpiscorpius* Gantenbein, Fet, Largiadèr & Scholl, 1999
 巴尔干蝎亚属 Subgenus *Balkanscorpius* Tropea, 2021 [the Balkan Peninsula + *scorpius* (scorpion)]^{fo}
 哈氏蝎亚属 Subgenus *Hadzius* Tropea, 2021 [Jovan Hadži]^{ep}

- 似厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hadruioides* Pocock, 1893
 似厚尾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Hadruioides* Pocock, 1893
 路氏似厚尾蝎亚属 Subgenus *Lourencoides* Rossi, 2014 [Wilson Roberto Lourenço + *Hadruioides*]^{ep&ta}
- 毒勇蝎属 Genus *Iomachus* Pocock, 1893
 非洲毒勇蝎亚属 Subgenus *Africanoiomachus* Lourenço, 2020 [African + *Iomachus*]^{to&ta}
 毒勇蝎亚属 Subgenus *Iomachus* Pocock, 1893
- 后棘蝎属 Genus *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861
 莫氏后棘蝎亚属 Subgenus *Monodopisthacanthus* Lourenço, 2001 [Lionel Monod + *Opisthacanthus*]^{ep&ta}
 丽蝎亚属 Subgenus *Nepabellus* Francke, 1974 [*nepa* (scorpion) + *-bellus* (pretty)]^{mo}
 后棘蝎亚属 Subgenus *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861

Supraspecific classification: a current consensus

- 蝎目 Order *Scorpiones* C. L. Koch, 1837
 新蝎亚目 Suborder *Neoscorpionina* Thorell & Lindström, 1885
 直胸下目 Infraorder *Orthosternina* Pocock, 1911
 杀牛蝎小目 Parvorder *Buthida* Soleglad & Fet, 2003
 杀牛蝎超科 Superfamily *Buthoidea* C. L. Koch, 1837
 杀牛蝎科 Family *Buthidae* C. L. Koch, 1837
 亚科未定 Subfamily *Incertae Sedis*
 爱琴杀牛蝎属 Genus *Aegaeobuthus* Kovařík, 2019
 非洲等蝎属 Genus *Afroisometrus* Kovařík, 1997
 非洲信使蝎属 Genus *Afrolychas* Kovařík, 2019
 无刺杀牛蝎属 Genus *Akentrobuthus* Lamoral, 1976
 无支蝎属 Genus *Ananteris* Thorell, 1891
 似无支蝎属 Genus *Ananteroides* Borelli, 1911
 杀人蝎属 Genus *Androctonus* Ehrenberg, 1828
 奇杀牛蝎属 Genus *Anomalobuthus* Kraepelin, 1900
 伪杀牛蝎属 Genus *Apistobuthus* Finnegan, 1932
 澳杀牛蝎属 Genus *Australobuthus* Locket, 1990
 棒尾蝎属 Genus *Babycurus* Karsch, 1886
 俾路支直钳蝎属 Genus *Baloorthochirus* Kovařík, 1996
 芭氏棒尾蝎属 Genus *Barbaracurus* Kovařík, 2018
 比氏蝎属 Genus *Birulatus* Vachon, 1974
 螫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthacus* Birula, 1908
 似小杀牛蝎属 Genus *Butheoloides* Hirst, 1925
 小杀牛蝎属 Genus *Butheolus* Simon, 1882
 弱杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthiscus* Birula, 1905
 似杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthoscorpio* Werner, 1936
 杀牛蝎属 Genus *Buthus* Leach, 1815
 迷蝎属 Genus *Charmus* Karsch, 1879
 西氏滑尾蝎属 Genus *Cicileiurus* Teruel, 2007
 西氏蝎属 Genus *Cicileus* Vachon, 1948
 秀杀牛蝎属 Genus *Compsobuthus* Vachon, 1949
 刚果杀牛蝎属 Genus *Congobuthus* Lourenço, 1999
 达氏蝎属 Genus *Darchenia* Vachon, 1977
 埃及杀牛蝎属 Genus *Egyptobuthus* Lourenço, 1999
 毫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Femtobuthus* Lowe, 2010
 费氏蝎属 Genus *Fetilia* Lowe & Kovařík, 2021
 阿姆哈拉蝎属 Genus *Gint* Kovařík, Lowe, Plíšková & Štáhlavský, 2013
 矛蝎属 Genus *Grosphus* Simon, 1880
 半杀牛蝎属 Genus *Hemibuthus* Pocock, 1900
 半信使蝎属 Genus *Hemilychas* Hirst, 1911
 喜山戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Himalayotityobuthus* Lourenço, 1997

- 霍屯督蝎属 Genus *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908
 伊朗杀牛蝎属 Genus *Iranobuthus* Kovařík, 1997
 似等蝎属 Genus *Isometroides* Keyserling, 1885
 等蝎属 Genus *Isometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828
 雅氏信使蝎属 Genus *Janalychas* Kovařík, 2019
 卡拉斯山蝎属 Genus *Karasbergia* Hewitt, 1913
 克氏蝎属 Genus *Kraepelinia* Vachon, 1974
 兰氏蝎属 Genus *Lanzatus* Kovařík, 2001
 滑尾蝎属 Genus *Leiurus* Ehrenberg, 1828
 光滑杀牛蝎属 Genus *Liobuthus* Birula, 1898
 润杀牛蝎属 Genus *Lissothus* Vachon, 1948
 信使蝎属 Genus *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845
 似信使蝎属 Genus *Lychasioides* Vachon, 1974
 毛里塔尼亚杀牛蝎属 Genus *Mauritanobuthus* Qi & Lourenço, 2007
 中杀牛蝎属 Genus *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950
 微无支蝎属 Genus *Microananteris* Lourenço, 2003
 微杀牛蝎属 Genus *Microbuthus* Kraepelin, 1898
 新杀牛蝎属 Genus *Neobuthus* Hirst, 1911
 新矛蝎属 Genus *Neogrosphus* Lourenço, 1995
 齿杀牛蝎属 Genus *Odontobuthus* Vachon, 1950
 齿尾蝎属 Genus *Odonturus* Karsch, 1879
 奥氏蝎属 Genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987
 似直钳蝎属 Genus *Orthochiroides* Kovařík, 1998
 直钳蝎属 Genus *Orthochirus* Karsch, 1891
 泛杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pantobuthus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009
 副杀牛蝎属 Genus *Parabuthus* Pocock, 1890
 栉杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pectinibuthus* Fet in Orlov & Vasilyev, 1984
 侏杀牛蝎属 Genus *Picobuthus* Lowe, 2010
 邻杀牛蝎属 Genus *Plesiobuthus* Pocock, 1900
 珀氏蝎属 Genus *Polisius* Fet, Capes & Sissom, 2001
 拟润杀牛蝎属 Genus *Pseudolissothus* Lourenço, 2001
 拟信使蝎属 Genus *Pseudolychas* Kraepelin, 1911
 拟织尾蝎属 Genus *Pseudouroplectes* Lourenço, 1995
 拉兹蝎属 Genus *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987
 雷氏蝎属 Genus *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972
 撒哈拉杀牛蝎属 Genus *Saharobuthus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2009
 萨珊蝎属 Genus *Sassanidotus* Farzanpay, 1987
 索马里杀牛蝎属 Genus *Somalibuthus* Kovařík, 1998
 索迷蝎属 Genus *Somalicharmus* Kovařík, 1998
 穴信使蝎属 Genus *Spelaelychas* Kovařík, 2019
 特氏蝎属 Genus *Teruelius* Lowe & Kovařík, 2019
 泰迷蝎属 Genus *Thaicharmus* Kovařík, 1995
 戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Tityobuthus* Pocock, 1893
 穴戾杀牛蝎属 Genus *Troglotityobuthus* Lourenço, 2000
 穴螫杀牛蝎属 Genus *Trypanothacus* Lowe, Kovařík, Stockmann & Štáhlavský, 2019
 织尾蝎属 Genus *Uroplectes* Peters, 1861
 小瓦氏蝎属 Genus *Vachoniolus* Levy, Amitai & Shulov, 1973
 瓦氏蝎属 Genus *Vachonus* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983
 诡杀牛蝎属 Genus *Xenobuthus* Lowe, 2018
 似刺尾蝎亚科 Subfamily *Centruroidinae* Kraus, 1955
 似刺尾蝎属 Genus *Centruroides* Marx, 1890
 异栉蝎属 Genus *Heteroctenus* Pocock, 1893
 纤螫蝎属 Genus *Ischnotelson* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017
 图皮蝎属 Genus *Jaguajir* Esposito, Yamaguti, Souza, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2017
 膨戮蝎属 Genus *Physoctonus* Mello-Leitão, 1934

- 棍尾蝎属 Genus *Rhopalurus* Thorell, 1876
 穴棍尾蝎属 Genus *Troglorhopalurus* Lourenço, Baptista & Giupponi, 2004
 戾蝎亚科 Subfamily *Tityinae* Bücherl, 1971
 阿氏戾蝎属 Genus *Alayotityus* Armas, 1973
 精灵蝎属 Genus *Chanek* Francke, Teruel & Santibáñez-López, 2014
 中戾蝎属 Genus *Mesotityus* González-Sponga, 1981
 微戾蝎属 Genus *Microtityus* Kjellesvig-Waering, 1966
 仿戾蝎属 Genus *Tityopsis* Armas, 1974
 戾蝎属 Genus *Tityus* C. L. Koch, 1836
 国君蝎属 Genus *Zabius* Thorell, 1893
 微迷蝎科 Family *Microcharmidae* Lourenço, 1996
 微迷蝎属 Genus *Microcharmus* Lourenço, 1995
 新原杀牛蝎属 Genus *Neoprotobuthus* Lourenço, 2000
 寇里蝎超科 Superfamily *Chaeriloidea* Pocock, 1893
 寇里蝎科 Family *Chaerilidae* Pocock, 1893
 寇里蝎属 Genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877
 拟蛮蝎超科 Superfamily *Pseudochactoidea* Gromov, 1998
 拟蛮蝎科 Family *Pseudochactidae* Gromov, 1998
 拟蛮蝎亚科 Subfamily *Pseudochactinae* Gromov, 1998
 拟蛮蝎属 Genus *Pseudochactas* Gromov, 1998
 穴甘蒙蝎亚科 Subfamily *Troglokhammouaninae* Lourenço, 2007
 穴甘蒙蝎属 Genus *Troglokhammouanus* Lourenço, 2007
 越南蝎亚科 Subfamily *Vietbocapinae* Lourenço, 2012
 老挝蝎属 Genus *Aemngvantom* Prendini, Ehrenthal & Loria, 2021
 越南蝎属 Genus *Vietbocap* Lourenço & Pham, 2010
 毒尾蝎小目 Parvorder *Iurida* Soleglad & Fet, 2003
 沟尾蝎超科 Superfamily *Bothriuroidea* Simon, 1880
 沟尾蝎科 Family *Bothriuridae* Simon, 1880
 沟尾蝎亚科 Subfamily *Bothriurinae* Simon, 1880
 沟尾蝎属 Genus *Bothriurus* Peters, 1861
 短胸蝎属 Genus *Brachistosternus* Pocock, 1893
 布兰德山蝎属 Genus *Brandbergia* Prendini, 2003
 巴西沟尾蝎属 Genus *Brazilobothriurus* Lourenço & Monod, 2000
 刺勇蝎属 Genus *Centromachetes* Lønneberg, 1897
 尾屠蝎属 Genus *Cercophonius* Peters, 1861
 毛氏蝎属 Genus *Mauryius* Ojanguren-Affilastro & Mattoni, 2017
 山沟尾蝎属 Genus *Orobothriurus* Maury, 1975
 君主蝎属 Genus *Pachakutej* Ochoa, 2004
 弑尾蝎属 Genus *Phoniocercus* Pocock, 1893
 石栖巨齿蝎属 Genus *Rumikiru* Ojanguren-Affilastro, Mattoni, Ochoa & Prendini, 2012
 阿拉乌咖那蝎属 Genus *Tehuanka* Cekalovic, 1973
 尖刺蝎属 Genus *Thestylus* Simon, 1880
 提玛蝎属 Genus *Timogenes* Simon, 1880
 尾弑蝎属 Genus *Urophonius* Pocock, 1893
 瓦氏沟尾蝎属 Genus *Vachonia* Abalos, 1954
 滑体蝎亚科 Subfamily *Lisposominae* Lawrence, 1928
 滑体蝎属 Genus *Lisposoma* Lawrence, 1928
 猎舟甲蝎超科 Superfamily *Caraboctonoidea* Kraepelin, 1905
 猎舟甲蝎科 Family *Caraboctonidae* Kraepelin, 1905
 猎舟甲蝎属 Genus *Caraboctonus* Pocock, 1893
 似厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hadrurides* Pocock, 1893
 迷信山蝎科 Family *Superstitioniidae* Stahnke, 1940
 迷信山蝎属 Genus *Superstitionia* Stahnke, 1940
 蛮蝎超科 Superfamily *Chactoidea* Pocock, 1893
 圣经蝎科 Family *Akravidae* Levy, 2007
 圣经蝎属 Genus *Akrav* Levy, 2007

- 将军蝎科 Family **Belisariidae** Lourenço, 1998
 将军蝎属 Genus *Belisarius* Simon, 1879
 萨丁蝎属 Genus *Sardoscorpius* Tropea & Onnis, 2020
- 蛮蝎科 Family **Chactidae** Pocock, 1893
 假尾戮蝎属 Genus *Anuroctonus* Pocock, 1893
 魔屋山蝎属 Genus *Auyanteputia* González-Sponga, 1978
 猎人蛮蝎属 Genus *Broteochactas* Pocock, 1893
 猎人蝎属 Genus *Brotheas* C. L. Koch, 1837
 蛮蝎属 Genus *Chactas* Gervais, 1844
 仿蛮蝎属 Genus *Chactopsis* Kraepelin, 1912
 似仿蛮蝎属 Genus *Chactopsoides* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjac, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013
 圭亚那蛮蝎属 Genus *Guyanochactas* Lourenço, 1998
 厚尾蛮蝎属 Genus *Hadrurochactas* Pocock, 1893
 硕仿蛮蝎属 Genus *Megachactops* Ochoa, Rojas-Runjac, Pinto-da-Rocha & Prendini, 2013
 新蛮蝎属 Genus *Neochactas* Soleglad & Fet 2003
 伪猎人蝎属 Genus *Nullibrotheas* Williams, 1974
 刺蛮蝎属 Genus *Spinochactas* Lourenço, 2016
 国王蝎属 Genus *Teuthraustes* Simon, 1878
 尾戮蝎属 Genus *Uroctonus* Thorell, 1876
 瓦氏蛮蝎属 Genus *Vachoniochactas* González-Sponga, 1978
- 真蝎科 Family **Euscorpiidae** Laurie, 1896
 山蝎属 Genus *Alpiscorpius* Gantenbein, Fet, Largiadèr & Scholl, 1999
 真蝎属 Genus *Euscorpius* Thorell, 1876
 硕躯蝎属 Genus *Megacormus* Karsch, 1881
 邻蛮蝎属 Genus *Plesiochactas* Pocock, 1900
 四孔蝎属 Genus *Tetratrachobothrius* Birula, 1917
 穴硕躯蝎属 Genus *Troglocormus* Francke, 1981
- 类蝎科 Family **Scorpiopidae** Kraepelin, 1905
 副类蝎属 Genus *Parascorpiops* Banks, 1928
 类蝎属 Genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861
- 盲蛮蝎科 Family **Typhlochactidae** Mitchell, 1971
 西语蝎亚科 Subfamily **Alacraninae** Vignoli & Prendini, 2009
 西语蝎属 Genus *Alacran* Francke, 1982
 盲蛮蝎亚科 Subfamily **Typhlochactinae** Vignoli & Prendini, 2009
 深洞蛮蝎属 Genus *Sotanochactas* Francke, 1986
 冥河蛮蝎属 Genus *Stygochactas* Vignoli & Prendini, 2009
 盲蛮蝎属 Genus *Typhlochactas* Mitchell, 1971
- 油鹱洞蝎科 Family **Troglotayosicidae** Lourenço, 1998
 油鹱洞蝎属 Genus *Troglotayosicus* Lourenço, 1981
- 厚尾蝎超科 Superfamily **Hadruroidea** Stahnke, 1974
 厚尾蝎科 Family **Hadruridae** Stahnke, 1974
 厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hadrurus* Thorell, 1876
 霍氏厚尾蝎属 Genus *Hoffmannihadrurus* Fet & Soleglad, 2004
- 毒尾蝎超科 Superfamily **Iuroidea** Thorell, 1876
 毒尾蝎科 Family **Iuridae** Thorell, 1876
 祭司蝎属 Genus *Calchas* Birula, 1899
 毒尾蝎属 Genus *Iurus* Thorell, 1876
 新祭司蝎属 Genus *Neocalchas* Yağmur, Soleglad, Fet & Kovařík, 2013
 原毒尾蝎属 Genus *Protoiurus* Soleglad, Fet, Kovařík & Yağmur, 2012
- 蝎超科 Superfamily **Scorpionioidea** Latreille, 1802
 双棘蝎科 Family **Diplocentridae** Karsch, 1880
 双目蝎属 Genus *Bioculus* Stahnke, 1968
 凯氏蝎属 Genus *Cazierius* Francke, 1978
 隐君王蝎属 Genus *Cryptoiclus* Teruel & Kovařík, 2012
 二棘蝎属 Genus *Didymocentrus* Kraepelin, 1905
 双棘蝎属 Genus *Diplocentrus* Peters, 1861

- 异尼博山蝎属 Genus *Heteronebo* Pocock, 1899
 纳瓦蝎属 Genus *Kolotl* Santibáñez-López, Francke & Prendini, 2014
 尼博山蝎属 Genus *Nebo* Simon, 1878
 君王蝎属 Genus *Oiclus* Simon, 1880
 孔跗蝎属 Genus *Tarsoporus* Francke, 1978
 异蝎科 Family **Heteroscorpionidae** Kraepelin, 1905
 异蝎属 Genus *Heteroscorpion* Birula, 1903
 半蝎科 Family **Hemiscorpiidae** Pocock, 1893
 半蝎属 Genus *Hemiscorpius* Peters, 1861
 链尾蝎科 Family **Hormuridae** Laurie, 1896
 螯戮蝎属 Genus *Cheloctonus* Pocock, 1892
 螯猛蝎属 Genus *Chiromachetes* Pocock, 1899
 螯勇蝎属 Genus *Chiromachus* Pocock, 1893
 冥神蝎属 Genus *Hadogenes* Kraepelin, 1894
 类链尾蝎属 Genus *Hormiops* Fage, 1933
 链尾蝎属 Genus *Hormurus* Thorell, 1876
 毒勇蝎属 Genus *Iomachus* Pocock, 1893
 滑螯蝎属 Genus *Liocheles* Sundevall, 1833
 后棘蝎属 Genus *Opisthacanthus* Peters, 1861
 古螯戮蝎属 Genus *Palaeocheloctonus* Lourenço, 1996
 藏毒勇蝎属 Genus *Tibetiomachus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006
 皱齿蝎科 Family **Rugodentidae** Bastawade, Sureshan & Radhakrishnan, 2005
 皱齿蝎属 Genus *Rugodentus* Bastawade, Sureshan & Radhakrishnan, 2005
 蝎科 Family **Scorpionidae** Latreille, 1802
 异距蝎亚科 Subfamily **Heterometrinae** Simon, 1879
 半岛异距蝎属 Genus *Chersonesometrus* Couzijn, 1978
 德干异距蝎属 Genus *Deccanometrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020
 巨异距蝎属 Genus *Gigantometrus* Couzijn, 1978
 异距蝎属 Genus *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828
 爪哇异距蝎属 Genus *Javanimetrus* Couzijn, 1981
 萨亚德里异距蝎属 Genus *Sahyadrimetrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020
 斯里兰卡异距蝎属 Genus *Srilankametrus* Couzijn, 1981
 后目蝎亚科 Subfamily **Opisthophthalminae** Rossi, 2016
 后目蝎属 Genus *Opisthophthalmus* C. L. Koch, 1837
 惧蝎亚科 Subfamily **Pandininae** Thorell, 1876
 博氏惧蝎属 Genus *Pandiborellius* Rossi, 2015
 似惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinoides* Fet, 1997
 类惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinops* Birula, 1913
 仿惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinopsis* Vachon, 1974
 尾惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinurus* Fet, 1997
 惧蝎属 Genus *Pandinus* Thorell, 1876
 肢惧蝎属 Genus *Pandipalpus* Rossi, 2015
 蝎亚科 Subfamily **Scorpioninae** Latreille, 1802
 蝎属 Genus *Scorpio* Linnaeus, 1758
 螯尾蝎科 Family **Urodacidae** Pocock, 1893
 盲蝎属 Genus *Aops* Volschenk & Prendini, 2008
 螯尾蝎属 Genus *Urodacus* Peters, 1861
 愈神蝎超科 Superfamily **Vaejovoidea** Thorell, 1876
 愈神蝎科 Family **Vaejovidae** Thorell, 1876
 鬃尾蝎亚科 Subfamily **Smeringurinae** Soleglad & Fet, 2008
 副尾戮蝎属 Genus *Paruroctonus* Werner, 1934
 鬃尾蝎属 Genus *Smeringurus* Haradon, 1983
 似愈神蝎属 Genus *Vejovoidus* Stahnke, 1974
 斯氏蝎亚科 Subfamily **Stahnkeninae** Soleglad & Fet, 2008
 哲氏蝎属 Genus *Gertschius* Graham & Soleglad, 2007
 锯指蝎属 Genus *Serradigitus* Stahnke, 1974

- 斯氏蝎属 Genus *Stahnkeus* Soleglad & Fet, 2006
 维氏蝎属 Genus *Wernerius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008
 合棱蝎亚科 Subfamily *Syntropinae* Kraepelin, 1905
 光滑巴尔萨斯蝎属 Genus *Balsateres* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
 奇瓦瓦蝎属 Genus *Chihuahuanus* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
 科氏蝎属 Genus *Kochius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008
 微纳瓦蝎属 Genus *Konetontli* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
 布雷佩查蝎属 Genus *Kuarapu* Francke & Ponce-Saavedra, 2010
 战神蝎属 Genus *Maaykuyak* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
 中墨愈神蝎属 Genus *Mesomexovis* González-Santillán & Prendini, 2013
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 合棱蝎属 Genus *Syntropis* Kraepelin, 1900
 托氏蝎属 Genus *Thorellius* Soleglad & Fet, 2008
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 愈神蝎亚科 Subfamily *Vaejovinae* Thorell, 1876
 卡特琳娜岛蝎属 Genus *Catalinia* Soleglad, 2017
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*Uroctoninae, Heteroscorpionidae, Typhlochactidae and Troglotayosicidae were considered as *incertae sedis* by Santibáñez-López et al. (2019); I tentatively included them in the above classification according to the previous studies. No subfamilies or tribes are considered for Chactidae in this paper; for previous considerations, see Soleglad & Fet (2004, 2005).

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